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I dedicate this thesis...

To, my **PAPA and AMMA**

Chakradhara Rao U.S.

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List of Abbreviations

µg	:	Microgram
µl	:	Microlitre
ABCB1	:	ATP-binding cassette sub-family B member 1
ADP	:	Adenosine diphosphate
ADRs	:	Adverse drug reactions
AHR	:	Aryl hydrocarbon receptor
AMC	:	Amoxicillin
ARNT	:	Aryl hydrocarbon receptor nuclear translocator
ATF	:	Activating transcription factor
ATF-2	:	Activating transcription factor 2
AU	:	Arbitrary units
AUC	:	Area under the curve
BID	:	Bis in die
bp	:	Base Pair
C/EBPB	:	CCAAT/ enhancing binding protein beta
CAM	:	Clarithromycin
cAMP	:	Cyclic adenosine monophosphate
CAR	:	Constitutive androstane receptor
CARRE	:	Constitutive androstane receptor response element
CBP	:	CREB binding protein
CCRP	:	Cytoplasmic CAR retention protein
CDP	:	CCAAT displacement protein
CEBP	:	CCAAT enhancer binding proteins
CEU: CEPH	:	Utah residents with ancestry from northern and western Europe
CG	:	Cycloguanil

CHB	:	Han Chinese in Beijing, China
CI	:	Confidence interval
c-Myc	:	Protein that binds to the DNA of other genes
CpG	:	Cytosine and guanine with phosphodiester bond
CREB	:	Cyclic AMP response element binding protein
C _t	:	Cycle threshold
CYP450	:	Cytochrome P450
DMEM	:	Dulbecco's Modified Eagles Medium
DNA	:	Deoxyribonucleic acid
dNTPs	:	Deoxyribonucleotide triphosphate.
DTT	:	Dithiothreitol
EBTM	:	Esomeprezole, Bismuth subcitrate, Tetracycline, Metronidazole
EDTA	:	Ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid
EETs	:	Epoxyeicosatrienoic acids
EM	:	Estimization Maximization
EMs	:	Extensive metabolizers
EMSA	:	Electrophoretic Mobility Shift Assay
EMZ	:	Esomeprazole
ER	:	Estrogen receptor
FBS	:	Fetal bovine serum
FDA	:	Food and Drug Administration
FKBP4	:	FK506 binding protein 4
f mol	:	Femto moles
GATA-1	:	GATA binding factor 1
GR	:	Glucocorticoid receptor
GRE	:	Glucocorticoid-response element
GRIP-1	:	Glucocorticoid receptor interacting protein 1

H.Pylori	:	<i>Helicobacter pylori</i>
HAT	:	Histone acetyltransferase
hCAR	:	Co-transfection with human CAR
HCC	:	Hepatocellular carcinoma
HDACs	:	Histone deacetylases
HDCA	:	Histidine decarboxylase
HEPES	:	(4-(2-hydroxyethyl)-1-piperazineethanesulfonic acid
HepG2	:	Hepato carcinoma cells
HMG	:	High mobility group
HNF	:	Hepatic nuclear factor
HNF4 α	:	Hepatic nuclear factor 4 alpha
HPLC	:	High Performance/Pressure liquid chromatography
hPXR	:	Human pregnane X receptor
hs-CRP	:	High sensitivity C-reactive protein
Hsp	:	Heat shock protein
IL	:	Interleukin
IMs	:	Intermediate metabolizers
IPA	:	Inhibition of platelet aggregation/activity
JPT	:	Japanese in Tokyo, Japan
kb	:	Kilo bases
KCl	:	Potassium Chloride
LD	:	Linkage disequilibrium
LPZ	:	Lansoprazole
LXR	:	Liver X receptor
MAF	:	Minor allele frequency
mg	:	Milligram
MgCl ₂	:	Magnesium Chloride

ml	:	Milli liters
miRNA	:	MicroRNAs
MR	:	Metabolic ratios
mRNA	:	Messenger RNA
MTZ	:	Metronidazole
N	:	Sample size/number
NCBI	:	National centre for Biotechnology information
N-CoR	:	Nuclear corepressor
NCoR2	:	Nuclear receptor corepressor
ng	:	Nano gram
nm	:	Nano meter
NRX	:	Nucleoredoxin
NSAIDs	:	Non steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs
OD	:	Optical density
OFH	:	Observed frequency of heterozygosity
OPZ	:	Omeprazole
OR	:	Odds ratio
PAGE	:	Polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis
PCI	:	Percutaneous coronary interventions
PCR	:	Polymerase chain reaction
PDB	:	Protein data bank
PG	:	Proguanil
PMs	:	Poor metabolizers
PMSF	:	Phenyl methyl sulfonyl fluoride
PP-2A	:	Protein phosphatase 2A
PPAR	:	Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor
PPIs	:	Proton pump inhibitors

pRL-SV40	:	Renilla luciferase plasmid
PTZ	:	Pantoprazole
PXR	:	Pregnane X receptor
PXRRE	:	Pregnane X receptor response element
q.d	:	Quaque die/once daily
q.i.d	:	Quater in diem/ four times a day
RBTM	:	Rabeprazole, Bismuth subcitrate, Tetracycline, Metronidazole
RBZ	:	Rabeprazole
RFLP	:	Restriction fragment length polymorphism
RLA	:	Relative luciferase activity
RMSD	:	Root mean square deviation
RNA	:	Ribonucleid acid
RNA pol II	:	RNA polymerase II
rsID	:	Reference SNP ID
RXR	:	Retinoid receptors
SC	:	Score- Shape Complementarity score
SDS	:	Sodium Dodecyl sulphate
SIT	:	South Indian TAMILIAN
SLE	:	Systemic lupus erythematosus
SMRT	:	Silencing mediator of retinoid and thyroid receptor
SNPs	:	Single nucleotide polymorphism
SPSS	:	Statistical Package for the Social Sciences
SRC-1	:	Steroid receptor co-activator -1
STEMI	:	ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction
TBP	:	TATA-binding protein
TBS	:	Transcription factor binding site
TBS	:	Transcription factor binding site

TF	:	Transcription factor
TF-TBS	:	Transcription factor and its binding site complex
TID	:	Ter in die/three times a day
TNF-alpha	:	Tumor necrosis factor-alpha
TNZ	:	Tinidazole
UMs	:	Ultra rapid metabolizers
VASP	:	Vasodilator-stimulated Phosphoprotein
WHO	:	World health organisation
YRI	:	Yoruba in Ibadan, Nigeria

Introduction

1.0 Introduction

The therapeutic response and occurrence of adverse events to most of the therapeutic agents is related to their and/or its active metabolite plasma levels. Drug metabolism not only inactivates the therapeutically active drug, but may also activates the therapeutically inactive drug and rarely results in the formation of toxic metabolites.¹ Drug metabolism also includes conversion of lipophilic agents to hydrophilic metabolites which facilitates their excretion via urine. The drug levels in the individuals receiving same dose of drug may vary which can be attributed to environmental factors, genetic factors and other patient characteristics. Thus interindividual variability in drug metabolism decides the duration and magnitude of the clinical response and adverse effects to most of the therapeutic agents.¹

Cytochrome P450s constitute a super family of heme-containing enzymes crucial for the oxidative, peroxidative, and reductive metabolism of xenobiotics, endogenous compounds such as steroids, bile acids, fatty acids, prostaglandins, leukotrienes, and environmental pollutants.^{2,3} Cytochrome P450 enzymes were classified based on the sequence homology of the amino acids into families (e.g. CYP2), sub families (e.g. CYP2C), and individual enzymes (e.g. CYP2C19). Alleles on the same gene are designated by an asterisk and number (e.g. *CYP2C19*2*). There are about 57 genes coding for the functional cytochrome P450 enzymes and were grouped into 50 distinct families in humans and are largely expressed in liver and intestine.² In liver CYP3A4 is the most abundant (28.8%), followed by the CYP2C family (18.2%), CYP1A2 (12.7%), CYP2E1 (7%), CYP2A6 (4%), CYP2D6 (1.5%) and CYP2B6 (0.2%). Of these, CYP3A metabolizes more than half of the currently prescribed drugs (51%), followed by CYP2D6 (24%) and the CYP2C subfamily (~20%).⁴

The human *CYP2C19* gene located on chromosome 10 encodes the cytochrome P450 enzyme CYP2C19, involved in the metabolism of xenobiotics. The CYP2C19 is a clinically important enzyme, which is known to play a major role in metabolizing about 5 % of the clinically used drugs such as omeprazole, diazepam, proguanil, voriconazole, nelfinavir, clopidogrel, several antidepressants, and some of the endogenously produced hormones such as steroids. The *CYP2C19* gene is expressed polymorphically.⁵⁻⁹ Owing to genetic polymorphisms, considerable interindividual variability exists in the metabolic activity of this enzyme.¹⁰ About 25 variant alleles of *CYP2C19* have been reported till

date (<http://www.imm.ki.se/CYPalleles>, access date: 14th July 2010). Of these, the most common defective variants are *2 (681G>A; splicing defect in exon 5) and *3 (636G>A; premature stop codon in exon 4). Population studies have described the bimodal distribution of subjects based on their metabolizing capacity of the enzyme.⁶

Studies on the genetic variability of *CYP2C19* gene and its activity have helped to identify the relationship between the genotypes of *CYP2C19* and its activity. Most of the genotype-phenotype association studies of *CYP2C19* in different ethnic groups were focused on exonic region variations, wherein the measurement of probe drug and its metabolite level in plasma or urine have been performed.¹¹⁻¹⁵ Based on the findings of these studies, subjects were categorized as poor metabolizers (PMs), having either of the most commonly seen defective alleles of *CYP2C19* namely c.636G>A (*3 allele; rs4986893) or c.681G>A (*2 allele; rs4244285); extensive metabolizers (EMs) carrying no variant alleles; and ultra-rapid metabolizers (UMs) carrying -806C>T and -3402 C>T variations (*17 allele) in the promoter region of *CYP2C19*.¹⁶ Thus, the activity of *CYP2C19* varies with the presence or absence of certain variations in its gene.¹² Variations in the distribution of these polymorphisms exist among various ethnic groups, with the incidence of PMs among Caucasians (1-6%), Asians (13-16%), Africans (4-8%), Orientals (8-11%) and South Indians (14%).¹⁷⁻²⁰

In recent past, a novel variant allele (*CYP2C19**17, -806C>T and -3402C>T which are in linkage disequilibrium with each other; rs12248560) in the 5'- flanking region was found to be associated with increased *CYP2C19* activity resulting in ultra-rapid metabolism of the *CYP2C19* substrates.¹⁶ Of the 25 variant alleles which exist in *CYP2C19*, the functional characterization was done for only a few of these polymorphisms in the exonic region.²¹⁻²³ Studies on clinical significance of these variations particularly *2 (c.681G>A; splicing defect in Exon 5) and *3(c.636G>A; pre mature stop codon in Exon 4) showed PM phenotype resulting in greater cure rates in gastric ulcers treated with normal dose of proton pump inhibitors (PPIs).²⁴ Recently, another study had shown the poor response to clopidogrel therapy in subjects carrying *CYP2C19**2 and *3 alleles compared to normal subjects resulting from inefficient activation of clopidogrel to its active metabolite in *2 and *3 allele carriers.²⁵ The poor response to clopidogrel therapy in subjects taking omeprazole as concomitant therapy had also been reported recently indicating the inhibitory potential of omeprazole on *CYP2C19* activity.²⁶

CYP2C19 activity differs among extensive metabolizers (EM), demonstrated by a wide range in the metabolic ratios (MR) of omeprazole.^{15;27} Previous study on effect of the *CYP2C19* genotype on MR of omeprazole in our laboratory reported discrepancies in genotype-phenotype association in 8% of the study subjects.²⁸ These differences could be attributed to rare heterozygous alleles like *4, *5 and *6 only to a small extent. As they were found to be absent in the South Indian population, an alternative explanation for these discrepancies could be polymorphisms in the regulatory region of *CYP2C19* gene, which might affect the amount and time taken for the appearance of the functional product of the CYP2C19 enzyme.²⁸

Promoter region variants influence the enzyme activity by altering the gene expression.²⁹ Overlapping distribution of exonic region genotype among the PMs and EMs of CYP2C19 substrates had provoked an interest in the promoter region of the gene.^{13;14} The promoter region controls gene expression by the interaction of *cis*-acting elements spanning through the promoter region with the transcription factors. Any variations in these *cis*-acting elements may alter the gene expression.²⁹ Few studies have reported the promoter region variations and only one study i.e. by Arefayene et al was available before the initiation of the present study.^{21;22;30} The study by Arefayene *et al* characterized various segments of *CYP2C19* promoter region showing the existence of positive elements and negative elements between -220 to -17 and -650 to -450 bp, respectively.²² The same study had also reported eight common variants in the *CYP2C19* promoter region among the African Americans and Europeans without the functional characterization of the variants. Potential binding sites for the transcription factors such as GATA proteins, progesterone receptor, TATA box elements and nuclear factors in *CYP2C19* promoter region have also been described in the same study.²² A recent study reported the presence of about five variations in the promoter region of *CYP2C19* in Japanese population. The same study described the haplotype structures and linkage disequilibrium (LD) analysis between various variations in the promoter, enhancer, exonic, and intronic regions of *CYP2C19*.³⁰ Functional characterization of these polymorphisms had not been performed in any of these studies. No such study was performed in a unique population like Indian population.

The polymorphisms in the 5' regulatory region may affect the transcription of the enzyme and in turn may influence the enzyme activity. Thus the present study aimed to identify

variations in 5'-flanking region of *CYP2C19* gene in South Indian population, to estimate the haplotype frequencies and to predict the influence of these variations on functional activity of the CYP2C19 enzyme *in silico*, *in vitro* and *in vivo*. Establishment of allele and genotype frequencies of functionally important allelic variants had also been attempted in this study. The possibility of presence of copy number variations in *CYP2C19* gene was also explored.

Review of

Literature

2.0 Review of Literature

2.1 Drug metabolism and role of Cytochrome P450 2C family of enzymes

Drugs or therapeutic agents administered undergo chemical modification or conjugation in the liver or sometimes in gut by certain enzymes in order to facilitate their excretion from the body. Drug metabolism in most of the cases results in the conversion of lipophilic agent to hydrophilic agent so that it can be easily excreted via urine.¹ Generally drug metabolism yields an inactive metabolite from the active drug, but sometimes an active metabolite may also be formed from an inactive drug (cycloguanil is an active metabolite formed from proguanil). In some cases the metabolites formed also exhibit the same pharmacological action similar to the parent drug (benzodiazepines). There is also a possibility of formation of more toxic compound from a nontoxic parent drug (N-acetyl-p-benzoquinone imine metabolite from paracetamol).¹ It is a well-known fact that the clinical response or adverse effect to most of the therapeutic agents is related to the plasma level of the drug and/or its metabolite. Hence, variability in the drug metabolism may lead to interindividual differences in the clinical response or occurrence of adverse effect to a drug.¹

The metabolism of drugs or xenobiotics occurs in specific tissues like liver with the involvement of specific enzymes in different phases. Phase I reactions include oxidation, reduction or hydrolysis reactions, whereas phase II reactions include conjugation reactions with sulfate or glucuronide.¹ Phase I reactions are mainly catalysed by a complex enzyme system known as the mixed function oxygenase system known as cytochrome P450 enzymes.

2.1.1 Cytochrome P450 enzymes

Cytochrome P450 is a super family of heme-containing mono-oxygenases located in the smooth endoplasmic reticulum of the cell. They are particularly abundant in the liver and intestine and are also found to be present to a smaller extent in brain and other tissues.³¹ The reduced form of iron in these enzymes (Fe^{+2}) forms a complex with that of carbon monoxide which has absorbance peak maximum at a wavelength of 450 nm and hence these enzymes are called as P450 enzymes.³¹ Cytochrome P450 super family of isoenzymes consists of families (>40% similarity) and sub families (>60% similarity) based on the homology of the amino acid sequence among these enzymes.² About 57

functional cytochrome genes are encoded by our human genome.³ In addition to metabolizing the drugs some families are involved in the metabolism of endogenous substances such as cholesterol, arachidonic acid and steroids.^{5,32} These enzymes are designated with a prefix CYP followed by an arabic numeral representing the family, a capital letter that follows the arabic numeral indicating the subfamily, and a second arabic number indicating the individual isoenzyme. Each CYP isoform is a product of specific gene and exhibits a characteristic spectrum of substrate specificity.³³ The major CYP enzymes involved in the drug metabolism of humans include 1, 2 and 3 and the specific isoforms involved are CYP1A2, CYP2E1, CYP2C9, CYP2C19, CYP2D6, CYP3A4 and CYP3A5.^{2,33,34} Out of which CYP3A4 and A5 are involved in the metabolism of almost 50 % of therapeutically active agents and constitutes of about 25% of the liver cytochrome content.³⁵ CYP2D6 metabolizes approximately 24 % of drugs, and CYP2C family is involved in the metabolism of 20 % drugs. Even though 2C family and 2D6 constitute about 26 % and 3 % of the total liver content, they are involved in the metabolism of around 45 % (20 % by 2C family, and 25 % by 2D6) clinically important drugs (Figure 1). The genes encoding these enzymes are polymorphic with different alleles and most of them are inducible except for CYP2D6.³⁻⁵

Figure 1. A) Major cytochrome P 450 content of human liver; B) Proportion of drugs metabolized by individual cytochrome P 450 enzymes. About 70 % of liver P-450 could be accounted for by P-450 1A2, 2A6, 2B6, 2C, 2D6, 2E1 and 3A proteins, with P-450 3A (about 30% of total P-450) and 2C (about 20%) enzymes as the major forms. Considerable levels of P-450 1A2 (about 13 %) and 2E1 (about 7 %) could be determined, whereas the P-450 2A6 (about 4 %), 2D6 (about 2 %) and 2B6 (< 1 %) were the minor P-450 forms. CYP3A4 metabolizes 50 % of drugs followed by CYP2D6 (25%) and CYP2C family (20%).³⁶

2.1.2 CYP2C family

The four isoforms CYP2C8, CYP2C9, CYP2C18 and CYP2C19 belonging to the CYP2C family represents ~ 18 % of the total hepatic CYP content. This family of enzymes metabolizes about 20 % of the commonly used therapeutic agents.⁵ The genes encoding these enzymes are located on chromosome 10q24 in the order of *CYP2C18-CYP2C19-CYP2C9-CYP2C8*. CYP2C proteins are predominantly expressed in the order of 2C9>2C8>2C19. CYP2C18 is principally expressed only in the level of mRNA and does not appear as protein.³⁷ In addition to liver these enzymes are also expressed in extra hepatic tissues such as brain, gut, heart, lung and aorta.³⁸ CYP2C9 metabolizes therapeutically important drugs such as non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), phenytoin, warfarin, glibenclamide, losartan etc.^{32;39} CYP2C19 is involved in the metabolism of omeprazole, clopidogrel, proguanil, voriconazole, cyclophosphamide, nelfinavir, diazepam, etc.^{5;6;12;40-42} Some of the substrates such as clopidogrel, glibenclamide, phenytoin, warfarin undergo metabolism by both CYP2C9 and CYP2C19 with variability in their relative contribution to the metabolism of these agents.^{6;32;43} The genes encoding CYP2C enzymes are polymorphic with different alleles. Till date 25 variant alleles have been reported for *CYP2C19* and 33 variant alleles have been reported for *CYP2C9* (<http://www.imm.ki.se/CYPalleles>, access date: 14th July 2010).⁴⁴ The other two isoforms CYP2C8, CYP2C18 are involved in the metabolism of thiozolidinediones, cilostazol, zopiclone, and some NSAIDs.⁵ The CYP2C isoforms are also known to be involved in the metabolism of endogenous substances such as arachidonic acid, estrogens and some steroids.^{5;45} CYP2C family genes are also involved in the hydroxylation of retinoic acid and also play a role in generation of biologically active molecules such as epoxyeicosatrienoic acids (EETs) and hydroxyl ETs from arachidonic acid in liver and other tissues.⁴⁶⁻⁴⁸

2.1.3 CYP2C19

CYP2C19 (OMIM 124020) is one of the most important enzymes contributing to the metabolism of clinically used drugs, although relative to other CYP isoforms, it is expressed at low levels almost exclusively in the liver and small intestine.^{49;50} *CYP2C19* gene is located in the same *CYP2C* gene cluster as *CYP2C9*, and it is fairly large gene, spanning over a 90-kb genomic region that consists of nine exons and large intronic regions spanning on chromosome 10 (10q24.1-q24.3) (Figure 2). The

three-dimensional structure of CYP2C19 has not yet been resolved, but it can be predicted to a great extent from the structure of CYP2C9.⁵¹ CYP2C19 and CYP2C9 enzymes differ by 43 residues out of 490, and the differences in substrate selectivity may be more due to the structure of the substrate-access channel than the amino acids within their active sites.⁵¹

Figure 2. Location of CYP2C19 and other CYP2C genes on chromosome 10. CYP2C19 has nine exons and lies between CYP2C18 and CYP2C9 on chromosome 10. The genes of CYP2C family are homologous and CYP2C19 and CYP2C9 are about >90% homologous (96% sequence similarity; 92% amino acid similarity) to each other.

Details of CYP2C19 gene: CYP2C19 (MIM: 124020); location: Chromosome 10; 10q24.1-q24.3; Reference sequence ID: NC_000010.10 (96522463..96612671); mRNA sequence ID: NM_000769.1; Gene ID: 1557.

2.1.4 Phenotype categories

Based on the metabolic capacity of CYP2C19 subjects can be divided into extensive metabolizers (EMs) who carry no defective variant alleles in CYP2C19 gene. Subjects carrying the defective alleles on one chromosome (heterozygous) with intermediate capacity of CYP2C19 can be designated as intermediate metabolizers (IMs), whereas subjects homozygous for the defective alleles with diminished CYP2C19 activity are designated as poor metabolizers (PMs). Subjects homozygous for alleles which increase the CYP2C19 expression or activity with greater CYP2C19 activity than EMs are designated as ultra-rapid metabolizers (UMs) (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Classification of phenotypes and the prediction of clinical outcome in different phenotype categories. The clinical outcome varies between phenotype categories depending upon the drug whether it is active or inactive and the metabolite whether it is therapeutically active or harmful. ADR: Adverse drug reaction.

2.1.5 Role of CYP2C19 in drug metabolism

CYP2C19 is primarily located in hepatic tissues and a significant amount is also found in the gut. CYP2C19 is responsible for the metabolism of approximately 10 % of commonly used therapeutic agents, including proton pump inhibitors (PPIs, e.g. omeprazole, lansoprazole, pantoprazole), antidepressants (imipramine, amitriptyline, sertraline, fluoxetine) anticonvulsants (phenytoin, S-mephenytoin), hypnotics (diazepam, flunitrazepam, phenobarbital), antimalarial (proguanil), antiretroviral (nelfinavir), antifungal (voriconazole), and antiplatelet drugs (clopidogrel) (Table 1).^{6;12;41;42} These substrates are usually amides or weak bases with two hydrogen bond acceptors.^{52;53} The relatively high frequencies of non-functional *CYP2C19* variants in some populations indicate that the enzyme does not have a major endogenous role. Indeed, for the few endogenous substrates identified, such as farnesol and melatonin, CYP2C19-mediated metabolism represents only a minor pathway.^{54;55} The details of the substrates and genotype-phenotype association studies and studies related to the utility of *CYP2C19* genotype are discussed under heading “genotype-phenotype association studies of CYP2C19 and clinical utility of *CYP2C19* genotyping”. The inducers and inhibitors are discussed under the heading “CYP2C19 induction, inhibition and drug interactions involving CYP2C19”.

Table 1. List of common substrates, inducers and inhibitors of CYP2C19^{5;12;56}

	Substrates	Inducers	Inhibitors
CYP2C19	Omeprazole (probe drug)	Carbamazepine	Omeprazole
	Lansoprazole	Norethindrone	Pantoprazole
	Pantoprazole	Phenobarbital	Rabeprazole
	Rabeprazole	Prednisone	Lansoprazole
	Proguanil (probe drug)	Rifampicin	Chloramphenicol
	Clopidogrel	<i>Ginko biloba</i>	Cimetidine
	S-mephenytoin (probe drug)		Felbamate
	Phenobarbitone		Fluoxetine
	Diazepam		Fluvoxamine
	Amitriptyline		Indomethacin
	Carisoprodol		Ketoconazole
	Citalopram		Modafinil
	Clomipramine		Oxcarbazepine
	Fluoxetine		Probenicid
	Sertraline		Ticlopidine
	Indomethacin		Topiramate
	Moclobemide		Grape fruit juice
	Teniposide		
	Cyclophosphamide		
	Propranolol		
	Nelfinavir		
	Voriconazole		
	Gliclazide		
	Phenytoin		
	Estradiol		
	Arachidonic acid		
	Endogenous steroids like testosterone and progesterone		

2.2 Inter individual variability in metabolism of *CYP2C19* substrates

There exists inter individual variability in the metabolism of the drugs including the substrates of *CYP2C19*.⁵⁷

2.2.1 Genetic sources of variation

Polymorphism is defined as the existence of two or more genetically determined forms (alleles) in a population in substantial frequency. In practice, a polymorphic gene is one which has a frequency of its most common allele less than 0.99.

About 15-30% of the variability in drug metabolism could be attributed to the genetic factors.⁵⁸ For the first time Kupfer *et al* in the year 1984 showed that the deficiency in (S)-mephenytoin hydroxylase is a monogenic trait. Followed by the study by Wrighton *et al* revealing that (S)-mephenytoin hydroxylase is the cytochrome P450 2C19 (*CYP2C19*).⁵⁹ Goldstein and co-workers cloned individual *CYP2C* enzymes in 1994 and tested activity towards (S)-mephenytoin *in vitro*.⁶⁰

2.2.2 *CYP2C19* Genetic variants:

The gene coding for *CYP2C19* is polymorphic and several variant alleles have been identified. Of the 25 variant alleles of *CYP2C19* that have been described to date, the two most common variants are *CYP2C19**2 and *3, both of which result in the total absence of enzyme activity.¹² The presence of other alleles also cannot be ignored especially in specific isolated populations. Recently, an allele in the promoter region also has been studied widely and was found to be present at detectable frequencies in most of the populations studied.¹⁶ It has been found that defective alleles other than *2 and *3 are absent in some populations and some of them are specific to a populations.²⁸ The details of the base change, aminoacid change, and the effect of the variations studied are given in the table 2.

Table 2. Details of the allelic variants of *CYP2C19* gene

<i>CYP2C19</i> allele	Nucleotide change (Ref : NM_000769.1)	NCBI rsID	Effect	Protein change (Ref: NP_000760.1)	Enzyme activity	Reference
*1	No variation	---	---	Normal	Normal	---
*2	c.681G>A in exon 5	rs4244285	Splicing defect	Termination	None	61
*3	c.636G>A in exon 4	rs4986893	Pre mature stop codon	Truncated	None	62
*4	c.1A>G in start codon	rs28399504	Start codon variation	No translation (p.Met1Val)	None	63
*5	c.1297C>T in exon 8	rs56337013	Aminoacid change	p.Arg433Trp	None	64
*6	c.395G>A in exon 3	rs3758581	Aminoacid change	p.Arg132Gln	None	65
*7	g. 19294T>A in intron 5	--	Nucleotide change at 5' splice site of intron 5	Splicing defect	None	66
*8	c. 358T>C in exon 3	rs41291556	Aminoacid change	p.Trp120Arg	Decreased	66
*9	c.431G>A in exon 3	rs17884712	Aminoacid change	p.Arg144His	Decreased (In vitro)	21
*10	c.680C>T in exon 5	rs6413438	Aminoacid change	p.Pro227Leu	Decreased	21
*11	c.449G>A in exon 3	--	Aminoacid change	p.Arg150His	---	21
*12	c.1473A>C in exon 9	rs55640102	Stop codon changes	stop491 Cys (p.X491CysextX)	Unstable	21
*13	c.1228C>T in exon 8	rs17879685	Aminoacid change	p.Arg410 Cys	---	21

Continued ...

Table 2. Details of the allelic variants of *CYP2C19* gene

<i>CYP2C19</i> allele	Nucleotide change (Ref : NM_000769.1)	NCBI rsID	Effect	Protein change (Ref: NP_000760.1)	Enzyme activity	Reference
*14	c.50T>C	rs55752064	Aminoacid change	p.Leu17 Pro	---	21
*15	c.55A>C	rs17882687	Aminoacid change	p.Ile19 Leu	---	21
*16	c. 1324C>T in exon 9	----	Aminoacid change	Arg442Cys	---	67
*17	c.-806C>T and c.-3402C>T	rs12248560	Increased transcription	Nucleotide change in 5' flanking region	Increased	16
*18	c. 991A>G, c.99C>T, c.986G>A	rs3758581	Aminoacid change	Arg329Gly; Ile331Val	----	30
*19	c.991A>G, c.99C>T; c.151A>G;	rs3758581	Aminoacid change	Ser51Gly; Ile331Val	-----	30
*20	636G>A; 991A>G; 1078G>A; 1251A>C	----	Aminoacid change	Trp212X; Asp360Asn; Ile331Val	----	30
*21	99C>T; 481G>C; 681G>A; 990C>T; 991A>G	-----	Aminoacid change	Ala161Pro; Ile331Val	splicing defect	30
*22	557G>C; 991A>G	-----	Aminoacid change	p.Arg186Pro; p.Ile331Val	----	68
*23	99C>T; 271G>C; 991A>G	-----	Aminoacid change	p.Gly91Arg; p.Ile331Val	----	69
*24	99C>T; 991A>G; 1004G>A; 1197A>G	-----	Aminoacid change	p.Ile331Val; p.Arg335Gln	----	69
*25	99C>T; 991A>G; 1344C>G	-----	Aminoacid change	p.Ile331Val; p.Phe448Leu	----	69
*26	99C>T; 766G>A; 991A>G	-----	Aminoacid change	p. Asp256Asn	----	70

2.2.3 Non genetic sources of variation

Non genetic sources of variation include the age, pathological status and environment. It is well known that CYP enzyme activity will be less in elderly compared to adults and in pathological states such as liver diseases which could diminish the CYP enzyme content and its activity. The food intake also affects the CYP content and their expression in the liver for e.g. high protein diet may increase the expression of CYP enzymes in liver.^{1,31} Gender and age also have an impact on the expression of CYP genes and is discussed under the heading “influence of gender on *CYP2C19* transcription”.

2.3 Interethnic variability in distribution of *CYP2C19* alleles

Ethnicity is an important factor contributing to inter-patient and inter-ethnic variability in drug response and toxicity. Such differences in drug response have been attributed to single nucleotide polymorphisms in drug metabolizing enzymes, transporters and targets. There is a large interindividual variability in the activity of *CYP2C19*. In recent years, numerous studies have been done in establishing the frequencies of variant alleles signifying the diversity among different populations.

A comparison of the variant allele frequencies of *CYP2C19* in the South Indian population with other ethnic groups revealed significant interethnic differences in the distribution of *CYP2C19* variants (Table 3). The frequency of *CYP2C19**2 and *3 in South Indians were 35% and 1% respectively. The frequency of *CYP2C19**2 was significantly higher than African Americans (18.2-25%) and other populations of African origins reported from Beninese (13%), Tanzania (17.9%), Ethiopia (14%), Zimbabwe (13.1%) and Ghana (6%). It was also higher than Caucasians (9.1 – 22%), Turkish (13%), Latin Americans (7.8-8.7%), Mexican Americans (9.7%), Iran (14%), Russians (11.4%), Jewish Israeli (15%), Egypt (11%), Saudi (15%) and Canadian Indians (19.1%). Further, it was relatively even higher than Caucasians reported from Croatia (0.15%) and Faroese Islands (2.9%). It was lower than Chinese (45.5%) and Vanuatu pacific islanders (63.3%). However, it was similar to East Asians (28.9%), South Asians (31.2%), Japanese (23-35%), Thai (35.1%), Hans Chinese (28.8-36.6%), Chinese Dai (30.3%), Chinese Taiwanese (32%) and Filipino (39%) (Table 3).

On the whole, a general uniformity was observed in Asians with respect to *CYP2C19**2 except Koreans and Chinese Bai, Kazakh, Uygur populations. The only other study

reporting the frequency of *CYP2C19* alleles in healthy native Indians was carried out by Lamba *et al* in the North Indian population. No significant differences was observed in the *CYP2C19**2 frequencies between South and North Indians, but *CYP2C19**3 was absent in North Indians. It indicates that the *2 allele frequency in North Indians was similar to that of Asians but resembled Caucasians in the total absence of *3 allele (Table 3).

The *CYP2C19**3 allele frequency in South Indians was comparable with Thai (2%), African Americans (0.8%), Tanzanians (0.6%), Ethiopians (2%), Africans (0.2%), Caucasians (0.9%), Swedish (0.7%), Turkish (0.4-1%), Russians (0.3%), Jewish Israeli (1%) and Egypt (0.2%). Conversely, it was significantly lower than other Asian populations reported from East Asians 9.6%, South Asians 5.7%, Japanese 10.4-11%, Koreans, Chinese ethnicities 4.5-9.4%, Chinese Taiwanese 5.5% and Filipino 8% as well as African Americans 10%. It was much lower than Vanuatu pacific islanders 13.3%. In contrast, it was significantly higher than Africans 0.4%, Caucasians 0.2%, Dutch 0.2%, Germans 0.2%, Mexican Americans 0.1%, and Bolivians 0.1% (Table 3).

The *CYP2C19**3 variant allele was rare in Caucasians and South American populations while it was prevalent in Asian populations (1-11.7%). The prevalence of *CYP2C19* variant allele in Vanuatu pacific islanders is the highest reported frequency (77.7%) so far. In a study conducted in 100 malaria patients to examine the effect of *CYP2C19* genotypes on the disposition of proguanil, the frequencies of *CYP2C19**2 and *3 were found to be 57% and 25%, respectively. Sixty eight percent (68%) of the patients had the poor metabolizer genotype. This was higher than any *CYP2C19* PM frequency reported in any other population (Table 3).

To further elucidate the high frequency of the PM genotype in the island of Vanuatu, Kaneko *et al* genotyped 5538 individuals from 24 populations of 16 different islands of Vanuatu. The frequencies of *CYP2C19**1, *2 and *3 were 22.3%, 63.3% and 14.4% respectively. The average PM genotype frequency was 61%, which ranged from 38-79% among the sub-populations. These frequencies were significantly higher than those reported to date in other ethnic groups. In addition, the analysis of *CYP2C19* variants in Croatians yielded an exceedingly low frequency of 0.15%, a trait which did not match with any other populations. Furthermore, the frequencies of *CYP2C19* variants were higher in Asians (23.4-50%) compared to Africans (6-28.3%) and Caucasians (0.15-22%) (Table 3).

Finally, *CYP2C19* variant allele frequencies of South Indians were distinctly different from Koreans, Africans and Caucasians (Table 3). The distribution of PMs among different populations varied, reflecting the defective allele frequencies in that population (Table 4). The genotype-phenotype studies using different probe drugs such as omeprazole, S-mephenytoin and proguanil established the EMs and PMs frequencies in different ethnic groups with highest PMs frequency in Asians. The PM phenotype frequencies in different ethnic groups are given in table 4.

Table 3. Distribution of common defective variant allele frequencies of *CYP2C19* in various populations and comparison with South Indians

Population	N	Variant Allele Frequency %		Reference
		<i>CYP2C19</i> *2	<i>CYP2C19</i> *3	
Asians				
East Asians	161	28.9	9.6*	71
South Asians	80	31.2	5.7*	71
Japanese	217	27.4	10.8*	72
Japanese	500	30.3	13.1*	73
Chinese	121	45.5*	4.5*	74
Korean	103	20.9*	11.7*	18
Korean	200	28.6	7.6*	73
Thai	121	35.1	5*	74
South Indian	341	35	1	75
North Indian	121	30	0	76
Chinese Han	101	36.6	7.5*	64
Chinese Bai	202	25.7*	5.5*	64
Chinese Kazakh	149	15.4*	8*	77
Chinese Uygur	107	16.1*	9.4*	77
Chinese Han	103	28.8	7.2*	77
Chinese Dai	193	30.3	3.4*	11
Chinese Taiwanese	118	32	5.5*	17
Chinese	398	30.7	4.5*	73
Japanese	53	23	10.4*	17

Continued...

Table 3. Distribution of common defective variant allele frequencies of CYP2C19 in various populations and comparison with South Indians

Population	N	Variant Allele Frequency %		Reference
		<i>CYP2C19*2</i>	<i>CYP2C19*3</i>	
Japanese	140	35	11*	78
Filipino	52	39	8*	17
Thai	107	27*	2	79
Africans Africans Americans#	481	18.3*	10*	80
Africans Americans	236	18.2*	0.8	71
Beninese	111	13*	0	81
Zimbabwean	336	13.1*	0	82
African Americans	108	25*	0	17
African	922	17.3*	0.4*	83
Tanzanian	251	17.9*	0.6	18
African	216	10*	0	84
Ethiopian	114	14*	2	85
Ghana	169	6*	0	86
Africans	250	19.2*	0.2	73
Caucasians Caucasians	273	12.7*	0.9	71
Spain#	32	22*	0	87
Spain#	200	16*	0	88
Caucasian	300	10.8*	0.2*	88
Dutch	765	13.3*	0.2*	89
Belgian	121	9.1*	0	81
American	210	12.9*	0	17
Canadian	304	11*	0	90
Danish	478	16.1*	0	91
Swedish	166	14.4*	0.7	92
German	280	15*	0	93
Australian	198	14.6*	0	94

Continued...

Table 3. Distribution of common defective variant allele frequencies of *CYP2C19* in various populations and comparison with South Indians

Population	N	Variant Allele Frequency %		Reference
		<i>CYP2C19</i> *2	<i>CYP2C19</i> *3	
Greek	283	13.1*	0	95
Croatian	200	0.15*	0	96
Italian	360	11.1*		97
European Americans	105	13*	0	17
Germans	328	15.9*	0.2*	98
Portuguese	153	13*	0	99
Swedish	160	16.6*	0	13
Faroese	312	2.9*	0	100
Caucasians	454	15*	0.1*	73
Others				
Turkish#	100	13*	1	101
Turkish	404	12*	0.4	98
Colombian	189	8.7*	0	102
Mexican Americans	346	9.7*	0.1*	71
Iranian	200	14*	0	103
Russian	290	11.4*	0.3	104
Bolivian	778	7.8*	0.1*	105
Jewish Israeli	140	15*	1	106
Egyptian	247	11*	0.2	107
Pacific Islanders	5538	63.3*	14.4*	108
Saudi Arabians	97	15*	0	17
Canadian Indian	159	19.1*	0	109

*Showed significant difference when compared to South Indians (p<0.05)

Patients

Table 4. Interethnic distribution of poor metabolizer phenotype of CYP2C19^{12;23;30;63;66;67;110-112}

	Ethnic group	PM (%)	Total PM (%)
Caucasian	Swedish	1.2-4.6(2.9)	3.03
	French	6	
	Danish	2.5-3.8(3.15)	
	Portuguese	1.3	
	Spanish	1.3	
	Australian	7	
	Russian	2.3	
	Estonian	0.95	
	Canadian	2.4	
	American	2-2.7(2.35)	
Asian and Middle East	South Indian	14-20(17)	21.51
	North Indian	11	
	Chinese	13.4-19.8(16.6)	
	Japanese	15.1-22.5(18.75)	
	Sri Lankan	13.4-19.8(16.6)	
	Indonesian	15.4	
	Korean	12.6	
	Vietnamese	21.6	
	South pacific Polynesian	13.6	
	Vantavu	79	
	Philipino	23.1	
	Turkish	0.94	
	Israeli	4.6	
	Greenland	2.9-9.3(6.1)	
	Jordanian	4.6	
	Saudi Arabian	2	
African	Ethiopian	5.2	4.3
	African-American	2-7(4.5)	
	Zimbabwean	4.0	
	Tanzanian	2.8-4.6(3.7)	
Others	Canadian Inuit	2	11.65
	Panama Cuna Indian	0	
	Australian aboriginals	25.6	
	Canadian Indian	19.1	

2.4 Genotype-phenotype association studies of CYP2C19 vs. clinical utility of CYP2C19 genotyping

2.4.1 Omeprazole and other proton pump inhibitors (PPIs)

Omeprazole is a benzimidazole derivative belonging to a group of agents known as proton pump inhibitors and is extensively hydroxylated to its primary metabolite 5-hydroxy-omeprazole by CYP2C19. Other proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) such as lansoprazole and rabeprazole are also hydroxylated by CYP2C19 to large extent. The variants in *CYP2C19* affect the metabolism of omeprazole and its pharmacokinetics. Omeprazole is used as a probe for evaluating the activity of *CYP2C19* as it is safer than S-mephenytoin.¹¹³ Several genotype-phenotype association studies using omeprazole as a probe drug and studies related to the clinical outcome of omeprazole therapy and its drug interactions indicate utilizing the pharmacogenetics knowledge for optimizing drug therapy.

The genotype-phenotype association study using omeprazole as a probe drug in South Indian population had established an antimode of 14.4 for omeprazole metabolic ratio i.e. ratio of concentration of omeprazole to 5-hydroxy omeprazole at 3 h after drug intake.²⁸ The study had reported PM frequency of 14 % in South Indian population, but about 7.7% of the subjects deviated from the genotype-phenotype association with no other variations in the exonic region. The reason for this discrepancy needs to be evaluated and the authors predicted that promoter region variants might have resulted in the deviation. Similarly, several genotype-phenotype association studies were performed in different ethnic groups and antimode was established in that particular population for differentiating PMs and EMs. A study in the Korean population had established an antimode of MR 6.95, with a PM frequency of 12.6%. The *CYP2C19* genotype explained 97% of the phenotypic PMs in this population.¹¹⁴ A study in North-Eastern Thai subjects, established an antimode of 7 with PM frequency of 6.5% with one individual value deviation.⁷⁹ Unlike South Indians, among North Indians an antimode of 50.1 was established with PM frequency of 11 %.¹¹⁵ The PM frequencies in different ethnic groups are given in table 4. These studies have also reported some discrepancies in the genotype-phenotype association, and it had also been found to show a wide range in the metabolic ratios of omeprazole in EMs, suggesting the role of some additional variants in the promoter region.^{15;27;28;79}

The gastric acid secretion inhibitory effect of proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) and their pharmacokinetics are well correlated with that of *CYP2C19* genotype. *CYP2C19* genotype can serve as a pharmacogenetic marker for predicting the PPIs therapeutic outcome in disorders such as gastroesophageal reflux disease, peptic ulcer and anti-*Helicobacter pylori* therapy. These are well studied all over the world.^{24;116-119;119-122} These studies have shown the increased therapeutic efficacy and better clinical outcome in PMs of *CYP2C19* i.e. subjects carrying defective alleles (*CYP2C19**2&*3) compared to EMs (*CYP2C19**1*1 genotype). But the *CYP2C19* genotype is unrelated to the adverse effects such as visual disorders and interstitial nephritis seen with that of PPIs.^{123;124} Recently, studies have also reported the increased metabolism of PPIs in carriers of *CYP2C19**17 allele suggesting the therapeutic failure or relapse in these subjects similar to that of EMs.^{16;125-127}

A study by Furuta *et al* has shown that pharmacogenomics based triple therapy of *H. pylori* (lansoprazole, clarithromycin and amoxicillin) with adjusted doses of lansoprazole in PMs (15 mg) and EMs (30 mg) of *CYP2C19* has resulted in the higher eradication rates (>92%) even in clarithromycin resistant strains of *H.pylori* against standard regimen (response rate <75%). The cost incurred for both genotypes based therapy and standard therapy per patient was USD 669 and USD 657, respectively. Thus this study has also shown that pharmacogenetics based therapy allowed full eradication of *H.pylori* without adding significant additional costs to the treatment.¹²²

In the treatment of *Helicobacter pylori* the eradication rate was higher in PMs of *CYP2C19* compared to EMs as observed in both dual therapy and triple therapy (Table 5). Thus the genotype-phenotype association studies in patients on omeprazole have shown greater efficacy and higher plasma levels of omeprazole and other PPIs in PMs (subjects carrying the defective alleles of *CYP2C19*) in conditions like gastritis and gastroesophageal reflux disease (Table 5 & 6). Lansoprazole and rabeprazole pharmacokinetics had been found to be influenced by *CYP2C19* activity (Table 6).¹²⁸ Even a recent study had shown that pantoprazole plasma levels were higher in subjects carrying defective alleles of *CYP2C19* compared to normal subjects.¹²⁹ From these studies it is clear that in ethnic groups like Caucasians increasing the dose of PPIs will be of more therapeutic value and economical as EMs frequency is more in Caucasians compared to Asians.

Table 5. Eradication of *H.pylori* with different PPI based therapies in relation to the *CYP2C19* genotypes

Treatment	Study parameter	N	Responders to therapy (%)				Ethnicity	References
			Homozygous EM (*1*1)	Heterozygous EM or IM (*1*2/*1*3/*2*17)	PM (*2*2/*3*3/*2*3)	UM (*1*17/*17*17)		
AMC (500 mg, TID) + OPZ (20 mg, BID) /RBZ (10mg BID)	<i>H.pylori</i> eradication rates	199	G1-74 G2-71	G1- 69 G2-77	G1-83 G2-73	---	Japanese	130
RBZ (10, 20, 40 mg, QD) AMC (750 mg, BD)/CAM (200 mg, BD) for 7 days	<i>H.pylori</i> eradication rates	102	86	----	77	---	Japanese	131
OPZ (20 mg, BID)/ LPZ (30 mg, BID) + AMC (500 mg TID)+CAM (200 mg TID) for 1 week	<i>H.pylori</i> eradication rates	261	73	92	98	--	Japanese	132
LPZ (30 mg QD for 8 weeks)	Cure rates for GERD	65	46	68	85	--	Japanese	119
LPZ(30 mg)/ RBZ (10 mg) + AMC (750 mg) + CAM (400 mg) for 1 week.	<i>H.pylori</i> eradication rates	187	G1-78 G2-89	---	G1-100 G2-86	---	Japanese	133
LPZ (30 mg) + AMC (1000 mg) + CAM (250 mg) + MTZ (400 mg) BID for 5 days	<i>H.pylori</i> eradication rates	131	80	98	100	---	Caucasian/ German	118
PTZ (40 mg) + AMC (1000 mg) + MTZ (500 mg) BID for 1 week, Followed by PTZ (40 mg) QD for 4 weeks	<i>H.pylori</i> eradication rates	125	52	88	100	61	Caucasian	125
LPZ+AMC+ CAM (30+500+200 BID for 14 days)	<i>H.pylori</i> eradication rates	139	58	67	76	--	Japanese	134
PTZ (40 mg)/EMZ +AMC (1000 mg)+CAM (5000 mg) BID for 7 days	<i>H.pylori</i> eradication rates	327	G1- 81 G2-87	----	G1- 96 G2-100	----	Korean	135

Continue...

Table 5. Eradication of *H.pylori* with different PPI based therapies in relation to the *CYP2C19* genotypes

Treatment	Study parameter	N	Responders to therapy (%)				Ethnicity	References
			Homozygous EM (*1*1)	Heterozygous EM or IM (*1*2/*1*3/*2*17)	PM (*2*2/*3*3/*2*3)	UM (*1*17/*17*17)		
OPZ(20 mg) + AMC(750 mg) + TNZ(500 mg) BID for 7 days followed by 20 mg of OPZ (qd) for 21 days	<i>H.pylori</i> eradication in gastritis	91	32	--	92	---	North Indians	136
LPZ (30 mg)+AMC (1000 mg)+ Clarithromycin (500 mg) BID for 14 days	<i>H.Pylori</i> eradication in chronic gastritis	105	70	92	80	---	Turks	137
G1. LPZ (30 mg)+CAM (500 mg)+AMC (1000 mg) BID for 7 days G2. RPZ (20 mg)+CAM (500 mg)+AMC (1000 mg) BID for 7 days	<i>H.Pylori</i> eradication rates	492	G1- 74 G2- 69	G1- 81 G2- 73	G1- 85 G2- 72	---	Koreans	138
EBTM/RBTM (Quadruple therapy)	<i>H.Pylori</i> eradication rates	155	68	88	86	---	Taiwanese	139
PTZ (40 mg) + AMC (1000 mg) + MTZ (500 mg) BID for 1 week followed by for 1 week, PTZ (40 mg) QD for 5 weeks.	<i>H. pylori</i> eradication in Peptic ulcer patients	139	68	89	100	74	Caucasian	129
RBZ (20 mg)+AMC(1000 mg)+ CAM (500 mg) BID for 2 weeks followed by RBZ (20 mg) for 8 weeks	<i>H.pylori</i> eradication in patients with cirrhosis and peptic ulcer.	91	81	90	100	-----	Chinese	140
Range of cures rates observed from all the studies	<i>cure rates range in different groups</i>	2609	32-87	67-98	72-100	61-74	----	---

AMC - amoxicillin; BID-bis in die; CAM - clarythromycin; EM - extensive metabolizer; EMZ - esomeprazole; EBTM - esomeprezole, bismuth subcitrate, tetracycline, metronidazole; LPZ - lansoprazole; PM - poor metabolizer; MTZ - metronidazole; OPZ - omeprazole; PTZ - pantoprazole; RBTM - rabeprazole, bismuth subcitrate, tetracycline, metronidazole; RBZ - rabeprazole; TID - ter in die; TNZ - tinidazole.; QD - quaque die; QID - quarter in dier; N - sample size.

Table 6. The pharmacodynamic /pharmacokinetics of different PPIs in relation to the *CYP2C19* genotypes

PPI treatment	Ethnicity	Parameter	CYP2C19 genotypes			Reference
			*1*1	*1*2/*1*3	*2*2/*3*3/*2*3	
OPZ (20 mg)QD X 1 day	Japanese	N	5	4	6	116
		Intragastric pH	2.14	3.3	4.47	
		OPZ AUC	421	1403	5109	
OPZ(20 mg) QD X 8days	Caucasians	N	6	6	2	141
		Intragastric pH	3.6	5.7	6.2	
LPZ (30 mg) QD X 7 days	Japanese	N	7	9	4	128
		Intragastric pH (day time)	3.1	3.5	6.2	
LPZ (30 mg) QD X 8 days	Chinese	N	5	5	5	142
		LPZ AUC	1700	2900	6600	
RPZ (10 mg)QD X 1 day	Japanese	N	5	6	4	143
		Intragastric pH	2.88	3.12	4.45	
		RPZ AUC	228	306	696	
LPZ (30 mg) QD X 8 days	Japanese	N	7	5	3	144
		Intagastric pH	4.4	4.9	5.4	
		LPZ AUC	2000	4400	9200	
RPZ (20 mg)QD X 8 days	Japanese	N	5	6	4	145
		Intagastric pH	3.8	3.8	6.1	
OPZ (20 mg) i.v. infusion BID	Japanese	N	5	5	5	146
		Intagastric pH	4.8	6.0	6.1	

AUC-area under the curve in ng.h/mL; BID-bis in die; OPZ-omperazole; LPZ-lansoprazole; RPZ-rabeprazole; N-number/sample size; QD-quaque die; PPI-proton pump inhibitor

2.4.2 Clopidogrel

Clopidogrel is a thienopyridine derivative used alone or in combination with aspirin for the secondary prevention of myocardial infarction. Clopidogrel drug is supposed to reduce the mortality in patients with acute ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) and in patients who are undergoing percutaneous coronary interventions (PCI). The drug is preferred to prevent the occurrence of restenosis in these patients.⁴¹

Clopidogrel undergoes activation to thiol metabolite in a two-step activation process involving various enzymes such as CYP2C19, CYP2B6, CYP1A2, CYP3A4, CYP2C9 and CYP3A5.^{25;41;147} Genes coding for various enzymes responsible for the conversion of clopidogrel to its active metabolite are polymorphic in expression. CYP2C19 is involved in both the steps of its activation. CYP2C19 contribute to around 44.9 % for the conversion of clopidogrel to the intermediate product 2-oxo-clopidogrel. The 2-oxo-clopidogrel needs to be converted to active metabolite to inhibit the receptor P2Y12. This step 2 also requires the contribution of cytochrome enzymes. CYP2C19 contributes around 20.7% for the conversion of 2-oxo-clopidogrel to thiol active metabolite. The variations in the genes alter the activity of the enzyme which in turn may alter the availability of the active metabolite of clopidogrel in plasma contributing to the variations in the response to the treatment.^{25;41;147;148} Clopidogrel is also metabolized by esterases to inactive carboxy metabolite whose levels can also be estimated for indirect measurement of plasma levels of active metabolite.⁴¹ Various studies including one land mark genome wide association studies have explored and established the influence of these genetic polymorphisms especially of CYP2C19 on clopidogrel response.¹⁴⁹ The USFDA(Food and drug administration of United states of America) has recently declared a black box warning for the usage of clopidogrel in patients carrying defective *CYP2C19* alleles and concomitant usage of proton pump inhibitors (omeprazole) which are inhibitors of this enzyme.¹⁵⁰

2.4.2.1 Variable response to clopidogrel and clinical utility of *CYP2C19* genotyping

The prevalence of individuals who are deemed to have an inadequate response to clopidogrel varies between 4% and 34%, depending on the method of testing and the definition of “resistance” or “hyporesponsiveness” used in the individual analyses.¹⁵¹ The incidence of restenosis in patients undergoing percutaneous coronary interventions is increasing inspite of treatment with clopidogrel.^{152;153} Most of the studies have found

non-responsiveness to clopidogrel which had been assessed clinically and also biochemically. The clinical assessment includes the development of adverse cardiovascular events as primary end point. The biochemical assessment is done by varied methods like measuring adenosine diphosphate (ADP) induced aggregation by optical methods, P2Y12 reactivity ratio by vasodilator-stimulated phosphoprotein (VASP) phosphorylation and flowcytometry assay of glycoprotein (Gp IIb/IIIa) expression etc. The most widely used method in assessing clopidogrel efficacy is platelet aggregation induced by ADP as agonist and evaluating the percentage of platelet inhibition. The current data shows that 30% of the patients do not respond to antiplatelet effect of clopidogrel.¹⁵³ A study in Indian sub-continent also showed that about 15.2% of patients respond inadequately to clopidogrel.¹⁵⁴ As the effects of clopidogrel are time and dose dependant, it is possible that changes in the metabolism of clopidogrel may affect its response due to altered formation of its active metabolite.

Matetzky *et al* in 2008 have reported that 25 % the patients undergoing PCI following STEMI had resistance to clopidogrel.¹⁵⁵ They have categorized the patients according to the level of platelet aggregation induced by ADP. The group exhibiting high levels of platelet aggregation also demonstrated higher risk of developing recurrent atherothrombotic events in subsequent follow up for a period of six months.

Guerbel *et al* (2005) have assessed the post treatment platelet reactivity in patients who have developed subacute stent thrombosis and who have not developed stent thrombosis. All these patients were on treatment with maintenance dose of clopidogrel (75 mg administered as q.i.d). The platelet aggregation was assessed by ADP induced aggregation by optical methods, P2Y12 reactivity ratio by VASP phosphorylation and Gp IIb/IIIa expression in response to ADP by flowcytometry. The results have clearly demonstrated higher post treatment platelet reactivity when the two groups were compared when adjusted for age.¹⁵⁶

There are many non-genetic factors which may be important to be considered. Compliance is an important factor contributing to the variable response. Concomitant therapy with proton pump inhibitors in most of these patients had been viewed as an important risk factor for the variable response. Proton pump inhibitors are potent inhibitors of this enzyme and affect the synthesis of the active metabolite of clopidogrel.²⁶

2.4.2.2 Loss of function polymorphisms of *CYP2C19* and Clopidogrel response:

The individuals who possess *CYP2C19**2 and *CYP2C19**3 alleles were considered as poor metabolizers. Several studies have well established the poor response to clopidogrel in these poor metabolizers.^{41;157} These studies have been done in healthy individuals and also in patients. The studies have correlated the clinical outcome with clopidogrel therapy as well as biochemical methods to evaluate the effect of clopidogrel. The biochemical methods available to evaluate the efficacy of clopidogrel includes ADP induced aggregation by optical methods, P2Y12 reactivity ratio by VASP phosphorylation and flow cytometry assay of Gp IIb/IIIa expression etc. The most common and widely used in various studies is ADP induced aggregation by optical methods. The resistance or non-responsiveness to clopidogrel is defined differently in various studies. The changes in maximal platelet aggregation from baseline are commonly used to assess the anti-platelet function.

Simon *et al*, studied the patients on clopidogrel following myocardial infarction for a period of one year. This study has nearly enrolled 2208 patients on clopidogrel therapy following myocardial infarction. They assessed the occurrence of death from any cause or non-fatal myocardial infarction or stroke. The study had included various pharmacogenetic determinants of clopidogrel response involved in absorption like (ABCB1), metabolic activation (*CYP3A5* and *CYP2C19*), and biologic activity (P2RY12). The risk was about 3.8 times higher among the patients with loss of function alleles in *CYP2C19* when compared with those with none of this alleles.¹⁵⁸

Another study in 162 healthy volunteers tested the association between plasma levels of active metabolite of clopidogrel and its platelet inhibition response. They also analysed the genetic determinants and cardiovascular outcome in 1477 subjects with myocardial infarction on clopidogrel. Statistically significant higher risk was demonstrated in individuals with reduced function of *CYP2C19* and they also had reduced levels of active metabolite of clopidogrel and reduced antiplatelet response.¹⁵⁸

A landmark genome wide association study to assess the pharmacogenetic markers for predicting the clopidogrel therapy was published in 2009.¹⁴⁹ In this Pharmacogenomics of AntiPlatelet Intervention (PAPI) study, 429 healthy volunteers and 227 patients undergoing percutaneous coronary intervention were included in this genome wide association study. The participants were also genotyped for *CYP2C19**2 allele.

The study concluded that 13 SNPs on chromosome 10q24 within the *CYP2C18–CYP2C19–CYP2C9–CYP2C8* cluster were associated with decreased clopidogrel response. Out of these high degree of statistical significance was achieved for a SNP (rs12777823) which was in strong linkage disequilibrium with that of *CYP2C19*2* variant, and was associated with diminished clopidogrel response.

Thus a wide range of studies have provided evidence that defective alleles of *CYP2C19* (*2 and *3) diminishes the clopidogrel therapeutic response by decreasing the conversion of clopidogrel to its active metabolite and the clinical utility of *CYP2C19* genotyping in predicting clopidogrel therapeutic response.

2.4.2.3 *CYP2C19*17* Polymorphism and Clopidogrel response

*CYP2C19*17* polymorphism have excess activity of this enzyme *CYP2C19*. The substrates metabolised by this enzyme will be rapidly metabolised and may lead to therapeutic failure if it leads to inactive metabolite production and excess activity if it leads to active metabolite production. Sibbing *et al*, had studied the influence of clopidogrel response in ST elevated patients treated on clopidogrel. The platelet inhibiting response was assessed by ADP induced platelet aggregation and aggregation measured with multiple electrode platelet aggregometry and quantified as arbitrary units (AU) in this study. The study had hypothesised to test the extensive metabolism of clopidogrel by this polymorphism biochemically by platelet inhibition and as part of the clinical counterpart bleeding episodes were also assessed. The patients in this study were undergoing percutaneous coronary intervention and were in a loading dose of clopidogrel 600 mg. The heterozygous and homozygous carriers of this allele showed reduced platelet aggregation and the incidence of bleeding episode within the 30 days of follow up was also at a higher rate.¹⁵⁹ Another recent study had also reported better efficacy of clopidogrel in patients with *CYP2C19*17* allele admitted for non-ST acute coronary syndrome.¹⁶⁰ The increased activity of the enzyme in EMs of *CYP2C19* itself is a good predictor of clopidogrel efficacy, and *CYP2C19*17* allele increases the activity of *CYP2C19* to a higher level compared to *CYP2C19*1*1* subjects. Studies must evaluate the impact of this allele on the risk of bleeding associated with increased clopidogrel activity.

2.4.2.4 Drug interaction of clopidogrel with PPIs

Proton pump inhibitors are often prescribed along with dual antiplatelet therapy to prevent gastrointestinal bleeding, which had been shown to reduce the inhibitory effect of clopidogrel on platelet aggregation.^{161;162} These studies and few other reports have opened a debate whether clopidogrel therapeutic efficacy is influenced by concomitant administration of proton pump inhibitors (PPIs). A recent meta analysis had evaluated the effect of PPIs on cardiovascular events and mortality in 93,278 patients from 23 studies receiving clopidogrel.¹⁶³ This study reported no association between the cardiovascular risk and mortality with PPIs treatment, but a significant association was seen in the observational studies included in the meta analysis. Thus, there is inconsistent and conflicting data on this interaction. However, physicians should consider the risk of bleeding in patients on dual antiplatelet therapy and accordingly prescribe or omit PPI therapy. Based on the existing literature and reports, recently published reviews on interaction between the PPI and clopidogrel had concluded for the choice of pantoprazole therapy instead of other PPIs (As omeprazole, lansoprazole and rabeprazole have shown diminished clopidogrel therapeutic response). The literature also suggested the administration PPI at least 4 hours after the administration of clopidogrel to prevent the interaction. But the evidence for diminished interaction due to the administration of both drugs at different times is not sufficient and inconsistent.^{26;164}

A recent explorative study had reported the influence of different PPIs on clopidogrel antiplatelet activity in relation to the *CYP2C19* genotype.¹⁶⁵ In this study PPIs (omeprazole, lansoprazole and rabeprazole) have diminished the clopidogrel antiplatelet activity to a greater extent in subjects carrying defective alleles (i.e. *CYP2C19**2 and *3) compared to the normal genotype subjects (*CYP2C19**1*1). Increased conversion rate of responders to non-responders was seen in subjects carrying *2 and *3 alleles (PMs) compared to normal genotype subjects (EMs). One of 15 EMs and 6 of 16 PMs became low responders when PPIs were administered, but at the same time some low responders (6) in PM group converted to responders when treated with PPIs. Wide ranges in the inhibition of platelet activity (IPA) among the PM group have also reported in this study. The time of administration was found to be beneficial in case of EMs and had shown no benefit in case of PMs. Thus the study directs a new path of identifying the drug interactions on the basis of genotype. The discrepancies observed in this study, i.e. increased activity in PMs after PPI administration and wide ranges of

IPA in PMs may be explained by some of the promoter region variants which have not been studied. The influence of *CYP2C19*17* allele had been ruled out as no subjects in this study was found to contain this allele.

2.4.3 Proguanil

Proguanil is a biguanide antimalarial agent used for prophylaxis along with chloroquine in North Africa, Middle East, and Asia. It is also being used along with atovaquone for prophylaxis in Sub-Saharan Africa, Caribbean and South East Asia.^{1:166} World Health Organization (WHO) recommends the combination of chloroquine and proguanil for the treatment of uncomplicated *Plasmodium falciparum* and *Plasmodium vivax* infections and for prevention of malaria in pregnancy.¹⁶⁷ Proguanil like other biguanide antimalarial agents is a prodrug and undergoes activation to cycloguanil which inhibits the dihydrofolate reductase of malarial parasite. Other metabolites of proguanil such as 4-chlorophenyl biguanide and dichlorophenyl biguanide do not possess antimalarial activity.¹⁶⁸⁻¹⁷⁰ Due to the short duration of action biguanide drugs are less likely to select resistant parasites. Both proguanil and its metabolite cycloguanil are excreted via urine.^{171;172}

The bioactivation of proguanil to cycloguanil was found to cosegregate with the genetically determined 4'-hydroxylation of S-mephenytoin, thereby suggesting that it was metabolized by CYP2C19.^{171;173} The metabolism of proguanil was studied in relation to S-mephenytoin 4'-hydroxylation in an Indonesian population.¹⁷⁴ After administering a single oral dose of 200 mg proguanil hydrochloride to 24 healthy volunteers, venous blood samples were collected over a period of 72 hrs and pharmacokinetic parameters of plasma proguanil, cycloguanil and 4-chlorophenylbiguanide were assessed. Similar results were found in a study on proguanil metabolism done in Tanzanians, Turks (antimode-15), Caucasians, South Pacific Polynesian (antimode-10), Bantu Tanzanians, Chinese and Nigerian populations (antimode -10).^{14;94;173;175-178} In these studies a wide ranges and overlapping of metabolic ratios of proguanil was observed in the EMs i.e. between the homozygous EMs and heterozygous EMs. Few individuals in PMs also have not shown the genotype-phenotype association.^{14;94;173;175-178}

A recent study in 43 adult Gambians had shown that subjects with *CYP2C19*17* allele had a higher plasma levels of cycloguanil compared to those without this allele.¹⁷⁹ The

effect of *CYP2C19**2 allele on proguanil pharmacokinetics was found to be small compared to the effects of *CYP2C19**17 allele on *CYP2C19/CYP2C9* locus. The study also has found no influence of *CYP2C9* variations on proguanil pharmacokinetics. Endogenous compounds such as oestrogens may also influence the conversion of proguanil to cycloguanil. A study had shown that oral contraceptives use and pregnancy have resulted in decreased conversion of proguanil to cycloguanil and the authors suggested 50 % increase in proguanil dose in pregnant women and in women on oral contraceptives.¹⁸⁰ Similar results were obtained in another study in pregnant women where a twofold decrease in the cycloguanil levels was observed in pregnant women.¹⁸¹ The role of endogenous factors, concomitant medication and other CYP isoforms in proguanil oxidation is also unknown. Further studies are required to establish the role of promoter region and exonic region variants of *CYP2C19* and role of other CYP isoforms on proguanil oxidation.

2.4.4 Nelfinavir

Nelfinavir is a protease inhibitor widely being prescribed along with other antiretroviral drugs in patients affected by human immunodeficiency virus as a part of highly active anti-retroviral therapy. The pharmacokinetics of nelfinavir involves MDR1 drug transporter affecting absorption and cytochrome P450 enzymes *CYP2C19* and *CYP3A5* affecting the conversion of nelfinavir to an active metabolite. Nelfinavir is converted to an active metabolite hydroxyl-tert-butylamide (M8) by *CYP2C19* enzyme. Nelfinavir is metabolized by *CYP2C19* and the formation of its hydroxyl-t-butylamide (M8), pharmacologically active metabolite varies according to the *CYP2C19* genotype.¹⁸² Various studies have been done to explore the pharmacogenetic influence of nelfinavir. The results of most of these studies are controversial as nelfinavir and its metabolite are equally active.¹⁸³ Significant association has been found between the defective alleles of *CYP2C19* (*2 & *3) and exposure of nelfinavir. The nelfinavir levels in plasma were 36 % higher in *CYP2C19**2*2 genotype subjects compared to *1*1 genotype subjects and there is a trend towards favourable virologic response observed.^{42;183-185} In contrast to these findings, studies have also suggested limited clinical utility of *CYP2C19* genotyping in predicting the therapeutic outcome or adverse effects to nelfinavir therapy. Significant difference in nelfinavir levels were seen between the subjects of *1*1 genotype and subjects carrying variant allele (*2). Whereas no significant difference in the levels of nelfinavir between *CYP2C19**1*2 and *2*2 subjects has been

observed.¹⁸⁶ The clinical implication of this differential exposure to nelfinavir and its metabolite in various genotypes is very controversial. The pharmacokinetic study of nelfinavir was studied by Hirt et al in 2007.⁴² The study had concluded the lower rate of conversion of nelfinavir to its metabolite in heterozygous *CYP2C19**1/*2 and homozygous *CYP2C19**2/*2 genotypes. In spite of difference of in the rate of metabolism, the difference in the concentration of nelfinavir was not appreciated between the different genotypes. The authors in this study have brought the role of CYP3A4 in the metabolism of nelfinavir which may be the reason for failure to demonstrate the difference in concentration in nelfinavir. This study failed to demonstrate a better correlation between an improved virological response in heterozygous (*1*2) and homozygous (*2*2) genotypes. As per the literature available currently the genetic variation in *CYP2C19* may not play a key role in the virological response of nelfinavir, even though it alters its pharmacokinetics. Further studies are needed to establish the clinical utility of *CYP2C19* genotyping in predicting the virologic response to nelfinavir treatment.

2.4.5 Cyclophosphamide

Cyclophosphamide is an alkylating chemotherapeutic agent, which is metabolized to its active metabolite 4-hydroxy cyclophosphamide. *In vitro* evaluation for the contribution of CYP2C19 on the activation of cyclophosphamide had shown a significant correlation between the 4-hydroxylation of cyclophosphamide and 5'-hydroxylation of omeprazole, indicating that CYP2C19 plays a role in the metabolism of this drug.¹⁸⁷ Another study has demonstrated that *CYP2C19**2 genotype influenced significantly pharmacokinetics of cyclophosphamide. The elimination of cyclophosphamide was significantly decreased in the individuals with *CYP2C19**2 allele.¹⁸⁸ Similarly, in a study during pulse treatment of cyclophosphamide in proliferative nephritis, it was found that subjects carrying *CYP2C19**2 allele are significantly at lower risk of developing ovarian failure and had a higher probability of poor renal response.⁴⁰ A recent study had evaluated the influence of *CYP2C19* genotype on cyclophosphamide induced ovarian toxicity in systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) patients of Thai origin.¹⁸⁹ Out of the 71 patients, 36 patients (59%) developed ovarian toxicity and the *CYP2C19**2 allele frequencies were 28% and 21% in the patients who developed ovarian toxicity and in those who did not developed toxicity, respectively. It had also been found that patients with *CYP2C19**1*1 genotype were at higher risk of developing the ovarian toxicity

[odds ratio (OR)=11 (95% CI: 1.2-99.1] compared to heterozygous and homozygous mutant subjects.¹⁸⁹

Thus few studies have shown the clinical utility of *CYP2C19* genotyping in predicting the cyclophosphamide toxicity. Further studies are required with larger sample size in conditions like leukemia, lymphoma and organ transplantation.

2.4.6 Voriconazole

Voriconazole is an azole group of anti-fungal widely used in systemic mycoses. The favorable pharmacokinetic aspect of the drug is its 100% bioavailability by oral administration. This property of the drug was advantageously used in substituting oral administration in the place of parenteral administration. Voriconazole is metabolized in the liver by various enzymes namely, CYP2C19, CYP3A4 and flavin monooxygenases. It is metabolized by two different pathways one being the hydroxylation and other being the oxidation yielding two different group of metabolites of voriconazole. The metabolites of voriconazole are voriconazole N-oxide, hydroxymethylvoriconazole and dihydroxymethylvoriconazole. CYP2C19 contributes the maximum in comparison to other enzymes in the formation of these metabolites. The plasma concentration of voriconazole and its metabolite was found to vary with various genotypes of *CYP2C19*.^{190;191}

A study conducted by Scholz *et al* in 2009 to assess the influence of these genotypes of *CYP2C19* on the plasma levels of voriconazole and its metabolite given by oral and intravenous route. The bioavailability in the poor metabolizers was in the higher range when compared to the extensive metabolizers. The poor metabolizers of CYP2C19 having genotypes heterozygous *CYP2C19*1*2* and homozygous *CYP2C19*2/*2* genotypes have higher exposure to voriconazole than its metabolites.¹⁹² This study was conducted in healthy volunteers and the correlation with the occurrence of adverse effects was not demonstrated.

The other study conducted by Matsumoto *et al* in 2009, assessed the correlation between the plasma concentration of voriconazole and development of hepatotoxicity.¹⁹³ They recommend dosage adjustment in various genotypes. Higher initial dosage is required for extensive metabolizers and lower initial dosage for poor metabolizers of *CYP2C19* genotypes. Another recent study had also found ultra-rapid metabolism of voriconazole in individuals with *CYP2C19*17* allele.¹⁹⁴ Thus the plasma

levels of voriconazole were influenced by *CYP2C19* genotyping, which might vary the response to treatment and occurrence of adverse effects to voriconazole therapy.

2.4.7 Clobazam

Clobazam is an anti-epileptic agent which shows wide inter-individual variability in metabolism. In a preliminary study on the possible involvement of *CYP2C19* in clobazam metabolism, epileptic patients on stable clobazam therapy were included for reference values of the drug and its metabolite, and for *CYP2C19* genotyping.^{195;195} In the predicted *CYP2C19* PM patients, the metabolic ratio was 10-27 fold higher than control epileptic patients. This data suggested that patients with one or two *CYP2C19**2 alleles may be at a higher risk of adverse effects with clobazam therapy.

Association between the *CYP2C19* genotype and clobazam metabolism to N-desmethyloclobazam among Japanese patients receiving clobazam for the treatment of epilepsy was studied in 16 patients who had received oral administration of clobazam for 4 weeks. They were classified based on the number of mutant *CYP2C19* alleles. A gene-dose effect was observed for clobazam metabolism based on the *CYP2C19* genotype.¹⁹⁶ The N-desmethyloclobazam/clobazam dose ratio in patients with two variant alleles was 6-fold higher than in normal patients. Clobazam metabolism was characterized *in vitro* by using P 450 specific inhibitors. N-desmethyloclobazam was 4'-hydroxylated to 4'-hydroxydesmethyloclobazam by *CYP2C19* and the study predicted that drug interactions and interindividual differences in clobazam metabolite levels may occur due to *CYP2C19* genetic variations.¹⁹⁷ A recent study had evaluated the association of *CYP2C19* genotype and adverse effects due to clobazam in Japanese epileptic patients.¹⁹⁸ Increased response rate for clobazam was seen in PMs of *CYP2C19* (65 %) followed by IMs/ heterozygous EMs (48 %) and with lowest response rate in EMs (33 %). The study could not detect any association between the adverse effects and *CYP2C19* genotype, but adverse effects are seen more in PMs as a consequence to the decreased metabolism of clobazam in these subjects. Thus *CYP2C19* genotype can serve as a predictor of response to clobazam treatment.¹⁹⁸

2.4.8 Tamoxifen

Tamoxifen is a selective estrogen receptor modulator commonly used in the treatment of breast cancer. Tamoxifen has to undergo activation to Z-4' hydroxy tamoxifen, a potent antiestrogen to exert its action. In an earlier study, tamoxifen metabolism was

investigated *in vitro* using recombinant human P450s which were co expressed in *Escherichia coli* with recombinant human NADPH-cytochrome P450 reductase.¹⁹⁹ This study has shown the involvement of CYP2C19 in 4' hydroxylation of tamoxifen. In another study it has been found that Z-4' hydroxy tamoxifen was formed by supersomes expressing CYP2B6, CYP2C9, CYP2C19 and CYP2D6, but not CYP3A4.²⁰⁰ A study in breast cancer patients has shown that patients with the *CYP2C19* *17 allele had a more favourable clinical outcome than the carriers of *1, *2, and *3 alleles.²⁰¹ Thus suggesting that genotyping for *CYP2C19**17 allele may identify the patients who likely to get benefit from tamoxifen therapy. The molecular mechanism how this variant allele results in favourable outcome has to be investigated. There is possibility of increased conversion of tamoxifen to its active metabolite in the presence of this allele in *CYP2C19*, and increased metabolism of estrogens by the increased CYP2C19 activity in the presence of this allele might have also contributed to the better clinical outcome. A recent study in postmenopausal women with breast cancer has found an association between tamoxifen and its metabolites and estrogen serum levels whose levels were influenced by *CYP2C19* genotype.²⁰² In contrast to the findings a case control study in breast cancer has reported no association between the *CYP2C19* variations and therapeutic outcome to tamoxifen therapy.²⁰³ CYP2C19 is involved in the metabolism of estrogens and estrogens have been shown to inhibit CYP2C19.²⁰⁴⁻²⁰⁶ Thus the role of estrogen levels during tamoxifen therapy must not be ignored and is still a matter of debate. Further prospective studies are required to examine the influence of *CYP2C19* genetic variations on tamoxifen therapy and estrogen kinetics on treatment outcome.

2.4.9 Antidepressants

CYP2C19 is involved in the metabolism of several antidepressants and its activity is likely to influence the pharmacokinetics and clinical effect of antidepressants. Higher plasma levels of antidepressants such as moclobemide, clomipramine, sertraline, citalopram, and venlafaxine were seen in the PMs of CYP2C19 (with defective *CYP2C19* alleles) compared to the EMs of CYP2C19.²⁰⁷⁻²¹¹ But some studies have shown the limited impact of CYP2C19 compared to CYP2D6.^{211;212}

A recent study in depressive patients who are on escitalopram had shown that the clearance of escitalopram was much faster in normal subjects (*CYP2C19**1*1) compared to *1*2/*1*3/*2*2/*2*17 subjects.²¹³ Another study on the influence of CYPs on escitalopram metabolism and treatment response had shown that the genetic

polymorphisms in *CYP2C19* may influence its serum concentrations, but may not be able to predict the response compared to *CYP2D6* genotype which can predict the treatment response to escitalopram.²¹¹ Due to the lower allele frequencies of *CYP2C19*17* and other variants in the study population, authors could not detect the influence of this allele on escitalopram levels. Whereas a study had reported that a homozygous *CYP2C19*17* genotype is associated with lower serum concentration of escitalopram, this may increase the risk of therapeutic failure.²¹⁴ The same group had also identified an alternate pathway of escitalopram metabolism by *CYP2C19 in vitro*. They have found that in addition to the N-demethylation, a propionic acid derivative is formed by *CYP2C19 in vitro*, which might affect the exposure levels of this drug in depressive patients.²¹⁵ But at present the data is inconclusive and prospective studies might give clear evidence for the influence of *CYP2C19* genetic polymorphisms on escitalopram treatment response

Several other studies have evaluated the influence of *CYP2C19* polymorphisms on the metabolism of other antidepressants and have reported higher levels of parent drugs in PMs of *CYP2C19*. In a study, serum concentration of sertraline and N-desmethylsertraline was evaluated in relation to *CYP2C19* genotype and was found that 3 fold and 5 fold higher dose-adjusted serum concentrations of sertraline and N-desmethyl sertraline in the homozygous PMs compared to normal subjects (**1*1*). The same study could not detect the variations in the levels of parent drug and metabolite in subjects carrying *CYP2C19*17*.²¹⁶ Studies have also reported that *CYP2C19* genotype influences the amitriptyline and nortriptyline levels but does not affect the treatment response.²¹⁷⁻²¹⁹ Thus the current literature suggests the consideration of *CYP2C19* genotype along with *CYP2D6* genotype, and adjusting the dose accordingly is one of the ways to improve the therapeutic outcome and the same had been suggested by Koostra-Ros *et al.*²²⁰ Studies must also explore the unknown variations in *CYP2C19* and the variability in the expression of *CYP2C19* among the depressive patients and the treatment outcome in future.

2.5 *CYP2C19* genetic markers and disease association

The genotypes of *CYP2C19* may serve as markers of certain disease conditions. In a study to evaluate the etiological role of genes encoding enzymes metabolizing dietary carcinogens in human cancer, common polymorphisms of *CYP450* were studied.²²¹ This also included the genotyping of 490 colorectal cancer patients and 593 controls for

CYP2C19 variant alleles. The analysis identified *CYP2C19*2* as a statistically significant determinant for colorectal cancer, with carriers of *CYP2C19*2* having a reduced risk of colorectal cancer. Another study investigated the relationship between the *CYP2C19* genotype and phenotype in 16 patients of advanced stages of cancers of lung, colon, breast, stomach, pancreas, or esophagus and found decreased metabolic capacity of *CYP2C19* substrates in patients with cancer.²²² This may influence the efficacy and toxicity of chemotherapeutic agents. The role of *CYP2C19* in the susceptibility to systemic lupus erythematosus had been studied by genotyping analysis and phenotyping using racemic mephenytoin in 70 systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) patients and 161 healthy controls. However, no significant association was observed between *CYP2C19* genotype and the predisposition to SLE.²²³ Another study also could not find an association between association between *CYP2C19* genotype and sporadic colorectal cancer when studied in 377 patients and 326 controls.²²⁴

Mochizuki *et al* compared the frequencies of CYP450 polymorphisms between hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) in Japanese patients and healthy subjects.²²⁵ The frequencies of *CYP2C19*2* and **3* were determined in 44 HCC positive patients. No significant difference was observed in prevalence of *CYP2C19* variations in the study group compared to controls. In order to study the possibility of *CYP2C19* polymorphism playing a role in the development of hepatocellular carcinoma in Japanese cirrhotic patients who were HCV-positive, a genotype analysis was done in 38 Japanese cirrhotic patients.²²⁶ The frequency of PMs among the HCV-seropositive patients who had developed hepatocellular carcinoma was significantly higher than in healthy controls. The authors concluded that the PM phenotype due to *CYP2C19* variations was associated with a higher risk of developing hepatocellular carcinoma in these individuals.

Inconclusive reports have also associated the *CYP2C19* genetic polymorphisms with that of lung cancer.²²⁷ A recent study had reported low frequency of *CYP2C19*17* allele in breast cancer patients, suggesting the protective role of this allele.²²⁸ This may be due to the increased metabolism of the estrogens in subjects carrying *CYP2C19*17* allele. Another recent study had evaluated the association of *CYP2C19* genetic polymorphisms with that of depressive symptoms in 1,472 patients of European ancestry and concluded that poor metabolizers (subjects carrying the defective alleles) have lower levels of depressive symptoms compared to the subjects carrying normal alleles.²²⁹ Studies must

explore the existence other variants in *CYP2C19* gene especially in regulatory regions and must evaluate the haplotype structures of *CYP2C19* with haplotype-disease association studies

2.6 Gene transcription and Transcription factors

In eukaryotes and prokaryotes, a DNA sequence that regulates the gene transcription by specifying RNA polymerase binding site and initiates transcription of a gene is called promoter. Transcription from a particular promoter is controlled by DNA-binding proteins, termed as transcription factors. Thus transcriptional regulation is mediated by proteins binding to specific DNA sequences or DNA structural motifs, usually located upstream of the target gene. Transcription factors are nuclear proteins that regulate the expression of target genes or gene families by acting on the regulatory regions of a gene. Transcription factors often belong to multi gene families that share common DNA-binding domains.²³⁰ The mechanism of action of transcription factors also involves binding to other proteins, sometimes in hetero dimeric complexes with specific partners and the final complex may have a regulatory function on the target gene. Transcription factors are the final link in the signal transduction pathway that converts extracellular signals into modulated changes in gene expression (Figure 4).²³¹ Regulation of gene expression by sequence-specific DNA binding proteins has emerged as one of the most important mechanisms governing cell differentiation, development, and homeostasis.²³² In addition to the normal growth of the cells these factors are also involved in the transcriptional control of several genes such as the ones coding for cytochrome P 450 enzymes.²³³

Figure 4. Gene regulation network and promoter region of a gene²³²

Eukaryotic cells contain proteins that contribute to the initiation of every RNA polymerase II primary transcript that eventually becomes mRNA. RNA polymerases (I, II and III) cannot initiate transcription in eukaryotic genes on their own. They require additional proteins; the general transcription factors (Figure 4). These proteins have to assemble with RNA polymerase into a complex on the promoter DNA. Transcription is initiated by assembly of a transcription initiation complex composed of RNA polymerase II and other associated basal factors (general transcription factors). This multi-protein complex binds to a short DNA sequence called the minimal promoter and often contains a conserved DNA sequence motif called the TATA box situated 20–30 nucleotides upstream of the transcription initiation site.²³⁴

The general transcription factors are characterized by their ability to control the activity of RNA polymerase II on the minimal promoter (Figure 5).²³⁵ Transcription factors (TFs) are often termed the master regulators of gene expression. By binding to the DNA, they tightly control where and when the nearby target gene is expressed. Despite their importance as a fundamental component of biological systems in all organisms, the transcription factors for many genomes have not been listed and characterized well till now. In addition to the general transcriptional machinery, there are approximately 2000-3000 transcription factors identified thus far that share two characteristic features: a DNA binding domain that interacts with gene-specific regulatory sites, and a domain that exhibits transcriptional activation potential.²³⁶

The basal transcription complex assembles through an extensive series of protein-protein interactions. Although the basal factors can assemble on the promoter in a step-wise manner *in vitro*, there is some evidence that many of the factor interactions can occur in the absence of DNA and that some of the factors may pre-assemble into a "holoenzyme".²³⁷ Transcription factors may exhibit a specific combinatorial distribution in different cell types that helps to direct determination (choice of cell fate) and differentiation (synthesis of recognized cell-specific proteins). In addition, transcription factors may be only minimally active until cells are exposed to the appropriate stimulus.²³⁶ These proteins also interact with co-activators or positive-acting transcription factors and/or a member of the transcription machinery to inhibit their activity.²³⁸ Therefore, the transcriptional activity of a gene is due to the interaction between its present transcriptional activator and repressor proteins, which are, in turn, mainly selected by the *cis*-acting promoter elements of the gene.

Figure 5. Regulation of gene expression and role of response elements and transcription factors. (Courtesy: Dr. Patric Manuel, Physiopathologie Hepatique, InsermU632, Montpellier)

2.6.1 Classification of transcription factors based on DNA binding domains:

Transcription factors are classified according to the structure of the DNA-binding domain including

- Helix-turn-helix
- Zinc finger
- Leucine zipper
- Helix-loop-helix
- High mobility group

2.6.1.1 Helix-turn-helix

The most common DNA binding sequence is the helix-turn-helix motif. This consists of two α -helices that are held at a fixed angle and are connected by an extended β -turn chain of amino acids. The COOH-terminal, or recognition helix, fits into the major groove of DNA, an interaction that is modulated by amino acid residues at the outer helical surface and by the conformation of peptides that house the domain. The helix-turn-helix conformation is a component of the homeobox, a conserved ~60 amino acid

domain within *Drosophila* (fruit fly) homeotic gene products. This homeobox domain has been identified in many invertebrates and also as vertebrate regulators of gene expression.²³⁹

e.g. Lac repressor protein, heat shock transfactor, CAMP regulatory protein, Oct-1.

2.6.1.2 Zinc finger

Zinc finger transcription factors recruit zinc in order to bind DNA. Two zinc-finger motifs have been identified. One consists of 30 amino acids including two invariably positioned cysteine-histidine pairings that co-ordinate tetrahedral binding to a single zinc atom, and was first identified in the RNA pol III associated TIIIFA. In the other zinc finger motif, which occurs for example in intracellular steroid hormone receptors, partnerships between cysteine-cysteine residues direct zinc chelation.²³⁹

e.g. SP1 transcription factor, GATA factors.

2.6.1.3 Leucine zipper

The leucine zipper motif mediates DNA association in many transcription factors including the proto-oncogene products Myc, Fos and Jun. In this domain, leucine residues present with regular, seven amino acid periodicity at every second turn along the hydrophobic face of an α -helix. Zip-like dimerisation and intertwining of two parallel helices occurs through leucine interactions and other hydrophobic amino acid interactions and brings together two carboxy clusters of basic amino acids which contact the surface of DNA and in so doing, transmit conformational changes that promote sequence-specific binding.²³⁹

e.g. ATF/CREB, C/EBP

2.6.1.4 Helix-loop-helix

The helix-loop-helix structure contains two amphipathic α -helices with highly conserved basic residues on the amino-terminal side and several hydrophobic residues on the carboxy-terminal flank. The helices are linked by amino acid sequences of variable length which form reverse turns and loops and the entire motif mediates homo- and hetero-dimerisation, which favours DNA-binding through the basic domains.²³⁹

e.g. c-Myc

2.6.1.5 High mobility group

DNA structure can be distorted by association with a particular class of transcription factor through the high mobility group (HMG) box, which spans 20bp of DNA when bound. This motif is a feature of many structural and non-chromosomal proteins in the nucleus and can mediate bending, wrapping, spacing and coiling of DNA.^{239;240}

2.7 Transcriptional regulation of cytochrome P 450 enzymes with an emphasis on CYP2C family

The genes encoding cytochrome P 450 enzymes are highly regulated during development and are influenced by hormonal factors, nutritional factors, including endogenous steroids, hormones and cytokines.²⁴¹ Most genes encoding the cytochrome P 450 enzymes are constitutively expressed in the hepatic tissues and their expression is under the control of the transcription factors expressed in the liver. These transcription factors include, hepatic nuclear factor-1 (HNF-1), hepatic nuclear factor-3 (HNF-3), hepatic nuclear factor-4 (HNF-4) and CCAAT enhancer binding proteins (CEBP).²⁴² These transcription factors may also act in pairs and may influence the expression of CYPs in liver as their expression is predominant in the liver.²⁴³ In addition to these other nuclear receptors and ligand activated receptors such as aryl hydrocarbon receptor (Ah), peroxisome proliferated activated receptor (PPAR- α), glucocorticoid receptor (GR), estrogen receptor (ER), retinoid receptors (RXR), constitutive androstane receptor (CAR), pregnane X receptor (PXR) also play a major role in the expression of *CYP* genes in the liver and in some other tissues.²⁴⁴ These receptors can be activated by some of the endogenously produced ligands such as hormones and xenobiotics which will bring about changes in the expression of the *CYP* genes. It is not clear whether only one single factor is responsible for a single *CYP* gene expression or multiple factors are involved in the expression. Studies have shown the involvement of more than one factor on *CYP* gene expression, and there exists a cross talk between these factors during the transcriptional control of *CYP* genes.²⁴⁴ Most of the experiments on the transcriptional control were performed *in vitro* using cell lines and by coexpressing the transcription factors in the cells and studying the target gene expression. But it is questionable whether a similar control exists in *in vivo* since multiple transcription factors are expressed and their expression varies in different individuals. It had also been shown that large number of inflammatory agents repress CYP450 mediated drug metabolism in humans.²⁴⁵ Bacterial endotoxins may also directly repress CYP450 expression by acting

on hepatocytes. This suggests the altered expression levels of CYPs in pathological conditions. The recruitment of co-activators and co-repressors along with transcription factors decides the process of gene transcription in response to the activation of nuclear receptors like RXR by an exogenous or endogenous ligand (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Role of nuclear receptors in controlling transcription (courtesy: Dr. Patric Manuel, Physiopathologie Hepatique, InsermU632, Montpellier)

In the absence of ligand nuclear receptors are not activated and recruitment of co-repressor like NcoR, SMRT occurs, followed by deacetylation and formation of the heterochromatin which cannot be transcribed for gene expression. In the presence of the ligand, these nuclear receptors recruit co-activators like CBP, SRC-1 and followed by acetylation of euchromatin which will be made available for gene expression.

2.7.1 Role of Pregnane X Receptors

Recent studies have found the role of pregnane X receptor (PXR) in the transcriptional regulation of CYP genes. Pregnane X receptor is a ligand activated transcription factor belonging to the nuclear receptor family and is closely related to constitutive androstane receptor (CAR). Activation of the PXR may result in the induction of CYP genes, and can impart beneficial effects such as protection from the toxicity due to cholestatic bile acids. However at the same time, their induction may also result in some harmful events such as acetaminophen induced hepatotoxicity.^{246;247}

PXR acts by forming a heterodimer with another receptor, retinoid X receptor (RXR). This hetero complex binds to the response elements in the promoter region of target genes and recruits the activator proteins and stimulates the gene transcription.²⁴⁸ PXR expression is higher in the hepatic tissues and also to lesser extent in extra hepatic tissues such as small intestine and colon.²⁴⁹⁻²⁵¹ PXR was known to regulate the transcription of *CYP2C* genes including *CYP2C9* and *CYP2C19*.^{252;253} There exists interindividual variability in the expression of PXR in the liver.^{254;255} The expression of PXR can also be altered by exposure to drugs, environmental chemicals disease state, and genetic variations.²⁵⁵⁻²⁵⁸ This variable expression levels and polymorphisms in PXR was also known to vary its function and thus may alter the transcriptional control of the target gene.²⁵⁹

It had been demonstrated that GR and CAR play a major role in *CYP2C9* gene transcription.²⁶⁰ A study by Chen *et al* had identified glucocorticoid responsive element (-1750 to -1736 bp) in the *CYP2C19* 5' flanking region.²⁵³ The role of GR in *CYP2C19* transcription needs to be elucidated in future. Majority of the reports indicates that drugs such as phenobarbital, rifampicin, dexamethasone, artemesinin derivatives up regulate *CYP2C* genes including *CYP2C19*.^{261;262} Studies must elucidate the existence of variations in these binding sites and their impact on the expression of *CYP2C19*.

2.7.2 Transcriptional control of *CYP2C19* gene by endogenous and exogenous factors

A study by Arefayene et al has characterized the promoter region of *CYP2C19* and has predicted the negative and positive regulatory elements in the promoter region.²² No other study had explored the regulatory elements in general for their effect on transcription of a gene. Few studies have located the PXR and GR elements in *CYP2C19* promoter region. It had been reported that *CYP2C19* promoter contains a single constitutive androstane receptor (CAR) binding site (CAR-RE; -1891/-1876 bp) and a glucocorticoid-responsive element (GRE; -1750/-1736 bp) in its promoter region.²⁵³ Binding of CAR-RE with CAR and pregnane X receptor (PXR) was evidenced in gel shift assays. It had also been found that mutation of the -1891 bp CAR-RE abolished up-regulation which was seen with wild type constructs when co-transfected with that of the transcription factor constructs. Co-transfection with human CAR (hCAR) also up-regulated endogenous *CYP2C19* mRNA content in HepG2 cells, whereas androstenol repressed the mCAR-mediated constitutive activation of the

CYP2C19 promoter in HepG2 cells. Transfection assays with ligand for PXR i.e. rifampicin produced a modest increase in promoter activity in cells co-transfected with human PXR (hPXR). Transfection assays with ligand for GR i.e. dexamethasone activated the -2.7-kb *CYP2C19* promoter constructs in HepG2 cells only in the presence of co-transfected glucocorticoid receptor (GR), whereas the GR antagonist mifepristone inhibited this response. It has also been found that mutation of the GRE abolished the dexamethasone activation of promoter constructs.²⁵³ This study suggested the presence of PXR and GR elements in the *CYP2C19* promoter region and suggests its role in *CYP2C19* expression. This study also highlights that variations in the transcription factor binding sites alter the interaction of factor with ligand resulting in increased or decreased activation of promoter region. *In vitro* and *in vivo* studies have shown the induction of *CYP2C19* by rifampicin, glucocorticoids, phenobarbital, dexamethasone, hyperforin, artemisinin and paclitaxel.²⁶³ Rifampicin based induction for *CYP2C19* was higher (4 fold) compared to *CYP2C9* (1.5 fold) whereas dexamethasone based induction was higher for *CYP2C9* (15 fold) compared to *CYP2C19* (4 fold).^{263;264} This suggests the variations in the regulatory functions of the homologous promoters of *CYP2C9* and *CYP2C19*. The schematic representation of transcriptional regulation by nuclear receptors such as RXR and GR in response to ligands such as rifampicin and glucocorticoids are given in figure 7 and figure 8.

Figure 7. PXR and CAR nuclear receptor transactivation. A ligand enters the cell either by passive diffusion or by an uptake transporter and binds to a nuclear receptor in the cytosol. CAR and PXR are retained in the cytoplasm in a complex with chaperones such as heat shock protein 90 (hsp90) or cytoplasmic CAR retention protein (CCRP) (1). Liganded nuclear receptor translocates to the nucleus (2). Phenobarbital triggers cytoplasmic-nuclear translocation of unliganded CAR complex indirectly by promoting the recruitment of protein phosphatase 2A (PP-2A) to the CAR/CCRP/hsp90 complex (3). The liganded nuclear receptor binds to RXR nuclear receptors forming PXR/RXR or CAR/RXR heterodimers, which recruits coactivators and bind to regulatory regions (PXRRE or CARRE) of a subset of target genes listed (4). The nuclear receptor heterodimer/coactivators complex promotes general transcriptional machinery of gene expression with RNA polymerase II (RNA pol II) (5). Coactivators possess histone acetyltransferase activity (HAT) that allows chromatin decompaction, which promotes gene activation, PXR is also supposed to be associated in a corepressors complex in the nucleus in the absence of ligand. The complex containing SMRT (NCOR2) corepressors recruits histone deacetylases (HDACs). Deacetylation of histones leads to chromatin compaction and transcriptional repression of a gene. Ligand binding to PXR nuclear receptor causes release of the corepressors, recruitment of a coactivator complex and transcriptional activation of gene expression (6). Feedback regulation of PXR-mediated regulation of CYP3A4 expression (7). SHP inhibits PXR-mediated transactivation of CYP3A4, activated PXR inhibits SHP expression. As a consequence, SHP expression is reduced and CYP3A4 transcription is activated. Crosstalk of PXR and CAR – these nuclear receptors share responsive elements of their target genes (8)

Figure 8. Transcriptional regulation through the glucocorticoid receptor (GR). GR predominantly resides in the cytoplasm in a complex with several proteins and partners including chaperones hsp90, hsp70 and FK506 binding protein 4 (FKBP4, FKBP52) etc. (1) Binding of glucocorticoids induces conformational changes in the receptor, dissociation from chaperone proteins, (2) dimerization of the receptor (3) nuclear translocation and DNA binding (4) Activated GR selectively recruits cofactors including SRC-1, TIF-2, p300/CBP, general transcription-factor-bridging factors, which activate general transcriptional machinery and recruitment of RNA polymerase II (5, 6) or factors with intrinsic histone acetyltransferase and methyltransferase activities which alter chromatin structure and facilitate access of transcription machinery components to DNA. (7) GR is degraded by proteasome in cytoplasm.

Another study had reported the role of HNF4 alpha in the pregnane X receptor (PXR)/rifampicin-mediated up-regulation of *CYP2C* genes including *CYP2C19*.²⁶⁵ It is believed that constitutive expression of *CYP2C* genes including *CYP2C19* in the liver is under control of factors such as HNF4 α , HNF3 γ and CCAAT/enhancer-binding protein α .²⁶⁶⁻²⁶⁹ Xenobiotics such as rifampicin, hyperforin, Phenobarbital and dexamethasone increases the expression of *CYP2C* genes including *CYP2C19*.²⁷⁰⁻²⁷² These agents induce the transcription of a gene by acting via binding sites or responsive elements present in the 5' flanking region of a gene such as PXR and CAR (Figure 9).^{273;274}

Figure 9. Activation of PXR and CAR by endogenous and exogenous ligands

(courtesy: Dr. Patric Manuel, Physiopathologie Hepatique, InsermU632, Montpellier)

Studies identified a total of three HNF4 α sites in the *CYP2C9* promoter, two in the *CYP2C8* promoter and two in *CYP2C19* promoter region.²⁶⁵ The extra HNF4 α site in *CYP2C9* (near -211 bp) may contribute to the transactivation of *CYP2C9* gene, but this site is absent in *CYP2C19* and it may not be involved in direct transactivation of *CYP2C19* gene as reported by Kawashima *et al.*²⁷⁵ HNF4 α might transactivate *CYP2C19* gene via activating the PXR or CAR elements in *CYP2C19* promoter region.²⁶⁵ Constructs with mutant alleles in these sites showed that the HNF4 α sites were needed for up-regulation of the *CYP2C8* and *CYP2C9* promoters by rifampicin. Furthermore, silencing of HNF4 α abolished transactivation of the *CYP2C8* and *CYP2C9* promoters by rifampicin. Constitutive promoter activity was also decreased. Silencing HNF4 α using small interfering RNAs reduced the constitutive expression of *CYP2C8* (53%), *CYP2C9* (55%), and *CYP2C19* (43%) mRNAs and significantly decreased the magnitude of the rifampicin-mediated induction of *CYP2C8* (6.6- versus 2.7-fold), *CYP2C9* (3- versus 1.5-fold), and *CYP2C19* (1.8- versus 1.1-fold). The down regulation of *CYP2C19* could be due to the down regulation of CAR and PXR elements.²⁶⁵ These results give evidence that HNF4 α contributes to the constitutive expression of the human *CYP2C* genes and is also important for up-regulation by the PXR agonist rifampicin.²⁶⁵ Thus these findings also suggest the cross talk between HNF4 α and PXR/CAR elements in the *CYP2C19* promoter region (Figure 10). It has

also been found that CYP2C19 is expressed in lower levels compared to CYP2C9 in liver. It may be due to the lack of sufficient HNF4 α to bind to the two responsive elements in *CYP2C19* promoter. However it is not clear why HNF4 α does not activates the basal expression of CYP2C19 in liver even though it has similar binding sites as seen in CYP2C9, which is activated by HNF4 α .²⁶³ Further studies must elucidate the role of HNF4 α in *CYP2C19* gene transcription.

Figure 10. Cross talk between various transcription factors and the regulation of CYP genes. (courtesy: Dr. Patric Manuel, Physiopathologie Hepatique, InsermU632, Montpellier)

There exists interindividual differences exist in the expression of the transcription factors. A recent study used a microarray approach to measure 16 drug metabolizing enzymes including CYP2C19, CYP2C9, CYP2C18, and 13 transcription factors in peripheral mononuclear cells from different individuals. Variations in the expression levels of the enzymes observed and some of the enzymes like CYP3A5, GST-T1 was absent in some of the individuals. It had also been found that transcription factors such as pregnane X receptor (PXR), myocyte enhancer factor 2, vitamin D receptor, liver X receptor (LXR), aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AHR), T-cell factor 7, constitutive androstane receptor (CAR), and aryl hydrocarbon receptor nuclear translocator (ARNT) were expressed in the majority of the subjects. However, glucocorticoid receptor (GR), peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor (PPAR)-gamma, and LXRbeta were expressed only in some individuals. Significant correlations were also observed between the expression of PXR and P450 involved in leukotriene metabolism (CYP2C, CYP4F2,

CYP4A11, CYP2J2, and CYP11B2).²⁷⁶ Another study also reported the correlation between the basal levels of CYP2C19 and HNF4 α expression analyzed in liver samples from 20 individuals.²⁷⁷ The role of other nuclear factors in the regulation of *CYP2C19* gene transcription needs to be elucidated in future.

2.7.3 Effect of gender on *CYP2C19* transcription

Most of the reports have shown no gender differences in the expression and activity of CYP2C19. However, very few reports have shown the gender differences in its expression.²⁷⁸⁻²⁸² The growth hormone levels and testosterone levels have been shown to regulate the gender specific expression of CYP2C19.²⁷⁹ Studies shall elucidate the response elements for growth hormone and androgen response elements and their role in gender specific transcriptional control.

Sex differences in CYP2C19 activity appear to show ethnic variations. CYP2C19 activity is higher in Chinese, Jewish-Israeli, and African American and Korean women than in men of these ethnic backgrounds.^{106;278;280;283} In an another study, growth hormone treatment in elderly males inhibited CYP2C19 to a lesser extent compared to women.²⁸⁴ However increased expression of CYP2C19 was observed in males, which was suppressed by growth hormone treatment.²⁸⁵ Sex specific transcription factor expression and sex specific gene expression may also involve the epigenetic modifications such as methylation of CpG islands and acetylation. The interactions with non coding RNAs known as microRNAs (miRNA) also play a major role in gene expression of factors and/or CYP 450 genes. Further investigations are needed to explore the gender specific expression of CYP2C19 and how various exogenous agents affected this expression in a gender specific manner.

2.7.4 Role of epigenetic mechanisms in *CYP2C19* gene expression

For a gene to express the chromatin shall be in the euchromatin (active) form than the heterochromatin (inactive form).²⁸⁶ The primary epigenetic mechanisms which control gene expression are methylation and acetylation. In addition to changing the chromatin confirmation (hypermethylation is seen more in heterochromatin), methylation of DNA of gene promoters may interfere in binding of the transcription factors to their DNA binding sites.²⁸⁷⁻²⁸⁹ DNA methylation primarily occurs at CpG sites in the mammalian genome which are more frequently observed as islands in regulatory regions or promoter region. DNA methyltransferases are involved in the methylation of a CpG

sites.²⁸⁸ Only cytosine among the four bases has the methylated analogue i.e 5-methyl cytosine, which is methylated at position C5 of the pyrimidine ring.²⁹⁰ Altered methylation patterns have been shown to be important in *CYP* gene expression.²⁹¹ It has been found that few CpG islands exist in the *CYP2C19* promoter region but their importance in *CYP2C19* gene expression must be studied in future.⁶

Another common mechanism of controlling gene expression is by non coding RNAs called as microRNAs (miRNA). These agents were identified recently, and they repress the gene expression by binding to the 3' un-translated region of target mRNA sequence and disturbs the translation by cleavage of target mRNA or by repression of translation.²⁹² These agents are found to regulate the expression of *CYP* genes such as *CYP3A4* and *CYP1B1*.^{293;294} The role of miRNAs in controlling the CYP2C family gene expression needs to be explored and as of now no data is available on its role in *CYP2C19* gene expression.

2.8 CYP2C19 induction and inhibition: Role in drug interactions involving CYP2C19 substrates

As explained under transcriptional control of *CYP2C19* gene, inter individual variability in the expression of endogenous factors and existence of variations in their genes or their binding sites in the target genes may result in the interindividual variability in the induction of the gene. The variations in the binding sites of the drug or the conformational changes in the active site of the enzyme after the drug is bound to the enzyme may also result in the enzyme induction or inhibition.

Drug interactions resulting from enzyme induction and inhibition are a concern for clinicians and patients. Inhibition of metabolism of a drug by competing with the active site of the enzyme results in higher concentration of the drug in plasma leading to toxicity. If the drug needs to be activated, then the inhibition results in decreased efficacy of the drug. Whereas enzyme induction increases the elimination of the active drug resulting in the therapeutic failure in case of inactive drug induction may enhance the efficacy by increasing the availability of active form of the drug.^{295;296}

The enzyme induction is a slow and long process which may not be necessarily caused due to increased transcription of a gene. However, inhibition is a quick process. *CYP2C19* is also an inducible enzyme, the induction and inhibition of this enzyme may be reversible or irreversible.²⁹⁵ Several drugs metabolized by *CYP2C19* also inhibit or

induce the enzyme affecting the metabolism of other substrates (Table 1). Similarly other agents metabolized by other isoforms of CYPs may induce or inhibit CYP2C19.

2.8.1 Interindividual variability in induction of CYP2C19:

Enzyme induction means the increase in the amount and activity of the enzyme upon exposure to an inducing agent. Thus induction of enzyme requires the balance between the production of the enzyme and its degradation which requires time and is a slow process mostly involving the transcriptional regulators of a gene.²⁹⁷ Induction is also influenced by the genotype. In a study on the influence of *CYP2C19* genotypes on induction, CYP2C19 induction by rifampicin was reported in EMs only and no induction was reported in PMs.²⁹⁸ The induction of the enzyme may be influenced by all the genetic factors which are known to alter the transcription of a gene and discussed under that heading. In addition to the drugs affecting the enzyme induction, diet and age also influences the enzyme induction.²⁹⁹ As discussed under the regulation of transcription by various exogenous and endogenous agents also decides the enzyme induction to a large extent.

2.8.2 CYP2C19 enzyme inducers

Unlike CYP2D6, similar to other CYPs CYP2C19 is inducible by several agents such as rifampicin, dexamethasone, and phenobarbital. The induction of the CYP enzymes including CYP2C19 occurs mainly via four mechanisms with the involvement of nuclear receptors. These receptors are aryl hydrocarbon (Ah), PPAR, CAR and PXR. CAR is involved in the induction by phenobarbital, whereas PXR is involved in the induction by rifampicin.¹² In case of CYP2C19 the molecular mechanisms of induction are not yet elucidated because of the lack of studies on its 5' flanking region. Only one study has characterized the promoter region of this gene and still studies are required to understand the response elements in its promoter region and to evaluate the impact of the variations on its expression and induction.²² Studies have shown that rifampicin induces CYP2C19 to detectable levels ranging from 3 fold to 8 fold.^{264;298;300} Studies have identified other inducers of CYP2C19 such as artemisinin an effective antimalarial drug and phenytoin an effective antiepileptic. However, the known inducers phenobarbital and carbamazepine have not shown inducing effects on CYP2C19.^{12;300;301} Even though some conflicting reports available on induction of CYP2C19 by phenobarbital, studies must elucidate the exact mechanisms involved.

Another recent study has reported the influence of herbal drugs on CYP2C19 induction. The commonly used herbals such as *St John's wort* and *Ginkgo biloba* showed an induction/inhibition profile towards CYP2C19 in a dose-dependent manner with induction at low doses and inhibition at higher doses.³⁰² Antiretroviral therapy also had influenced induction and inhibition of CYP2C19 depending on the exposure of the drug. A single dose of tipranavir/ritonavir had weakly inhibited CYP2C19, whereas multiple dosing produced moderate induction of CYP2C19.³⁰³

Thus administration of these agents increases the metabolism of the CYP2C19 substrates, resulting in therapeutic failure in case of active drugs or increased efficacy in case of inactive drugs which is manifested as drug interaction. Lack of understanding of the 5' regulatory region is the limiting factor in understanding the mechanisms of induction. Mechanistic studies are required to characterize the promoter region and its variants to understand the drug induction.

2.8.3 Interindividual variability in inhibition of CYP2C19

The inhibition of enzyme is an immediate effect unlike induction. Unlike induction inhibition of enzyme occurs in all CYP isoforms including CYP2D6. The substrates which are bound to the active site of the enzyme may produce conformational changes in the enzyme. Endogenous or exogenous chemicals are involved in the enzyme inhibition process. Certain transcriptional repressors also act via the response elements in the 5' flanking region of the target genes and regulate the inhibition of the enzyme.³⁰⁴ Mechanisms of CYP2C19 inhibition are poorly elucidated or unknown because of the lack of availability of crystal structure and lack of information on response elements in 5' flanking region. Many factors contribute to the large variability observed in CYP inhibition-mediated drug interactions such as the concentration of inhibitor, timing of administration between substrate and inhibitor, and route of administration, basal levels of the enzymes and genetic factors such as variations in the response elements of promoter region.³⁰⁵

2.8.4 Inhibitors of CYP2C19

Several *in vitro*, *in vivo* studies have reported the inhibitory effect of several drugs on CYP2C19 substrates. Few of them were substrates of CYP2C19 and were also known to inhibit their own metabolism (Table 7). The reasonable substrate for evaluating the inhibitory effect is S-mephenytoin and the inhibitor drug for probing CYP2C19

inhibition is omeprazole.¹² Omeprazole is a potent inhibitor and co-administration of omeprazole results in increased plasma levels of diazepam and proguanil especially in EMs with little or no effect in PMs of CYP2C19.³⁰⁶ Omeprazole inhibits its own metabolism and the same is being hypothesized for clopidogrel too that it inhibits its own metabolism by inhibiting CYP2C19 and CYP2B6.³⁰⁷ An oral hypoglycaemic agent nateglinide also reported to have CYP2C19 inhibitory activity which may be prone to have some interactions in patients on nateglinide, but studies are needed to establish the interactions with nateglinide. Some herbal products and diet can cause the inhibition of CYPs for e.g. kava lactones in kava extract are known to inhibit CYP2C19, which might result in drug interactions with that of other CYP2C19 substrates.³⁰⁸

Recent studies have focussed on evaluating the interaction between proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) and clopidogrel. PPIs are commonly prescribed in the patients who are on dual antiplatelet therapy to prevent the risk of gastrointestinal bleeding.³⁰⁹ It has been found that omeprazole inhibits the activity of clopidogrel probably by inhibiting its conversion into active form which occurs in two steps involving CYP2C19. In addition to the possible synergistic inhibition of CYP2C19 by clopidogrel and potent inhibitor omeprazole (most commonly used PPI), clopidogrel also inhibits CYP2B6 which is involved in its activation. Altogether this may result in decreased activation of clopidogrel and decreased therapeutic efficacy.³⁰⁷ Another explorative study had also shown that subjects with PM genotype may be at more risk of treatment failure compared to EMs when they were administered PPIs along with clopidogrel.¹⁶⁵ The current literature suggests the use of pantoprazole for patients who are at risk of bleeding or with past history of bleeding and who are on dual antiplatelet therapy.²⁶

2.8.5 Oral contraceptives and CYP2C19 activity

The effect of oral contraceptives on CYP2C19 activity was assessed using probe drugs mephenytoin and omeprazole.³¹⁰ The mephenytoin S/R ratio was 2.5-fold and the omeprazole metabolic ratio 2-fold higher in women who took oral contraceptives than in those who did not. Oral contraceptives were thus found to inhibit CYP2C19 activity, both in carriers of the *CYP2C19**1 and *2 allele. Similar findings were seen in case of carisoprodol in relation to the CYP2C19 genotype.³¹¹ The use of oral contraceptives caused a 60% larger AUC (0- α) of carisoprodol in both extensive and intermediate metabolizers and longer t_{1/2} in extensive metabolizers. There was, however, no influence of oral contraceptives on the degree of adverse effects with carisoprodol.

Table 7. Inhibitors of CYP2C19 studied *in vivo* and *in vitro*

Inhibitor	Substrate whose metabolism is affected	Reference
Cimetidine	Proguanil, diazepam	312 313
Ketoconazole	S-mepheytoin	314
Omeprazole	Proguanil, diazepam, S-mephenytoin, clopidogrel, S-citalopram	26; 315;316;317;318;319
Lansoprazole	S-mephenytoin, clopidogrel	26;315
Esomeprazole	Diazepam, R-warfarin	320
Isoniazid	S-mephenytoin	321
Sertraline	S-mephenytoin	322
Fluvoxamine	Proguanil, omeprazole, S-mephenytoin	323-325
Oral contraceptives	S-mephenytoin, omeprazole	310
Voriconazole	Tilidine	326
Clopidogrel	Omeprazole	327

2.8.6 Effect of genotype on enzyme induction and inhibition

Genotype does influence the drug interactions by altering the capacity of a drug to induce or inhibit the enzyme. It has been found that concomitant administration of omeprazole resulted in decreased metabolism of diazepam in EMs and had no effect in PMs.^{313;328} In contrast to these findings in an another study ketoconazole administration had decreased omeprazole metabolism in PMs of CYP2C19 but not in EMs. This may be explained by the involvement of the alternate pathways by CYP3A4 in PM which is also inhibited by ketoconazole resulting in increased omeprazole levels in these subjects. The involvement of different mechanisms of inhibition and existence variations in the binding regions of these ligands also cannot be ignored.³²⁹ A recent study had also shown that clopidogrel inhibits the hydroxylation of omeprazole in EMs only.³²⁷ Herb drugs also sometimes have shown variability in induction. For example *Ginko biloba* had shown genotype dependant induction of Omeprazole. However, the chemical constituent which results in the induction and the cause of this variability

remain mystery.³³⁰ It has been proposed that ethnicity is one of the factors altering the induction and inhibition profile of drugs, for e.g. inhibition of diazepam and S-mephenytoin metabolism is greater in EMs of Caucasian origin than Chinese.^{317;318} This data suggests inter ethnic differences in drug induction and inhibition profiles. This might be due to the variability in the distribution of the variations in the promoter region and variability in the linkage disequilibrium pattern between promoter region and exonic region variants. These suggest that EMs are more susceptible to enzyme inhibition than PMs. Further understanding the 5' regulatory region will provide a clear understanding of the genotype influence on induction and inhibition.

In drug discovery, phenotyping new chemical entities for CYP2C19-mediated metabolism as well as for their potential to inhibit or induce CYP2C19 is a common practice because of the potential liabilities of the *CYP2C19* polymorphism. CYP2C19 substrates are used to measure the capacity of the CYP2C19 enzyme. A recent study had evaluated 24 substrates of CYP2C19 and concluded that S-mephenytoin is more sensitive substrate for evaluating the inhibition followed by omeprazole.³³¹ Thus screening the chemicals for their inhibition and induction behaviour will enable us to predict the drug- drug interactions.

2.8.7 Drug interactions involving CYP2C19 substrates and inducers/inhibitors

Even though a large number of reports on drug interactions involving induction and inhibition for CYP2C19 are available, very few interactions seem to be of clinical importance.^{313;316;328;332} Most of the studies reported the pharmacokinetic changes in the substrate, but the pharmacodynamic changes have not been studied except for few substrates such as antidepressants and clopidogrel.^{12;26} Few other recent reports were also available on the inhibitory effect of voriconazole on tilidine metabolism and omeprazole inhibitory effect on clopidogrel action i.e. inhibition of platelet aggregation.²⁶ The interactions of the CYP2C19 substrates are not limited to the drugs undergoing metabolism by CYP2C19 and may involve other enzyme substrates. A study reported that *CYP2C19* defective genotype in the native intestine affected the interaction between tacrolimus and omeprazole in living-donor liver transplant defective genotype patients. But the effect was attenuated by wild-type genotype in the graft liver even when the patients had the *CYP3A5**3/*3 genotype in both the native intestine and the graft liver. This suggests that the genotyping of *CYP2C19* and *CYP3A5* both in the

native intestine and in the graft liver might contribute to safer dosing and monitoring of tacrolimus co-administered with omeprazole.³³³

The drug interactions are dependent on both substrate and inhibitor/inducer concentrations and the genotype of *CYP2C19* may also have an influence.¹² Many reports were available on the drug interactions involving inducers and inhibitors of *CYP2C19*.¹² Proton pump inhibitor plasma levels were known to be increased by ticlopidine, oral contraceptives and fluvoxamine and their administration with that of PPIs may result in the drug interactions.^{310;324;334} But the influence of such interaction on clinical outcome needs to be investigated in future. On the other hand the induction of *CYP2C19* and its effect on the therapeutic outcome of *CYP2C19* substrates must be investigated. For example induction of *CYP2C19* results in the decreased plasma levels of PPIs which might reduce their therapeutic efficacy. There are no such studies available in the literature to test the therapeutic outcome when *CYP2C19* substrates are administered with *CYP2C19* inducers. For example in tuberculosis patients who are on rifampicin and omeprazole might be less responsive to omeprazole or other PPIs. Studies are needed to explore the influence of genotype and promoter region variants on drug induction/inhibition which in turn may explain its influence on drug-drug interactions.

2.8.8 Manipulation of drug interactions of *CYP2C19* substrates for therapeutic benefit -Hypothesis:

One of important factors that contribute to the inter-individual variability in the expression of *CYP2C19* is the inducibility after exposure of the individuals to xenobiotics. Exposure of primary hepatocytes to drugs like rifampicin, paclitaxel, phenobarbital and glucocorticoids had resulted in increased expression of *CYP2C* genes including *CYP2C19*.^{261;270} *In vivo* experiments have also shown the increased metabolism of *CYP2C* substrates when exposed to these drugs.^{298;335} Thus co-administering the substrates of *CYP2C19* along with its inducers may result in therapeutic failure in case of agents inactivated by *CYP2C19* (omeprazole) and may enhance the therapeutic efficacy in case of agents activated by *CYP2C19* (clopidogrel, proguanil).

The drug interactions involving *CYP2C19* may also be manipulated for therapeutic uses. It has been reported that artemisinin derivatives induce cytochrome P 450

enzymes including CYP2C19.³³⁶ These derivatives are commonly used for treating the multidrug resistant *Plasmodium falciparum* infection.³³⁷ Proguanil is another drug which is being promoted for its use in multidrug resistant *P.falciparum* infections and it undergoes activation by CYP2C19. Proguanil to cycloguanil conversion is important for its antimalarial activity and the conversion occurs to a greater extent in EMs of CYP2C19. Thus there is a possibility that a combination of the artemisinin derivatives along with proguanil may have improved therapeutic benefit. Because CYP2C19 induction by artemisinin may bring about increased plasma levels of cycloguanil resulting in increased efficacy. But the data is available in the literature supporting the idea that the parent drug proguanil also has some intrinsic anti malarial activity.¹⁷⁰ But still it is unclear how this is related to a clinical situation and studies are needed to establish this hypothesis.

2.9 Molecular modelling of CYP2C19 and computational prediction of substrates, inducers and inhibitors:

A study by Lewis et al has modelled the CYP2C19 and its interaction with its substrates *in silico*.^{338;339} It has been shown that the amino acid residues between 200 to 300 including serine, threonine, lysine, phenyl alanine, valine, asparagine are mostly involved in the binding to the substrates. Amino acid residues at positions 46 (asparagine), 50(valine), 72(glutamate), 73(arginine), 74(methionine), 365(serine), 473(valine) also forms its binding site along with other amino acid residues from 200 to 300. The π - π stacking interactions have been predicted between the substrates of CYP2C19 and its active site. Benzimidazole, pyridine rings from the substrates (omeprazole) interact with the aromatic side chains of phenylalanine at 114, 473 positions along with hydrogen bonding from histidine at 99 position and glutamine at 214 position. The experimental and predicted binding affinity toward the active site of the enzyme is highest for omeprazole followed by mephenytoin and proguanil. These modelling studies will help us to understand the substrate specificity and can also be used to predict the inducers and inhibitors of the enzymes by studying the interaction of the ligands with that of different sites in the enzymes.³⁴⁰ The results obtained by these prediction models are easily interpretable but of limited value unless experimental evidence is obtained for the same. Different approaches such as homology modelling and docking, combined 3 dimensional quantitative structural activity relationship homology, semi imperial quantitative mechanical models are commonly used for these studies. Basically the

structural information of the molecules interacting with that of enzyme is used for studying the interaction. The electronic structure of the ligands and calculation of activation energies, binding energies, and other properties such as lipophilicity, hydrogen bond donor capacity of the ligands along with the structural information of the protein obtained by X-ray crystallography or homology modelling are usually considered in these approaches. These studies predict the orientation of one molecule and its interaction with another molecule in the complex and the method is called as docking. In these studies we can also predict how the substrate changes the conformation of the enzymes and its active sites which may further decreases its affinity towards the active site and inhibiting its own metabolism.³⁴¹ One may also use these tools to predict the effect of the variations on its interaction with the substrates.³⁴² There are several tools, database and software available for this purpose. One should use the results with precaution for planning experimental studies or to understand the results obtained in laboratory experiments. The list of the tools and database are given in table 8.

Table 8. Commonly used tools/software for computational analysis of DNA-protein-drug interactions

S.No	Tool/Software/Database (company name)	Website address/link/URL
1	Biotransformation database (Accelrys)	www.accelrys.com
2	METAPC (Multicase)	www.multicase.com
3	Metabolexpert (Compudrug)	www.comdrug.com
4	Metabolic database (MDL information system)	www.mdl.com
5	METEOR (Lhasa)	www.chem.leeds.ac.uk/LUK/
6	QUANTA Discovery Studio (Accelrys)	www.accelrys.com
7	AutoDock	www.autodock.scripps.edu/
8	UCSF Dock	http://dock.compbio.ucsf.edu/
9	ANR DOCK	http://dockinggrid.gforge.inria.fr/
10	GRAMM	http://vakser.bioinformatics.ku.edu/main/resources_gramm.php
11	Molegro Virtual Grid	http://www.molegro.com/
12	Quickprop (Schrodinger)	www.schrodinger.com
13	GRID (molecular discovery)	www.moldiscovery.com
14	Chemtree (Golden Helix)	www.goldenhelix.com/index.jsp
15	GOLD	http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/products/life_sciences/gold/

3.0 Lacunae in the current literature

Except for the studies by Arefayene *et al*²² and Fukushima-Uesaka *et al*³⁰ no study has explored the variations in the promoter region of *CYP2C19* gene. There are conflicting reports about the involvement of transcription factors in *CYP2C19* gene regulation. The functional characterization of the variants in the *CYP2C19* promoter region was not performed in the previous studies, except for one study by Sim *et al*.¹⁶ It explained the ultra rapid metabolism due to *CYP2C19**17 allele, but could not establish the role of transcription factors. The role of constitutively expressed CCAAT binding proteins, nuclear factor cAMP response element binding protein and nuclear receptors other than PXR and GR in controlling the transcription of *CYP2C19* gene was not explored. The reason for wide ranges in the metabolic ratios of *CYP2C19* in extensive metabolizers and discrepancies in genotype-phenotype association studies was unknown. The variations are population specific and no data from Indian sub continent was available on *CYP2C19* promoter region. No study was available which explored the linkage disequilibrium pattern between *CYP2C19* promoter region variants and *CYP2C9**2 and *3 alleles. There was no data available on copy number variations of *CYP2C19* in the literature at the time of starting this study to the best of my knowledge.

Objectives

4.0 Aims and Objectives

- **1:** To identify SNPs in the 5'-regulatory region of *CYP2C19* gene and to construct the haplotypes of genetic variations of *CYP2C19* in South Indian subjects.
- **2:** To functionally characterize the genetic variations in *CYP2C19* 5' regulatory region *in silico*, *in vitro* and *in vivo*
- **3:** To study genotype-phenotype relation of *CYP2C19* in South Indian population using proguanil as a probe drug.
- **4:** To explore the effect of *CYP2C9* and *CYP2C19* genotypes on proguanil oxidation in South Indian population
- **5:** To establish the allele and genotype frequencies of *CYP2C19* *17 (-806C>T) in South Indian Tamilian population.
- **6:** To perform relative copy number variation analysis of *CYP2C19* in South Indian population.

Materials and Methods

5.0 Materials and Methods

All chemicals used are molecular biology grade/AR grade/HPLC grade. The list of chemicals and reagents used for DNA extraction, gel electrophoresis, high performance liquid chromatography, polymerase chain reaction, restriction fragment length polymorphism, cell culture, transfection experiments, gel shift assays, list of instruments and software used for *in silico* analysis and statistical analysis are given in tables 9-16.

Table 9. Chemicals used for DNA extraction

Chemical/REAGENT	GRADE	Source
Ammonium bicarbonate	Molecular biology	ICN Biomedicals, Inc., Ohio, USA
Ammonium chloride	Pro Analysis	Merck Specialities Limited, Mumbai, India
Chloroform	HPLC	Qualigens fine chemicals, Mumbai, India
EDTA disodium hydrate	Biotechnology	Amersco, Ohio, USA
Ethanol absolute 99.9%	Molecular biology	S.d. fine-chem Ltd., Mumbai, India
Hydrochloric acid	Analytical Reagent	Qualigens fine chemicals, Mumbai, India
2-Mercaptoethanol	Pro Analysis	Merck Specialities Limited, Mumbai, India
1-Octanol	Sigma	Sigma-Aldrich co., MO, USA
Phenol	Analytical Reagent	Rankem, Ranbaxy Laboratories, S.A.S. Nagar, India
Proteinase K	Molecular biology grade	Genei, Bangalore, India
Sodium chloride	Ultrapure ACS reagent	USB Corporation, OH, USA
Tri-Sodium citrate	Laboratory reagent	Qualigens fine chemicals, Mumbai, India
Sodium lauryl sulphate	Molecular biology	SISCO Research Laboratories Pvt. Ltd, Mumbai
Sodium hydroxide pellets	Analytical reagent	Rankem, Ranbaxy Laboratories, S.A.S. Nagar
Tris buffer	Molecular biology	Merck Specialities Limited, Mumbai, India

Table 10. Reagents used for polymerase chain reaction & restriction digestion

Purpose	Chemical/REAGENT	Source
Polymerase Chain Reaction	Primers	Alpha DNA, MontreL, Quebec
		Sigma-Aldrich co., MO, USA
	Taq DNA polymerase	New England Biolabs, Inc., MA 01915, USA
	dNTPs	Bangalore Genei, Bangalore, India
		MBI Fermentas International Inc, Canada
		Medox Biotech India Pvt Ltd, Chennai, India
	Magnesium chloride	Sigma-Aldrich Co., MO, USA
Expand Long Template PCR system™	Roche Diagnostics GmbH, Mannheim, Germany	
Restriction Digestion	<i>Ava</i> II	New England Biolabs, Inc., MA 01915, USA
	<i>Nsi</i> I	New England Biolabs, Inc., MA 01915, USA
	<i>Kpn</i> I	MBI Fermentas International Inc, Canada
	<i>Sma</i> I	MBI Fermentas International Inc, Canada
	<i>BamH</i> I	New England Biolabs, Inc., MA 01915, USA
Sequencing	GeNei™ Quick PCR Purification kit	Bangalore Genei, Bangalore, India
	ABI Big Dye Terminator Cycle Sequencing Kit	Applied Biosystems, CA, USA (performed at Macrogen Inc, Korea and INSERM 775, France)

Table 11. Chemicals used for horizontal & vertical gel electrophoresis

Chemical/Reagent	Source
Acrylamide: bisacrylamide 30%, 29:1	Genei, Bangalore, India (ER02)
	Medox Biotech India Pvt Ltd, Chennai, India
Agarose	Sigma, St. Louis, Missouri, USA (A7802)
	Bangalore Genei, Bangalore, India
	Medox Biotech India Pvt Ltd, Chennai, India
Tris base	Himedia Laboratories Ltd., Mumbai, India
Glacial acetic acid	Spectrum reagents and chemicals Pvt, Ltd, Cochin, India
Boric acid	Ranbaxy Fine Chemicals Ltd., S.A.S. Nagar, India
Disodium EDTA	Amersco, Ohio, USA
Ammonium persulphate	SISCO research laboratories pvt. ltd., Mumbai
TEMED	AppliChem GmbH, Darmstadt, Germany
Ethidium bromide	Medox Biotech India Pvt Ltd, Chennai, India
Bromophenol blue	S.d.fine chem Ltd., Mumbai, India
Xylene cyanol	Loba Chemie, Mumbai, India
Ficoll	Loba Chemie, Mumbai, India
DNA ladder (50bp, 100 bp, 1kb)	New England Biolabs, Beverly, MA, USA
	MBI Fermentas International Inc, Canada

Table 12. Chemicals used for HPLC analysis (HPLC grade)

Purpose	Chemical/Reagent	Source
Proguanil and cycloguanil measurement in plasma by HPLC	Acetonitrile	MERCK Specialties Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India
	Sodium lauryl sulphate	SISCO Research laboratories Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India
	Triethylamine	SISCO Research laboratories Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India
	Glacial acetic acid	Spectrum Reagents and Chemicals Pvt Ltd, Cochin, India
	Methanol	MERCK Specialties Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India
	Proguanil pure powder	Unicare Remedies Pvt. Ltd, Baroda, India
	Cycloguanil pure powder	Walter Reed Army Institute of Research, Silver Spring, Maryland, USA
	Laveran TM	Unicare Remedies Pvt. Ltd, Baroda, India

Table 13. Chemicals /reagents/kits used for cloning and transfection experiments

Purpose	Chemical/Reagent/Kits	Source
Cloning of <i>CYP2C19</i> regulatory region into <i>pGL-3</i> basic reporter vector , transfection of fused plasmids into <i>HepG2</i> cell lines and Dual luciferase activity measurement	<i>pGL-3</i> basic reporter vector	Promega corporation, Madison, USA
	<i>pRL-SV40</i> reporter vector	Promega corporation, Madison, USA
	DH10-beta chemical competent cells	Promega corporation, Madison, USA
	Lipofectamine TM reagent	Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA, USA
	<i>HepG2</i> cell lines	NCCS, Pune, India
	Dual Luciferase Reporter [®] Assay System	Promega corporation, Madison, USA
	Dulbecco's Modified Eagles Medium (DMEM)	Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA, USA
	Alkaline phosphatase	New England Biolabs, Beverly, MA, USA

Continued...

Table 13. Chemicals /reagents/kits used for cloning and transfection experiments

Purpose	Chemical/Reagent/Kits	Source
Cloning of <i>CYP2C19</i> regulatory region into <i>pGL-3</i> basic reporter vector , transfection of fused plasmids into HepG2 cell lines and dual luciferase activity measurement	KpnI, Hind III, Xba I, T ₄ DNA ligase, Bovine serum albumin	New England Biolabs, Beverly, MA, USA
	Ethanol	S.d. fine-chem ltd., Mumbai, India
	Isopropyl alcohol	MERCK Specialties Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India
	Saturated phenol	Rankem, Ranbaxy Laboratories, S.A.S. Nagar, India
	Chloroform	MERCK Specialties Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India
	Octanol	MERCK Specialties Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India
	Sodium acetate	SISCO Research laboratories Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India
	Glycerol	SISCO Research laboratories Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India
	Calcium chloride	Qualigens fine chemicals, Mumbai, India
	Tris	Qualigens fine chemicals, Mumbai, India
	Sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS)	SISCO Research laboratories Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India
	EDTA	Qualigens fine chemicals, Mumbai, India
	Glucose	Himedia laboratories ltd., Mumbai, India
	Potassium chloride	Qualigens fine chemicals, Mumbai, India
	Sodium chloride	USB Corporation, OH, USA
	Magnesium chloride	Qualigens fine chemicals, Mumbai, India
Bacotryptone, Yeast extract	Himedia laboratories ltd., Mumbai, India	
Quiagen Miniprep® plasmid extraction kits	Quiagen, GmBH, Hilden, Germany	
Quiagen Maxiprep® plasmid extraction kit	Quiagen, GmBH, Hilden, Germany	
Quiagen Gel elution® kits	Quiagen, GmBH, Hilden, Germany	

Table 14. Chemicals /reagents/kits used for electrophoretic mobility shift assays

Purpose	Chemical/Reagent/Kits	Source
Setting up of binding reactions of predicted binding site oligos and HepG2 nuclear extract, separation on native Polyacrylamide gel, transferring of the free oligos and complexes onto a Biodyne B membrane by blotting and chemiluminescence detection	LightShift [®] Chemiluminescent EMSA Kit	PIERCE, Rockford, IL, USA
	Labeled and unlabeled oligos representing transcription factor binding sites	Bioserve Biotechnologies, Hyderabad, India
	Bradford reagent	Sigma-Aldrich Corporation Bangalore, India
	Nuclear extraction protease inhibitor cocktail	Cayman chemical, Michigan, USA
	Dithiothreitol (DTT)	Sigma-Aldrich Corporation Bangalore, India
	Phenyl methyl sulfonyl fluoride (PMSF)	Sigma-Aldrich Corporation Bangalore, India
	HEPES	Sigma-Aldrich Corporation Bangalore, India
	Potassium chloride	Sigma-Aldrich Corporation Bangalore, India
	Glycerol	SISCO Research laboratories Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India
	Biodyne B nylon membrane	Thermoscientific, Rockford, USA
	Polyacrylamide	Medox Biotech agencies, Chennai

Table 15. List of instruments used

Equipment	Make/Model
ABI Prism 7700 DNA Genetic Analyzer	Applied Biosystems, CA, USA (at Macrogen Inc, Korea)
Infinite M 200 Multianalyzer	Tecan, Austria
CO ₂ Incubator	Thermoscientific, USA
Inverted Microscope	Olympus, Singapore
Cryogenic liquid nitrogen container	Thomas Scientific, USA
Class II Laminar Air hood	ESCO, Singapore
Real time PCR (ABI7300)	Applied Bio Systems, USA
Biophotometer	Eppendorf, Germany
Centrifuge	Remi Instruments Ltd, Mumbai, India
Deep freezer(-80°C)	Sanyo Ultra low, Gumma, Japan

Continued...

Table 15. List of instruments used

Equipment	Make/Model
Dry bath	Genei, Bangalore, India
Electronic balance	Precisa, Dietkon, Switzerland
Elix RIO3 water purification system	Millipore, USA
Milli-Q Biocel water purification system	Millipore, USA
Gel documentation system	Vilber Lourmat, France and UVP, LLC Upland, CA
Gel rocker	Genei, Bangalore
Horizontal Electrophoresis system	Appelx, Paris, France
HPLC system	Shimadzu, Maryland, USA
Microcentrifuge	Hettich, Fohrenstr, Tuttlingen
Micropipettes and accessories	Eppendorf, Hamilton, Finpipette, Nichipipette
Microwave oven	Kenstar
Orbital shaker	Scigenics biotechnologies, Chennai
Incubator	Scigenics biotechnologies, Chennai
pH meter	Digisun Electronics, Chennai
Spectrophotometer	Hitachi Technologies America Inc, California, USA
Thermal cycler	Eppendorf Master cycler Gradient
UV sterilization chamber	Genei, Bangalore
Vertical Electrophoresis system	Shelton Scientific, Iowa, USA
Vortex mixer	Remi cycle mixer, Mumbai
FLA 3000 Phosphorimager	Fujifilm
Semidry blotting apparatus	C.B.S Scientific, CA, USA
UV Stratalinker® 1800	Stratagene
Ice maker	Cryotech technologies, Chennai
Autoclave	Rajendra Scientific, Pondicherry
Water bath	Maitri, Pondicherry
Rocker vacuum pump	Tarsons products (P)Ltd, India

Table 16. List of software and statistical tools used

Tool/ Software name	Company name and available source
Lasergene version 7	DNASTAR, Inc., Madison, Wisconsin, USA (Commercial software procured and made available by pharmacogenomics laboratory, JIPMER)
Helix Tree software version 6.0.2	Helix, Inc. Bozeman, MT, USA. HelixTree®Software. http://www.goldenhelix.com (used trial version)
Haploview version 4.1	Available at: http://www.broadinstitute.org/mpg/haploview (Free software)
Nucplot	Available at: http://www.biochem.ucl.ac.uk/bsm/nucplot.html (Free software)
DNA sequence to structure tool	Available at: www.scfbio-iitd.res.in/software/drugdesign/bdna.jsp (Free tool)
Patchdock	Available at : http://bioinfo3d.cs.tau.ac.il/PatchDock/ (free tool)
MatInspector	Available at : http://www.genomatix.de/products/MatInspector/index.html (Free for academic users)
NEB cutter version 2.0	Available at : http://tools.neb.com/NEBcutter2/ (Free tool)
BioEdit	Available at : http://www.mbio.ncsu.edu/BioEdit/BioEdit.html (Free tool)
Chromas	Available at : http://www.technelysium.com.au/chromas.html (Free tool)
BLAST	Available at: http://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi (Free tool)
Primer 3	Available at: http://frodo.wi.mit.edu/primer3/
Image J software	Available at: rsbweb.nih.gov/ij/
SPSS version 13	SPSS Inc., Chicago, USA (procured and made available by JIPMER)
GraphPad Instat® version 3.06	GraphPad software Inc., San Diego, USA
Microsoft Office Suite 97-2003	Microsoft Corporation,

Figure 11. Study Design

5.1 Study design

An overview of the study design is given in figure 11. After explaining the procedure and taking written informed consent from the healthy volunteers of South Indian origin, and tab proguanil hydrochloride (LaveranTM) 200 mg was administered. Four hours later, 5 ml of blood was collected in a polypropylene tube containing 100 µl of 10% ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid (EDTA). After centrifugation, the cellular part (leucocytes) was used for DNA extraction and the remnant plasma was used for estimation of proguanil and its metabolite cycloguanil. The DNA was used for 5' flanking region amplification, sequencing and genotyping of *2 and *3 alleles by polymerase chain reaction and restriction fragment length polymorphism (PCR-RFLP) method. Following the sequence analysis nine constructs were made by cloning 5' flanking region from nine different individuals into *pGL-3* reporter vector. They were transfected into *HepG2* cell lines and luciferase activity was measured. The allele and genotype frequencies of *CYP2C19*17* was also established in a larger and homogeneous Tamilian population, followed by the exploration of copy number variation of *CYP2C19* gene in South Indian population. This study protocol was approved by Institutional Human Ethics Committee of JIPMER. A copy of the consent form for the study is enclosed in the annexure.

5.2 Subjects

The study was conducted in Pharmacogenomics laboratory, Department of Pharmacology, JIPMER, Pondicherry, India from January 2007 to August 2010. The subjects were all healthy volunteers of South Indian origin belonging to any of the South Indian states i.e. Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Tamilnadu and Pondicherry. The number of subjects selected were different for sequencing and identification of polymorphisms in *CYP2C19* 5' flanking region (n=58), for genotype-phenotype analysis of *CYP2C19* using proguanil as a probe drug, copy number variation analysis of *CYP2C19* in South Indian population (n=50), and for establishment of genotype and allele frequencies of *CYP2C19*17* (n= 206). For sequencing and identification of new polymorphisms and for genotype-phenotype association studies, subjects selected were from any of the South Indian states and speak the local language. Less number of subjects were included as it was an explorative study to identify the most frequent variations only. For establishment of *CYP2C19*17* allele and genotype

frequencies subjects selected were from the states of Tamilnadu and Pondicherry only (South Indian Tamilian population).

Sequencing of CYP2C19 5' regulatory region

Unrelated, healthy volunteers of South Indian origin (n = 58), of either sex (45 men and 13 women) aged between 18-55 years (mean \pm SD of 29.0 ± 8.6 years) were included in the study. They were assigned South Indian status based on their family history of past three generations staying in any of the South Indian states and speaking the local language.

Genotype-Phenotype association of CYP2C19 using proguanil as a probe drug and copy number variation analysis

Fifty unrelated, healthy volunteers of South Indian origin from the above, of either sex (42 men and 8 women) aged between 19-55 years (mean \pm SD of 27.8 ± 6.7 years) were included in the study. None of the subjects had a history of hepatic, gastrointestinal, renal or hematological abnormalities. Subjects with a history of drug allergy were excluded from the study. All the subjects were non-smokers and had abstained from taking alcohol for at least 10 days prior to and during the study. They were not on any concomitant medication including herbal drugs

*Establishment of genotype and allele frequencies of CYP2C19*17*

Unrelated healthy volunteers of Tamilian origin (n=206), of either sex (98 men and 108 women) between the age of 18–60 years (mean \pm SD of 37.6 ± 10.4 years) were included in the study. The subjects were assigned Tamilian status based on their family history of the past three generations staying in Tamil Nadu and speaking the local language.

5.3 Collection of blood and DNA extraction procedure

About 5 ml of blood was collected from each volunteer into a polypropylene tube containing 100 μ l of 10% ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid (EDTA) as an anticoagulant. Genomic DNA was extracted from peripheral leukocytes using standard phenol-chloroform extraction method.³⁴³ The quality and quantity of DNA was estimated using a spectrophotometer. Each DNA sample was diluted to an optimal

concentration of 50-100 ng/ μ l, which was suitable for the Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR), and stored in aliquots at 4°C.

DNA extraction procedure:

The blood samples that were collected in polypropylene tubes containing 100 μ l of 10% EDTA were centrifuged at 2500 rpm for 10 minutes at 4°C. Plasma was separated, and the cellular fraction was used for DNA extraction. The cellular part was thawed at room temperature. After adding 10 ml of RBC lysis solution into these tubes, it was gently shaken for 3 min and kept in a freezer at -20°C for 10 min. It was then centrifuged at 2500 rpm for 10 min at 4°C. The upper layer was discarded. RBC lysis solution was added again, mixed, centrifuged and upper layer was discarded. This process was repeated till the RBCs were lysed and removed completely. To the remaining cellular part, 2.25 ml of WBC lysis solution was added and mixed well using Pasteur pipette. This was followed by addition of 125 μ l of 10% sodium lauryl sulphate, 50 μ l of proteinase K, and 75 μ l of milliQ water. It was mixed well again and incubated at 37°C, overnight.

After ensuring complete lysis, 1 ml of saturated NaCl was added and mixed using pasteur pipette. This was followed by addition of 3.5 ml of chloroform and mixed till the solution became a homogenous mixture. It was centrifuged at 4000 rpm at 4°C for 25 min. The upper aqueous layer was removed carefully with a Pasteur pipette without disturbing the lower organic layer. The lower organic layer was discarded. The aqueous layer was transferred to a fresh tube into which 2.5 ml of equilibrated phenol was added, mixed gently for 5 min and centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 20 min at 4°C. The upper layer was removed using the Pasteur pipette without disturbing the lower layer and transferred to a fresh tube. Then 2.5 ml of chloroform: octanol (24:1) was added to the tube containing the transferred upper layer, and mixed gently for 5 min by inverting and centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 20 min. The supernatant was transferred to another fresh tube into which 2 volumes of ice-cold absolute ethanol was added and mixed. High molecular DNA was precipitated which was removed using a clean pipette tip and washed with 70 % ethanol by tapping the tube five to six times. The DNA was removed from the ethanol tube and air dried. It was transferred to a micro centrifuge tube containing 200 μ l of 1XTE buffer (pH 7.4). After proper mixing, the micro centrifuge tube containing the extracted DNA was incubated at 37°C overnight.

The optical density (OD) of the extracted DNA was measured at 260, 270 and 280 nm using spectrophotometer. The OD at 260nm corresponds to DNA, 270nm corresponds to phenol and 280nm corresponds to proteins.

Quantification of DNA (ng/μl) = OD at 260nm x d x 50

d→ dilution factor.

50→ 1OD of DNA= 50ng/μl of double stranded DNA.

5.4 Amplification of 5' regulatory region of *CYP2C19* for sequencing

Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) conditions for amplification:

The 5'-regulatory region of *CYP2C19* was amplified by long-range PCR according to the method described by Arefayene *et al* with minor modifications.²² The 1.7 kb fragment was amplified by the following *2C19* gene specific primers to avoid the amplification from the homologous genes (Forward primer: P2- 5'-CAG CAC ACA CCA TGT TCT TGG CTA CAG-3'; Reverse primer: pEX12- 5'-ACA GAG CAC AAG GAC CAC AAA AGG A-3'). The location of the primers and their sequences are given in table 17. The PCR was performed using the expand long template PCR system (Roche Molecular Biochemical's, Mannheim, Germany) in a 50 μl reaction mixture, containing 50 ng of genomic DNA template, 10 mmol/l dNTPs, 300 nmol/l of each primer, 3.00 mmol/l MgCl₂, 1X PCR buffer and 0.75 μl of the supplied enzyme mix. The following cycle conditions were used: 94°C for 2s, 72°C for 3 min of seven cycles, followed by 94°C for 2s, 71°C for 3 min of 32 cycles and a final 67°C elongation for 4 min using Eppendorf Mastercycler Gradient (Eppendorf, Hamburg, Germany). Following the PCR amplification, products were checked for amplification by horizontal gel electrophoresis (Apelex, Massey Cedex, France), using 1% agarose gel. Amplified fragments were visualized by staining with ethidium bromide (Vilber Lourmat, France) and the fragment size was checked using 1 kb DNA ladder (New England Biolabs, Beverly, MA, USA). The PCR product was visualized between 1.5 and 2.0 kb segments of 1 kb DNA ladder (Figure 12).

Table 17. Primer sequences used for amplification and sequencing of *CYP2C19* gene

Amplified or sequenced region	Primers		Amplified length (bp)	Position	
				From translational start site	NC_000010.9
<i>CYP2C19</i> 5'-flanking region	<i>2C19-P2(F)</i>	5'-CAG CAC ACA CCA TGT TCT TGG CTA CAG-3'	1708	-1678 to -1652	96510775 – 96510801
	<i>2C19-pEX12(R)</i>	5'-ACA GAG CAC AAG GAC CAC AA A AGG A-3'		+3 to +27	96529767 – 96529791
<i>CYP2C19</i> *2 & *3	<i>2C19*2(F)</i>	5'-AAT TAC AAC CAG AGC TTG GC-3'	169	+19036 to +19055	96531488 – 96531508
	<i>2C19*2(R)</i>	5'- TATC ACT TTC CAT AAA AGC AAG-3'		+19182 to +19202	96531634 – 96531654
	<i>2C19*3(F)</i>	5'-TAT TAT TAT CTG TTA ACT AAT ATG A-3'	329	+18024 to +18043	96530167 – 96530191
	<i>2C19*3(R)</i>	5'-ACT TCA GGG CTT GGT CAA TA-3'		+17715 to +17739	96530476 – 96530495
Sequencing of 5'-flanking region	<i>2C19-P2 (F)</i>	5'-CAG CAC ACA CCA TGT TCT TGG CTA CAG-3'		-1678 to -1652	96510775 – 96510801
	<i>2C19-pEX12 (R)</i>	5'-ACA GAG CAC AAG GAC CAC AA A AGG A-3'		+ 3 to + 27	96529767 – 96529791
	<i>2C19-M1 (F)</i>	5'-TAT GTT TGG TTA TTG AAG AT-3'		-580 to -561	96511873 – 96511892
	<i>2C19-M2(F)</i>	5'-CCT ATG CTT GCT TTG CAT TG-3'		-1205 to -1186	96511248 – 96511267
	<i>2C19-PR2(R)</i>	5'-TAT CGA AGA TTA GGA GAC TTT GTC C-3'		-480 to -456	96511973 – 96511997
	<i>2C19-PR3(R)</i>	5'-TTC TGA ATA TAT ACC ACA TTC ATC CTG-3'		-923 to -897	96511530 – 96511556
	<i>2C19-PR5(R)</i>	5'-TGT GAA TCT AAT AGA GGA TGG GAG G-3'		-1252 to -1228	96511201 – 96511225

F-Forward primer ; R- Reverse primer; bp-base pair

Figure 12. Purified PCR amplified product visualized in 1% agarose gel (1708 bp)

Sequencing of the amplified PCR product:

PCR amplified products were purified by using GeNei™ Quick PCR Purification Kit (Bangalore Genei, Bangalore, India) and sequenced on both strands using the ABI Big Dye Terminator Cycle Sequencing Kit and the ABI Prism 7700 DNA sequencer (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA, USA). All the samples were sequenced at Macrogen Inc, Korea and repeated sequencing reactions were performed at Bioserve biotechnologies, Hyderabad, India. Samples were sequenced with the two primers used for the product amplification and with the other primers shown in Table 17. A total of seven primers (3 forward and 4 reverse primers) were used to get overlapping sequences to confirm any variations at a particular location. The alignment details of each primer are given in the figure 13.

5.4.1 Identification of variations/polymorphisms in *CYP2C19* 5' regulatory region:

The individual sequences from each subject i.e. the sequences obtained by using seven primers were assembled into a single contig using the SeqMan Pro module of Lasergene software from DNASTAR, Inc. (Madison, Wisconsin, USA). Each sequence was confirmed as 5' regulatory region of *CYP2C19* by aligning with the other 2C gene sequences, and all the sequences were checked for specific regions in *CYP2C19* 5' regulatory region which differ from the other homologous gene sequences, especially

CYP2C9. All the contigs constructed were found to be different from the nearest homologous gene *CYP2C9*.

The contigs constructed from 58 individuals were also compared among themselves and were aligned with the reference sequence (NC_000010.9) to identify inter-individual differences using the MegAlign module of Lasergene software from DNASTAR, Inc. (Madison, Wisconsin, USA). Each variation was verified by manual inspection of the electropherogram. Confirmation of each variation was done by resequencing that particular region by using newly generated PCR product from the same sample and by manual inspection for the existence of the mutation on the electropherogram.

ENSEMBL GENE ID: ENSG00000165841

Forward Primer : 5'-CAGCAGACACCATGTTCTTGGCTACAG-3' (P2)

Reverse primer : 5'-ACAGAGCACAAGGACCACAAAAGGA-3' (pEX12)

Primers for DNA Sequencing : 5'-TATGTTTGGTTATTGAAGAT-3' (M1)
5'-TGTGAATCTAATAGAGGATGGGAGG-3' (PR5)
5'-TTCTGAATATATAACCACATTCATCCTG-3' (PR3)
5'-TATCGAAGATTAGGAGACTTTGTCC-3' (PR2)

Long PCR product size : 1708 bases

CAGCAGACACCATGTTCTTGGCTACAGTACTGAATCTTCAAGGCTCAGCCTCCTCATTTCCTGAGATGGGTC
AATTTTATTGTAAGCAAAGGCAATTGAGAGATTCCAAAGGGATATGAGGTGTGAGAATTCTCTCTAAATGG
GGTTAGAATCCCTGTTAAAAATGACCAGTGAACATTTGTGCAATTGTGTCTTAAACATAACTTACTTTTTCT
TAATAAGAGAAGTGGAAATAACCTCATTAGGAAATTTAGAACAAATACGATGATATCTTTAAAGAAAATGG
CTTTGTGTAAGTATTGTCGTTAGTGATCTAGTAATGTGTATCTTTCTGGTTGATTTAGACCTTCAACTCA
AATGTCAGCTCCCCTAAGGTCTATACATTGTGGTGGTTTTGTGCTGTGGGTCCATTTAGTGATTTCCCTA
CCTCCCATCCTCTATTAGATTCACA ACTGTTGTTCTGCCATAATTCCTATGCTTGCTTTGCATTGTTAC
ATTTTTTTTTGAAAATCAGAAAGCAAATCAATATAAAGCAGCCATGTCTGGAGGAGACCAGGAGGTCAAG
AAGCCTTAGTTTTCTCAAGCCCTTAGCACCAATTTCTCTGAGATCAGCTCTTCCTTCAGTTACACTGAGCAT
TTCCCCTCTGCAGTGTGAGAAGGGAGAACTCTATTTTTTCTCATGAGCATCTCTGGGGCTGTTTTCT
TAGATAAATAAGTGGTTCTATTTAATGTGAAGCCTGTTTTATGAA CAGGATGAATGTGGTATAIATTCAGA
ATAACTAATGTTTGGAAAGTGTGTTTTGTTTTGCTAAAACAAAGTTTTAGCAAACGATTTTTTTTTTCAAAT
TGTGTCTTCTGTTCTCAAAGCATCTCTGATGTAAGAGATAATGCGCCACGATGGGCATCAGAAGACCTCAG
CTCAAATCCCAGTTCTGCCAGCTATGAGCTGTGTGGCACCAACAGGTGTCTCTCCAGGGTCTCCCT
TTTCCCATTTGAAATATAAAAAATAACAATTCCTGCCTTACAGTGTTTTTTTAGGGGGTTAAATGGTAAAG
GTGTTTATATCTGCTAAGGTAATTTACTTGATA TATGTTTGGTTATTGAAGATATATGAGTTATGTTAGCT
ATTTTCATGTTTAGGCTGCTGTTTTTTAGTAGGCTATATTTAAATAGAGGATTTTCATTATAAAAGGACAAAGT
CTCCTAATCTTCGATA TAGGATTGACATACTTTTTAAATATACAAGGCATAGAATATGGCCATTTCCGTTA
AATCATAAATTCCAAAGTGGTTATTAATCTAAGAATTCAGAAATTTAAGTAATGTTTTTGCATCAGATTG
TTTACTTCAGTGCTCTCAATTATGACGGTGCATTGGAACCACTTGGGTAAACATTTTTTTGTTTTTATTAC
CAATACCTAGGCTTCAACCTAGTACAATGAAACCAGAATGTACAGAGTGGGCACCTGGGACGAAGGAGAACA
AGACCAAAGGACATTTTATTTTATCTATCAGTGGGTCAAAGTCTTTTCAGAAGGAGCATATAGTGGGC
CTAGGTGATTGGCCACTTTATCCATCAAAGAGGCACACACACTTAATTAGCATGGAGTGTATATAAAAAGCT
TGGAGTGCAAGCTCACGGTTGTCTTAAACAAGAGGAGAAGGCTTCAATGGA TCCTTTTTGTGGTCTTTGTGCT
CTGTCTCTCATGTTTGTCTCTCTTTCAATCTGGAGACAGAGCTCTGGGAGAGGAAAACCTCCTCCTGGCC
CTACTCCTCTCCAGTGATTGGAATATCCTACAGATAGATATTAAGGATGTCAGCAAATCCTTA

Translational start site: 96512453(A of ATG i.e. translational start site)

Annotation: Chromosome 10, NC_000010.9 (96512453..96602661)

Figure 13. Alignment of primers in *CYP2C9* 5' flanking region

5.4.2 Genotyping of *CYP2C192 and *CYP2C19**3 alleles by PCR-RFLP method:**

In addition to the sequencing of 5' flanking region, all the samples were genotyped for *2 (681G>A; splicing defect) and *3(636G>A; W212X) alleles of *CYP2C19* by PCR-RFLP method as described earlier.¹⁰⁹

Prediction of transcription factor binding sites in CYP2C19 5' flanking region

The promoter sequence was analyzed for potential Transcription Binding Sites (TBS) from TRANSFAC database using MatInspector (http://www.genomatix.de/cgi-bin/matinspector_prof/mat_fam.pl, access date: 20th August 2007).

5.4.3 Prediction and generation of unbound DNA models of transcription factor binding sites

Putative transcription factor binding sites (TBS) were predicted by using MatInspector tool (http://www.genomatix.de/cgi-bin/matinspector_prof/mat_fam.pl). The theoretical three-dimensional models of TBS sequences for transcription factors (TFs) such as activating transcription factor 2 (ATF-2), transcriptional repressor CDP, CCAAT/enhanced binding protein beta (C/EBPB), GATA binding factor 1 (GATA-1) and glucocorticoid receptor (GR) with normal and variant alleles were predicted using DNA sequence to structure web server (<http://www.scfbio-iitd.res.in/software/drugdesign/bdna.jsp>, access date: 2nd December 2007), developed based on fiber diffraction studies.

5.4.4 Homology modeling of transcription factors

The protein sequences of transcription factors ATF-2 (P15336), C/EBPB (P17676), GR (P04150) were retrieved from Swiss-Prot database (<http://www.expasy.org>, access date: 9th December 2008) and of CDP (AAB26579), GATA-1 (NP_002040) were retrieved from GenPept database (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>, access date: 9th December 2008). Basic local alignment search tool (NCBI-BLAST_P; <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/blast/Blast.cgi>, access date: 10th December 2008) was carried out against protein data bank (PDB) in order to find suitable templates for the TFs. The three-dimensional models of these proteins were predicted by using Swiss model, an automated comparative modeling server (<http://www.expasy.org/tools>). The sequences of all the TFs and their templates were aligned using ClustalW web server and a model was built. These theoretical models were subjected to Swiss-PDB Viewer for energy minimization

with a harmonic constraint of $100 \text{ kJ/mol/\text{Å}^2}$ applied for all protein atoms, using the steepest descent and conjugate gradient technique to correct the stereochemistry of the mode.³⁴⁴ Energy minimization was carried out in vacuo with the GROMOS96 43B1 parameters set, without reaction field to find the stabilization energy of the predicted TFs structure. A few problematic side chain conformations were identified and rectified. Backbone conformation of these refined models was validated by the examination of Psi/Phi Ramachandran plot obtained from RAMPAGE web server.³⁴⁵

5.4.5 Molecular docking of transcription factor into transcription factor binding site

PatchDock web server (<http://bioinfo3d.cs.tau.ac.il/PatchDock/>, access date: 12th December 2008) was used for molecular interaction studies of TFs and their corresponding TBS with normal and variant alleles. The modeled structures of TBS and TFs were used as inputs in these docking simulations. This method is based on shape matching algorithm and has four major stages such as molecular shape representation, surface patch matching, filtering and scoring for DNA protein interaction.³⁴⁶ One hundred docking conformations were performed for each of the TFs with their TBS. For each docking simulation, the binding affinity was inferred by the Geometric Shape Complementarity (SC) score, as the highest score implying the best solution. The docking accuracy was evaluated in terms of clustering root mean square deviation (RMSD) between the docked conformation and the modeled conformation for the TFs. The prediction was considered successful if a RMSD value of less than 2.0 \AA for the best scored conformation was obtained. The schematic 2D plot of TBS-TF complexes were generated by NUCPLOT to find out the binding residues, position, hydrogen bond and non-bonded contact between DNA-protein complexes.³⁴⁷ The details of the tools used in *in silico* analysis are given in table 18.

Table 18. List of tools used for computational/insilico analysis

S. No	Tool Name	Application	Reference
1.	Sequence to Structure server	Modeling of nucleotide sequence	348
2.	BLAST server	Similarity search	349
3.	ClustalW server	Target-template alignment	350
4.	SwissPDB viewer	Protein modeling & energy minimization	344
5.	Rampage server	Ramachandran plot analysis	345
6.	Patch dock server	DNA-Protein interaction	346
7.	Nucplot	Schematic representation of DNA-Protein interaction	347

5.5 Functional characterization of the variations *in vitro*

5.5.1 Construction of reporter plasmids

The 1708 bp fragment upstream from the ATG initiation codon of *CYP2C19* was amplified from human genomic DNA using *KpnI* –P2 (forward primer with *KpnI* restriction site incorporated) and pEX12 (reverse primer). The details of the primers used for amplification and sequencing are given in table 19. *CYP2C19* 5' flanking region from nine different individuals who were found to have different patterns of single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) were amplified using Expand Long Template PCR system (Roche Molecular Biochemical's, Hamburg, Germany) as described earlier.²² The amplified products were then purified using QIAquick Gel Extraction Kit (Qiagen, Chatsworth, CA, USA). They were then digested sequentially by *KpnI* and *HindIII* enzymes (New England Biolabs, Beverly, MA, USA) and the PCR products were cloned into *KpnI* and *HindIII* sites of *pGL3*-basic promoterless luciferase reporter vector (Promega, Madison, Wisconsin, USA). The nine different constructs of varying pattern of SNPs in the *CYP2C19* 5' flanking region that were cloned are given in Figure 14. The genotype details of the loci in the *CYP2C19* 5' region constructs cloned are given in the table 20. They were named J₁ to J₈ with different alleles at the polymorphic loci and were constructed using the insert, spanning from -1635 to -4. The construct

without promoter was named as J₀, whereas the construct fused with promoter region without any variations was named as J_N. All the constructs were sequence verified and their orientation was confirmed. The fused plasmids with *CYP2C19* 5' flanking region were transformed into *DH10β E. coli* cells and cultured. The plasmids were then extracted in bulk and purified by Qiagen miniprep and maxiprep kits (Qiagen, Chatsworth, CA, USA). The purified fused plasmids were used for transfection experiments. The detailed cloning protocol is given under appendices and the pictorial representation of different steps such as location of restriction sites in vector, checking of extracted plasmid, transformation, checking for the presence of insert by digesting the plasmid is shown in figures 15,16 and 17.

5.5.2 Cell culture

HepG2 cell lines were employed in the present study. *HepG2* cells were obtained from National Centre for Cell Science, Pune, India and were cultured in Dulbecco's Modified Eagles Medium (DMEM, Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA, USA) containing 10 % v/v heat inactivated foetal bovine serum (FBS, Hi-Media, India), 100 U/ml penicillin, 100 µg/ml streptomycin and 0.1 mM non-essential amino acids (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA, USA) in an atmosphere of 5% CO₂ at 37°C. Cells were passaged after reaching 80-90% confluence. Cells at passage number 51 to 55 (Figure 18) were used for transfection experiments. Cloning protocol is given under appendices.

Figure 14. *CYP2C19* promoter constructs fused with *pGL3* reporter plasmid used for transfection experiments

(a)

(b)

KpnI site
(4) |

Hind III site
(1643) |

CYP2C19 5' region amplified with *KpnI* restriction site incorporated forward primer

Figure 15. Restriction sites for *KpnI* and *Hind III* in *pGL3* basic vector (a) and *CYP2C19* 5' region (b). *pGL3* basic vector size : 4818 bp, digested product size : 4770bp; *CYP2C19* 5' region amplified: 1714 bp , digested product size: 1635 bp; The promoter region of *CYP2C19* upto 1635 bp and start codon of *Luc+* gene situated at 87th position of *pGL3* basic vector. Total size of the fused plasmid was: 6405 bp.

Figure 16. A, B) Miniprep of plasmid alone run on 0.8 % agarose gel. All wells were loaded with minipreps prepared from the transformed colonies after transformation of 1ng/ μ l of plasmid into DH10 β chemical competent cells run in agarose gel- 0.8%; **C) Transformed colonies selectively grown in ampicillin containing medium.**

Figure 17. Confirmation of cloned insert in fused plasmid. 1-10 minipreps obtained from sub culturing different colonies obtained after transforming the ligation mixture into DH 10 β chemical competent cells. With insert: Two bands of 1635 bp and 4818 bp; Without insert: Single band of linearized plasmid of 4818 bp.

Table 19. Details of primers used for amplification of *CYP2C19* 5' region for cloning and sequencing

Amplified or sequenced region	Primers	Amplified/sequenced length (bp)
<i>CYP2C19</i> 5'-flanking region – for amplification	<i>KpnI</i> -P2(F) 5'- <u>GGTACCC</u> CAG CAC ACA CCA TGT TCT TGG CTA CAG-3'	1714bp
	2C19-pEX12(R) 5'-ACA GAG CAC AAG GAC CAC AA A AGG A-3'	
<i>CYP2C19</i> 5'-flanking region and <i>pGL3</i> -basic vector constructs- for sequencing	2C19-M2(F) 5'-CCT ATG CTT GCT TTG CAT TG-3'	1635 bp
	2C19-PR2(R) 5'-TAT CGA AGA TTA GGA GAC TTT GTC C-3'	
	2C19-PR3(R) 5'-TTC TGA ATA TAT ACC ACA TTC ATC CTG-3'	
	2C19-PR5(R) 5'-TGT GAA TCT AAT AGA GGA TGG GAG G-3'	
	RVprimer3 5'-CTA GCA AAA TAG GCT GTC CC-3'	
RVprimer4 5'-GAC GAT AGT CAT GCC CCG CG-3'		

F: Forward primer; R: Reverse primer. Underlined portion in *Kpn I*-P2 (F) primer indicates the *Kpn I* recognition site incorporated in the primer. RV primers 3 and 4 were used to check for the orientation of the cloned fragment.

Table 20. Genotype details of the constructs used for luciferase reporter assays

S.NO	Construct	-1498T>G	-1442T>C	-1418C>T	-889T>G	-833del>T	-828T>A	-806C>T	-779A>C	-98T>C
1	J _N	TT	TT	CC	TT	Deldel	TT	CC	AA	TT
2	J ₁	<i>TG</i>	TT	CC	TT	Deldel	TT	<i>CT</i>	AC	TT
3	J ₂	TT	TT	CC	<i>TG</i>	<i>delT</i>	<i>TA</i>	CC	AC	<i>CC</i>
4	J ₃	TT	TT	<i>CT</i>	TT	Deldel	TT	CC	AC	<i>CC</i>
5	J ₄	<i>TG</i>	TT	CC	TT	<i>delT</i>	TT	<i>CT</i>	AC	TT
6	J ₅	TT	<i>CT</i>	CC	<i>TG</i>	Deldel	TT	CC	AA	TT
7	J ₆	<i>TG</i>	TT	CC	TT	Deldel	TT	CC	AA	<i>CT</i>
8	J ₇	TT	<i>CT</i>	CC	TT	Deldel	TT	CC	AA	TT
9	J ₈	TT	TT	CC	TT	<i>delT</i>	TT	CC	AA	TT

The genotypes with variant alleles are italicized. The numbering of nucleotides is from start codon of (ATG) *CYP2C19* gene in the 5' flanking region.

Figure 18. *HepG2* cell lines maintained for transfection experiments

5.5.3 Transient transfection and luciferase assays

The day before transfection, the cells were seeded in 12-well plates (Axygen Inc, CA, USA) at approximately 2×10^5 cells/well in an antibiotic free medium. Transient transfections were performed in serum and antibiotic free DMEM medium with Lipofectamine[™] 2000 (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA, USA) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Briefly, the test fused plasmid DNA (1 μ g) and *Renilla* luciferase plasmid *pRL-SV40* (10 ng) were cotransfected into *HepG2* cells (at 80-85% confluence in 12 well plates). The transfected cells were maintained in culture and the growth medium was changed six hours after transfection. The cells were grown for 48 hours in an antibiotic-free medium, after which they were harvested and analyzed for luciferase activity. All the transfection experiments were performed in triplicates and the experiment was repeated four times with four independent plasmid preparations of the same clone to ensure validity. Transfection protocol is given under appendices.

Luciferase reporter gene activity in cell lysates was evaluated with Dual-Luciferase Reporter Assay System[®] (Promega) according to manufacturer's instructions using an Infinite M 200 Multianalyzer (Tecan, Austria). The *Renilla* luciferase activity was used to normalize the results of the firefly luciferase activity of the test plasmids (relative luciferase activity). After subtraction of the activity in untreated cells, the results were expressed as the ratio of firefly luciferase activity to *pRL-SV40* activity. The values are

represented as mean \pm SD of 12 determinations. The relative luciferase activity (RLA) of fused plasmid with normal *CYP2C19* 5' flanking region was considered as one. The fold change in RLA of the other fused plasmids was taken as a ratio of RLA of test fused plasmids to that of fused plasmid with normal *CYP2C19* 5' flanking region. The normalized luciferase data (*firefly/renilla*) was used to perform statistical analysis and expressed relative to *pGL3* normal construct.

5.5.4 Electrophoretic Mobility Shift Assay (EMSA):

The nuclear protein extracts were prepared from *HepG2* cell lines as described earlier.³⁵¹ Briefly, *HepG2* cells were grown in DMEM culture medium (Invitrogen) to confluence. At 70-80 % confluence cells were harvested in ice cold phosphate buffer saline, pelleted by centrifugation and were washed with hypotonic buffer, 10 mM HEPES at pH 7.9, 1.5 mM MgCl₂, 10 mM KCl, 0.2 mM phenyl methyl sulfonyl fluoride and 0.5 mM dithiothreitol. The cells were allowed to swell on ice in hypotonic buffer for 10 min before homogenization in a glass homogenizer. The nuclei were collected after centrifugation for 15 min at 12000 rpm, and were resuspended in 200 μ l of buffer containing 20 mM HEPES pH 7.9, 25 % glycerol, 1.5 mM MgCl₂, 10 mM KCl, 0.2 mM EDTA, 0.2 mM phenyl methyl sulfonyl fluoride, 0.5 mM of dithiothreitol and 1X nuclear extraction protease inhibitor cocktail (Cayman chemical, Michigan, USA). This was followed by KCl was added to a final concentration of 0.4M and nuclear proteins was extracted at 4⁰C for 30 min under continuous gentle mixing. This was centrifuged at 12000 rpm for 30 min and the resulting supernatant was aliquoted and was frozen at -80⁰C. The protein content was quantified by Bradford method using bovine serum albumin as standard.³⁵²

Eight different double stranded (ds) oligonucleotide predicted to be the binding sites for activating transcription factor (ATF-2), CCAAT displacement protein (CDP repressor protein), CCAAT enhancing binding protein beta, cyclic AMP responsive element binding protein and glucocorticoid receptor (GR) were annealed using biotin labelled sense and anti-sense strands (Bioserve Biotechnologies, Hyderabad). The double stranded oligonucleotide fragments namely TFwt, DPwt, CEBPBwt, CREBwt and GRwt have the normal alleles at the positions -806, -98, -1498, -779 and -828, respectively (Table 21). Whereas, the oligonucleotide fragments TFmut, DPmut, CEBPBmut, CREBmut and GRmut have the variant alleles at these

positions (Table 21). Electrophoretic mobility shift assays were performed using LightShift[®] Chemiluminescent EMSA Kit (PIERCE, Rockford, IL) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Briefly, a total volume of 20 µl of binding reactions were carried out with final concentration of 20 fmol of double stranded biotin labelled oligonucleotide, 1X binding buffer, 50 ng/µl of poly(dI-dC), 0.05% NP-40 and 10 µg of nuclear protein from *HepG2*. For competition experiments, 100 or 200 fold excess of the respective wild type and variant unlabeled double-stranded oligonucleotide was added to the reaction mixture prior to the addition of biotin labelled double-stranded oligonucleotides. Binding reaction mixtures with nuclear extract were pre-incubated at room temperature for 10 min followed by the addition of the respective labelled double-stranded oligonucleotide. The complete mixture was incubated again at room temperature for 20 min. Five µl of loading buffer was added and protein- bound as well as unbound DNA were resolved on a 5 % non denaturing polyacrylamide gel. Following this, DNA fragments were blotted onto a Biodyne B nylon membrane (Thermoscientific, Rockford, USA) using semi dry blotting apparatus (C.B.S Scientific, CA, USA) for 30 min at 350 mA. The DNA fragments transferred were cross linked onto the membrane using UV Stratalinker[®] 1800 (Stratagene, La Jolla, CA, USA) for 5 minutes and then blocked and conjugated with horse radish peroxidase. Following the addition of substrate, the chemiluminescence was captured using phosphorimager (Fujifilm, Tokyo). Concentration of labelled DNA was calculated and analyzed using NIH Image J software (version 1.42q; Available at: <http://rsb.info.nih.gov/ij>, accessed on 3rd April 2010). For CEBPB and CREB binding sites Cy-3 labelled oligos were also used for the Gel shift assays and the fluorescence of the complexes and free oligos was measured using phosphorimager (Fujifilm). Super shift assays were performed using specific polyclonal antibodies (Santacruz Botechnology, Inc, Santa Cruz, CA,U.S.A.)

Table 21. Oligonucleotides used for EMSA experiments

Oligonucleotides (forward)	Sequence	Base pairs	Predicted binding site
TFwt	5' CAT CTC TGA TGT AAG AGA TAA 3'	21	Activating transcription factor-2
TFmut	5' TAT CTC TGA TGT AAG AGA TAA 3'	21	Activating transcription factor-2
DPwt	5' GCC ACT TTA TCC ATC AAA G 3'	19	CCAAT displacement protein
DPmut	5' GCC ACT TCA TCC ATC AAA G 3'	19	CCAAT displacement protein
CEBPBwt	5' AAC ATT GTG CAA TTG 3'	15	CCAAT enhancing binding protein beta
CEBPBmut	5' AAC ATT GGG CAA TTG 3'	15	CCAAT enhancing binding protein beta
CREBwt	5' CCA TCG TGG CGC ATT ATC TCT 3'	21	Cyclic AMP responsive element binding protein
CREBmut	5' CCA TCG GGG CGC ATT ATC TCT 3'	21	Cyclic AMP responsive element binding protein
GRwt	5' TTT GTG TCT TCT GTT CTC A 3'	19	Glucocorticoid receptor
GRmut	5' ATT GTG TCT TCT GTT CTC A 3'	19	Glucocorticoid receptor

TFwt: Predicted activating transcription factor binding site with wild type allele at -806 position

TFmut: Predicted activating transcription factor binding site with variant allele at -806 position

DPwt: Predicted CCAAT displacement protein binding site with wild type allele at -98 position

DPmut: Predicted CCAAT displacement protein binding site with variant allele at -98 position

CEBPBwt: predicted CCAAT binding protein beta binding site with wild type allele at -1498 position

CEBPBmut: predicted CCAAT binding protein beta binding site with variant allele at -1498 position

CREBwt: predicted cyclic AMP responsive element binding protein binding site with normal allele at -779 position

CREBmut: predicted cyclic AMP responsive element binding protein binding site with variant allele at -779 position

GRwt: Predicted glucocorticoid receptor binding site with wild type allele at -828 position

GRmut: Predicted glucocorticoid receptor binding site with variant allele at -828 position

5.6 Functional characterization of the variations *in vivo*

5.6.1 Phenotyping procedures

After an overnight fast, the subjects were administered an oral dose of 200 mg proguanil hydrochloride (2 tablets of 100mg each, Laveran Tabs, Unicare Remedies Pvt. Ltd, Baroda, India). Food was avoided for two hours post dose. Four hours after the intake of drug, 5 ml of blood was collected from the antecubital vein into polypropylene tubes containing 100µl of 10% ethylene diamine tetra acetate. The samples were centrifuged at 2500 rpm for five minutes. The plasma was separated and stored at -20°C until the assay.

5.6.2 Determination of plasma concentrations of proguanil and cycloguanil

Proguanil pure powder (Unicare Remedies Pvt. Ltd, Baroda, India), the metabolite cycloguanil (Walter Reed Army Institute of Research, Silver Spring, Maryland, USA), internal standard pyrimethamine (Sigma-Aldrich, St.Louis, USA), acetonitrile (Merck specialities Pvt Ltd, Worli, Mumbai, India), triethylamine (Merck specialities Pvt Ltd, Worli, Mumbai, India), and sodium lauryl sulphate (USB corporation, Cleveland, Ohio, USA) were used for determining drug and metabolite levels in plasma. The plasma levels of proguanil (PG) and cycloguanil (CG) were estimated by reverse phase high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) as described by Setiabudy *et al*, with minor modifications.¹⁷⁴ One ml of plasma was extracted with 5ml of dichloromethane after the addition of 1ml of 1N NaOH and 30µl of pyrimethamine as internal standard (10µg/ml). After orbital shaking at 160 rpm at 37°C for 15 minutes, the organic layer was evaporated and reconstituted in 0.1ml of mobile phase. The mobile phase consisted of acetonitrile/water containing sodium lauryl sulphate 75 mM/triethylamine (50/50/1 v/v/v) with a pH of 2.7, by using glacial acetic acid. The HPLC system consisted of a Shimadzu LC-10AD vp solvent delivery module, Shimadzu SPD-10A vp UV-VIS detector, a 100 µl injection loop and a Hypersil ODS column 4.6 mm, with 5 µm particle size. Flow rate was maintained at 1 ml/min. The analytes were detected at 254 nm, with the absorbance set at 0.005 Afs. Cycloguanil, pyrimethamine and proguanil were eluted at 7.1 min, 9.4 min and 16.8 min, respectively (Figure 19). The mean recovery of compounds was consistent, being more than 68 % for proguanil and 65 % for cycloguanil. The intraday and interday coefficients of variation (n=3) were less than 5.4%, and 8.2% for proguanil and for cycloguanil they were less than 7.8 % and 9.6 %, respectively.

Figure 19. Retention times and peaks of proguanil, cycloguanil, and pyrimethamine obtained during HPLC

5.7 Construction of haplotypes of 8 SNPs across *CYP2C19* and *CYP2C9* in South Indian population and four HapMap populations

5.7.1 Genotyping of *CYP2C19**2 and *CYP2C19**3 alleles by PCR-RFLP method

In addition to the sequencing of 5' flanking region, all the samples were genotyped for *2 (681G>A; splicing defect) and *3(636G>A; W212X) alleles of *CYP2C19* by PCR-RFLP method as described earlier.¹⁰⁹ The primers used for the analysis of mutant alleles *CYP2C19**2 and *3 were given in table 17. The PCR products of *CYP2C19**2 (169 bp) and *3 (329 bp) were digested with *SmaI* and *BamHI*enzymes, respectively and separated on a 6% polyacrylamide gel. PCR products were not digested by enzymes in case of mutant alleles (*CYP2C19**2 and *CYP2C19* *3), due to the absence of restriction sites. In *CYP2C19* *1 (wild type) allele the enzymes *SmaI* and *BamHI* spliced the 169 bp and 329 bp PCR products into 120 bp, 49 bp and 233 bp, 96 bp, respectively (Figure 20). Positive and negative controls were always included in each PCR analysis and digestion of amplified products with enzymes. The PCR conditions for amplification are given in table 22.

Table 22. PCR conditions for amplification of *CYP2C192 and *CYP2C19**3**

	<i>CYP2C19</i> *2, *3	No. of cycles
Initial denaturation	94° C x 5 min	1
	94° C x 30 s	
Amplification	53° C x 10 s	35
	72° C x 20 s	
Terminal Extension	72° C x 5 min	1

Figure 20. Vertical gel electrophoresis of digested PCR products of *CYP2C192 and *3 alleles**

5.7.2 Genotyping of *CYP2C9**2 and *3 alleles by PCR-RFLP method

The standard PCR for detection of alleles *CYP2C9**2 and *CYP2C9**3 was done by the method described by Sullivan-Klose et al with minor modifications.³⁵³ The details of the primers used for amplification are given in table 23. Amplified samples were subjected to restriction digestion (*Ava II* for *2 and *Nsi I*, *KpnI* for *3 alleles) which recognized the SNP of interest. The conditions for amplification of PCR products are given in table 24. The digested products were checked on 8 % PAGE for checking the genotype status (Figure 21).

Genotype details of the SNPs / markers from the HapMap project which includes four major populations namey, U.S. residents with northern and western European ancestry by the Centre d'Etude du Polymorphisme Humain (CEU), Han Chinese in Beijing (CHB), Japanese from Tokyo (JPT) and Yoruba people of Ibadan, Nigeria (YRI) were obtained from HapMap project website (www.hapmap.org, access date: 10th February 2010).³⁵⁴ Pair wise linkage disequilibrium (LD) pattern and haplotype frequency were estimated using HAPLOVIEW software v4.1.³⁵⁵ The haplotype blocks were constructed using solid spine of LD incorporated in haploview. The confidence interval minima for strong LD was set between 0.7 to 0.98 i.e. D' values from 0.7 to 1 indicate strong LD between a pair of markers, where as D' value less than 0.7 indicates moderate LD and D' values 0 to 0.2 indicates no LD.

Table 23. The primers used for amplification of *CYP2C9*2* and *CYP2C9*3*

Allele	Primer sequences	
<i>CYP2C9*2</i>	2C9-F-I1(F)	5'TAC AAA TAC AAT GAA AAT ATC ATG 3'
	2C9-R-I3(R)	5'CTA ACA ACC AGA CTC ATA ATG 3'
<i>CYP2C9*3</i>	2C9-F1-E7(F)	5'AAT AAT AAT ATG CAC GAG GTC CAG AGA TGC 3'
	2C9-F2-E7(F)	5'AAT AAT AAT ATG CAC GAG GTC CAG AGG TAC 3'
	2C9-R-I7(R)	5'GAA GTC CCC AAA TTC ATA GTA TC 3'

Table 24. PCR conditions for amplification of *CYP2C9*2* and *CYP2C9*3*

	<i>CYP2C9*2</i>	<i>CYP2C9*3</i>	No. of cycles
Initial denaturation	94°C x 5 min	94°C x 5 min	1
Amplification	94°C x 20 s	94°C x 20 s	35
	53°C x 10 s	59°C x 10 s	
	72°C x 10 s	72°C x 10 s	
Terminal Extension	72°C x 5 min	72°C x 5 min	1

Figure 21. Vertical gel electrophoresis of digested PCR products of *CYP2C9*2* and **3* alleles

5.7.3 Validation of the PCR-RFLP Protocol

All mutant samples were reanalyzed to ensure accuracy of the PCR-RFLP method. Samples representative of each *CYP2C9* and *CYP2C19* genotype were sequenced to confirm the mutations detected by PCR-RFLP. Sequencing was done by the dideoxy mediated chain termination method of Sanger *et al*³⁵⁶ DNA sequencing with chain-terminating inhibitors using the ABI Prism[®] 7700 sequencer and ABI Prism BigDye[®] Terminator v3.0 cycle sequencing kit at the Macrogen Inc, Korea.

5.8 Establishment of allele and genotype frequencies of *CYP2C1917 in South Indian Tamilian population**

5.8.1 Genotyping of *CYP2C1917 (-806C>T, rs12248560) allele by PCR-RFLP method:**

The *CYP2C19**17 (-806C>T and -3402C>T) allele was identified and analyzed according to the method described earlier with minor modifications.^{16;126} As -806C>T was in linkage disequilibrium with that of -3402C>T, in the present study 206 subjects (females = 108, males = 98) were genotyped for only -806C>T polymorphism. Briefly, a nested polymerase chain reaction approach was used, wherein in the first PCR, 470 bp product was amplified using the gene specific primers. The first PCR was performed in a 50 µl reaction mixture which contained 50 ng genomic DNA template, 10 mmol/l dNTPs, 300 nmol/l of each primers, 3.00 mmol/l MgCl₂, 1X PCR buffer and 1µl (5U) of the Taq DNA polymerase (New England Biolabs, MA, USA) using Eppendorf Mastercycler Gradient (Eppendorf, Hamburg, Germany). The subsequent nested PCR was performed to introduce an allele-specific restriction site for the sequential restriction fragment length polymorphism analysis. In this second PCR step, a 143 bp fragment with an allele specific *NsiI* restriction site was amplified with 1 µl of the first PCR amplified product, 10 mmol/l dNTPs, 300 nmol/l of each primers 3.00 mmol/l MgCl₂, 1X PCR buffer and 0.25 µl (1.25U) of the Taq DNA polymerase (New England Biolabs, MA, USA) using Eppendorf Mastercycler Gradient (Eppendorf, Hamburg, Germany). The details of the primers, annealing temperature and cycle conditions are given in table 25.

The restriction digestion of the above resultant PCR product was performed at 37°C for 8 hours and the reaction mixture (20 µl) contained the following: 8µl of II PCR product,

2µl 10X NEB reaction buffer and 1.5µl (15U) *NsiI* (New England Biolabs, MA, USA). The restriction digested products were separated in a 12 % polyacrylamide gel in a vertical gel electrophoresis unit (MIDIGEL2, Apelex, Massy, France) and were visualized in gel documentation unit (UVP-GelDoc-It™ Imaging System, Cambridge, UK) after staining with ethidium bromide. The restriction site (ATGCA↓T) for *NsiI* enzyme was created in the absence of *CYP2C19*17* allele, and so the PCR products with no -806C>T variant allele were digested by *NsiI* to give two bands of 116 bp and 27 bp and these subjects were represented as CC genotype (Homozygous normal). In the presence of -806C>T variant allele (Homozygous status) no restriction site was created and hence were not digested by *NsiI* enzyme resulting in one band of 143 bp and the subjects were represented as TT genotype (Homozygous variant). Subjects heterozygous for -806C>T (CT) gave three bands of sizes 143 bp, 116 bp and 27 bp (Figure 22). Positive and negative controls were included in each PCR analysis and digestion of samples with the restriction enzymes. The results of polymerase chain reaction-restriction fragment length polymorphism (PCR-RFLP) method were confirmed by sequencing few samples of I PCR product from each representative group i.e. homozygous normal, homozygous variant and heterozygous variant types. The samples were purified using the GeNei™ Quick PCR purification Kit (Bangalore Genei, Bangalore, India) and were sequenced on both strands using the ABI Big Dye Terminator Cycle Sequencing Kit and the ABI Prism 7700 DNA sequencer (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA, USA) at Macrogen DNA sequencing services, Korea. The electropherogram of the representative groups are given in figure 22.

Figure 22. Genotyping of *CYP2C1917 (-806C>T) allele by PCR-RFLP method**

- a) **I PCR products (470bp) visualized on 1% agarose gel:** Lane 1 represents 100 bp DNA ladder and the products were visualized between 400 and 500 bp of 100 bp ladder. Volume of the PCR product loaded was 2 μ l.
- b) **II PCR products (143bp) visualized on 1% agarose gel:** Lane 1 represents 100bp DNA ladder and the products were visualized between 100bp and 200bp of 100bp DNA ladder. Volume of PCR product loaded was 5 μ l.
- c) **PCR products subjected to restriction digestion by *NsiI* enzyme were separated on 12% Polyacrylamide gel:** Lane 1 represents 50 bp DNA ladder, Lane 2 represents undigested II PCR product (143bp), Lane 3 represents homozygous *17*17 genotype (143bp), Lane 4 represents homozygous *I*I genotype or absence of *17 allele (116bp) and Lane 6 represents heterozygous genotype i.e. *I*17 (143bp and 116bp). 27 bp which was supposed to be present along with 116bp product was not visualized due to prolonged run.
- d) **This electropherogram represents homozygous normal genotype of a subject without any variation at -806 site:** AAAGC, The underlined 'C' is a normal allele at -806 position.
- e) **This electropherogram represents heterozygous genotype of a subject with both the alleles at -806 site:** AAAGC, the underlined position consists of both the alleles ('C' and 'T') as visualized in the electropherogram.
- f) **This electropherogram represents homozygous variant genotype of a subject with T allele at -806 site:** AAAGT, 'T' is present in place of 'C' allele.

Table 25. Primers, PCR conditions and restriction digestion used for genotyping of *CYP2C19*17* allele by PCR-RFLP method

Gene	Primers	PCR Conditions	Size of the PCR product (bp)	Enzymes	Size of the digested products (bp)
<i>CYP2C19*17</i> (I PCR)	F: 5'-GCCCTTAGCACCAAATTCTC- 3' R: 5'ATTTAACCCCCTAAAAAACACG-3'	94°C – 1 min	470 bp	-	-
		94°C – 30 sec			
		52°C – 30 sec			
		72°C – 30 sec			
		72°C – 7 min			
<i>CYP2C19*17</i> (II PCR)	F : 5'- AAATTTGTGTCTTCTGTTCTCAATG-3' R: 5'- AGACCCTGGGAGAACAGGAC-3'	95°C – 1 min	143 bp	<i>NsiI</i>	143 (TT) 116, 27 (CC) 143, 116, 27 (CT)
		95°C – 30 sec			
		51°C – 30 sec			
		72°C – 30 sec			
		72°C – 7 min			

F: Forward primer; R: Reverse primer; bp: Base pairs

5.8.2 Haplotype construction and Linkage disequilibrium (LD) analysis:

The genotype data obtained for the three loci (-806, 681 and 636) were used for constructing the Haplotype blocks. Genotype details of the SNPs / markers from the HapMap project including four major populations i.e. Caucasian (CEU), Chinese (CHB), Japanese (JPT) and Africans (YRI) were obtained from HapMap project website (www.hapmap.org).³⁵⁴ A total of 87 samples with the genotype details for the three alleles were used for haplotype analysis.

Pair wise linkage disequilibrium (LD) pattern and haplotype frequency were estimated using HAPLOVIEW software v4.1.³⁵⁵ All the markers/SNPs with minor allele frequencies less than 0.01% were excluded and the minimum haplotype frequency was set at 1%. Haplotype blocks were defined by using four gametes rule incorporated in the Haploview program. Haplotypes were estimated using an accelerated EM algorithm in Haploview. The confidence interval minima for strong LD was set between 0.7 to 0.98 i.e. D' values from 0.7 to 1 indicate strong LD between a pair of markers, where as D' value less than 0.7 indicates moderate LD and D' values 0 to 0.2 indicates no LD.

5.9 Copy number variation analysis of *CYP2C19* by relative C_t (Cycle threshold) method

Relative copy number was approximated using a real-time PCR ($\Delta\Delta C_t$ method of relative quantification) approach based on existing methodologies.³⁵⁷ Cycle threshold (C_t) is defined as the number of cycles required for the fluorescent signal to cross the threshold i.e. exceeds background level. Briefly, the efficiency and specificity of primer pairs for *CYP2C19* (F: 5'-GCC ATT TCC CAC TGG CTG AAA G-3'; R: 5'-ACG AAA CTA GGA GGG AGA TCC-3') and IL-2 (F: 5'-TGCA CAT AAT CTC ATC TTT CTA ACA CTC TT-3'; R: 5'-TTG AAA GCG CAA TAG ATG GAC AT-3') genomic sequences were evaluated using serial 2-fold dilutions of human gDNA ranging from 200 to 0.02 ng. The primers used for *CYP2C19* amplification are specific to prevent the amplification of other homologous genes such as *CYP2C9* located on the same chromosome. The forward primer of *CYP2C19* is located in the exon 2 and the reverse primer in intron 3 with no variations in the area where primers are spanning. The annealing temperature was adjusted for amplification of *CYP2C19* gene alone.

Reaction mixtures were of 25 μ l and contained the following: 12.5 μ l of 2XSYBR Green Master Mix (Sigma-Aldrich, St.Louis, USA), human gDNA, and the appropriate primer pair (400 nM). The PCR thermoprofile consisted of initial activation of the polymerase at 95°C for 15 min followed by 40 PCR cycles of 95°C for 15 s, and 60°C for 1 min (40 cycles) followed by a melting curve to verify the presence of a single amplification product. Assays were performed in triplicate on an Applied Biosystems 7300 Fast Real-Time PCR system. The PCR was performed in a 96-well clear optical reaction plate MicroAmp™ (Applied Biosystems). IL-2 gene was coamplified with *CYP2C19* gene and served as internal standard (reference gene). To calculate the *CYP2C19* copy number relative to the human gDNA sample with no genetic variation, the following equation was used: relative copy number = $2^{2^{-\Delta\Delta C_t}}$, where $-\Delta\Delta C_t = (C_t \text{ of reference gene} - C_t \text{ of target gene}) \text{ of standard} - (C_t \text{ of reference gene} - C_t \text{ of target gene}) \text{ of sample}$. Mean C_t values were taken for each sample derived from duplicate reactions. Efficiency of the assay was calculated using the formula $E = 10^{(-1/\text{slope})} - 1 \times 100$.

Haploid copy number was calculated from the observed C_t values, and then multiplied by 2 to give the diploid copy number as mentioned above.

$$\text{Haploid copy number} = 2^{-\Delta\Delta C_t} = (1+E)^{-\Delta C_t \text{ test gene}} / (1+E)^{-\Delta C_t \text{ reference gene}}$$

E=Efficiency of the PCR reaction

$\Delta C_t \text{ test gene}$ = Difference in the threshold cycle value between the test sample and calibrator sample for the gene (test gene) under investigation.

$\Delta C_t \text{ reference gene}$ = Difference in the threshold cycle value between the test sample and calibrator sample for reference gene.

6.0 Statistical analysis

SPSS software version 13 (Chicago, USA) and GraphPad InStat[®] version 3.06 (San Diego, USA) were used for statistical analysis. Genotypes generated for each allele were analyzed for Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium, linkage disequilibrium, haplotype frequency analysis, and diplotype configurations using Helix Tree software version 6.0.2 (Golden helix[™]) and HAPLOVIEW software v4.1. The chi square test was used to analyze the differences in the allele/genotype frequencies between South Indians and other ethnic populations. Plasma levels of proguanil and cycloguanil were compared between the groups by unpaired 't' test (Welch corrected) and proguanil metabolic ratio (MR) values by the Mann–Whitney U test. Frequency histograms and probit plots were generated for proguanil metabolic ratios. Phenotypic data were expressed as mean \pm SEM, unless otherwise specified. Luciferase assay data were expressed as mean \pm SD, unless otherwise specified. The mean fold change in the RLU activity was compared among the groups using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey-Kramer multiple comparisons post test. Multiple linear regression analysis was performed to analyze the correlation between different variations and luciferase activity. 95 % confidence intervals were calculated using Confidence Interval Analysis software version 1.0. P value $<$ 0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

Results

7.0 Results:

7.1 Genetic variations and Haplotypes of *CYP2C19* 5' flanking region

In this study, novel variations in the 5' regulatory region of *CYP2C19* in South Indian population were identified. *CYP2C19* 5' flanking region including the promoter region (up to 1020 bases upstream of the translational start site) and a part of the enhancer region (from 1708 to -1590 bases upstream of translational start site) were sequenced from 58 healthy volunteers of South Indian origin. All the contig sequences from this population were submitted to Genbank and are available in the public domain (Accession Nos. EU369428 to EU 369485). Total thirteen variations including eight novel ones were identified in the *CYP2C19* 5' flanking sequence among 58 human genomic DNA samples from South India. The identified novel variations in 5' flanking region of *CYP2C19* and their percentage frequencies were as follows: -779A>C (16.4), -828T>A (2.6), -934del>T (3.5), -1051T>C (1.72), -1289T>G (3.4), -1442T>C (12.1), -1498T>G (25.0) and -1558T>G (2.6). The previously reported variations in other populations found in the study population were: -98T>C (28.4), -806C>T (2.6), -833del>T (9.5) 889T>G (10.3), -1418C>T (1.7). Another previously reported variation in other population i.e. -1041A>G (rs7902257) was found to be absent in South Indian population. Among the variations identified in 5' flanking region, three novel variations i.e. -779A>C, -828T>A, -934del>T, and four reported variations i.e. -98T>C, -806C>T, -833del>T, 889T>G were present in the promoter region (bases -1020 to +1) of *CYP2C19* gene. The allele and genotype frequencies for these SNPs are given in table 26. The genotype frequencies of all the detected variants were found to be in Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium. The flanking sequence, location of the SNP, and number of subjects with each genotype in South Indian population are given in table 27. The nucleotide change, location of the variations in the *CYP2C19* 5' flanking region and predicted transcriptional start site, TATA box are given in the figure 23.

7.1.1 Comparison of 5' flanking regions of *CYP2C9* and *CYP2C19*

The homology between *CYP2C19* and *CYP2C9* 5' flanking regions was very high, which requires differentiation between these two flanking regions for better understanding of each promoter. There was about 93 % sequence homology existing within 800 bp from the start codon, 91 % from -850 to -1060 bp, and 88 % homology from -1070 to -1678 bp from the start codon. The important differences between these two 5' flanking regions are given in figure 24.

Table 26. Allele and genotype frequencies of *CYP2C19* 5' flanking region polymorphisms in South Indian population

Location from translational initiation codon	-1558	-1498	-1442	-1418	-1289	-1051	-934	-889	-833	-828	-806	-779	-98
Common allele	T	T	T	C	T	C	Del	T	del	T	C	A	T
Less common allele	G	G	C	T	G	T	T	G	T	A	T	C	C
<u>Allele frequencies</u>													
Common allele	97.4	75.0	87.9	98.3	96.6	98.3	96.6	89.7	90.5	97.4	97.4	83.6	71.6
Less common allele	2.5	25.0	12.1	1.7	3.4	1.7	3.4	10.3	9.5	2.6	2.6	16.4	28.4
<u>Genotype frequencies</u>													
Homozygous common allele (n)	94.8 (55)	51.7 (30)	75.9 (44)	96.6 (56)	93.1 (54)	96.6 (56)	93.1 (54)	82.8 (48)	81.0 (47)	94.8 (55)	94.8 (55)	67.2 (39)	53.5 (31)
Homozygous less common allele (n)	0.0 (0)	1.7 (1)	0.0 (0)	0.0 (0)	0.0 (0)	3.4 (2)	0.0 (0)	3.4 (2)	0.0 (0)	0.0 (0)	5.2 (3)	0.0 (0)	10.3 (6)
Heterozygous (n)	5.2 (3)	46.6 (27)	24.1 (14)	3.4 (2)	6.9 (4)	0.0 (0)	6.9 (4)	13.8 (8)	18.96 (11)	5.2 (3)	0.0 (0)	32.8 (19)	36.2 (21)

Table 27. Single nucleotide polymorphisms in 5' flanking region and non synonymous alleles of *CYP2C19* in South Indian population

Nucleotide change and flanking sequences (5' to 3')	Position		Number of subjects (Total n=58)			SNP ID
	NC_000010.9	from the translational initiation site	Homozygous Wild-type	Heterozygous	Homozygous Mutant	db SNP ID
TATGAGG(T>G)GTGAGAA	96510895	-1558	55	03	0	Novel
AACATTG(T>G)GCAATTG	96510955	-1498	30	27	1	Novel
AA TAACC(T>C)CATTAGG	96511011	-1442	44	14	0	Novel
ACAAATA(C>T)GATGATA	96511035	-1418	56	02	0	rs3814637
ATTGTGG(T>G)GGTTTTG	96511164	-1289	54	04	0	Novel
CTTCAGT(T>C)ACACTGA	96511402	-1051	56	02	0	Novel
TGAAGCC(del>T)GTTTTATG	96511519	-934	54	04	0	Novel
TAACTAA(T>G)GTTTGGA	96511564	-889	48	08	2	rs11568732
TTTTTTT(del>T)CAAATTT	96511620	-833	47	11	0	rs17880036
TTTCAAA(T>A)TTGTGTC	96511625	-828	55	03	0	Novel
CTCAAAG(C>T)ATCTCTG	96511647	-806	55	03	0	rs12248560
ATGCGCC(A>C)CGATGGG	96511674	-779	39	19	0	Novel
GCCACTT(T>C)ATCCATC	96512355	-98	31	21	6	rs4986894
ACCCCTG(G>A)ATCCAGG	96530400	636	55	03	0	rs4986893
TTATTCCC(G>A)GGAACCC	96531606	681	20	32	6	rs4244285

NCBI ACCESSION Nos: EU 369428 to EU 369485

Forward Primer: 5'-CAGCAGACACCATGTTCTTGGCTACAG-3' (P2)

Reverse primer : 5'-ACAGAGCACCAAGGACCACAAAAGGA-3' (pEX12)

Primers for DNA Sequencing: 5'-TATGTTTGGTTATTGAAGAT-3' (M1)
5'-TGTGAATCTAATAGAGGATGGGAGG-3' (PR5)
5'-TTCTGAATATATACCACATTCATCCTG-3' (PR3)
5'-TATCGAAGATTAGGAGACTTTGTCC-3' (PR2)
5'-CCTATGCTTGCCTTGCATTG 3' (M2)

Long PCR product size: 1708 bases

P2, F-primer

CAGCAGACACCATGTTCTTGGCTACAGTACTGAATCTTCAAGGCTCAGCCTCCTCATTCTGAGATGGGTCAATTTTATTGTA
-1558
AGCAAAGGCAATTGAGAGATTCCAAAGGGATATGAGG [T/G]GTGAGAATTCTCTCTAAATGGGGTTAGAATCCCTGTTAAAA
-1498 -1442
ATGACCAGTGAAACATTG [T/G]GCAATTGTGTCTTAACATACTTACTTTTTCTTAATAAGAGAAGCTGAAAATAACC [T/C]
-1418
CATTAGGAAATTTAGAACAAATA [C/T]GATGATATCTTTAAAGAAAATGGCTTTGTGTAAGTATTGTCGTTAGTGATCTAGT
-1289
AATGTGTATCTTTCTGGTTGTATTTAGACCTTCAACTCAAATGTCAGCTCCCGTTAAGGTCTATACATTGTGG [T/G]GGTTT
PR5, R-primer M2, F-primer
TGTGCTGTGGGTCCATTTAGTGATTTCCCTACTCCCATCCTCTATTGATTCCACTGTTGTTCTGCCATAATTTCTTAT
GCTTGCCTTGCATTGTTACATTTTTTTTTGAAAATCAGAAAGCAAATCAATATAAAGCAGCCATGTCTGGAGGAGACCAGGA
-1051 -1041
GGTCAAGAAGCCTTAGTTTCTCAAGCCCTTAGACCAAATCTCTGAGATCAGCTCTTCTTCAGT [T/C]ACACTGAGC [A/
G]TTTCCCCTCTGCAGTGATGGAGAAGGAGAAGCTTATTTTTTCTCATGAGCATCTCTGGGGCTGTTTTCTTAGATAAAT
-934 PR3, R-primer -889
AAGTGGTCTATTTAATGTGAAGCC [T/del]GTTTTATGAA CAGGATGAATGIGGTATATATTCAGAA TAACATAA [T/G]GT
-833 -828
TTGGAAGTTGTTTTGTTTTGCTAAAACAAAGTTTTAGCAAACGATTTTTTTTT [T/del]CAAA [T/A]TTGTGCTTCTGTT
-806 -779
CTCAAAG [C/T]ATCTCTGATGTAAGAGATAATGCGCC [A/C]CGATGGGCATCAGAAGACCTCAGCTCAAATCCCAGTTCTG
CCAGCTATGAGCTGTGTGGCACCAACAGGTGCTCTGTTCTCCAGGGTCTCCCTTTTCCATTTGAAATATAAAAAATAACAA
M1, F-primer
TTCTGCCTTCACGTGTTTTTTAGGGGTTAAATGGTAAAGGTGTTTATATCTGCTAAGGTAATTTACTTGTATA TATGTTT
GTTATTGAAGATATATGAGTTATGTTAGCTATTTTCATGTTTAGGCTGCTGTATTTTTAGTAGGCTATATTAATAGAGGATTT
PR2, R-primer
CATTATAAAGGACAAAGTCTCCTAATCTTCGATA TAGGATTGACATACTTTTTAAATATAACAAGGCATAGAATATGGCCATTT
CCGTTAAATCATAAATCCCAACTGGTTATTAATCTAAGAATTCAGAATTTAAGTAATGTTTTTGCATCAGATTGTTTACT
TCAGTGCTCTCAATTATGACGGTGCATTGGAACCACTTGGGTTAACATTTTTTGTTTTTATTACCAATACCTAGGCTTCAAC
CTAGTACAATGAAACCAGAATGTACAGAGTGGGCACTGGGACGAAGGAGAACAAGACCAAAGGACATTTTATTTTTATCTCTA
Y-Box -98
TCAGTGGGTCAAAGTCTTTCAGAAGGAGCATATAGTGGGCCTAGGTGATTGCCACTT [T/C]ATCCATCAAAGAGGCACAC
Transcription start region Start Codon
ACACTTAATTAGCATGGAGTGTATAAAAAGCTTGGAGTGCAAGCTCACGGT TGTCTTAACAAGAGGAGAAGGCTTCAATGGA
pEX12, R-primer
TCCTTTTGTGGTCTTGTGCTCTGTCTCTCATGTTTGTCTTCTCTTCAATCTGGAGACAGAGCTCTGGGAGAGGAAAATCC
CTCCTGGCCCTACTCCTCTCCAGTGATTGAAAATATCCTACAGATAGATATTAAGGATGTCAGCAAATCCTTA

Figure 23. Genetic variations identified in *CYP2C19* 5' region and their location in the contig sequence

Gene	CYP2C19	CYP2C9	
	-340	-313 -335	-308
	GCATCAGATT <u>G</u> TTTACTTCAGTGCTCTC	GCATCAGATT <u>A</u> TTTACTTCAGTGCTCTC	
	-357	-330 -352	-325
	TTTAAGTAATT <u>G</u> TTTTGCATCAGATTG	TTTAAGTAATT <u>G</u> TTTTGCATCAGATTG	
	-369	-342 -364	-337
	AGAATTCAGAATTTT <u>A</u> AGTAATTGTTTT	AGAATTCAGAATTTT <u>G</u> AGTAATTGTTTT	
	-816	-793 -811	-788
	TGTTCTCAA <u>A</u> GCAT <u>T</u> CTCTG <u>A</u> TGTAA	TGTTCTCAA <u>G</u> GCAG <u>C</u> TCTG <u>G</u> TGTAA	
	-791	-769 -786	-764
	AGATAAT <u>G</u> <u>C</u> <u>C</u> CCACGATGGGCAT	AGATAAT <u>A</u> <u>C</u> <u>A</u> CCACGATGGGCAT	
	-652	-632 -628	-623
	CTGCCTTC <u>A</u> <u>C</u> <u>G</u> <u>T</u> GTT TTTTT-AGGG	CTGCCTTC <u>A</u> <u>G</u> <u>G</u> <u>A</u> TT TTTTTAGGG	
	-630	-610 -625	-605
	GGGGGTT <u>A</u> AATGGTAAAGGTG	GGGGGTT <u>T</u> AATGGTAAAGGTG	
	-575	-551 -570	-546
	TTGGTTATT <u>G</u> AAGATATATGAGTTA	TTGGTTATT <u>T</u> AAGATATATGAGTTA	
	-504	-482 -499	-477
	TTAAATAG <u>G</u> -----AGGATTCATTA	TTAAATAT <u>T</u> <u>T</u> <u>T</u> <u>G</u> <u>A</u> AAGGATTCAT	
	-359	-375 -346	-370
	ATTT <u>T</u> TTTGT <u>T</u> TTTATTACCAATAC	ATTT <u>G</u> TTTTTT--ATTACCAATAC	
	-103	-123 -98	-118
	CA <u>C</u> TTTATCCATCAAAGAGG <u>C</u> ACAC	CA <u>A</u> TTTATCCATCAAAGAGG—CAC	
	-78	-65 -73	-60
	ACACT <u>T</u> AATTAGCA	ACAC <u>C</u> <u>G</u> AATTAGCA	
	-1673	-1647 -1668	-1642
	GACA <u>C</u> CATGTTCTTGGCTA <u>C</u> AGTACTG	GACAGCATGTTCTTGGCTA <u>A</u> GATACTG	
	-1557	-1531 -1552	-1526
	GT <u>G</u> AGAATTCTCT <u>C</u> TAAAT <u>G</u> <u>G</u> <u>G</u> GTTAG	GT <u>A</u> ACAATTCTCT <u>G</u> TAAAT <u>T</u> G—TTAG	
	-1393	-1369 -1388	-1364
	TTT <u>G</u> <u>T</u> AAGTATT <u>G</u> <u>T</u> <u>C</u> GTTAGTGA	TTT <u>G</u> <u>C</u> <u>A</u> CAAGTATT <u>G</u> <u>A</u> CATTAATGA	
	-1246	-1220 -1241	-1215
	ATC <u>C</u> TCTATT <u>A</u> <u>G</u> AT <u>T</u> CACAACCTG <u>T</u> TGT	ATC <u>T</u> TTTATT <u>G</u> <u>C</u> AT <u>C</u> CACAACCTG <u>G</u> TGT	

Figure 24. Differences in nucleotide sequences of 5' flanking regions of *CYP2C19* and *CYP2C9* genes. Nucleotides are numbered from the translational start codon ATG (+1). Differences in nucleotides are highlighted bold and underlined

7.1.2 Linkage disequilibrium (LD) analysis and haplotypes of *CYP2C19* 5' regulatory region in South Indian population

LD analysis showed strong linkage between several variations identified in the gene. Perfect linkage ($D'=1$) was observed among 681G>A (*2), -1558T>G, -1289T>G, -828T>A, -806C>T, and among -1051T>C, -889T>G, and -806C>T. Pair wise linkage analysis showed perfect linkage between the pairs 636G>A and -1418C>T, 636G>A and -833del>T, 636G>A and -779A>C, -1558T>G and -1442T>C, and between -1498 T>G and -1051T>C, -1442T>C and -833del>T, -1418C>T and -806C>T, and between -1558T>G and -1442T>C, -828T>A and -806C>T. Several variations were found to be in strong LD such as, 681G>A and -1558T>G ($D'=0.9$), -828T>A and -98C>T ($D'=0.9$), -1442T>C and -833del>T ($D'=0.9$), -1498T>G and -828 T>A ($D'=0.86$), -1498T>C and -1289T>G ($D'=0.9$), and -1418C>T and -779A>C ($D'=0.9$). LD analysis of variations of 5' flanking region of *CYP2C19* are given in figure 25.

Haplotype analysis was performed and out of the 43 haplotypes predicted by Estimation Maximization (EM) method, 13 were of frequency more than 1% (Table 28). The most frequent haplotype was haplotype 1 (36.6%) followed by 2 to 13 (ranging from 10.6 to 1.3%). The frequencies of other haplotypes were less than 1%. Haplotypes 1 to 13 share the common alleles at positions 636(G), -1558(T), -1289(T), -1051(T), -1041(G), -934(del), -833(del), -828(T), and -806(C). They differed from each other at the following positions viz. 681(G/A), -1498(T/G), -1442(T/C), -889(T/G), -779(A/C), and -98(T/C). More frequent haplotypes namely 1-3 differ from each other at positions 681, and -98. Among the samples examined, 33 different combinations of these haplotypes were found. The most frequent haplotype pairs were 1/5 (7%), and 3/4 (7%), followed by 1/11, 2/4, 5/13, 1/7, and 3/8 at a frequency of 5%, and 6/6, 1/12, 6/8, 1/3, 1/4 1/1, 1/2, 3/13, and 1/9 at a frequency of 3.5%. The 43 haplotype structures are given under appendices.

Figure 25. Linkage disequilibrium (LD) analysis of *CYP2C19* genetic variations. Pair wise LD depicted using the D' (from 0 to 1) by a 10-graded coloured scale. Dark red colour indicates the highest LD.

Table 28. Frequent haplotypes of *CYP2C19* 5' flanking region from South Indian population

Location of SNPs from the translational start site (ATG)																	
Haplotype	636	681	-1558	-1498	-1442	-1418	-1289	-1051	-1041	-934	-889	-833	-828	-806	-779	-98	Frequency (n=58)
1	G	G	T	T	T	C	T	C	G	Del	T	Del	T	C	A	T	36.56
2	.	A	.	T	T	T	.	.	.	A	C	10.62
3	.	A	.	T	T	T	.	.	.	A	T	4.32
4	.	G	.	G	T	T	.	.	.	A	T	3.99
5	.	A	.	G	T	T	.	.	.	A	T	3.94
6	.	G	.	T	T	G	.	.	.	A	T	3.64
7	.	A	.	T	C	T	.	.	.	A	T	2.60
8	.	G	.	T	C	T	.	.	.	A	T	1.95
9	.	G	.	G	T	T	.	.	.	C	T	1.95
10	.	A	.	T	T	T	.	.	.	C	C	1.91
11	.	A	.	G	T	T	.	.	.	A	C	1.66
12	.	G	.	T	C	G	.	.	.	A	T	1.52
13	.	G	.	T	T	T	.	.	.	A	C	1.36

7.2 Functional characterization of genetic variations of *CYP2C19* 5' flanking region in silico

Prediction of transcription factor binding site (TBS)/cis-acting elements in CYP2C19 5' flanking region:

The predicted TBS with corresponding TF and the location of existing polymorphism in the TBS are given in table 29. Polymorphisms were found in the putative binding sites for enhancer factors like CCAAT enhancer binding protein beta (-1505 to -1491, and -1443 to -1429), glucocorticoid receptor (-828 to -810), mammalian LTR TATA box (-939 to -923), activating transcription factor 2 (-806 to -786), GATA 1 binding factor (-103 to -91), cAMP responsive element binding protein (-793 to -773), and for repressor elements like CDP repressor protein (-105 to -87), and CDE elements (-837 to -825) which were predicted to be present in the *CYP2C19* 5' flanking region

7.2.1 Three-dimensional modeling of transcription factors

BLAST_P results were used to retrieve the structural templates from Protein Data Bank (PDB) for modeling of TFs. The templates of ATF-2, CDP, CEBPB, GATA-1 and GR were transactivation domain of CRE-BP1/ATF-2 (PDB ID: 1BHI), CUT domain of human homeobox protein Cux-2 Cut-like 2 (PDB ID: 1X21), transcription factor ATF4-C/EBP beta Bzip Hetero dimer (PDB ID: 1CI6), N-terminal zinc finger of murine GATA-1 (PDB ID: 1GNF) and glucocorticoid receptor DNA-binding domain (PDB ID: 1GDC). The alignment result of TFs with their templates showed more than 90% sequence similarity. The calculated minimized energy values of all modeled TFs namely, ATF-2, CDP, C/EBPB, GATA-1 and GR were -689.446, -4522.263, -3265.176, -1612.896 and -2942.936 Kcal/mol, respectively. The modeled amino acid residues for all TFs were found to be in the favored (91-95 %) and allowed region (5.4-8.3 %) of Ramachandran Plot. No amino acid residue was found in the outlier region (For details see table 30).

Table 29. Predicted transcription factor binding sites for *CYP2C19* promoter

SNP position from the translational initiation site	Transcription factor binding site location in <i>CYP2C19</i> 5' flanking region	Strand	Name of transcription factor	Sequence
-1558	-1559 to -1535	--	Heat shock factor 2 (HSF2)	ccccatttagagAGAAttctcacac
-1498	-1506 to -1490	+	Hepatic leukemia factor (HLF)	aaacattgtGCAAttgt
-1498	-1505 to -1491	+	CCAAT/enhancer binding protein beta (CEBPB)	aacattgtGCAAttg
-1442	-1464 to -1440	--	Nuclear hormone receptor TR2, DR5 binding sites (TR2)	tgaggttattccaGTTCTcttatt
-1442	-1449 to -1433	--	Homeodomain transcription factor Gsh-2	ttccTAATgagggtatt
-1442	-1443 to -1429	+	CCAAT/enhancer binding protein beta (CEBPB)	ctcattagGAAAtt
-1289	-1294 to -1280	+	Runt-related transcription factor 2 / CBFA1 (core-binding factor, runt domain, alpha subunit 1) (AML3)	tgtgGTGGTtttgtg
-934	-939 to -923	--	Mammalian C-type LTR TATA box	gttcaTAAAacaggctt
-833	-837 to -825	--	Cell cycle gene homology region (CDE/CHR tandem elements regulate cell cycle dependent repression) (CHR)	aaatTTGAaaaaa
-828	-828 to -810	+	Glucocorticoid receptor, C2C2 zinc finger protein binds glucocorticoid dependent to GREs, IR3 sites (GRE)	tttgtgtcttctGTTCTca
-806	-806 to -786	+	Activating transcription factor 2 (ATF2)	catctcTGATgtaagagataa
-779	-793 to -773	--	Tax/CREB complex	ccatcgTGGCgcattatctct
-98	-105 to -87	+	Transcriptional repressor CDP	gccactttATCCatcaaag
-98	-103 to -91	--	GATA-binding factor 1	gatgGATAaagtg

- The capital, italicized bases include core sequence of TBS.

Table 30. Ramachandran Plot results of transcription factors predicted from Rampage web server

S. No	Transcription factors	Favoured region (%)	Allowed region (%)	Outlier region
1.	ATF-2	91.7	8.3	Nil
2.	CDP	94.3	5.7	Nil
3.	CEBPB	100	-	Nil
4.	GATA-1	93.3	6.7	Nil
5.	GRE	94.6	5.4	Nil

ATF-2: Activating transcription factor 2, CDP: Transcriptional repressor CDP, C/EBPB: CCAAT/enhancer binding protein beta, GATA-1: GATA-binding factor-1, GRE: Glucocorticoid response element.

7.2.2 Molecular docking studies of transcription binding site with transcription factors

The docking results for best-scored conformations of TF-TBS complex are given in table 31. The docking simulation of ATF-2 into its TBS with normal allele at -806 position resulted in the formation of two hydrogen bonds. OG1 atom of THR 10 and NZ atom of LYS 36 act as hydrogen bond donors and interacted with the backbone phosphate group of cytosine 6 and N7 atom of adenine 33 with bond distance of 1.91 and 2.44 Å, respectively (Figure 26). Inspection of the docked complex of ATF-2 into TBS with variant allele at -806 position revealed that LYS 5 and THR 10 were involved in hydrogen bond formation to adenine of 14th and 16th bases with bond distance of 1.40 and 2.94 Å, respectively (Figure 26). The SC scores for the interaction of ATF-2 into its TBS with normal and variant allele were 8088 and 8442, respectively. A stronger interaction was observed in case of CDP repressor protein, C/EBPB, GATA-1 and GR into TBS with normal alleles as compared to the TBS with variant alleles (Figure 27, 28). This was evident with the high shape complementarity scores (SC scores). Inspection of other TF-TBS docking results (Table 32) revealed that GLU and ARG residues had a major role in hydrogen bond formation with nucleotide bases of TBS, in addition to LYS, HIS, ALA, SER, GLY, ASN THR, CYS and ASP residues. The TF-TBS interactions of different responsive elements containing normal and variant alleles with its factors are given in the figures 27 and 28.

Table 31. Molecular interactions of transcription factors into its binding sites

TFs	Allele in TBS	Hydrogen bond donor	Hydrogen bond acceptor	Bond distance (Å)	SC Score
ATF-2	Normal (-806 C)	TF::THR 10:OG1	TBS::C 6:A:O1P	1.91	8088
		TF::LYS 36:NZ	TBS::A 33:B:N7	2.44	
	Variant (-806T)	TF::LYS 5:NZ	TBS::A 14:A:O1P	1.40	8442
		TBS::A 16:A:O3	TF::THR 10:OG1	2.94	
CDP	Normal (-98T)	TBS::T 26:B:O3	TF::GLY 635:O	2.40	10268
		TBS::G 28:B:O3	TF::GLN 630:O	2.43	
		TF::GLN 612:NE2	TBS::G 37:B:O3	1.74	
	Variant (-98C)	TF::SER 585:OG	TBS::A 9:A:N7	2.08	9888
		TBS::A17:A:O3	TF::GLU 632:OE2	1.36	
		TBS::A 25:B:O3	TF::GLN 630:O	2.62	
CEBPB	Normal(-1498T)	TF::ARG 512:NH1	TBS::G 27:B:N7	2.44	7750
		TF::GLN 583:NH2	TBS::G 28:B:N7	2.33	
		TBS::A 11:A:N6	TF::GLU 304:OE2	2.00	
	Variant (-1498G)	TF::ARG 296:NE	TBS::A 18:B:O1P	2.58	7362
		TF::THR 307:OG1	TBS::G 21:B:O2P	2.96	
		TBS::C 22:B:N4	TF::GLU 304:O	2.74	
GATA-1	Normal (-98T)	TF::LYS 315:NZ	TBS::A 23:B:O2P	1.55	7836
		TF::ARG 323:NH2	TBS::T 5:A:O1P	2.15	
		TF::LYS 311:NZ	TBS::G 21:B:O6	2.49	
	Variant (-98C)	TBS::C 24:B:N4	TF::GLU 322:OE2	2.62	7798
		TF::HIS 232:ND1	TBS::G 11:A:O1P	2.68	
		TBS::G 11:A:O3	TF::ARG 217:O	2.85	
GR	Normal(-828T)	TF::ARG 216:NH2	TBS::T 17:B:O2	2.19	8626
		TBS::T 7:A:O3	TF::LYS 233:O	1.25	
		TBS::G 8:A:O3	TF::HIS 232:ND1	2.78	
	Variant (-828A)	TBS::A 9:A:O3	TF::ARG 217:O	1.47	8278
		TF::ARG 217:NH1	TBS:A 10:A:O1P	2.61	
		TF::ARG 216:NH2	TBS:A 10:B:O4	2.44	
GR	Normal(-828T)	TBS::T 21:B:O3	TF::ASN 226:OD1	2.91	8626
		TF::LYS 23:NZ	TBS::T 21:B:O2	2.20	
		TF::ASN 226:ND2	TBS::C 22:B:O2P	2.72	
	Variant (-828A)	TF::ARG 470:NH1	TBS::C 8:A:O2P	2.80	8626
		TF::SER 440:OG	TBS::C 8:A:O3	2.45	
		TF::ARG 477:NH1	TBS::T 9:A:O2P	2.46	
GR	Normal(-828T)	TF::GLN 452:NE2	TBS::C 11:A:O1P	2.64	8626
		TF::ASN 454:N	TBS::C 11:A:O2P	2.57	
		TF::ARG 460:NH1	TBS::C 16:A:O4	2.36	
	Variant (-828A)	TF::ARG 460:NH2	TBS::C 16:A:O3	2.05	8278
		TBS::A 24:B:O3	TF::ALA 458:O	1.68	
		TBS::C 26:B:O3	TF::ASP 462:OD1	2.77	
Variant (-828A)	TF::CYS 463:SG	TBS::A 27:B:O2P	2.44	8278	
	TF::ARG 460:NE	TBS::T 7:A:O2	2.91		
	TF::CYS 463:N	TBS::C 8:A:O1P	2.43		
Variant (-828A)	TF::CYS 457:SG	TBS::C 8:A:O2P	2.31	8278	
	TF:: ARG 470:NE	TBS::A 27:B:O2P	2.44		
	TF::ARG 460:NH2	TBS::A 34:B:O4	2.66		

TF-transcription factor, TBS-transcription factor binding site or response elements, A-A chain of TBS, B-B chain of TBS, ATF2-activating transcription factor 2, CDP- CDP repressor proteins, CEBPB- CCAAT enhancer binding protein beta, GATA-1- GATA binding factor 1, GR- glucocorticoid receptor. Each amino acid is represented by the standard symbol. SC score- Shape Complementarity score. Standard amino acid and atom symbols were used to represent the amino acid involved in interaction between TF and TBS. In response elements (TBS) nitrogenous bases: adenine (A), guanine (G), thymine (T) and cytosine (C) are represented with their respective symbols in bold and their location. Atoms are represented by their respective symbols (like 'O' for oxygen, 'H' for hydrogen, 'N' for nitrogen) followed by distance abbreviation in the order of increasing distance i.e. "A" for alpha, "B" for beta, "G" for gamma, "D" for delta, "E" for epsilon, "Z" for zeta, and "H" for eta, followed by a digit designating the branch direction (absence of digit after distance abbreviation indicates that the side chain is unbranched).

Figure 26: NUCPLOT diagram of (a) TBS (with normal allele at -806 position) and ATF-2 complex (b) TBS (with variant allele at -806 position, *17) and ATF-2 complex, (c) Representative three-dimensional docking model of TBS (with variant allele at -806 position) and ATF-2 complex. DNA helix is represented with their base pair numbers. ATF-2 protein is represented in secondary structural models, (d) Representative three-dimensional docking model of TBS (with normal allele at -806 position) and ATF-2 complex. The base pairs (represented by one-letter codes) and its DNA backbones: sugars and phosphates are coloured according to their type. The base numbers are written inside the sugars. Interacting transcription factor protein residues are represented by their atom name, residue name and number with hydrogen bonds drawn as blue dotted lines on either side of the strands. Atom names are coloured blue for nitrogen and red for oxygen.

Figure 27. The three dimensional docking models of TF and TBS with normal alleles in TBS (a) transcriptional repressor CDP (b) CCAAT/enhanced binding protein beta (CEBPB) (c) GATA binding factor 1 (GATA-1) and (d) glucocorticoid receptor into their respective DNA binding sequence (TBS)

DNA helices are represented with their base pair numbers. Interacting transcription factor proteins are represented in secondary structural models. This figure was generated by PyMOL viewer

Figure 28. The three dimensional docking models of TF and TBS with variant alleles in TBS (a) transcriptional repressor CDP (b) CCAAT/enhanced binding protein beta (CEBPB) (c) GATA binding factor 1 (GATA-1) and (d) glucocorticoid receptor into their respective DNA binding sequence (TBS)

Note: The NUCPLOT derived 2D views of other interactions are given in the appendices.

7.3 Functional characterization of genetic variations in CYP2C19 5' flanking region *in vitro*

To investigate the effect of common polymorphisms, the effect of nine different constructs of *CYP2C19* 5' flanking region and *pGL-3* basic vector was measured. The fold change in the relative luciferase activities (RLA) of these constructs with respect to the normal construct are given in figure 29. Fold change in RLA compared to that of *pGL-3* basic vector and the mean values of RLA are given in the table 32. All the fused plasmids with *CYP2C19* 5' flanking region showed significant increase in luciferase activity compared to promoterless construct (*pGL-3* basic vector) revealing the presence of a functional promoter region. Construct with allelic variants -98T>C, -779A>C, -1051T>C, -1418C>T (J_3) and with allelic variants -98T>C, -1498T>G (J_6) showed a significant increase in luciferase activity compared to all other reporter constructs. The common variant in both of these constructs was -98T>C which was present in the putative CCAAT displacement protein (CDP) repressor binding site. Docking analysis of CDP repressor protein with its responsive element revealed relatively weaker interaction in the presence of 'C' allele against 'T' allele at -98 position. The increased activity in these constructs may be attributed to this variant allele which may have disrupted the functional repressor region and increased the transcription of the gene.

Reporter construct with allelic variants -889T>G, -833del>T, -828T>A, -779A>C, -98T>C (J_2) showed a significant increase in luciferase activity compared to normal promoter construct, but significantly lower activity than the constructs J_3 and J_6 . Further, it showed increased luciferase activity when compared to normal construct (J_N) and constructs with -1442T>C, -889T>G (J_5) and -833del>T (J_8) variants. Even though -98T>C was a common variant seen in J_2 , J_3 and J_6 constructs, only J_3 and J_6 constructs showed a steep rise in luciferase activity. In the construct with additional variants (J_2) such as -889T>G, -833del>T, -828T>A, -779A>C, decreased luciferase activity was observed as compared to J_3 and J_6 . This suggests that presence of -98T>C variant in CDP repressor region in a construct increased the transcription of luciferase gene, which manifests as increase in luciferase activity. Electrophoretic mobility shift assay (EMSA) had shown the specific binding of nuclear protein to the region surrounding -98 position. The aggravated binding was observed with DPLwt probe than with DPLmut, suggesting the decreased

interaction of nuclear protein with the probe containing variant allele (Figure 30). The intensity or concentrations of the labelled probes analyzed using Image J software are given in the table 33.

Construct with -1498T>G, -806C>T and -779A>C (J₁) showed a significant decrease in the luciferase activity compared to that of all other constructs including one with normal promoter region (J_N). Whereas a construct with similar SNP pattern and an additional variation -833 del>T (J₄) showed a significant increase in luciferase activity compared to a normal construct. However, a construct with a variant -833del>T (J₈) alone did not increase or decrease the activity compared to a normal construct. Variation -806C>T failed to increase the promoter activity in the construct (J₁) with other variations -1498T>G and -779A>C. However, it has increased the luciferase activity in the construct (J₄) with -1498T>G, -833del>T and -779A>C. EMSA experiments with predicted binding sites i.e. TFLwt and TFLmut have shown the increased interaction of nuclear protein to the TFLmut probe with -806T allele (Figure 30).

The decreased luciferase reporter activity in J₂ construct compared to other two constructs with -98T>C (J₃ and J₆) variant can be attributed to other variants especially to that of the -828T>A which was present in the putative glucocorticoid receptor region. Docking analysis of glucocorticoid receptor with its responsive element showed decreased interaction in the presence of 'A' allele against 'T' allele at -828 position, which may have decreased the transcription of the gene. However, no significant difference in the luciferase activity was seen between the constructs J₂ and J₄ (-1498T>G, -833del>T, -806C>T and -779A>C). EMSA experiments with predicted binding sites for GR i.e. GRLwt and GRLmut have shown interaction with the nuclear proteins. No significant difference in the interaction between normal type (-828T) and mutant probe (-828A) was observed. But, the interaction with the mutant probe had been efficiently competed by both normal and mutant unlabelled probes. The binding with normal probe was not significantly competed by unlabelled probes suggesting the weaker interaction of the nuclear protein with mutant probe compared to normal probe (Figure 30).

EMSA experiments with the predicted binding sites for CEBPB and CREB binding sites surrounding the variations -1498T>G and -779 A>C had revealed some interesting findings. No significant differences in the interaction of wild type and normal oligos was

observed with that of CEBPB binding site, but higher affinity was observed with that of the normal probe compared to that of variant probe in competition experiments (Figure 30). A specific interaction was observed at this site which was confirmed in the competition experiments, but there is no clear difference in the interaction was observed between the normal and variant probes. Super shift assays with CEBPB specific antibodies (Santacruz Botechnology, Inc, Santa Cruz, CA, U.S.A.) had resulted in the dissociation of the complexes formed, which is not seen with that of non specific antibodies. Whereas the EMSA with CREB sites had shown that nuclear proteins had increased affinity towards the variant probe with “C” allele at -779 position. Competition experiments revealed a specific interaction of nuclear proteins and the super shift was also observed in super shift assays with CREB specific antibody (Figures 31, 32 and 33). This could also explain the increased luciferase activity seen the constructs J₃ and J₆.

Results of the multiple regression analysis of genotypes of different polymorphic loci with luciferase activity are shown in table 34. The variants -1498T>G, -828del>T were significantly associated with decreased luciferase activity, whereas variants -1442T>C, -779A>C and -98T>C were significantly associated with increased luciferase activity. -889del>T variant was also observed to be associated with decreased luciferase activity, but it was not statistically significant ($p=0.05$). The correlation coefficient of the model was 0.941 ($p<0.0001$) with a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 88.6%. Thus, the study indirectly suggests an important role of CREB, CEBPB, CDP repressor protein, and glucocorticoid receptors in transcription of *CYP2C19* gene. The variations in these binding sites may influence transcription, which may be due to altered interaction of *trans*-acting factors with *cis*-acting elements.

Figure 29. pGL-3 basic reporter vector constructs fused with 9 different patterns of CYP2C19 promoter region and promoter activities of various reporter gene constructs in HepG2 cell lines. Data were obtained from a minimum of four experiments conducted in triplicates each time. Data were expressed as mean \pm SD (* $p < 0.05$, compared with J_N).

Table 32. Relative luciferase activity (RLA) of different constructs of *CYP2C19* promoter regions.

S.No	Constructs	n	RLA (mean±SD)	Median
1	<i>pGL3</i> basic (J ₀)	15	0.14±0.08	0.09
2	J _N	12	1.0±0.21	0.99
3	J ₁	12	0.66±0.34	0.60
4	J ₂	12	1.24±0.33	1.18
5	J ₃	12	5.56±1.19	6.07
6	J ₄	12	1.26±0.28	1.20
7	J ₅	12	0.99±0.23	0.88
8	J ₆	12	2.22±0.35	2.21
9	J ₇	12	1.41±0.32	1.46
10	J ₈	12	0.90±0.42	0.89

p values are significant ($p < 0.05$) between the promoterless construct (J₀) and all other constructs and between J₃, J₆ and all other constructs.

p values are also significant ($p < 0.05$) between J_N and J₃ and between J_N and J₆. Significant differences were also seen between ($p < 0.05$) J₁ and J₇.

Table 33: Intensity/concentration of the labelled probe-nuclear extract complexes measured by Image J software.

S. No	Label	Area	Mean	Min	Max
1	DPLwt	2346	55.97	30	113
2	DPLmut	2346	69.69	41	118
3	DPLwt+DPwt	2346	82.54	54	122
4	DPLmut+DPwt	2346	90.21	59	134
5	DPLwt+DPmut	2346	77.48	47	116
6	DPLmut+DPmut	2346	81.38	49	132
7	TFLwt	3410	139.93	83	196
8	TFLmut	3410	85.87	13	161
9	TFLwt+TFwt	3410	126.51	63	172
10	TFLwt+TFmut	3410	122.36	69	170
11	TFLmut+TFwt	3410	58.36	1	123
12	TTFLmut+TFmut	3410	62.89	0	132
13	TFLwt free oligo	3410	105.56	52	164
14	TFLmut free oligo	3410	175.10	126	210

Lower mean values indicates higher concentration and higher mean values indicates lower concentration of labelled DNA and nuclear protein complexes

Table 34: Influence of individual locus variations (unstandardized and standardized regression coefficients by independent variables) on luciferase activity of the constructs

S. No	Independent variable (Variant alleles at different loci)	Unstandardized regression coefficient	Standardized regression coefficient	Standard error	p value
1	-1498 T>G	-0.087	-0.492	0.007	0.0001
2	-1442T>C	0.002	0.113	0.001	0.045
3	-889T>G	-0.023	-0.116	0.012	0.055
4	-833del>T	0.005	0.028	0.008	0.560
5	-828T>A	-0.021	-0.795	0.002	0.0001
6	-779A>C	0.086	0.509	0.007	0.0001
7	-98T>C	0.016	0.937	0.001	0.0001
8	Constant	0.312	-	0.181	0.089

Model Predictors: (constant), -98T>C, -833 del>T, -1498T>G, -889T>G, -779A>C, -1442T>C, -828T>A

R=0.941; R² =0.886; Adjusted R²=0.878; p<0.0001

Figure 30: DNA-EMSA analysis for a) -98T>C b) -806C>T and c) -828G>A polymorphisms using *HepG2* nuclear extracts, labelled and unlabelled probes with normal and variant alleles. Binding of *HepG2* nuclear extracts to located CCAAT displacement repressor protein binding site (CDP repressor); b) Binding of *HepG2* nuclear extracts to located activating transcription factor -2 binding site (ATF-2); c) Binding of *HepG2* nuclear extracts to located glucocorticoid receptor (GR)

Figure 31. EMSA with CREB oligos. A) Competition assay of CREB consensus probe with normal allele with normal oligo; B) Competition assay of CREB consensus probe with normal allele with variant oligo; C) Competition assay of CREB consensus probe with normal allele with non specific oligo.

NE: *HepG2* nuclear extract; CREB WtL: Cy-3 labelled CREB consensus from *CYP2C19* promoter with wild or normal allele, CREB Wt: unlabeled CREB consensus from *CYP2C19* promoter with wild allele, CREB Mut: unlabeled CREB consensus from *CYP2C19* promoter with variant allele, Non specific: non specific competitor. 20 f mol of labelled oligos was used in all reactions along with assay with 1ug of poly dI.dC and 75mM of salt. For competition assays varying concentrations of unlabeled oligos were used in the range of 1 fold (+1), 2 fold excess (+2), 4 fold excess (+4), 8 fold excess (+8), 25 fold

Figure 32. EMSA with CREB oligos.

A) EMSA with CREB consensus from *CYP2C19* promoter with normal allele; B) EMSA with CREB consensus from *CYP2C19* promoter with variant allele

HepG2 nuclear extract was used, and for competition experiments 50 fold of unlabeled probes. Anti-CREB: antibody specific to CREB, antiCEBPB: antibody specific to CEBPB, CREBWtL: Cy-3 labelled CREB consensus from *CYP2C19* promoter with wild allele, CREB MutL: Cy-3 labelled CREB consensus from *CYP2C19* promoter with variant allele, CREB wt: unlabeled CREB consensus from *CYP2C19* promoter with wild allele, CREB Mut: unlabeled CREB consensus from *CYP2C19* promoter with variant allele, Non specific: non specific competitor, NE: HepG2 nuclear extract. Antibodies were used in the concentration of 1 ug (+1), 2ug (+2) and supershift was observed with CREB specific antibodies, but not with CEBPB specific antibodies. The CREB protein has more affinity towards CREB Mut(variant oligo) compared to CREB Wt (normal oligo). 20 fmol of labeled and 1000 fmol of unlabeled probes were used in the assay with 1ug of poly dLdC and 75mM of salt.

Figure 33. EMSA with CEBPB consensus from *CYP2C19* promoter with normal allele

HepG2 nuclear extract was used, and for competition experiments 50 fold of unlabeled probes, antiCEBPB: antibody specific to CEBPB, Anti-CREB: antibody specific to CREB, CEBPBWtL: Cy-3 labelled CEBPB consensus from *CYP2C19* promoter with wild allele, CEBPB MutL: Cy-3 labelled CEBPB consensus from *CYP2C19* promoter with variant allele CEBPB wt: unlabeled CEBPB consensus from *CYP2C19* promoter with wild allele, CREB Mut: unlabeled CREB consensus from *CYP2C19* promoter with variant allele, Non specific: non specific competitor, NE: HepG2 nuclear extract. Antibodies are used in the concentration of 1 ug (+1), 2ug (+2) and no complex formation was observed with CEBPB specific antibodies, but not with CREB specific antibodies. The CEBPB protein has more affinity towards CEBPB Mut(variant oligo) compared to that of CEBPB Wt (normal oligo). 20 fmol of labeled and 1000 fmol of unlabeled probes were used in the assay with 1ug of poly dLdC and 100 mM of salt.

7.4 Functional characterization of genetic variations of *CYP2C19* 5' flanking region *in vivo*

The subjects were classified into three groups according to the observed *CYP2C19* genotype: *CYP2C19**1/*1 (homozygous normal subjects, n=16), *CYP2C19* *1/*2 or *1/*3 (heterozygous subjects, n=27) and *CYP2C19**2/*2 or *2/*3 (homozygous variant subjects, n=7). The mean age of the study subjects was 27.8 ± 6.7 (mean \pm SD). There were no significant differences among the three genotypes with respect to age (27.5 ± 1.6 , 28.4 ± 1.4 , and 26.5 ± 2.1 years, respectively) or body mass index (22.34 ± 0.7 , 23.2 ± 0.5 , and 21.7 ± 0.9 kg/m², respectively).

7.4.1 *CYP2C19* genetic polymorphisms and proguanil metabolic ratio

The proguanil, cycloguanil levels and proguanil metabolic ratios (MR) in subjects with different genotypes are given in table 35. Subjects with two defective alleles or one defective allele (*2/*2, *1/*2 or *1/*3) had lower cycloguanil levels, while *1/*1 subjects had the highest levels. Proguanil levels were highest in subjects with two defective alleles, with intermediate levels in *1/*2 subjects and lowest in *1/*1 subjects. Accordingly, proguanil metabolic ratios (MR) were highest in subjects with two defective alleles or with one defective allele (*2/*2, *1/*2 or *1/*3), while *1/*1 subjects had lowest. There was a significant difference in proguanil metabolic ratios between the subjects with *1/*1 and *1/*2 or *1/*3 (p=0.03) and between the subjects *1/*1 and *2/*2 or *2/*3 (p=0.04). These results indicate that *CYP2C19* genotype influences the proguanil metabolic ratio. The study group did not pass the test for normality (KS=0.2620) indicating a non-gaussian distribution. The skewed frequency histogram, curvilinear probit plot and asymmetrical NTV plots indicate that proguanil metabolic ratios were not normally distributed indicate that proguanil metabolic ratios were not normally distributed (Figure 34). A significant correlation was observed between the *CYP2C19* genotypes and proguanil MR (r=0.3; p=0.02), but the correlation coefficient is not close to 1 and hence the genotype based prediction of phenotype is questionable. The antimode of proguanil metabolic ratio in South Indians was 12.4. Individuals with proguanil MR less than 12.4 were characterized as EMs; whereas those with MR more than 12.4 were characterized as PMs. In the study population, 43 subjects were EMs with a mean proguanil MR of 4.8 ± 2.9 (mean \pm SD) and seven were PMs with a mean MR of 28.5 ± 19.1 . Thus, the prevalence of PMs in the South

Indian population was 14 %. Among 16 subjects with *CYP2C19**1/*1, 15 were EMs with a MR of 3.8 ± 3.16 (mean \pm SD), and one was PM with a MR of 18.3. Of 27 subjects with *CYP2C19**1/*2 or *3, 22 were EMs and 5 were PMs with MRs of 5.3 ± 2.9 and 29.4 ± 22.5 , respectively. In the third group of *CYP2C19**2/*2, *2/*3 individuals (n=7), six were EMs and one was a PM with MR values of 5.2 ± 2.2 and 34.7, respectively.

As per the evidence from *in silico* and *in vitro* studies, the subjects were grouped according to -98T>C genotypes. Phenotype values were analyzed among normal genotype subjects (*1/*1) with -98TT normal genotype and -98CT or CC variant genotypes in promoter region, subjects with one defective allele in exonic region (*1/*2 or *1/*3) with -98 TT normal genotype and -98CT or CC variant genotype in promoter region. Subjects with *2/*2 or *2/*3 genotype were not included in the analysis as presence of both defective alleles results in no CYP2C19 activity and the effects of promoter region variations cannot be observed. There was a significant difference in the proguanil MRs between -98TT and -98CT or CC genotypes, irrespective of their exonic region genotypes (Table 36). Lower proguanil MR was also seen in two subjects with *CYP2C19**17 allele (-806C>T) in the promoter region (mean MR value = 1.98). One subject had no defective allele in exonic region (*1/*17) and -98 TT normal genotype in promoter region whereas another subject had one defective allele in exonic region (*2/*17) and -98 CC variant genotype in promoter region.

Subjects with *1/*1 and -98TT genotypes (Group1) had a higher metabolic ratio (median=3.9) compared to subjects with *1/*1 and -98TC or CC genotype (Group 2; median=0.6; p=0.02). Similarly subjects with -98TT and any of the genotypes *1/*2, *1/*3, *2/*2 and *2/*3 (Group 3) had a higher metabolic ratio (median=8.3) than the subjects with -98CT or CC and genotypes *1/*2, *1/*3, *2/*2 and *2/*3 (Group 4) (median=5.3). The values did not differ significantly (between group 3 and group 4), but there was a trend towards significance (p=0.06). Significant differences in the metabolic ratios was observed between group1 (median=3.9) and group 3 (median=8.3; p=0.02). There was no significant difference in the metabolic ratios of group 1 (median=3.9) and group 4 (median=5.3). Details of grouping of subjects with different haplotypes are given in table 36. Similar differences in the metabolic ratios were observed between the groups after the exclusion of outlier's metabolic ratio data. Significant difference (p=0.04) in the

metabolic ratios (mean \pm SEM) was observed between group 1 (n=13; 4.3 ± 0.86 ; median = 3.92) and group 3 (n=9; 6.4 ± 0.3 ; median = 6.20). Similarly significant differences (p=0.02) were observed between group 1 and group 2, and between group 2 and group 3 (p=0.01). There is also a trend towards significance was observed between group 3 and group 4 (n=13; 4.58 ± 0.8 ; median = 4.24; p=0.08). There were no significant differences among the four groups with respect to body mass index (22.3 ± 3.2 , 22.7 ± 0.2 , 22.8 ± 2.4 and 23.4 ± 3.3 kg/m², respectively; values are mean \pm SD). The overall significance for haplotype trend regression was p=0.01 ($R^2 = 0.8$). Decreased *CYP2C19* activity, which was evident as higher proguanil metabolic ratios was associated with the 681G>A (haplotype 6, p=0.0001) and 681G>A, -98T>C, -779 A>C and -889T>G (haplotype 12, p=0.003).

When subjects were grouped according to -1498T>C genotypes and analyzed, the mean metabolic ratios were higher in subjects with variant allele compared to the subjects carrying normal allele irrespective of their exonic region genotype (Table 37). This suggests the decreased activity of the enzyme might have been due to the decreased transcription of a gene. But, statistical significance was not present. Subjects were also grouped according to the -779A>C genotypes (Table 38). The metabolic ratios were lower in subjects carrying the variant allele at -779 position irrespective of their exonic region genotype suggesting the increased enzyme activity. This might be due to the increased amount of the enzyme due to increased transcription of a gene. But statistical significance was not achieved. A study with larger sample size may give a statistical significance.

Figure 34. Probit and frequency distribution histogram plot and NTV plots for proguanil MRs in South Indians. In NTV plot different genotypes of CYP2C19 are represented as follows: *CYP2C19**1/*1 (dark circles), *CYP2C19**1/*2 or *3 (dark square), *CYP2C19**2/*2 or *3 (dark triangle).

Table 35. Plasma concentration of cycloguanil (CG), proguanil (PG) and proguanil metabolic ratio (PG/CG) in individuals with different *CYP2C19* genotypes (n=50)

	<i>CYP2C19</i> *1/*1 (n = 16) (G1)	<i>CYP2C19</i> *1/*2 and *1/*3 (n = 27) (G2)	<i>CYP2C19</i> *2/*2 and *2/*3 (n = 7) (G3)	p value		
				G1 vs. G2	G1 vs. G3	G2 vs. G3
CG (ng/ml)	85.7 ± 18.0 (45.2 – 124.1)	47.2 ± 7.1 (32.5 – 61.8)	50.2 ± 12.3 (21.1 - 79.3)	0.03	<i>0.06</i>	0.41
PG (ng/ml)	206.7 ± 18.6 (167.4 – 246.5)	216.9 ± 14.2 (187.6 – 246.4)	269.1 ± 13.0 (238.4 – 300.0)	0.33	0.01	0.03
MR (PG/CG)	4.7 ± 1.2 (2.3 – 7.2)	9.6 ± 2.6 (4.1 – 15.1)	9.9 ± 3.7 (1.2 – 18.6)	0.03	0.04	0.33

Values are mean±SEM (95% confidence interval); p<0.05 was considered statistically significant. Significant figures are given in bold letters.

Table 36. Metabolic ratios (proguanil/cycloguanil) of proguanil in individuals with different *CYP2C19* genotypes with respect to -98T>C variation in promoter region

Group	<i>CYP2C19</i> genotype	No. of subjects	MR (proguanil/cycloguanil)
G1	*1/*1, -98 (TT)	14	5.3 ± 1.3(3.96)
G2	*1/*1, -98 (CT or CC)	2	0.6 ± 0.3(0.59)
G3	*1/*2 or *1/*3, -98 (TT)	12	12.1 ± 4.7(8.28)
G4	*1/*2 or *1/*3, -98 (CT or CC)	15	7.8 ± 2.7(4.60)

Values are mean ± SEM (median). *1/*1- homozygous normal type, *1/*2 or *1/*3- heterozygous, MR: Metabolic ratio.

G1 (group1) - haplotypes 1, 3, 5, 8, 9 and 10; G2 (group 2) -haplotype 11; G3 (group 3) - haplotypes 4, 6 and 7; G4 (group 4) -haplotypes 2 and 12

p values are **G1vs G2 (0.02)**, **G1 vs G3 (0.02)**, G1 vs G4 (0.3), **G2 vs G3 (0.01)**, **G2 vs G4 (0.007)** and G3 vs G4 (0.06). p <0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

Table 37. Metabolic ratios (proguanil/cycloguanil) of proguanil in individuals with different *CYP2C19* genotypes with respect to -1498T>G variation in promoter region

Group	<i>CYP2C19</i> genotype	No. of subjects	MR (proguanil/cycloguanil)
G1	*1/*1, -1498 (TT)	9	4.6±1.8(2.9)
G2	*1/*1, -1498 (TG or GG)	7	5.0±1.5(4.0)
G3	*1/*2 or *1/*3, -1498 (TT)	11	5.6±1.0(4.6)
G4	*1/*2 or *1/*3, -1498 (TG or GG)	13	6.3±1.1(6.1)

Values are mean ± SEM (median). *1/*1- homozygous normal type, *1/*2 or *1/*3- heterozygous, MR: Metabolic ratio.

G1 (group1) - haplotypes: 1, 6, 8, 12, and 13; G2 (group 2) - haplotype: 4 and 9; G3 (group 3) - haplotypes: 2, 3, 7, and 10; G4 (group 4) - haplotypes: 5 and 11

3 outlier values from group 3 were excluded in the analysis.

p values are G1 vs G2 (0.68), G1 vs G3 (0.13), G1 vs G4 (0.19), G2 vs G3 (0.17), G2 vs G4 (0.58) and G3 vs G4 (0.49).

Table 38. Metabolic ratios (proguanil/cycloguanil) of proguanil in individuals with different *CYP2C19* genotypes with respect to -779A>C variation in promoter region

Group	<i>CYP2C19</i> genotype	No. of Subjects	MR (proguanil/cycloguanil)
G1	*1/*1, -779 (AA)	11	5.3±1.5(3.9)
G2	*1/*1, -779 (AC or CC)	4	1.8±1.1(0.9)
G3	*1/*2 or *1/*3, -779 (AA)	18	6.6±0.9(6.2)
G4	*1/*2 or *1/*3, -779 (AC or CC)	7	5.5±1.8(3.3)

Values are mean ± SEM (median). *1/*1- homozygous normal type, *1/*2 or *1/*3- heterozygous, MR: Metabolic ratio.

G1 (group1) - haplotypes: 1, 4, 6, 8, 12 and 13; G2 (group 2) - haplotype: 9; G3 (group 3) - haplotypes: 2, 3, 5, 7 and 11; G4 (group 4) - haplotypes: 10

One outlier from each group was excluded in the analysis

No statistical significance was observed between any groups.

7.4.2 Effect of *CYP2C9* and *CYP2C19* genotypes on proguanil oxidation

The metabolic ratios were lowest in subjects with similar *CYP2C19* genotype and having variant alleles of *CYP2C9*. There was no statistical significant difference observed (Table 39).

Table 39. Metabolic ratios (proguanil/cycloguanil) of proguanil in individuals with different *CYP2C19* and *CYP2C9* genotypes

Group	<i>CYP2C19</i> genotype	<i>CYP2C9</i> Genotype	No. of subjects	MR (proguanil/cycloguanil)
G1	*1*1	*1*1	13	5.3 ±1.1 (4.94)
G2	*1*1	*1*3/*1*2	5	4.5 ±1.5 (5.13)
G3	*1*1	*2*2/*3*3/*2*3	0	---
G4	*1*2 or *1*3	*1*1	18	8.9 ±2.3 (6.0)
G5	*1*2 or *1*3	*1*2/*1*3	5	4.0 ±1.0 (4.0)
G6	*2*2	*1*1	2	7.4 ±3.5 (7.4)
G7	*2*2	*1*3/*1*2	3	3.2 ±0.3 (3.2)

Values are mean ± SEM (median). *1*1- homozygous normal type, *1*2 or *1*3- heterozygous, *2*2/*3*3- homozygous variant, MR: Metabolic ratio.

p values are not significant between any groups (p>0.05).

7.5 Linkage disequilibrium and haplotypes of 8 SNPs across *CYP2C19* and *CYP2C9* in South Indian and four HapMap populations

The minor allele frequencies of *CYP2C9* c.430C>T and c.1075A>C were found to be 4.1 % and 9.8 %, respectively. The LD analysis has revealed distinct LD pattern among South Indians compared to other HapMap populations. Strong LD was observed between *CYP2C9**3 and -889T>G in all the populations except for YRI population. The haplotypes were constructed using the eight markers (Table 40). The minor allele frequencies and observed heterozygosity at each of these loci are given in table 41. The details of location of SNPs and LD pattern in all the population studies are given in figure 35. Eleven different haplotypes were constructed (Table 42) and have shown varying frequency in South Indian population and other HapMap populations.

Table 40. The 8 reported polymorphisms (SNPs) studied across *CYP2C19* and *CYP2C9* in South Indian and four HapMap populations

Gene	dbSNP	Alleles	Minor allele	Position on chromosome 10 NC_000010.9	Position in the gene	Order of SNP in haplotypes
<i>CYP2C19</i>	rs3814637	C/T	T	96511035	-1418	1
<i>CYP2C19</i>	rs7902257	A/G	A	96511412	-1041	2
<i>CYP2C19</i>	rs11568732	T/G	G	96511564	-889	3
<i>CYP2C19</i>	rs12248560	C/T	T	96511647	-806	4
<i>CYP2C19</i>	rs4986894	T/C	C	96512355	-98	5
<i>CYP2C19</i>	rs4244285	G/A	A	96531606	681	6
<i>CYP2C9</i>	rs1799853	C/T	T	96692037	430	7
<i>CYP2C9</i>	rs1057910	A/C	C	96731043	1075	8

Table 41. Allele and genotype frequencies of 8 variants spanning the genes *CYP2C19* and *CYP2C9* in South Indians and the selected HapMap populations

SNP ID	Major/Minor Allele	SI MAF	SI OFH	CEU MAF	CEU OFH	CHB MAF	CHB OFH	JPT MAF	JPT OFH	YRI MAF	YRI OFH
rs3814637	C/T	0.02	0.03	0	0	0.12	0.19	0.13	0.22	0.13*	0.23
rs7902257	A/G	0	0	0.01	0.01	0	0	0	0	0.06	0.13
rs11568732	T/G	0.10	0.14	0.05	0.1	0.09	0.13	0.13	0.22	0.08	0.16
rs12248560	C/T	0.03	0.05	0.21*	0.37	0.02	0.04	0	0	0.28*	0.41
rs4986894	T/C	0.28	0.36	0.16	0.24	0.26	0.51	0.28	0.43	0.14*	0.22
rs4244285	G/A	0.38	0.55	0.15	0.23	0.26	0.51	0.28	0.43	0.15*	0.23
rs1799853	C/T	0.04	0.08	0.09	0.18	0	0	0	0	0	0
rs1057910	A/C	0.10	0.20	0.05	0.1	0.04	0.09	0.03	0.07	0	0

SI: South Indian; MAF: minor allele frequency; OFH: observed frequency of heterozygosity; YRI: Yoruba in Ibadan, Nigeria; JPT: Japanese in Tokyo, Japan; CHB: Han Chinese in Beijing, China; CEU: CEPH (Utah residents with ancestry from northern and western Europe)

*The MAF values are significant ($p < 0.05$) when compared to that of South Indian population.

Figure 35. The location of 8 SNPs studied across *CYP2C19* and *CYP2C9* and LD pattern in South Indian and HapMap populations.

Table 42. The haplotype structures of 8 common variations spanning over CYP2C19 and CYP2C9 genes in South Indian and four HapMap populations and their frequencies estimated by haploview.

Haplotype	NCBI rsID (Marker location in haplotype)								Frequency (%)				
	rs3814637 (1)	rs7902257 (2)	rs11568732 (3)	rs12248560 (4)	rs4986894 (5)	rs4244285 (6)	rs1799853 (7)	rs1057910 (8)	South Indians (n=50)	CEU (n=90)	CHB (n=45)	JPT (n=45)	YRI (n=90)
HS1	C	G	T	C	T	G	C	A	50.8	59.0	64.0	58.0	38.1
HS2	C	G	T	C	C	A	C	A	31.2	15.0*	23.0	28.4	14.4*
HS3	C	G	G	C	T	G	C	C	8.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
HS4	C	G	T	C	T	A	T	A	4.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
HS5	C	G	T	T	T	G	C	A	3.0	21.0*	0.0	0.0	28.3*
HS6	C	G	G	C	T	A	C	A	2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
HS7	C	G	G	C	T	G	C	A	0.0	5.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
HS8	T	G	G	C	T	G	C	A	0.0	0.0	5.0	13.6	7.8
HS9	C	A	T	C	T	G	C	A	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.3
HS10	T	G	G	C	T	G	C	C	0.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	0.0
HS11	T	G	T	C	T	G	C	A	0.0	0.0	2.0	0.0	5.0

* p<0.05 compared to South Indian population.

The minor allele frequencies of -1418C>T,-806C>T and -98T>C in South Indians are significantly lower and the frequency of 681G>A was significantly higher from that of African population (YRI). Caucasians (CEU) were also found to have significantly lower frequencies of 681G>A compared to that of South Indians. Linkage disequilibrium analysis showed wide ranges of LD between different populations. A strong LD was observed between *CYP2C9**3 allele and -889T>G among South Indians and other HapMap populations except for YRI population. A strong LD was also observed between -1418C>T and *CYP2C9**2 and *3 and between *CYP2C19**2 and *CYP2C9**2 alleles in South Indians. A strong LD was also observed between -98T>C and *CYP2C19**2 alleles in all the populations. The haplotype frequencies were varied among different populations. The wild type haplotype (HS1) frequency was lower in YRI population compared to South Indians and other HapMap populations. The haplotype (HS2) carrying -98C and 681A (*CYP2C19**2) was found to be at higher frequencies in south Indians compared to CEU and YRI populations. Haplotypes HS3, 4, and 6 were found to be unique to South Indian populations and absent in HapMap populations. Haplotype 3 has a variant alleles in *CYP2C9* i.e. *CYP2C9**3 and -889T>G in *CYP2C19* gene, haplotype 4 has *2 variant alleles in both *CYP2C19* and *CYP2C9* genes, whereas haplotype 6 had a variant alleles at -889 and 681 positions in *CYP2C19* gene. Haplotypes HS7, 8, 9, 10 and 11 were found to be absent in South Indians and present in other HapMap populations. Thus the haplotype with both *CYP2C9**2 and *CYP2C19**2 allele do occur in South Indians. The haplotypes HS3 and HS10 contain the variants in promoter region of *CYP2C19* and also *CYP2C9* *2 or *3 alleles suggesting the interaction of these two genes especially in relation to common substrates.

7.6 Allele and genotype frequencies of *CYP2C1917 in South Indian (Tamilian) population**

*CYP2C19**17 allele frequency in the study population (n=206) was found to be 19.2% (95% CI: 15.4 - 23.0). Out of the 206 subjects, 7 subjects were homozygous (TT) for *17 allele (3.4%, 95% CI: 1.4-6.9), 134 subjects were of homozygous normal genotype (CC) (65.1%, 95% CI: 58.5 - 71.6) and 65 subjects were heterozygous having both the alleles (CT) (31.6%, 95% CI: 25.2 - 37.9). The genotype frequencies of *CYP2C19**17 (-806C>T) in the study population were found to be in Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium. There was no significant difference found between the observed and expected genotype

frequencies ($p > 0.05$). In a subset of the study population wherein 87 subjects were genotyped for all the three alleles of *CYP2C19* i.e. *CYP2C19**2, *3 and *17, the *CYP2C19**17 allele was found at a frequency of 17.8% (95% CI: 12.1 - 23.5) followed by the *2 allele frequency of 40.2% (95% CI: 32.9 - 49.3). The *CYP2C19**3 allele was not found in this subset of 87 subjects. The allele and genotype frequencies of *CYP2C19* in this subset population (n=87) are given in table 43. In relation to the earlier study wherein only *2 and *3 alleles were genotyped, differences in the genotype frequencies of *CYP2C19* was observed. The *CYP2C19**1/*1 observed genotype frequency of 16.1% was different from that of earlier study conducted in our laboratory (29.5%), followed by *CYP2C19**1/*2 frequency of 31.0% compared to the earlier reported frequency of 58.0%. Similarly, *CYP2C19**2/*2 genotype frequency observed was 18.4% compared to earlier reported frequency of 8.0%.¹⁹

In the present study, it has also been observed complete absence of *CYP2C19**2 allele in subjects homozygous for *17 allele. Similarly the absence of *17 allele in subjects homozygous for *2 allele has also been observed. In previous study subjects carrying *17 allele have been considered as carriers of wild allele (*1) and was estimated as 59.8%.¹⁹ In the present study the same was recalculated as 41.2% in view of our findings with *CYP2C19**17 allele in South Indian Tamilian population. The allele frequency of *17 i.e. 17.8% combined with *1 allele frequency in the present study gives a total frequency of 59.8% which was similar to that previously reported frequency of *1 allele in the study population. Hence, with the detection of novel alleles the wild type allele frequency has to be re calculated depending upon the frequency of newer allele in the population studies. Accordingly, the previously reported frequency of *CYP2C19**1/*1 (29.5%), *1/*2 (58.0%) was recalculated as 16.1% and 31.0%, respectively (table 43).

7.6.1 Comparison of *CYP2C19* allele frequencies in South Indian Tamilian and HapMap populations

*CYP2C19**17 (rs12248560) allele frequency in the study population was also compared to that of four major population data from the HapMap project. This allele frequency was found to be significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) in Chinese population (CHB, 2.2%) and slightly higher in African population (YRI, 20.6%) compared to that of the South Indian Tamilian population (17.8%). The *CYP2C19**17 allele frequency was comparable between

Caucasian (CEU, 18.3%) and South Indian TAMILIAN population. This allele was found to be absent in Japanese samples (JPT) of HapMap project. The details of *CYP2C19*17*, **3* and **2* allele frequencies in the study population and HapMap populations are given in table 44.

7.6.2 Phenotype prediction based on CYP2C19 genotype

Based on the genotype frequencies observed, CYP2C19 phenotypes were predicted and are shown in table 45. Subjects homozygous for *CYP2C19*17* allele were designated as homozygous UMs, whereas subjects carrying one allele of **17* were designated as heterozygous UMs. Subjects carrying *CYP2C19*2* and **17* alleles were designated as EMs. In view of *CYP2C19*17* allele the EMs frequency was recalculated to 28.7% and intermediate metabolizers (IMs) or heterozygous extensive metabolizers (hetEMs) frequency was found to be 31.0%. The homozygous ultra rapid metabolizer's (UMs) frequency was observed to be 1.2%, with heterozygous ultra rapid metabolizer frequency of 20.7%.

7.6.3 Haplotype structures of CYP2C19*17, *2 and *3 alleles in Tamilians and other global populations

The linkage disequilibrium (LD) analysis of the alleles included in the study revealed a perfect linkage ($D'=1$) between *CYP2C19*17* and **2* alleles in South Indian, Chinese, Caucasian and African populations. Even though these two alleles were in LD, the correlation coefficient (r^2) between these alleles varied from 0.17 in South Indians to 0.04 in CEU and YRI populations. In Chinese population correlation coefficient (r^2) between **17* and **2* alleles was calculated as 0.06. The haplotype analysis was then performed with 87 samples which had genotype data for *CYP2C19*17*, *CYP2C19*3* and *CYP2C19*2* alleles. The haplotype analysis showed HS1 (42.7%) as the most frequent haplotype in South Indian TAMILIAN population, followed by HS2 (39.8%) and HS3 (17.5%). Haplotype HS2 was found to be the predominant haplotype in the four HapMap populations (table 46).

Table 43. *CYP2C1917, *2 and *3 genotype and allele frequencies in South Indian Tamilian population**

<i>CYP2C19</i> genotypes	Number of subjects		Frequency	95% Confidence interval
	Males	Females		
*1*1	10	4	16.09	9.09 - 25.05
*1*17	12	6	20.69	12.8 - 30.7
*1*2	13	14	31.03	21.6 - 41.9
*17*17	0	1	1.15	0.03 - 6.24
*2*17	5	6	12.64	6.49 - 21.5
*2*2	9	7	18.39	10.9 - 28.1

Alleles	No. of alleles	Frequency	95% Confidence interval
<i>CYP2C19</i> *1	73	41.95	34.6 - 49.3
<i>CYP2C19</i> *2	70	40.22	32.9 - 47.5
<i>CYP2C19</i> *3	0	0	0
<i>CYP2C19</i> *17	31	17.82	12.1 - 23.5

Total number of subjects genotyped for *CYP2C19**2, *3, and *17 alleles were 87(males = 49, Females = 38); Total no. of alleles = 174;

There was no gender difference observed in the distribution of *17 and *2 alleles.

Table 44. Allele and genotype frequencies of *CYP2C192, *3 and *17 in South Indian Tamilian and HapMap selected populations**

SNP ID	Major/ minor Allele	SIT MAF	OFH	CEU MAF	OFH	CHB MAF	OFH	JPT MAF	OFH	YRI MAF	OFH
rs12248560 (<i>CYP2C19</i> *17)	C/T	17.8	30.9	18.3	36.7	2.2*	4.4	0.0	0.0	20.6	41.1
rs4986893 (<i>CYP2C19</i> *3)	G/A	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.3	6.7	2.4	4.8	0.0	0.0
rs4244285 (<i>CYP2C19</i> *2)	G/A	40.2	47.1	14.9*	23.0	25.6*	51.1	28.4*	43.2	14.8*	22.7

SIT: South Indian tamilian; MAF: minor allele frequency; OFH: observed frequency of heterozygosity; YRI: Yoruba in Ibadan, Nigeria; JPT: Japanese in Tokyo, Japan; CHB: Han Chinese in Beijing, China; CEU: CEPH (Utah residents with ancestry from northern and western Europe). *The MAF values are significant ($p < 0.05$) when compared to that of south Indian Tamilian population.

Table 45. Predicted CYP2C19 phenotypes based on CYP2C19*2, CYP2C19*3 and CYP2C19*17 genotyping in South Indian Tamilian population.

Predicted phenotype	CYP2C19 genotype	Number of individuals (%)	95 % Confidence interval
EM	CYP2C19*1/*1 & CYP2C19*2/*17	25 (28.8)	19.5 – 39.4
hetEM/IM	CYP2C19*1/*2	27 (31.0)	21.6 – 41.9
PM	CYP2C19*2/*2	16 (18.4)	10.9 – 28.1
hetUM	CYP2C19*1/*17	18 (20.7)	12.8 – 30.7
UM	CYP2C19*17/*17	1 (1.2)	0.03 – 6.24

Table 46. Haplotype structures and frequencies of CYP2C19*17 (rs12248560), CYP2C19*3 (rs4986893) and CYP2C19*2 (rs4244285) in South Indian Tamilian population and HapMap populations.

Haplotype	Location from ATG			Percentage frequency in				
	-806C>T	636G>A	681G>A	South Indian Tamilians (n=87)	CEU population (n=90)	CHB population (n=45)	JPT population (n=45)	YRI population (n=90)
HS1	C	G	A	42.7	15.0*	23.2*	28.1*	14.6*
HS2	C	G	G	39.8	66.7*	71.2*	69.5*	64.8*
HS3	T	G	G	17.5	18.3	0.0	0.0	20.3
HS4	C	A	G	0.0	0.0	3.2	2.1	0.0
HS5	T	G	A	0.0	0.0	2.2	0.0	0.0

SIT: South Indian Tamilian; MAF: minor allele frequency; OFH: observed frequency of heterozygosity; YRI: Yoruba in Ibadan, Nigeria; JPT: Japanese in Tokyo, Japan; CHB: Han Chinese in Beijing, China; CEU: CEPH (Utah residents with ancestry from northern and western Europe)

*The values were significant (p<0.05) when compared to that of South Indian Tamilian population.

7.7 Relative copy number variations of *CYP2C19* in South Indian population

There were no copy number variations of *CYP2C19* in South Indian population in the current study. All the samples studied were found to have the 2 copies of the gene. The *CYP2C19* copy numbers were in the range of 1.7-2.2. The values were obtained after taking mean values of $\Delta\Delta Ct$ from 2 reactions of the same sample and calculating copy number of each sample $2^{2-\Delta\Delta Ct}$. The efficiency of the assay for *IL-2* was between 87-100 % whereas for *CYP2C19* it was between 94-100 %. The slope of the standard curve for *IL-2* was in the range of -2.7 to -4.3 with R^2 (mean) of 0.99. The slope of the standard curve for *CYP2C19* was in the range of -3.2 to -4.5 with R^2 (mean) of 0.99.

The product sizes for *CYP2C19* and *IL-2* were 193 bp and 93 bp. Dissociation curves have shown the specific melting temperatures for both *IL-2* and *CYP2C19* products and/or any primer dimer formed during amplification. The amplification plots, dissociation curves, and standard curves of *CYP2C19* and *IL-2* are given in figures 36,37,38,39,40 and 41.

Selected Detector: All
 Well(s): C1,C3-C5,C7
 Document: CYP2C19 copynumber analysis IL2 13.12.08 (Absolute Quantification)

Figure 36. Amplification plot for *CYP2C19* gene

Selected Detector: All
 Well(s): A1-A2,A5-A8
 Document: CYP2C19 copynumber analysis IL2 13.12.08 (Absolute Quantification)

Figure 37. Amplification plot for *IL-2* gene

Dissociation Curve

Detector = CYP2C19, Tm = 60.0 °C

Well(s): E12-F4,F7-G12

Document: CYP2C19 copy number analysis _ 24.04.09 (Absolute Quantification)

Figure 38. Dissociation curve for *CYP2C19* gene amplification

Dissociation Curve

Detector = IL2, Tm = 60.0 °C
Well(s): A3-A4,A8,B1-C12
Document: CYP2C19 copy number analysis _ 24.04.09 (Absolute Quantification)

Figure 39. Dissociation curve for IL-2 gene amplification

Standard Curve

Detector: CYP2C19, Slope: -3.316034, Intercept: 27.078743, R2: 0.999290
Document: CYP2C19 copynumber analysis IL2 13.12.08 (Absolute Quantification)

Figure 40. Standard curve for *CYP2C19* gene

Standard Curve

Figure 41. Standard curve for *IL-2* gene

Discussion

8.0 Discussion:

8.1 South Indian population

India has more than two thousand ethnic groups, with a population of approximately 1.15 billion people (http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Demographics_of_India, access date: 10 July 2010). Each group is a derivative from four major ethnic groups including: austroloid, caucasoid, negrito and mongoloid. North India and East India comprises of caucasoid and mongoloid populations. Central, West, and South India comprises of the australoid population and the negritos are restricted only to the Andaman Islands.³⁵⁸ Linguistically, Indian population can be divided into four major language families such as Dravidian, Austro-Asiatic, Tibeto-Burman and Indo-European (Indo-Aryan). Indo-European and Dravidian languages are spoken by a majority of Indians residing in the northern and southern parts of the country, respectively. Genetic diversity is seen to greater extent in the Indian population as compared to most of the geographical territories in the world.

States of Tamilnadu, Kerala, Karnataka and Andhra Pradesh form the southern part of India. These four states speak the Dravidian languages. Thus, there is a relative linguistic homogeneity in South India. Endogamy has probably been a major reason for genetic diversification among the people of this region.³⁵⁹ A recent study by Thangraj *et al* had shown the evidence for genetically divergent two ancient populations i.e. ancestral north Indians and ancestral south Indians and proposed the existence of the admixture of these two ancestral populations in the mainland of India with major contribution from ancestral North Indian ancestry (39-71 %).³⁶⁰ They have also found allele frequency differences between groups in India compared to that of Europe, reflecting strong founder effects whose signatures have been maintained for thousands of years owing to endogamy. Thus it is of interest to study the genetic structure for the existence of any novel variation, establishment of allele frequencies and genotype-phenotype relationships in South Indian populations for understanding the disease and for applying the genetic knowledge in personalizing the treatment.

8.2 Genetic variations and haplotypes of 5' regulatory region of *CYP2C19* in South Indian population

Hepatic expression of *CYP2C19* is highly variable and may depend on many exogenous and endogenous factors, including drug exposure, diet, gender, age, and various physiological and genetic factors. The 5' regulatory region which includes enhancers, repressors, and promoter, controls the expression of a gene. This study identified novel variations in the 5' regulatory region of *CYP2C19* in South Indian population. *CYP2C19* 5' flanking region including the promoter region (up to 1020 bases upstream of the translational start site) and a part of the enhancer region (from 1708 to -1590 bases upstream of translational start site) was sequenced from 58 healthy volunteers of South Indian origin. All the contig sequences from this population were submitted to Genbank and are available in the public domain (Accession Nos. EU369428 to EU 369485). Total thirteen variations (-1041 A>G is not polymorphic) including eight novel ones were identified in the *CYP2C19* 5' flanking sequence among 58 human genomic DNA samples from South India. The identified variations were also submitted to NCBI dbSNP data base (ss#158145850 to ss# 158145863)

Marked inter-ethnic differences were noted in the allelic frequencies reported from the current study, in contrast to the other global populations. The variant allele frequency of -98T>C (28.45%) was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) than Afro-American (4.41%), and Caucasian (12.1%) populations.²² Allele frequencies of other reported variations i.e. -1418C>T, -889T>G were similar in South Indians, Caucasians, and Afro-Americans. The allele frequencies of *CYP2C19**1(60.3), *2(37.1) and *3 (2.5) were similar to the previous published reports in the study population.²⁸ The A>G change at position -1041 was found in all subjects and hence the wild type sequence in South Indian population contains nucleotide 'G' instead of 'A' at -1041 position.

Haplotype analysis was performed and the most frequent haplotype was haplotype 1(36.6%) followed by 2 to 13(ranging from 10.6 to 1.3%). The frequencies of other haplotypes were less than 1%. Haplotypes 1 to 13 share the common alleles at positions 636(G), -1558(T), -1289(T), -1051(T), -1041(G), -934(del), -833(del), -828(T), and -806(C). They differ from each other at the following positions viz. 681(G/A), -1498(T/G), -1442(T/C), -889(T/G), -779(A/C), and -98(T/C). More frequent haplotypes namely 1-3

differ from each other at positions 681 and -98. Among the samples examined, 33 different combinations of these haplotypes were found. The most frequent haplotype pairs were 1/5 (7%), and 3/4 (7%), followed by 1/11, 2/4, 5/13, 1/7, and 3/8 at a frequency of 5%, and 6/6, 1/12, 6/8, 1/3, 1/4 1/1, 1/2, 3/13, and 1/9 at a frequency of 3.5%. The haplotype structure of *CYP2C19* 5' flanking region (including promoter) is likely to vary in different ethnicities, due to changes in the allele frequencies and/or absence or presence of certain polymorphisms. Additional studies are required to elucidate the haplotype structure of *CYP2C19* 5' flanking region in Indian population and other populations of the world. Further studies are necessary to evaluate the existence of linkage disequilibrium in *CYP2C19* promoter and test whether it extends up to the exonic region polymorphisms which will enable us to understand genotype dependant expression, induction and inhibition of the *CYP2C19* gene.

8.3 Functional characterization of the variations in *CYP2C19* 5' regulatory region

The activity of *CYP2C19* varies with the presence or absence of certain variations in the gene. A recent study had characterized the *CYP2C19*17* allele in the promoter region which is responsible for ultra rapid metabolism of *CYP2C19* substrates.¹⁶ Limited reports were also available on other variations present in the *CYP2C19* promoter region and to the best of our knowledge no study had explored the influence of promoter region variants of *CYP2C19* on its activity.²² It is well known that the allele frequencies of *CYP2C19* differ with population and ethnicity. A locus would be polymorphic in certain ethnic groups whereas, the same may be monomorphic in other ethnic groups. The -1041 locus (-1041A/G) in *CYP2C19* promoter region was found to be monomorphic in South Indian population, whereas it was polymorphic in the north-western Europeans. Promoter region variants influence the enzyme activity by altering the gene expression.²⁹ Overlapping distribution of exonic region genotype among the PMs and EMs of *CYP2C19* had provoked an interest in the promoter region of the gene.¹⁴ The promoter region controls gene expression by the interaction of *cis*-acting elements spanning through the promoter region with the transcription factors. Any variations in these *cis*-acting elements might alter the gene expression.²⁹ Different segments of *CYP2C19* 5' promoter region have been characterized in a study suggesting the presence of positive and negative regulatory elements between -220 to -17 and -650 to -450 bases, respectively.²² The same study had

also reported eight common variants in the *CYP2C19* promoter region among the African Americans and Europeans. However, the functional characterization of these variants had not been performed. Potential binding sites for the transcription factors such as GATA proteins, progesterone receptor, TATA box elements and nuclear factors in *CYP2C19* promoter region had also been described.²²

In the initial stages of the study the 5' flanking region of *CYP2C19* was sequenced and eight variations among the South Indian population were identified. A few of them were present in the *cis*- acting elements of the promoter region of *CYP2C19*. Differences were also observed among populations in the minor allele frequencies of reported variations in the promoter region. It has also been predicted few binding sites in the 1.7 kb promoter region of *CYP2C19* including sites for CCAAT displacement protein binding (CDP), cyclic AMP responsive element beta (CREB) complex proteins, TATA box elements, CCAAT enhancer binding protein beta (CEBPB) and glucocorticoid receptor (GR). Due to the exploratory nature of this study, this was confined to limited sample from the heterogeneous population of the four states of South India. However, the minor allele frequencies of the detected variations need to be established in a homogenous population of individual states with an adequate sample size in future. Establishment of allele frequencies at polymorphic loci may not be essential for all the observed variants. Hence, the functional characterization of variations is important before large scale studies are planned for frequency determination or conducting a genotype phenotype association study. Considering the existence of variations in the putative *cis*- acting elements, it was hypothesized that these variations may alter the promoter activity and hence functional characterization of promoter region variations of *CYP2C19* using luciferase reporter gene assays and electrophoretic mobility shift assays was attempted.

Functional characterization of the variations in the *CYP2C19* 5' regulatory region was attempted in three steps. In the first step *in silico* analysis was performed, including the prediction of the responsive elements or TBS in the *CYP2C19* 5' regulatory region and docking analysis of predicted binding sites with corresponding TF. In the second step the *in vitro* analysis with the selection of the constructs based on the *in silico* findings was performed. The influence of the variation was explored using different constructs of *CYP2C19* 5' regulatory regions fused with *pGL-3* basic vector which were transfected into

HepG2 cell lines. The influence of the variations was measured in terms of the dual luciferase activity of the constructs measured. Following this *in vivo* analysis was performed using proganil as a probe drug.

In silico analysis of TF-TBS interactions with and without variations in TBS revealed that the interaction of ATF-2 with its TBS is stronger in the presence of variant allele (*CYP2C19* *17) in its site. The interaction of CDP repressor protein to its TBS has been found to weaken in the presence of variant allele at -98 position (T>C), which may interfere in the repression of gene transcription. These two TF-TBS complexes had the highest SC scores. Similarly, C/EBPB, GATA-1 and GR have high binding affinity to the TBS with normal alleles at positions -1498, -98 and -828, respectively as evidenced by high SC scores. Ultra rapid metabolism with -806C>T (*CYP2C19**17) variation may be due to boosted interaction of ATF-2 to its TBS, resulting in increased expression of the enzyme. Further -98T>C variant allele weakens the interaction with CDP repressor protein and hence may increase the transcription of *CYP2C19* in individuals with -98 CT or CC genotypes. Both CDP repressor protein and ATF-2 are known to be expressed in the liver and play an important role in regulating the expression of various genes including CYP enzymes.^{361;362}

The transcription factor binding sites (TBS) or response elements for transcription factors (TFs): activating transcription factor-2 (ATF-2), the mammalian CCAAT displacement protein (CDP repressor protein, Cut11), CCAAT/enhancer-binding protein beta (CEBPB), GATA binding protein 1(GATA-1) and glucocorticoid receptor (GR) are located in the 5' flanking region of *CYP2C19* ranging from -806 to -786 (catctcTGATgtaagataa), -105 to -87 (gccactttATCCatcaaag), -1505 to -1491 (aacattgtGCAAttg), -103 to -91 (gatgGATAaagtg), and -828 to -810 (tttgttcttctGTTctca), respectively. A putative orphan nuclear receptor binding site was predicted from -168 to -146 (ttttatctctATCAgtgggtcaa), and no variation was identified in the orphan nuclear receptor site.

Similar TBS exists in all members of 2C family except for 2C18, Differences in the sequence of potential transcription factor binding sites and transcriptional repressor elements among the 2C family members had been described earlier. Two putative TATA boxes were predicted one at 56 bases upstream, and other at 486 bases upstream of translational start codon. The transcriptional start site for *CYP2C19* gene was predicted to

be present 25 bases upstream from the start codon (ATG). A reporter assay study by Arefayene *et al* showed the presence of positive and negative regulatory elements between -153 to -17 and -650 to -363 bp from the start codon respectively.²² Another report revealed the presence of glucocorticoid responsive elements and androstane receptor enhancer elements between -1750 to -1736 and -1891 to -1876 respectively.²⁵³ Transcription factor binding sites may be lost or generated by polymorphisms like -1041A>G, -1418C>T, -806C>T, and -98T>C. -806C>T variation creating a binding site similar to that of GATA binding site, increases the transcription of *CYP2C19* gene resulting in ultrarapid metabolism of *CYP2C19* substrates.¹⁶ In-silico analysis showed the loss of GATA-binding factor 1 binding site upon -98T>C variation, generation of new binding site for glucocorticoid response and related elements (androgen receptor binding site, IR3 sites) upon -1418C>G variation, and nuclear factor binding site generation upon -1041A>G variation. In future, it will be valuable to study the impact of these variations on transcriptional activity of *CYP2C19* gene. It will be of great importance to evaluate particular variations such as -806C>T (*CYP2C19* *17) for its influence on pharmacokinetics and therapeutic response of *CYP2C19* substrates in South Indian population.

Luciferase reporter assay results have shown increased activity in the constructs (J₃ and J₆) with -98T>C variant supporting the *in silico* analysis results. The increased activity in these constructs may be attributed to this variant which may have disrupted the functional repressor region and increased the transcription of the reporter gene. Reporter construct with allelic variants -889T>G, -833del>T, -828T>A, -779A>C, -98T>C (J₂) also showed a significant increase in luciferase activity compared to normal promoter construct, but significantly lower activity than the constructs J₃ and J₆. Further, it showed increased luciferase activity when compared to normal construct (J_N) and constructs with -1442T>C, -889T>G (J₅) and -833del>T (J₈) variants. Even though -98T>C was a common variant seen in J₂, J₃ and J₆ constructs, only J₃ and J₆ constructs showed a steep rise in luciferase activity. In the construct with additional variants (J₂) such as -889T>G, -833del>T, -828T>A, -779A>C, decreased luciferase activity was observed as compared to J₃ and J₆. This suggests that presence of -98T>C variant in CDP repressor region in a construct increased the transcription of luciferase gene, which manifests as increase in luciferase activity. Electrophoretic mobility shift assay (EMSA) had shown the specific binding of

nuclear protein to the region surrounding -98 position. The aggravated binding was observed with DPLwt probe than with DPLmut suggesting the decreased interaction of nuclear protein with the probe containing variant allele. This binding in turn is effectively competed with unlabelled DPwt probe and less significantly with unlabelled DPmut probe. Thus the decreased recruitment of nuclear proteins to DPLmut probe compared to DPLwt and increased transcription seen in the constructs with -98T>C variation suggests the presence of repressor protein binding site surrounding -98 position. The observed linkage disequilibrium between -98T>C and 681G>A (*CYP2C19*2*) and increased luciferase activities with decreased recruitment of nuclear proteins seen in constructs with -98T>C may define the variability in enzyme induction and thus the CYP2C19 activity in subjects heterozygous for 681G>A polymorphism.

The variation -806C>T failed to increase the promoter activity in the construct (J₁) with other variations -1498T>G and -779A>C. Whereas it increased the luciferase activity in the construct (J₄) with -1498T>G, -833del>T and -779A>C. A probable explanation could be the possible cross talk between CCAAT/ enhancer binding protein beta (CEBPB) binding site and cell cycle-dependent element (CDE)/ cell cycle gene homology region (CHR) elements with existing variations -1498T>G and -833del>T, respectively. This might have resulted in an increased transcription of the gene and hence increased luciferase activity. Further, this could have been augmented with increased transcription by -806C>T variant, which was predicted to be present in the putative ATF-2 binding site. EMSA experiments with predicted binding sites i.e. TFLwt and TFLmut have shown the increased interaction of nuclear protein to the TFLmut probe with -806T allele. The nuclear protein binding was efficiently competed by TFmut probe and less significantly with TFwt probe. Thus increased interaction of nuclear protein to mutated probe suggests increased transcription process by increased recruitment of nuclear proteins.

A study by Sim *et al* had shown two fold higher hepatic reporter gene expression with 0.9 kb construct of CYP2C19 promoter with -806T allele compared to the construct with normal allele.¹⁶ In our study, 1.6 kb constructs with -806T allele (J₄) had shown increased reporter gene expression. However, another construct (J₁) with -806T had not shown the increased reporter gene expression. These discrepancies can be attributed to the large size of the construct with other variants. A construct with single variant allele generated by site

directed mutagenesis may reveal the exact influence of the particular variant. Earlier GATA like binding site was predicted to be present surrounding the -806 position.¹⁶ However, EMSA and reporter assays could not confirm GATA dependant transactivation of these constructs.¹⁶ Further, another study by Myini *et al* could not locate GATA like motifs surrounding -806 position. The same study had identified a GATA-4 binding site in *CYP2C19* promoter region (-165 to -156) and reported the role of GATA- 4 in the regulation of *CYP2C19* gene expression.³⁶³ In this study although GATA like motifs could not be located, a motif for ATF-2 was located. ATF-2 is a member of cAMP response element binding protein (CREB) family and is known to regulate the expression of isoforms of CYPs in liver. The ATF-2 factor may also interact with the putative CREB complex binding site (-793 to -773) in which a genetic variation (-779A>C) had been detected in the study population. CREB is known to play an important role in the expression of *CYP11A1* and aromatase enzymes and in different stages of spermatogenesis.^{362;364;365} It is also an important regulator of genes involved in gluconeogenesis in liver. Its role in transcriptional regulation and alteration of *CYP2C19* gene expression through inhibitors of CREB like PXR (which can bind directly to CREB and may repress the genes actively controlled by CREB) needs to be further evaluated.

The increased luciferase activity seen with the construct J₃ containing -779A>C variant allele, increased affinity of the nuclear protein to variant binding site in EMSA and super shift assays with CREB polyclonal antibody have confirmed the specific interaction of CREB to the region surrounding the -779 position. It had also been found that in the presence of variant allele at -779 position in CREB predicted binding site this interaction is stronger and thus might have resulted in increased luciferase gene expression in the construct J₃. But the other constructs with this variant i.e. J₁, J₂, and J₄ have not shown significant increase in luciferase activity. This could be due to the presence of other variants in the constructs which might have resulted in decreased recruitment of proteins and might have resulted in lower luciferase activity. For example CREB and CEBPB are known to interact with each other. If the binding of CEBPB with that of promoter is affected (e.g. in case of constructs with “G” at -1498 position i.e. J₄), then there is a possibility of the altered interaction of both CREB and CEBPB which might affect the final transcription of a gene. The molecular mechanisms underlying the CREB interaction

with other transcription factors in controlling the transcription of *CYP2C19* gene needs to be investigated.

The decreased luciferase reporter activity in J₂ construct compared to other two constructs with -98T>C (J₃ and J₆) variant can be attributed to the presence of other variants especially to -828T>A which was present in the putative glucocorticoid receptor region. Docking analysis of glucocorticoid receptor with its responsive element showed decreased interaction in the presence of 'A' allele against 'T' allele at -828 position, which might have decreased the transcription of the gene. However, no significant difference in the luciferase activity was seen between the constructs J₂ and J₄ (-1498T>G, -833del>T, -806C>T and -779A>C). EMSA experiments with predicted binding sites for GR i.e. GRLwt and GRLmut had shown interaction with the nuclear proteins. No significant difference in the interaction between normal type (-828T) and mutant probe (-828A) was observed. But, the interaction with the mutant probe had been efficiently competed by both normal and mutant unlabelled probes. The binding with normal probe was not significantly competed by unlabelled probes suggesting the weaker interaction of the nuclear protein with mutant probe compared to normal probe. A study by Chen *et al* had reported the presence of CAR elements (-1891 to -1876 bp) and glucocorticoid receptor binding sites (-1750 to -1736) in *CYP2C19* promoter region.²⁵³ Dexamethasone induction of *CYP2C19* in *HepG2* cell lines was shown to be mediated by this region and have also disrupted dexamethasone induction by mutating this site.

Drug induced induction of *CYP2C19* is known to be mediated by nuclear receptors, namely constitutive androstane receptor (CAR) and pregnane X receptor (PXR).^{263;270;366} CAR is constitutively expressed and xenobiotics are known to act by translocation of this receptor to nucleus thus increasing the transcription of *CYP2C19*. Drugs such as rifampicin act as a ligand to PXR thus increases the transcription of *CYP2C19*.²⁶³ Presence of variations in these sites may alter the induction by drugs. Other nuclear receptors or transcription factor binding sites for hepatic nuclear factor – 4 alpha (HNF-4 alpha), hepatic nuclear factor -3 gamma and CCAAT enhancing binding protein alpha are also known to influence the *CYP2C19* expression.^{263;275} Studies have shown that C/EBP α is a responsible for liver specific expression of drug metabolizing enzymes.^{367;368} C/EBP α and C/EBP β , both are found to bind to the same recognition sequence and activate many of the

promoters with sequence homology.²⁴¹ In this study, a C/EBP β binding site in *CYP2C19* promoter region was located and suggests a role of this transcription factor in *CYP2C19* gene expression.

EMSA studies have shown the specific interaction of nuclear protein to the predicted binding site for C/EBP β surrounding -1498 position. But, we could not find a clear cut difference in the interactions between the normal probe and variant probes. But, normal probe was found to have a strong interaction with nuclear proteins compared to the variant probe. Thus the presence of the variant allele in the binding site (“G” allele at -1498 positions) may decrease the interaction and thus might result in decreased transcription of *CYP2C19* gene. This interaction was reflected as decrease in luciferase activities in the constructs with variant allele at -1498 position i.e. constructs J₁ and J₄. But, the construct J₆ has shown increased luciferase activity which might be due to the other variant allele at -98 position. Super shift assays with C/EBP β antibody had shown the breakdown of the complex formation compared to the non specific antibody, suggesting the involvement specific interaction with C/EBP β , but might be a family of proteins must be interacting with the binding site as a smear of labelled oligos bound to complex was observed. Thus these luciferase assay experiments and EMSA assays provided an evidence for the interaction of the transcription factors in regulating the transcription of a gene. These results suggest that transcription of a gene is not regulated by a single factor but by a multiple factors which might interact in different ways either synergistically or antagonistically. This also suggests that the variations in the promoter region alone might have influence on transcription of a gene. This influence of these variants on transcription must be considered with the due consideration of all the variants. Because, some of the variants might increase interaction of proteins to the binding sites whereas some might not. The resultant net effect on transcription of a gene due all the variations and their interactions with the proteins was observed in the luciferase assays. Further studies needs to be performed to investigate the molecular mechanism of transcription factors interaction in regulating *CYP2C19* gene expression.

A study by Kawashima *et al* had shown that HNF-4 alpha controls *CYP2C9* gene expression to greater extent rather than controlling *CYP2C19* expression in hepatic cell lines.²⁷⁵ In this study, only 1.7 kb of *CYP2C19* promoter region was amplified based on the

deletion analysis performed by Arefayene *et al* and predicted glucocorticoid receptor binding site ranging from -828 to -810. Super shift EMSA experiments and induction experiments with dexamethasone will give an explicit evidence for the existence of GR in this region. Our study results suggested the weak interaction of the nuclear protein to the mutated GR probe (-828A) which might have resulted in decreased transcription rate in the constructs with this allele.

Supporting the *in silico* data and *in vitro* data lower proguanil metabolic ratios (proguanil/cycloguanil) were observed in subjects carrying -98C allele as compared with that of subjects carrying -98T allele. Moderate LD between 681G>A and -98T>C, which occurred at a higher frequency in *CYP2C19* *1/*2 genotype subjects as compared to *1/*1 genotype subjects may explain the increased inhibition of the enzyme in EMs than in PMs as reported in few studies.^{330;369} Thus genotype does influence the drug interactions by altering the capacity of a drug to induce or inhibit the enzyme. It had been found that concomitant administration of omeprazole resulted in decreased metabolism of diazepam in EMs and had no effect in PMs, suggesting that EMs are more susceptible to enzyme inhibition than PMs.³²⁸ Similar study had also found the inhibition of omeprazole metabolism by clopidogrel in EMs only and did not shown any inhibitory effect in PMs.³²⁷ This genotype dependant inhibition could be explained by the promoter region variants especially -98T>C which is in LD with that of *CYP2C19**2. In this study no significant difference in proguanil MRs was found between *1/*2 and *2/*2 or *2/*3 individuals. However, this observation was not in agreement with an earlier study, where no difference in MRs between *1/*1 and *1/*2 individuals had been reported.¹⁴ Of note is that the earlier study had taken urine levels of drug and metabolite in contrast to the plasma levels measured in our study. There exists a substantial overlap of proguanil MRs between these genotypes and hence it cannot be used to distinguish between these genotypes. Few studies have concluded that this overlapping of MRs may be due to unknown variations in the gene especially in promoter region or may be due to the involvement of another enzyme in the metabolism of *CYP2C19* substrates.^{14;28} The influence of promoter region polymorphisms on the levels of proguanil and cycloguanil was however not explored in these studies. The observed discrepancy in the present study may be due to variations in the promoter region, especially the -98T>C polymorphism, which was seen at higher frequencies (30.0%) in South Indians. Further, activation of proguanil to cycloguanil by

CYP3A4 or CYP2D6 and the effect of exposure to chemicals and diet variations might have resulted in overlapping of MRs between different genotypes.¹⁴

The metabolic ratios were lowest in the subjects with similar *CYP2C19* genotype and having variant alleles of *CYP2C9*. The possible explanation could be the variant alleles of *CYP2C9* are in LD with that of -806C>T which might have increased the *CYP2C19* expression and hence its activity. This resulted in increased metabolism of proguanil and lower MR in subjects carrying variant alleles of *CYP2C9*. Another possible explanation could be the decreased conversion of proguanil to another metabolite (other than cycloguanil which is not measured in this study) by *CYP2C9* in subjects with variant alleles of *CYP2C9* resulting in increased availability of proguanil for cycloguanil conversion by *CYP2C19*. However, the values were not statistically significant, suggesting a minor role of *CYP2C9* in proguanil oxidation.

Proguanil had been proposed as a safe alternate probe drug to S-mephenytoin for phenotyping of *CYP2C19*. Studies across ethnic groups with proguanil have shown comparable results to mephenytoin.^{178;370;371} The overlapping of metabolic ratio values between different *CYP2C19* genotypes had been observed in several genotype-phenotype association studies.^{14;28;94;176} This overlapping might be due to the involvement of other CYP isoforms in the metabolism of proguanil. However, limited information is available on the role of other CYP isoforms in the metabolism of proguanil. *In vitro* studies have demonstrated the role of CYP3A4 in the metabolism of proguanil.³⁷² Variations in the promoter region might offer a possible explanation for the observed overlapping metabolic ratios of proguanil between different *CYP2C19* genotypes. The large inter individual variability in the *CYP2C19* activity may reflect the differences in transcriptional regulation. The variations in the coding region of human *CYP2C19* have been widely studied in different ethnic populations.¹⁷⁻²⁰ However, the impact of *CYP2C19* genotype on proguanil oxidation in an Indian population had not been studied. Moreover, variations in the promoter region of *CYP2C19* have been studied only to a limited extent and the influence of promoter region polymorphisms of *CYP2C19* on proguanil oxidation is unknown. In the present study it has been found that *CYP2C19* genotype influences the proguanil oxidation and some of the promoter region variants also influence its oxidation. This suggests the clinical utility of *CYP2C19* genotyping in predicting the

responders and non responders to proguanil treatment. Proguanil is a prodrug used for prophylaxis of malaria caused by *Plasmodium falciparum*. It is also a drug of choice in some African countries to suppress malaria in sickle-cell anaemia patients, especially in children and pregnancy.¹⁷⁸ Bio-activation of proguanil to cycloguanil is mediated by the enzyme, CYP2C19 in the liver. The metabolism of proguanil co-segregates with the genetically determined CYP2C19 mediated metabolism of S-mephenytoin.³⁷⁰ This genetically influenced proguanil metabolism can be of clinical importance, as the genetic polymorphism is characterized by large interethnic differences in the PM phenotype. About 6% Caucasians, 20% Asians, 14% South Indians, 11% Orientals, and 8% Africans are PMs of CYP2C19.¹⁷⁻²⁰ In this study the variations -98T>C and -1498T>G might also explain the wide ranges in the metabolic ratios observed in the heterozygous subjects. It might also explain the variations in the activity of CYP2C19, which was due to the variable expression of CYP2C19 in these subjects.

8.4 Linkage disequilibrium and haplotypes of 8 SNPs across CYP2C19 and CYP2C9 in South Indian and four HapMap populations and its importance in association studies

The observed phenotypic differences in the genotype-phenotype association studies could be due to the detected polymorphism being causative, the detected variation being in linkage disequilibrium with the causative variation, or the detected polymorphism interacts with another polymorphism to cause the phenotypic effect. Analysis of data on various polymorphisms for a particular gene coupled with linkage equilibrium analysis may give a better view on association studies, as it includes the haplotypes instead of single variations. This analysis shall also include the promoter region variations as they may influence the exonic region variations and /or may directly influence the enzyme levels by altering the transcription process.

There existed a varying pattern of LD between the populations. There was strong LD between ($D'=1$) the alleles in YRI and CHB populations compared to other HapMap populations and south Indian population. Strong LD was observed between -1418C>T and -889T>G in *CYP2C19* in all the populations except for CEU population with $D'=1$. The correlation coefficient (r^2) between these two alleles was 0.6 in YRI, 0.8 in CHB and 1.0 in JPT populations. In South Indians a r^2 of 0.02 was observed between these two alleles.

Strong LD had also been observed between -98T>C and 681G>A in *CYP2C19* in all the HapMap populations with $D'=1$ and $r^2=1$, whereas the LD was moderate in South Indians ($D'=0.5$). *CYP2C9*3* (1075A>C) allele was in strong LD with that of -1418C>T of *CYP2C19* in South Indians, CHB and JPT populations. Strong LD was also observed between -98T>C of *CYP2C19* and 430C>T of *CYP2C9* in South Indian and CEU populations. Thus the LD between the *CYP2C9* and *CYP2C19* exonic region alleles with of *CYP2C19* promoter region allele may have combined effect on the phenotype observed in case of *CYP2C19* substrates. In this study, the decreased MR of proguanil in subjects carrying variant alleles of *CYP2C9* may be explained to a certain extent by this observed LD pattern.

CYP2C19 and *CYP2C9* are involved in the metabolism of arachidonic acid and incubation of poly unsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) with *CYP2C9* or *CYP2C19* in the presence of NADPH resulted in the decrease of PUFA concentrations in the incubation mixtures.³⁷³ These results indicate that the PUFAs are potent inhibitors as well as substrates of *CYP2C9* and *CYP2C19*. Thus the subjects carrying the haplotype (HS4) with defective alleles on both genes may be more prone to coronary artery diseases. This is due to the decreased availability of eNOS in coronary arteries resulting due to the defective *CYP2C19* and *CYP2C9* enzymes. A recent study had also demonstrated the association between the inflammatory markers interleukin (IL)-6, tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF-alpha) and high sensitivity C-reactive protein (hs-CRP) with that of *CYP2C19*2* allele.³⁷⁴ The study had also suggested that *CYP2C19*2* allele might be a risk factor for cardiovascular disease via inflammation. As both *CYP2C9* and *CYP2C19* have been involved in the metabolism of arachidonic acid to produce epoxyeicosanoid acids, which were involved in vascular tone and inflammation, subjects carrying the defective alleles in both genes were at more risk of cardiovascular vascular risk via inflammation. The interaction of these variants with variants of other genes on same chromosome i.e. *ADRB1*, *CYP2C8* also cannot be ignored. The haplotype HS3 had the variant alleles in *CYP2C19* promoter region (-889T>G) and *CYP2C9* exonic region (*CYP2C9*3*). Hence in the subjects carrying this haplotypes the metabolism of common substrates may be affected as -889 T>G was also shown to decrease the *CYP2C19* expression and *CYP2C9*2* decrease its activity.

Estrogens are also one of the endogenous substrates metabolized by CYP2C19. The haplotypes with defective alleles in exonic region and promoter region may have influence on estrogen metabolism and thus may alter the disease risk in women carrying those haplotypes. The haplotypes of these enzymes may also play a role in predicting the response to a treatment of tamoxifen, wherein defective alleles in the enzyme may cause the therapeutic failure to tamoxifen therapy as CYP2C19 metabolizes estrogens and in subjects with defective CYP2C19 alleles more estrogens are available in the tissues resulting in therapeutic failure of tamoxifen.²⁰³ It is also known that tamoxifen undergoes metabolism by CYP2C9 and also inhibits CYP2C9.³⁷⁵ This may be aggravated in the subjects carrying haplotypes with defective alleles of CYP2C9. Thus in subjects with haplotypes in which defective alleles are present in both CYP2C19 and CYP2C9 are more prone to therapeutic failure and drug interactions. Whereas the subjects carrying haplotypes with CYP2C19*17 allele and normal alleles of CYP2C9 may respond well to tamoxifen therapy.

A recent study by Janha *et al* had showed the influence of the CYP2C19 and CYP2C9 variations on proguanil oxidation in African population.¹⁷⁹ Eventhough the sample size was less in this explorative study, it suggests the varying haplotype structures in South Indians and Africans might have resulted in different findings. In this study the authors concluded that CYP2C19*17 determines the metabolic profile on CYP2C19 and CYP2C9 locus. The LD pattern among the Africans and South Indians vary and in this study it was found that CYP2C9*2 allele is in linkage disequilibrium with that of -98 T>C and few other promoter variants which were shown to increase the promoter activity and increased luciferase expression. Whereas in YRI population (the same population Janha *et al* also have studied) there was no LD between the CYP2C9*2 and any of the reported promoter variants of CYP2C19. This might be the reason for the observed differences in the plasma cycloguanil levels between subjects carrying different genotypes of CYP2C9. Another study had reported strong LD between the wild alleles of CYP2C9 i.e. CYP2C9*1 with that of CYP2C19*17 allele in Nordic population suggesting the influence of the LD pattern among the variants on common substrates of CYP2C19 and CYP2C9.³⁷⁶

The important role of CYP2C9*3 in addition to CYP2C19*2 allele had been demonstrated in determining the response to clopidogrel in patients on dual antiplatelet therapy

undergoing coronary stenting.³⁷⁷ This study suggested the importance and superiority of haplotype based prediction over genotype based prediction of therapeutic response. A recent study had shown LD between *CYP2C9*1B* allele (-3089G>A, -2633 del>T,G) with that of *CYP2C19*2* allele.³⁷⁸ These variations in *CYP2C9* regulatory region have explained 10% of the variation in phenytoin maintenance dose in epileptic patients. Reporter assays with the wild type and variant haplotype constructs have shown increased *CYP2C9* induction by phenytoin in the constructs with wild type alleles. The effect of these variations on phenytoin dependant induction are comparable to that of *CYP2C9*2* and **3* alleles.³⁷⁸ Thus in subjects carrying *CYP2C19*2* allele, the activity of *CYP2C9* can be enhanced by the inducers which may influence the metabolism for the common substrates of *CYP2C19* and *CYP2C9* such as phenytoin, Warfarin and tolbutamide.

Some *CYP2C19* substrates act as inhibitors of *CYP2C9* such as fluconazole.³⁷⁹ Thus determining the haplotype structure of the *CYP2C19* and *CYP2C9* may predict the influence of particular haplotype on drug interaction with *CYP2C9* substrates such as warfarin and phenytoin. Understanding the haplotype structure of these two genes may be able to explain the probable cause for the drug interaction reported between the warfarin and oral contraceptives.³⁸⁰ The defective alleles of *CYP2C19* might have resulted in increased concentrations of estradiol which might have displaced warfarin from the protein binding site. This could have been further aggravated by the defective alleles of *CYP2C9* by increasing the plasma warfarin concentrations resulting in increased bleeding risk in such patients. Thus understanding the LD pattern and studying the haplotype structures may enable us to understand the genotypes influence on drug interactions resulting from gene-gene interactions.

Recent study on influence of genotype on inhibition of *CYP2C19* activity by omeprazole in subjects taking clopidogrel has shown that PMs are at more risk of inhibition. However, a wide range was seen in the inhibition of platelet aggregation (IPA) activities, suggesting the role of promoter region polymorphisms on *CYP2C19* activity.¹⁶⁵ In this study PPIs (omeprazole, lansoprazole and rabeprazole) have diminished the clopidogrel antiplatelet activity to a greater extent in subjects carrying defective alleles (i.e. *CYP2C19*2* and **3*) compared to the normal genotype subjects (*CYP2C19*1*1*). Increased conversion rate of responders to non responders was seen in subjects carrying **2* and **3* alleles (PMs)

compared to normal genotype subjects (EMs). One of 15 EMs and 6 out of 16 PMs became low responders when PPIs were administered. Further, some low responders (n=6) in PM group converted to responders when treated with PPIs. Wide ranges in the inhibition of platelet activity (IPA) among the PM group have also been reported in this study. The time of administration had been found beneficial in case of EMs and has shown no benefit in case of PMs. Thus this study directed a new path of identifying the drug interactions on the basis of genotype. The discrepancies observed in this study, i.e increased activity in PMs after PPI administration and wide ranges of IPA in PMs may be explained by some of the promoter region variants which have not been studied. The influence of *CYP2C19*17* allele had been ruled out as no subjects in this study were found to contain this allele. Thus other promoter region variants such as -98T>C, -828T>A, -1498T>G, -889T>G might have influenced the *CYP2C19* activity in these subjects in addition to the possible involvement of other genes such as multidrug resistant protein (*MDR1* or *ABCB1*).

Evaluation of the relationship between the haplotypes of *CYP2C19* and *CYP2C9* and their common substrates such as phenytoin, fluoxetine, sertraline, warfarin, tolbutamide and clopidogrel might predict the metabolic profile of the substrates. Thus haplotype-phenotype association studies might yield a more reliable prediction on the therapeutic response of common substrates rather than genotyping for one or two alleles in one gene. These association studies have to be performed in different ethnic groups as the LD varies among different groups.

8.5 *CYP2C19*17* allele and genotype frequencies in South Indian Tamilian's and its clinical importance

The frequency of *CYP2C19*17* (-806C>T) in South Indian tamilian population as carried out in the present study, is found to be high (19.2%). In addition, it's prevalence in this study population is depicted to be unique and distinct as compared to other populations. *CYP2C19*17* allele frequency was found to be significantly lower ($p<0.05$) in Chinese population (CHB, 2.2%) and slightly higher in African population (YRI, 20.6%) compared to that of the South Indian Tamilian population (17.8%). The *CYP2C19*17* allele frequencies were comparable between Caucasian (CEU, 18.3%) and south Indian Tamilian population. This allele was found to be absent in Japanese samples (JPT) of HapMap project.

This data was also in agreement with other reports from different populations.^{16;381-383} This data also suggests a significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher frequency of *CYP2C19**2 (40.2%) allele in South Indian Tamilian population compared to that of other populations. There also existed a significant inter-ethnic difference in the distribution of *CYP2C19**17 allele as compared to other populations of the world as reported by independent researchers of different populations. The *CYP2C19**17 allele frequency in Japanese (1.3%) and Chinese (4.4%) was significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) as compared to that of the Tamilian population, which is comparable to that of Swedish (18%) and Ethiopian (18%) populations.^{16;381-383}

A genotype-phenotype association study from our laboratory had established EMs frequency of 47.0% having *CYP2C19**1/*1 genotype in South Indian population.²⁸ The same study had also reported a total EM frequency of 86% which includes subjects from *1/*2 genotype (40.7%) and *2/*2 genotype (4.3%). The total EM frequency of 82% had been observed with the exclusion of subjects carrying *2/*2 genotype (4.3%). In the present study a frequency of PMs based on the genotype frequencies i.e. 18.4% was predicted, which was slightly higher than that of previous report (14%). In view of *CYP2C19**17 allele the EMs frequency was recalculated to 28.7% and intermediate metabolizers (IMs) or heterozygous extensive metabolizers (hetEMs) frequency was found to be 31.0%. The ultra rapid metabolizer's (UMs) frequency was observed to be 1.2 %, with heterozygous ultra rapid metabolizer frequency of 20.7%. In the previous study, wherein subjects were not genotyped for *CYP2C19**17 allele, EMs frequency was reported to be 82% (after the exclusion of *CYP2C19**2/*2 subjects), which is similar to the total frequency of EMs, hetEMs, UMs, hetUMs i.e. 82% observed in the present study. The phenotype prediction based on the few detected variant genotypes may be inappropriate as it is also influenced by other factors such as age, sex, concomitant medication, disease condition and by other undetected variants. Hence, genotype-phenotype association studies must evaluate the relationship between genotypes of newly detected variants and phenotype. A recent study proposed assignment of EM status to *CYP2C19**17 homozygous subjects rather than UM status. This study analyzed the reports on this allele since its discovery in 2006 and had found overlapping of *CYP2C19* substrates plasma levels between *CYP2C19**1/*1 and *CYP2C19**17/*17 subjects,³⁸⁴ but the sample size in most of these studies was less to detect the unequivocal impact of this allele on *CYP2C19* substrates. In this study, UM status was assigned to the subjects homozygous for

*CYP2C19*17* in accordance with the earlier literature; however genotype-phenotype association studies with large sample size are needed to establish the status of this allele.

Few studies have reported the clinical relevance of *CYP2C19*17* allele. One study had shown association of *CYP2C19*17* allele with the therapeutic failure in Caucasian subjects receiving approved doses of PPIs.³⁸¹ Lower serum levels (42% lower) of escitalopram had also been reported in psychiatric patients homozygous for **17* allele compared to **1/*1* subjects posing an increased risk of therapeutic failure in the subjects carrying **17* allele.²¹⁴ A study had been conducted so as to analyze the effect of *CYP2C19*17* gene variant on *Helicobacter pylori* eradication in the peptic ulcer patients and the result suggested *CYP2C19*17* to have no impact on the efficacy of *H. pylori* eradication in the patients.¹²⁵ Another study in Caucasians had shown the increased dose requirement of PPIs in subjects carrying **17* allele.¹²⁶ This can be explained by the ultra rapid metabolism caused by this variant allele thus decreasing the therapeutically active drug levels in plasma. Hence a higher dose of the CYP2C19 substrates was advised in the carriers of this variant allele to prevent therapeutic failure. Reduction in dosages of drugs whose metabolite is therapeutically active such as proguanil, tamoxifen, and clopidogrel may be beneficial in *CYP2C19*17* allele carriers to avoid adverse effects due to active agent. Further studies are required to establish the clinical relevance of this allele in different conditions requiring treatment with CYP2C19 substrates. Another study had reported lower incidence of breast cancer in *CYP2C19*17* allele carriers suggesting its protective role.²²⁸

Albeit taking into consideration of these reports, a recent study analyzed the clinical utility of *CYP2C19*17* allele and concluded limited impact of this allele on CYP2C19 substrates except on the drugs with narrow therapeutic indices.³⁸⁴ Another study in hospitalized patients observed the decreased serum levels of citalopram and amitriptyline and their metabolic ratios in subjects carrying *CYP2C19*17* allele, but *CYP2C19*17* allele was unlikely to predict the therapeutic outcome for citalopram and amitriptyline.³⁸⁵ Similarly, another study found no significant difference in dose corrected plasma levels of imipramine between *CYP2C19*17/*17* and *CYP2C19*1/*1* groups. Thus *CYP2C19*17* genotyping was unlikely to predict therapeutic response to imipramine in depressed patients.³⁸⁶ Contrary to these findings Sibbling *et al* have reported a significant impact of

*CYP2C19*17* on clopidogrel therapeutic outcome in coronary artery disease patients with coronary stent placement. Increased risk of bleeding with clopidogrel had been found to be associated with *CYP2C19*17* allele suggesting enhanced response and increased risk of bleeding in subjects carrying this allele.¹⁵⁹ Further replication studies with larger sample size and with other *CYP2C19* substrates are warranted to establish the clinical utility of *CYP2C19*17* allele. Owing to its higher frequency in the study population, studies are required to establish its role in predicting the therapeutic efficacy of *CYP2C19* substrates

With the advent of this novel variant allele, there is an indispensable need for critical reassessment of the wild type allele. The present study was first of its kind to be executed in an Indian population. There were few reports that have emphasized the important clinical implications of this novel variant allele and that further studies are required to assess its clinical utility. The high prevalence of this variant allele in this study population might serve to be a useful bio marker in foreseeing the metabolic and clinical attributes of *CYP2C19* substrates. Owing to its existence at high frequency, it is feasible to conduct genotype-phenotype association studies or studies on clinical relevance of this allele in South Indian Tamilian population.

8.6 Relative copy number variations of *CYP2C19* in South Indian population

Absence of the copy number variations in South Indian population indicates that the genetic variations such as single nucleotide polymorphisms may predict the changes in the activity of the enzyme. The discrepancies in genotype-phenotype association studies and wide ranges in the metabolic ratios of *CYP2C19* substrates in EMs are due to other variations in the regulatory region. The involvement of other CYP isoforms in the metabolism of *CYP2C19* substrates may also result in the discrepancies observed in a genotype-phenotype association studies. Further studies are needed on a larger scale to investigate the copy number variations of *CYP2C19* in healthy volunteers and in disease states using a proper standard from bacterial artificial chromosomes and comparative genomic hybridization.

9.0 Limitations of the study

- This study is confined to only 1.7 kb of the 5' flanking region of *CYP2C19*. The region beyond the 1.7 kb of the promoter region had not been studied for the existence of any regulatory elements or variations. Only 1.7 kb of promoter region was chosen based on the findings from a study by Arefayene *et al.*²²

- Selection of probe for phenotyping:

We selected proguanil which has been suggested as a probe drug for assessing CYP2C19 activity. Some volunteers could have been phenotyped with omeprazole also which is also a recommended probe drug. However selection of proguanil itself has some advantages of being the alternate probe drug for phenotyping the CYP2C19 as it lacks the inhibitory activity on CYP2C19 unlike omeprazole which inhibits CYP2C19 activity. Usage of proguanil in *CYP2C19* genotype-phenotype association studies on large scale may provide evidence for the clinical utility of *CYP2C19* genotyping in predicting response to proguanil therapy.

- Selection of standard for copy number analysis. A sample with no variations in its exonic region and promoter region and whose phenotype showed perfect relation with its genotype has been selected. Ideally the cloned sample whose copy number is being established could have been chosen. But the results of our study are similar to that of a study wherein *CYP2C19* gene from bacterial artificial chromosome was used as a standard and copy number of CYP2C19 was evaluated using comparative genomic hybridization in microarrays at Manipal Life Science Center, Manipal (Personal communication)
- Co-transfection of factors into *HepG2* cell lines might have helped in understanding the interaction efficiently. With the limited resources these assays and super shift assays were not performed for all the factors.

Conclusion

10.0 Conclusion

This is the first study to identify and functionally characterize different polymorphisms in 5' regulatory region of *CYP2C19* using different constructs. This is the first report on allele and genotype frequencies of *CYP2C19**17 in South Indian Tamilian population. In this study the copy number variations of *CYP2C19* was also explored for the first time.

The conclusions drawn from this study are as follows:

1. *CYP2C19* 5' flanking region is polymorphic in South Indian population. Eight novel variations in 1708 bp region of *CYP2C19* 5' region were identified.
2. Novel variations were identified and their percentage frequencies were: -779A>C (16.4), -828T>A (2.6), -934del>T (3.5), -1051T>C (1.72), -1289T>G (3.4), -1442T>C (12.1), -1498T>G (25.0) and -1558T>G (2.6). The reported variations found in the study population and their frequencies were: -98T>C (28.4), -806C>T (2.6), -833del>T (9.5), -889T>G (10.3) and -1418C>T (1.7). The two known non synonymous single nucleotide polymorphisms, 681G>A (*2 allele) and 636G>A (*3 allele) were detected at 0.371 and 0.025 frequencies, respectively.
3. Strong LD was observed between several variations identified and 43 haplotypes were constructed among which 13 were found to occur at a frequency greater than 1%. This can explain the interaction of exonic region variations with that of those in regulatory region.
4. *In silico* analysis predicted few important transcription factor binding sites such as ATF-2 binding site, CEBPB binding site, GR and CDP binding site surrounding identified variations such as -806C>T, -1498T>G, -98T>C and -828T>A. Transcription factor binding interaction analysis showed the altered interaction of the factor to its binding site in the presence of the variant allele.
5. The reporter gene assay results have shown that the variants -1498T>G and -828del>T were significantly associated with decreased luciferase activity, whereas variants -1442T>C, -779A>C and -98T>C were significantly associated with increased luciferase activity. These variants may have similar influence on *CYP2C19* gene transcription.

6. EMSA analysis also showed specific interaction of nuclear proteins with putative binding sites for CDP repressor protein, ATF-2 and GR. Variation at -98T>C and -828 T>A had resulted in weak interaction of nuclear proteins with CDP binding site and predicted GR binding site, whereas presence of variant allele at -806 position has resulted in stronger interaction of binding site with nuclear proteins.
7. EMSA analysis also showed a specific interaction of nuclear proteins with putative binding sites for CREB and CEBPB. Variation at -779A>C had resulted in increased interaction of CREB like proteins to the binding site. Super shift assays have confirmed the CREB proteins interaction to the putative site.
8. Genotype-phenotype association study with proguanil as a probe drug revealed that the mean metabolic ratios (proguanil/cycloguanil) were higher in *1/*2, *1/*3, *2/*2 and *2/*3 as compared to *1/*1 subjects. Subjects with promoter region variation -98T>C showed decrease in the metabolic ratios irrespective of other variation, which may explain the deviation from the genotype-phenotype association of *CYP2C19*.
9. The antimode of proguanil metabolic ratio in South Indians was 12.4. Individuals with proguanil MR less than 12.4 were characterized as EMs and those with MR more than 12.4 were characterized as PMs.
10. *CYP2C9* genotype had no or minor effect on proguanil oxidation. The decreased metabolic ratios observed in subjects carrying defective alleles of *CYP2C9* (*2 and *3) may be due to the effect of promoter region polymorphisms of *CYP2C19* which are in LD with *CYP2C9**2 & *3 alleles.
11. The *CYP2C19**17 allele frequency in South Indian TAMILIAN population (n=206) was found to be 19.2% (95% CI: 15.4 - 20.3) indicating relatively higher frequency of this allele and the importance of conducting genotype-phenotype association studies for this allele.
12. No copy number variations of *CYP2C19* were found in South Indian population.

The study concludes that 5' regulatory region polymorphisms such as -98T>C, -779A>C -1498T>G and -828T>A influence the expression of *CYP2C19* gene reflected as changes in the luciferase gene expression. The study also suggests the role of CDP repressor region, ATF-2, CREB and CEBPB on regulating the *CYP2C19* gene expression.

11.0 Summary

CYP2C19 is involved in the metabolism of clinically important drugs such as proton pump inhibitors, proguanil, anti depressants, nelfinavir, voriconazole, etc. Various studies have established the genotype-phenotype correlation of *CYP2C19* in different populations. Discrepancies were found in these studies; where no correlation was observed between the *CYP2C19* genotype (variations in the exonic region) and phenotype in some individuals, indicating the presence of variations in 5' flanking region or intronic region. The objective of this study was to sequence and functionally characterize the 5'regulatory region of *CYP2C19* in South Indian individuals. In this study, the 5' regulatory region of *CYP2C19* was sequenced from 58 unrelated healthy volunteers of South Indian origin, and 8 novel variations were identified. All the sequences of 5' regulatory region of CYP2C19 were submitted to Genbank database and are available in public domain (Accession ID: EU369428 to EU 369485). Identified novel variations and their percentage frequencies were: -779A>C (16.4), -828T>A (2.6), -934del>T (3.5),-1051T>C (1.72), -1289T>G (3.4), -1442T>C (12.1), -1498T>G (25.0) and -1558T>G (2.6). The reported variations found in the study population and their frequencies were: -98T>C (28.4),-806C>T (2.6), -833del>T (9.5), 889T>G (10.3) and -1418C>T (1.7). Some of these variations were found to be present in the transcription factors binding site such as ATF-2, GATA 1, CREB, CEBPB and CDP repressor protein etc. All the subjects were also explored for exonic region polymorphisms of *CYP2C19*, 681G>A (*2 allele) and 636G>A (*3 allele) and were detected at 0.371 and 0.025 frequencies, respectively. 43 different haplotypes were constructed with all the variations observed in this population, of which frequency of 13 haplotypes were found to be more than 1%. Phenotyping of 50 subjects was also performed by using proguanil as a probe drug (subjects were phenotyped by measuring the plasma concentrations of proguanil and cycloguanil by reverse phase HPLC after a single oral dose (200mg) of proguanil), and correlated with the variations in exonic region and 5' flanking region. The gene-dose effect of *CYP2C19* and proguanil metabolic ratio (proguanil/cycloguanil) was found in this population. The mean proguanil metabolic ratios (proguanil/cycloguanil) were highest in *CYP2C19**1/*2 or *1/*3 subjects (9.6 ± 2.6 ; $p=0.03$) and in *2/*2 or *2/*3 (9.9 ± 3.7 ; $p=0.04$) as compared to normal subjects (*1/*1; 4.7 ± 1.2), but still some overlapping of the metabolic ratios were found between different genotypes, which may be due to the variations found in the promoter region. Further

analysis showed that variations -98T>C and -806 C>T have influenced the proguanil metabolic ratio irrespective of their exonic region variations. *In silico* docking analysis of transcription factors to its binding sites in *CYP2C19* 5' regulatory region with and without variations revealed the alteration in the interaction of transcription factors to their binding sites in the presence of variant alleles. The 5' regulatory region of samples with 13 different inferred haplotypes were cloned into *pGL-3* basic reporter vectors for studying the impact of the promoter variations on expression of luciferase gene in human *HepG2* cell lines. Transfection of *pGL-3* fused vectors with *CYP2C19* 5' regulatory region using lipofectamine reagent into *HepG2* cell lines and luciferase assay have shown that variations present in the *cis*-acting elements of the *CYP2C19* promoter region such as -1442T>C, -779A>C and -98T>C -1498T>G and -828del>T alter the transcription of the gene. Electrophoretic mobility shift assays had shown the sequence specific binding of proteins from *HepG2* nuclear extracts. These results indicate the influence of these variations on gene expression which can explain the Interindividual differences in *CYP2C19* gene expression. This also helps us to understand the genotype dependant differences in enzyme induction and inhibition in a clinical setting. The results also suggest the role of activating transcription factor-2, cyclic AMP response element binding protein and CCAAT displacement repressor protein on *CYP2C19* gene transcription.

— *Future directions*

12.0 Future Directions

1. Development of cost effective genotyping methods like allele specific oligo hybridization (ASO-dotblot) technique for screening of promoter region variants and exonic regions variants for routine diagnostic use.
2. Studies on *CYP2C19* genetic variants especially *CYP2C19*2*, **3* and **17* on clopidogrel and its metabolite plasma levels and therapeutic outcome in South Indian population.
3. Studies on exploring the influence of promoter region variants on *CYP2C19* substrate drug interactions especially between PPIs and clopidogrel
4. Case-control studies on breast cancer disease to evaluate association of *CYP2C19*17* allele and influence of *CYP2C19* genotypes on tamoxifen therapy in breast cancer patients.
5. Genotype dependant induction and inhibition of *CYP2C19* in relation to the promoter region variants and Genotype-phenotype association studies of promoter region variations of *CYP2C19*.
6. Exploring different transcription factor networks and their impact on *CYP2C19* gene expression in cell lines

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13.0 References

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Appendices

Procedure for vertical gel electrophoresis

1. Assembling the apparatus and preparing the gel solution: The glass plates and spacers are cleaned with methanol. They are then rinsed well with deionised water followed by ethanol and air dried. Care was taken to ensure that the glass plates are free of grease spots. The large unnotched plate is laid on the bench and the spacers are arranged on each side parallel to the two edges. The notched plate is then placed above the larger plate resting on the spacers. The plates are clamped on either side with bulldog paper clips. Based on the size of the glass plates and the thickness of the spacers the following amount of each component is taken in a conical flask to make 60 ml of the gel.

- a. Distilled water (Elix) - 38 ml
- b. 30% 29:1 acrylamide-bisacrylamide -16 ml
- c. 10X TBE buffer - 6 ml
- d. 10% Ammonium persulphate -250 μ l
- e. TEMED - 45 μ l

The glass plates are now placed on a solid rack above the level of the table and the mixture is poured carefully between the plates. This should be done quickly so as to complete the preparation before the acrylamide polymerizes. Any air bubble if present should be removed. The comb is inserted immediately into the gel and the acrylamide is allowed to polymerize for 30-60 min at room temperature. Once the polymerization is completed the comb can be removed and the surface of the plate is washed with running water.

2. Loading the samples and running the gel: The plates are mounted on the electrophoresis apparatus which is filled with 1 X TBE buffer and the plates are clamped with clips. The notched plate should face inwards towards the buffer reservoir. 3ml of gel loading buffer is added to the digested product. The first well should usually be loaded with the appropriate marker or ladder based on the size of the bands to be resolved. The second well is loaded with undigested sample. The digested samples are loaded from the third well onwards. The electrodes are connected to the power pack and set to a voltage of 220V. The gel is allowed to run till the marker dyes have migrated atleast three fourths of the well. This usually lasts for 2 hours. After disconnecting the leads the glass plates are detached using a strong metallic wedge and the gel is dipped inside a water tub containing a solution of ethidium bromide and water (20 μ l ethidium bromide in 1000 ml of water) and rocked for 2 minutes. The gel is then placed on the UV platform in such a way that the marker coincides with the left margin of the platform. The UV illuminator is switched on and is adjusted so as to get a good image of the gel pattern that is recorded on the computer.

Cell culture protocols

Culturing HepG2 cells

Materials Required: Equipment and other consumables

Laminar air flow (Type 2 model), CO₂ incubator with cylinders, Inverted Microscope, Water bath, Micropipettes & filter tips, Pipettman, Disposable pipettes, Culture plates/ flasks, Liquid Nitrogen , Deep freezer (-20°C) / Fridge, Suction pump, Cell counting chamber, Tissue paper / sterile cotton / Parafilm, Autoclave, 15 ml & 50 ml PP tubes, Schott Duran bottles, Test tube stands (Multiple uses), Eppendorf tubes, cryovials & cryogloves, Plastic or wooden cupboards with mica sheet

Reagents:

DMEM medium, FCS / FBS (Fetal calf/bovine serum), Sodium pyruvate (100 mM), Sodium bicarbonate (7.5 %), Amino acids (non essential) (100X), Antibiotics/ Antimycotics (100X) (Penicillin & Streptomycin), L-Glutamine (200 mM), Trypsin-EDTA (0.05%), DPBS with out CaCl₂ & MgCl₂, Ethanol (70%), Tryptan blue stain (0.4%), Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), Milli Q Water (Autoclaved), Sodium hypochlorite solution, Aquaclean disinfectant (Microbiocidal liquid, to use in CO₂ incubator).

Media preparation:

- ❖ Bring all the reagents to room temperature.
- ❖ **Decomplementation:** Heat FCS at 56°C for 30 mins in water bath (single time).
- ❖ Filter and Aliquot FCS & L-Glutamine 50 ml & 5ml respectively. Mix the above reagents as per the volume mentioned in sterile condition.
- ❖ Filter the medium in 0.22µ filter.
- ❖ Every 15 days add 1% of glutamine to the media i.e. 1:100 ml.

Note:

- Store FCS & L-Glutamine at -20°C and all other working reagents at 4-8°C.
- Do all the preparation in laminar air flow under sterile conditions.
- Wipe all the materials and the work area with 70% ethanol before and after use.
- Use disposable or autoclaved pipettes (with filter) each time.
- All centrifugation are done at 1000 rpm for 5-6 mins at room temperature.
- Use pipettman to take and deliver the solution and suction pump to discard the solution.
- Check the cells and change the medium twice or thrice in a week. Change the medium before the week end.
- Keep the complete medium, PBS in water bath (37°C) for 30 minutes before use and wipe the outer surface with alcohol and bring it to working hood.
- Do not keep the Trypsin EDTA in water bath. Use directly from the fridge at room temperature as the activity gets destroyed by itself at 37°C.
- Use Autoclaved water in the water bath.

- Always label the tubes and plates (Name of the cell line, Passage no., user name, date, media changed or treated)
- Label all the reagents (date of opening) and use different containers for each lot.
- Pour few drops of hypochlorite to the plate, keep overnight and incinerate. Closed containers can be directly incinerated.

Subculture from the parent culture:

1. Take the low number of passaged cell line aliquot (0.5 ml) & thaw it immediately to room temperature from the liquid nitrogen (if required, keep in water bath for few mins at 37°C).
2. Add 1ml of medium to it, mix gently (repeat twice) and put in 9 ml of medium (total 10 ml) in a 15 ml tube (to wash the cells to remove excess FCS and DMSO which was used for storage).
3. Centrifuge and remove the supernatant.
4. To the pellet add 10 ml of medium mix gently and pour into the plate.
5. Check for cell morphology and contamination (mycoplasma & yeast or bacteria) under inverted microscope. FCS facilitates bacterial growth.
6. Incubate at 37°C, 5% CO₂ in CO₂ incubator.

Maintaining the cell lines:

1. Check the cells under microscope for confluence and contamination. (Attached cells will be rectangular in shape and unattached round in shape & dead cells round black).
2. Remove the entire medium and add 3 ml of PBS and rotate the plate gently to wash the cells.
3. Remove the PBS and add 10 ml of fresh medium.
4. Check under microscope and incubate.
5. Repeat the same every second or third day until cells become confluent. (Frequency of the media change will depend on type of cells used.)
6. Do not allow the cells to over grow.

Passage of cell lines (1st passage):

1. Check the cells under microscope for confluence. (>80%)
2. Label the tubes and plates.
3. Remove the entire medium and add 3 ml of PBS and rotate the plate gently to wash the cells.
4. Remove the PBS and add 3 ml of 0.05% Trypsin EDTA, rotate the plate gently and incubate for 5 minutes in CO₂ incubator.
5. Tap the plate gently and look under the microscope for detachment of cells (repeat incubation for few more minutes if detachment is not complete), detached cells will become round in shape.
6. Add 7 ml of fresh medium mix gently with pipette and deliver into 15 ml tube.
7. Centrifuge and discard the supernatant.
8. To the pellet add 2 or 4ml of medium and mix gently (for 2 plates, 2 ml per plate, 2-3 million cells per plate). Less number of cells will take long time to become confluent. If needed, cells can be counted and accordingly distributed but each HepG2 plate will have approximately 10-12 million cells when it is confluent with single layer.

9. Deliver 8 ml of fresh medium to each 2 plates (1 plate for next passage and 1 plate for storage). No experiments should be done directly from the 1st subculture plate.
10. Add 2 ml of mixed cells to each plate. Mix gently by rotating and look under the microscope.
11. Incubate the plates and maintain the cell lines.

Passage of cell lines (2nd passage):

1. Check the cells under microscope for confluent (>80 %).
2. Label the tubes and plates.
3. Remove the entire medium and add 3 ml of PBS and rotate the plate gently to wash the cells.
4. Remove the PBS and add 3 ml of 0.05% Trypsin EDTA, rotate the plate gently and incubate for 5 minutes in CO2 incubator.
5. Tap the plate gently and look under the microscope for detachment of cells (repeat incubation for few more minutes if detachment is not complete), detached cells will become round in shape.
6. Add 7 ml of fresh medium, mix gently with pipette and deliver into 15 ml tube.
7. Take last few drops in an eppendorf tube for cell count.
8. Centrifuge and discard the supernatant from the 15 ml tube.
9. To the pellet add 6ml of medium and mix gently (for 6 plates, 1ml per plate, 2-3 million cells per plate).
10. Deliver 9 ml of fresh medium to each 6 plates (5 plates for treatment with drug and 1 plate for storage).
11. Add 1 ml of mixed cells to each plate. Mix gently by rotating and look under the microscope.
12. Incubate the plates and maintain the cell lines.

Cell Count (Hycor –Kova slides with grid or cell counting chamber)

1. Take 90 µl of Tryphan blue and 10 µl of well mixed cells in an eppendorf tube.
2. Mix well and load the chamber. Wait for few seconds for the cells to settle.
3. Count the three diagonal squares and use the formula to calculate the total no. of cells in a plate.

$$\text{Total no. of cells} = \frac{\text{No. of cells counted}}{\text{No. of squares}} \times 10^4 \times \text{dilution factor} \times \text{total volume}$$

No. of squares – 3; Dilution factor – 10; Total volume – 10 ml

e.g. No. of cells counted =3

Total no. of cells = 10 million cells / Plate

Preparation of cell lysis buffer: (according to Nucleospin RNA extraction kit)

For 5 x 10⁶ eukaryotic cultured cells - 350 µl RA1 buffer + 3.5 µl β-Mercaptoethanol

1 confluent cell plate has ≈ 12 x 10⁶ cells

Therefore 1ml of lysis buffer is needed per plate. Prepare 1 volume extra. For 5 plates prepare 6ml of lysis buffer + 60 µl of β-Mercaptoethanol. Vortex and keep it ready.

1. **Protein estimation:** Take 2 ml of medium from the plate, centrifuge and take 1 ml of supernatant in an eppendorf tube and store at -20°C for estimation of protein induced by the action of the drug using ELISA.
2. Remove the entire medium and add 3 ml of PBS and rotate the plate gently to wash the cells.
3. Remove the PBS and add 3 ml of 0.05% Trypsin EDTA, rotate the plate gently and incubate for 5 minutes in CO₂ incubator.
4. Tap the plate gently and look under the microscope for detachment of cells (repeat incubation for few more minutes if detachment is not complete)
5. Add 7 ml of fresh medium, mix gently with pipette and deliver into 15 ml tube.
6. Centrifuge and discard the supernatant from the 15 ml tube.
7. Immediately add 1 ml of lysis buffer to the pellet and vortex for few seconds to make it homogenous.
8. Store at -80°C to extract the RNA (use within 1 month)

Freezing the cell lines:

1. Check the cells under microscope for confluence (>80 %).
2. Label the cryovials with pencil.
3. Remove the entire medium and add 3 ml of PBS and rotate the plate gently to wash the cells.
4. Remove the PBS and add 3 ml of 0.05% Trypsin EDTA, rotate the plate gently and incubate for 5 minutes in CO₂ incubator.
5. Tap the plate gently and look under the microscope for detachment of cells (repeat incubation for few more minutes if detachment is not complete).
6. Add 7 ml of fresh medium mix gently with pipette and deliver into 15 ml tube.
7. Take last few drops in an eppendorf tube and count the number of cells.
8. Centrifuge and discard the supernatant from the 15 ml tube.
9. Add 10 ml of fresh medium to the pellet, mix gently with pipette and take required quantity.
10. Approximately 3 million cells / vial are needed. Therefore for 2 vials 6 million cells are needed. For e.g. if 2 million cells/ml is present during cell count, take 3 ml of medium with cells in a 15 ml tube.
11. Centrifuge and discard the supernatant.
12. To the pellet add 0.9 ml of medium and 100 µl of DMSO (10%). Mix gently and distribute 0.5 ml to each cryovial.
13. Keep the vials immersed up to the level of the solution in a container with 70% ethanol. Keep at -80°C overnight. (Ethanol will bring down temperature slowly)
14. Store at -186°C in the liquid nitrogen for 1 year. If needed subculture after 1 year and maintain the cell lines.

Cloning protocol:

Objective: Cloning of *CYP2C19* promoter region into *pGL-3* basic vector

Steps in cloning:

Check for all the reagents, consumables for each step ahead and plan accordingly, once you start with one step continue till the confirmation of insertion and perform transformation. Perfect planning and arrangements of consumables, reagents, plates (autoclaved) is important.

1. Amplify the insert and purify by gel elution protocol.
2. Prepare the vector and the insert for cloning, ie. Digest the vector and insert with restriction enzymes as per the protocol given by enzyme manufacturers (double digestion [if compatible buffer is available for both the enzymes/digestion with individual enzymes])
3. Check for effective digestion of vector and insert by running in 0.8% agarose gel.
4. Treat vector with CIP or alkaline PO_4 tase to dephosphorylate the ends, which will prevent its reannealing / closure.
5. Then purify both the vector (after CIP treatment) and insert by running in agarose gel and by elution.
6. Prepare a ligation reaction by using DNA ligase enzyme, with appropriate quantities of enzyme, insert (check the other protocol for formula) and vector (as recommended by commercial sources)
7. Check for effective ligation by running the vector, ligation mixture, linearized vector, and insert in separate wells in 0.8% agarose gel.
8. Elute the vector+insert by gel elution.
9. Prepare the competent cells (as per the protocol given below, other protocol for electro competent cells can also be used but for our lab chemical competent cells procedure should be used, which do not require additional equipment except for a water bath)
10. Transform the vector+insert into competent cells (transformation protocol)
11. Maintain the culture of competent cells, and prepare/ extract the plasmid from the culture as per your requirement (miniprep for checking transformation efficiency, and Maxiprep for performing Transfection experiments).
12. Troubleshoot at each and every step for efficient cloning (reagents, enzymes, buffers, temperatures, ligation bath time, overnight incubation, etc).

Cloning into *pGL3* basic vector:

1. Amplify the Insert with KpnI restriction site incorporated primer
2. Digest the Insert & Vector with KpnI and HindIII as per the protocol.
3. Treat Vector with alkaline Phosphatase (CIPing)
4. Purify Vector & Insert by phenol chloroform method/gel extraction and run on agarose gel to check the quantity
5. Set up the ligation reaction as per the protocol
6. Transform the ligation mixture as per the protocol
7. Pick the colonies and do the miniprep and digest the miniprep as per the protocol
8. After confirmation of insert in plasmid, prepare maxiprep and add RNase and store at -80 degrees.

Restriction enzymes:

1. *KpnI* (G_↓GTAC[^]C) 5/1; *SacI* (G_↓AGCT[^]C) 11/7 in vector sequence.
2. *Kpn I* cuts PGL-3 basic vector at position 1 and Insert at position 5 lies within the incorporated site
Kpn I = GTAC/C produces 3' overhang- GTAC
C/CATGG
3. *Hind III* (AAGCTT)cuts PGL-3 basic vector at position 53 and in insert cuts at position 1635-8 leaving 70bp

CAACCCAGTCAGCTCCTTCCGGTGGGCGCGGGGCATGACTATCGTCGCCGCACTTATGACTG
TCTTCTTTATCATGCAACTCGTAGGACAGGTGCCGGCAGCGCTCTTCCGCTTCCCTCGCTCACT
GACTCGCTGCGCTCGGTTCGGTTCGGCTGCGGCGAGCGGTATCAGCTCACTCAAAGGCGGTAA
TACGGTTATCCACAGAATCAGGGGATAACGCAGGAAAGAACATGTGAGCAAAAAGGCCAGC
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TGACGAGCATCACAAAAATCGACGCTCAAGTCAGAGGTGGCGAAACCCGACAGGACTATA
AAGATAACCAGGCGTTTTCCCTGGAAGCTCCCTCGTGCCTCTCCTGTTCCGACCCTGCCGC
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CGACTTATCGCCACTGGCAGCAGCCACTGGTAACAGGATTAGCAGAGCGAGGTATGTAGGC
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AAAAAGGATCTCAAGAAGATCCTTTGATCTTTTTCTACGGGGTCTGACGCTCAGTGGAACGA
AACTCACGTTAAGGGATTTTGGTCATGAGATTATCAAAAAGGATCTTCACCTAGATCCTTT
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GCCTGACTCCCCGTCGTGTAGATAACTACGATACGGGAGGGCTTACCATCTGGCCCCAGTGC
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CAACGATCAAGGCGAGTTACATGATCCCCATGTTGTGCAAAAAAGCGGTTAGCTCCTTCG
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AACAAACTAGCAAAATAGGCTGTCCCCAGTGCAAGTGCAGGTGCCAGAACATTTCTCTATC
GATA

Insert: CYP2C19 promoter**pGL3-CYP2C19 clone:6400bp**

GGTACCCAGCAGACACCATGTTCTTGGCTACAGTACTGAATCTTCAAGGCTCAGCCTCCTCA
TTCCTGAGATGGGTCAATTTTATTGTAAGCAAAGGCAATTGAGAGATTCCAAAGGGATATG
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 TCCACGTTCTTTAATAGTGGACTCTTGTTCAAAACCTGGAACAACACTCAACCCTATCTCGGT
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 TCAGGCTGCGCAACTGTTGGGAAGGGCGATCGGTGCGGGCCTCTTCGCTATTACGCCAGCC
 CAAGCTACCATGATAAGTAAGTAATATTAAGGTACGGGAGGTAAGTGGAGCGGCCGCAATA
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 ACGCTCTCCATCAAAAACAAAACGAAACAAAACAACTAGCAAAATAGGCTGTCCCCAGTGC
 AAGTGCAGGTGCCAGAACATTTCTCTATCGATA

Amplification and Purification of Insert (CYP2C19 promoter region):

Materials required for amplification of Insert:

1. Template genomic DNA (50ng/ul)
2. primers (F-primer with KpnI restriction site incorporated, and R-primer pEX12)(0.5ul of each primer)
3. dNTPs (2.0 ul of 2.5mM)
4. Proofreading Taq DNA polymerase(2U-5U)
5. MgCl₂ (3mM including 1.5mM of buffer) and DMSO (0.1%)
6. MilliQ water(autoclaved)

Materials required for amplification check:

1. Agarose (1.5% gel)
2. TAE buffer(1X)

3. EtBr (Ethidium bromide)
4. 1 kb DNA ladder
5. Dye

Note: After amplification load all the PCR product on agarose gel and elute and purify by phenol-chloroform extraction or by using Gel extraction kit, and store it at room temperature.

Gel elution protocol:

1. Run the PCR product or Plasmid on 0.8% agarose gel in 0.5X TAE buffer along with ladder
2. Cut the band after visualizing on transilluminator and keep it on a clean & sterile glass plate
3. Chop it with a sterile scalp blade vertically into fine pieces
4. Take a 1.5 ml sterile microfuge tube and put the chopped band into it
5. Add 250 μ l of Saturated phenol to it, Mix gently or vortex gently and keep it at -80 degrees overnight
6. **Next Day:** Add 150 μ l of MilliQ water and mix in hand by inverting gently and then centrifuge it at 12000rpm for 15 min at 4 degrees
7. Transfer the supernatant to another tube
8. Add equal volume of 24:1 (Chloroform: isoamyl alcohol) and mix it for 20 min gently and then centrifuge at 12000rpm for 15 min at 4 degrees
9. Transfer the supernatant to another tube and add 1/10th of sodium acetate (3M pH5.3) and mix gently, then add two volumes of ethanol
10. Keep it at -80°C for at least 2 hrs (4 hrs)
11. After take out the sample and keep it at room temperature, then centrifuge at 12000 rpm for 15 min at 4°C, then discard the supernatant gently without disturbing the pellet
12. Add 500 μ l of 70% ethanol tap it gently (dislodge the pellet) and then centrifuge at 12000 rpm for 15 min at 4 degrees
13. Discard the supernatant, and Dry it on bench top for 10 min
14. Add required amount of MilliQ water or 1X TE and incubate at room temperature for 2 hrs and store at -20 degrees.

Elution by using Column:

1. Elute the fragments (insert, vector after digestion or PCR product) after running in 0.8% agarose gel in TAE buffer
2. Chop it properly
3. Transfer to a column, you may add few drops of 1XTE buffer
4. Centrifuge at 10000 rpm for 2-3 min (for about 5 min)
5. Take out the column from the tube and measure the volume of liquid with DNA.
6. Then add 1/10th of sodium acetate and 2.5 volumes of 100 % ethanol. Keep it at -20 °C overnight or at -80 °C for 2-3 Hrs
7. Centrifuge at 13,000 rpm for 15-30 min and discard the supernatant.

8. Wash it with 70% ethanol. Add 0.5ml of ethanol and centrifuge at 13000 rpm for 15-20 min and discard the supernatant
9. Then air dry the pellet with caps open for 10 min. then add required volume of milliQ water or 1XTE.

Purification by traditional Phenol-Chloroform method:

Purification of insert, plasmid can be done by this method but care should be taken that all reagents are of molecular biology grade and pure without any contamination and gentle operation is required to prevent fragmentation. Pipette tips can be cut by scissors so that shear stress on DNA can be lowered, you can add milliQ water to sample before processing the sample to minimize the loss of DNA and to prevent shear stress during the process.

1. Add around 200 µl of MilliQ water to 100 ul of sample
2. Add equal volume of Phenol to the sample (if sample if of 300 ul add 300 ul of saturated phenol) and then gently mix it for 10 min (5 rpm on rotator)
3. Then centrifuge it at 12000rpm for 15 min at 4 degrees
4. Transfer the supernatant into another tube
5. Add equal volume of Chloroform : isoamyl alcohol or octanol (24:1), mix it gently for 20 min
6. Centrifuge at 12000rpm for 15 in at 4°C
7. Transfer the supernatant to another tube and add 1/10th of sodium acetate (3M pH5.3) and mix gently, then add two volumes of ethanol
8. Keep it at -80 degrees for at least 2 hrs (4 hrs)
9. After take out the sample and keep it at room temperature , then centrifuge at 12000 rpm for 15 min at 4 degrees, then discard the supernatant gently without disturbing the pellet
10. Add 500ul of 70% ethanol tap it gently(dislodge the pellet) and then centrifuge at 12000 rpm for 15 in at 4 °C
11. Discard the supernatant, and dry it on bench top for 10 min
12. Add required amount of MilliQ water or 1X TE and incubate at room temperature for 2 hrs and store at -20 degrees.

Restriction digestion of Insert & Vector with Kpn I and Hind III:

With Kpn I

	<u>Insert</u>	<u>Vector</u>
DNA (Insert/plasmid)	15ul	5ul (1ug/ul)i.e.5ug
NEB Buffer3	4ul	5ul
10XBSA	4ul	5ul
KpnI	2ul	2ul
MilliQ	15ul	33ul
Total reaction volume:	40ul	50ul

Incubate at 37 degrees overnight, check it on agarose gel for digestion.

With Hind III

	<u>Insert</u>	<u>Vector</u>
Digested product with KpnI	38ul	50ul
NEB Buffer2	7ul	8ul
10XBSA	0ul	0ul
HindIII	2ul	2ul
MilliQ	33ul	40ul
Total reaction volume:	80ul	100ul

After digestion check both the products (Insert & vector) for complete digestion, and treat the vector with alkaline phosphatase (calf intestinal alkaline phosphatase, CIP), after CIPing deactivate the CIP by using 0.25 M EDTA, and 10 % SDS, and keep at 42 degrees for 45 min.

Use Buffer and 10XBSA in 1X concentration (final concentration in reaction mixture) and if the digestion is not proper try with high amount of enzyme and check for quality of all reagents used.

CIPING:

CIP enzymes: 10 units/ μ l; make 1:10 dilution so that 1 unit/ μ l will be the final concentration. Use 2.5 ul so 2.5 units will be using for treatment.

Digested plasmid DNA	50 μ l
10X CIP buffer 2	5 μ l
CIP enzyme	2.5 μ l (use 0.5 units per ug of DNA)
MQ water	42.5 μ l
Total volume	100 μl

Then incubate the reaction mixture at 37 degrees for one hour and then add

0.25 M EDTA	2 μ l
10% SDS	2 μ l

And incubate at 45°C for one hour. (You may also add 200 ul of MQ water) then extract the plasmid from the reaction mixture by phenol chloroform method.

In brief: Add equal volume of saturated phenol, gently mix it for 10 min, centrifuge at 12000 rpm for 15 min, transfer the supernatant, and add equal volumes of chloroform: isoamyl alcohol (24:1), mix it for 20 min and then follow the same procedure given under phenol-chloroform extraction method.

Preparation of chemical competent cells:**Preparation of 2XYT medium:**

2XYT medium = 10 g of yeast extract

16 g of Bacotryptone

5 g NaCl dissolve in 200-300 ml of water distilled water.

And make up to 1 ltr by distilled water and autoclave it.

For agar plating, add 20 g of agar powder per litre of solution. i.e. 2g for 100ml of medium And plate around 20ml in one plate (use four plates at a time as a reserve, unused plates can be kept at 4 degrees)

- First prepare 100ml of 2XYT, add 2g of agar powder, then autoclave it.
- After autoclaving, transfer it into 56 0 C water bath for 2 Hrs, then pour into plates.
- After 2 Hrs(approx) it will solidify (after pouring into plates show the flame over the plate and covering plate for sterilization
- Streak the glycerol stock cells by taking with a needle. (During streaking, first red heat the loop needle 2-3 times, then just touch the needle (tip of the needle) to the media late, then take a full loop of bacteria from glycerol streak and streak form the corner only, then again red heat the needle and streak from the corner only, and select only one area where uniform growth is there and pick them for preparation of competent cells.
- When preparing medium with antibiotics, keep the medium after autoclaving n water bath at 55 degrees and before plating bring and add antibiotics when it is cool and then you plate into the culture plates.
- Overnight incubated plates can be stores at 4 degrees after sealing with parafilm.

Chemical Competent Cell protocol:preparation

First you prepare plates without antibiotic and then streak the culture (DH 10 beta or DH 5 alpha or JM109 cells and incubate at 37 degrees overnight and then you pick colony from the grown culture)

1st day:

1. Inoculate single colony of DH10B or DH5Alpha into a 2ml of 2XYT medium and incubate overnight at 37°C with shaking at 250 rpm (No ampicillin in medium) Take a tooth pick or pipette tip and pick the colony and place in tube.

Next day:

2. Inoculate next day at 1:100 (100ml for e.g. dilute 2XYT (No ampicillin). Keep it shaking at 37°C until the OD₆₀₀ is about 0.4 (it will take 2-4 Hrs to reach this OD; 2.5 hrs usually)(this is to check for the Growth phase of the bacteria; Log phase)
3. Immediately transfer the flask on ice completely covered and keep it for 10 min
4. Spin the bacteria at 3000 rpm at 4°C for 15 min in a pre chilled centrifuge
5. Discard completely the supernatant and re suspend the pellet in half the volume (50ml for log; 25 ml for each tube) of pre chilled sterile 100mM CaCl₂, keep it on ice for 30 min, dislodge the pellets by vortexing (CaCl₂ .2H₂O has been used if you are using other reagent 5 H₂O calculate the amount required on the basis of mol wt accordingly.
6. Centrifuge at 4°C at 3000 rpm for 15 min
7. Completely discard supernatant and resuspend the pellet in 1/20th (5ml, i.e. 2.5 ml in each tube) of sterile 85mM cacl₂ containing 15% glycerol.
8. Aliquot into sterile microfuge tubes, at 100 µl and 500 µl placed directly on ice
9. Freeze the tubes at -70°C

Calculations:

Step - 5: CaCl₂ calculations: Total volume 100 ml is divided into two 50 ml

Half the volume means for 100 ml- 50ml since it was divided into 50 ml add 25 ml in each tube. (Since you have taken two tubes and each tube is with 50 ml)

Step 7: 1/20th of 100 ml (total volume) means 5ml but it was divided into two tubes, so in each tube add 2.5 ml.

Glycerol Stock preparation: (All procedures dealing with cultures should be done at sterile environment in laminar hood, over the flame)

15% of glycerol (sterilized)

Directly from culture take 850µl of culture + add 150 µl of glycerol (sterilized)

Then this 1ml mixture should be vortexed

And put a parafilm around it, and store at -80 °C for future use (competent cells stock, when ever required take them, thaw and grow culture in medium)

Transformation protocol:

1. Take 100ul of DH10B or DH5 Alpha chemical competent cells (free zed at -80 °C)
2. Thaw it on ice by keeping in ice for 5 min
3. Add 1ul (in one tube)and 2 ul(in another tube) of vector (commercial) shall be added(vector i.e. cloned /uncloned should be diluted to 1 ng/ul concentration and then add to competent cells; whenever you are transforming ligation mixtures transform 1 ul of ligation mixture, 1 ul of 1:1 diluted ligation mixture, 1 ul of 1:4 diluted ligation mixture, and 2 ul of undiluted ligation mixture and check for efficient transformation) you can add 1 ul of DMSO to increase efficiency
4. Tap gently to mix the DNA
5. Incubate on ICE for 45 min
6. Give heat shock at 42 °C for 80 sec (60-90 sec), then it was immediately transferred to ice and mixed in 0.9ml SOC (0.9ml 2XYT media which was pre heated to 37 degrees by keeping it in water bath at 37 degrees). (this step is very crucial)
7. The tubes were then incubated at 37 °C on an orbital shaker at 260 rpm for 60-90 min (approx 2 Hrs)
8. Take 200µl of the above mixture (transformed) and plate on agar medium with ampicillin/kanamycin (antibiotic) (for plating use glass beads or inoculating loop)
9. Result analysed after 16-24 Hrs (2XYT media for culture), check for colonies, translucent for DH 10 beta.

Equation for transformation efficiency (cfu/µg)

Transformant cfu = No. of bacteria colonies × dilution ratio × original transformation volume/plated volume

Example: If 21 colonies are observed on the plate, before plating, the transformed competent cells were diluted 10000 times, and the original transformation volume was 100 µl, 50 µl was used to plate, then transformant cfu is: $21 \times 10000 \times 100 / 50 = 4.2 \times 10^5$

Transformation efficiency = Transformant cfu /plasmid DNA (µg).

If the plasmid DNA was added 0.5 µl (1µg/µl), the transformation efficiency = $4.2 \times 10^5 / 0.5 = 8.4 \times 10^5$ cfu/µg.

PLASMID ISOLATION: (mini prep from 2ml of culture):

- pick a colony with toothpick or pipette tip and inoculate in 2ml of culture with antibiotic (ampicillin/kanamycin 100ug/ml final concentration and incubate overnight at 37 degrees on an orbital shaker with 250 rpm)
- when you are using liquid culture inoculate 100 - 500 ul of culture into 2ml or 100 ml culture with antibiotic respectively
- 1.5 ml of cultured bacteria is taken in a micro centrifuge (eppendorf) tube of 1.5 ml capacity. And incubate for 5 min at 37°C
- Shift or place it on ice for further steps
- Centrifuge at 7000rpm for 5 min at 4°C
- Discard the supernatant (not completely, 50ul must remain with pellet), and mix the pellet using a rotor/spinix rotor-vertex mixer, completely mix so that no pellet will stick to the tube.
- To the pellet add 300 ul of TENS(pH 8.0) TENS(tris EDTA NaCl SDS)
- Place it on ice for 5-10min
- Vertex it for few minutes
- 150 ul of 3Msodium acetate pH 5.2 should be added to it
- Vortex slightly
- Place it on ice for 5-10 min, then centrifuge at 12000 rpm for 15 min at 4°C
- Pour collected supernatant; add 0.7 vol (350ul) of isopropyl alcohol. (0.7 vol means for 1 ul of supernatant add 0.7 ul of isopropyl alcohol)
- Mix it and keep it on ice for 1 min
- Centrifuge at 12000 rpm for 10-15min at 4°C
- Discard the supernatant
- Wash the pellet in 500 ul of 70% ethanol
- Centrifuge at 12000 rpm for 15min at 4°C
- Discard the supernatant
- Air dry it at room temperature, add 20ul of 1XTE buffer and store at -20 °C

MAXIPREP: (For 100 ml or 50 ml culture)-

1. Freeze the bacteria, then take 850µl of bacteria+ add 150µl of sterile glycerol.
2. keep 500µl of inoculated in 100 ml media for overnight incubation in incubator at 37 degrees C
3. transfer the 100 ml of broth to 2-tubes
4. spin it at 7000rpm for 5 min at 4°C
5. discard the supernatant, add 10 ml of P1 to one tube and vortex it and transfer to another tube, vortex again so that pellet will suspend completely(for precipitation)
6. vortex and keep it on ice for 10min
7. add 10ml of P2, keep it on ice for 5-7 min (this step is crucial do not exceed 7 min , maximum 10 min , not more than that)
8. add 10 ml of P3, mix by inversion keep it on ice for 10min

9. spin at 12000 rpm for 15 min at 4 degrees
10. Transfer the supernatant to another 50 ml tube
11. add 0.7 vol of chilled isopropyl alcohol
12. keep on ice for 5 min
13. spin at 10,000 rpm for 15-20min at 4 OC
14. discard the supernatant
15. wash the pellet with with 1 ml of 70% ethanol
16. spin at 7000 rpm for 10 min at 4 OC
17. Bench dry, dissolve it in 0.5 ml of TE

Note: Whenever you are preparing plasmid dry the pellet for only 10 min (Bench dry) and then add TE buffer accordingly (usually 25-50ul), check on gel and then dilute accordingly.

PLASMID DNA PURIFICATION using QUIAGEN plasmid mini and maxi kits:

Before starting extraction procedure:

1. Add the provided RNase A solution to buffer P1 before use. Use one vial of RNase A (centrifuge briefly before use) per bottle of buffer P1 to give a final concentration of 100ug/ml
2. Check buffer P2 for SDS precipitation due to low storage temperatures. If necessary dissolve the SDS by warming at 4 °C.
3. Pre chill buffer P3 at 4°C
4. Optional: Add the provided lyse blue reagent to buffer P1 and mix before use. Use one vial lyse blue (centrifuge briefly before use) per bottle of buffer P1 to achieve a 1:1000 dilution. Lyse blue provides visual identification of optimum buffer mixing thereby preventing the common handling errors that lead to inefficient cell lysis and incomplete precipitation of SDS, genomic DNA, and cell debris.

Procedure:

1. Pick a single colony from a freshly streaked selective plate and inoculate a starter culture of 2 ml LB medium containing the appropriate selective antibiotic. Incubate for approx 8Hrs at 37 °C with vigorous shaking (approx 300 rpm) (we can use 250 rpm)
2. Take 100-200 ul of culture to 100 ml of LB medium. Grow at 37 °C for 12-16 Hrs with vigorous shaking (250rpm). Use a flask or vessel with volume of at least 4 times volume of the culture. The culture should reach a cell density of approximately $3-4 \times 10^9$ cells/ml, which corresponds to a pellet wet weight of approximately 3 g/ lt of medium.
3. Harvest the bacterial cells by centrifugation at 6000rpm for 15 min at 4 °C (divide 100 ml into two 50 ml tubes)If you wish to stop the protocol and continue later, freeze the cell pellets at -20 °C
4. Resuspend the bacterial pellet in 10ml buffer P1 (5ml each to 50ml tube i.e. 5+5) for efficient lysis it is important to use a vessel that is large enough to allow complete mixing of the lysis buffers. Ensure that RNase A has been added to buffer P1. If lyse blue reagent has been added to buffer P1, vigorously shake buffer bottle before use to ensure lyse blue particles are completely resuspended. The bacteria should be resuspended completely by vortexing or precipitating up and down until no cell clumps remain.

5. Add 10 ml (5 ml to each tube i.e. 5+5 for tube1+tube2) buffer P2 , mix thoroughly by vigorously inverting the sealed tube 4-6 six times, and incubate at room temperature (15 -25 0C) for 5 min. Do not vortex, as this will result in shearing of genomic DNA. The lysate should appear viscous. Do not allow the lysis reaction to proceed for more than 5min. After use, the bottle containing buffer P2 should be closed immediately to avoid acidification from CO₂ in the air.

If lyse blue has been added to buffer P1 the cell suspension will turn blue after addition of buffer P2. Mixing should result in a homogenously colored suspension. If the suspension contains localized colourless regions or if brownish, cell clumps are still visible, continue mixing the solution until a homogenously colored solution is achieved.

6. Add 10ml (5+5) of chilled buffer P3. Mix immediately and thoroughly by vigorously inverting 4-6 times, and incubate on ice for 15 min or 20 min or 30min.

Precipitation is enhanced by using chilled buffer P3 and by incubating on ice. After addition of buffer P3, a puffy white material forms and the Lysate becomes less viscous-the precipitated material contains genomic DNA, proteins, cell debris and KDS. The lysate should be mixed thoroughly to ensure even potassium dodecyl sulphate precipitation (KDS). If the mixture still appears viscous, more mixing is required to completely neutralize the solution.

If lyse blue reagent has been used, the suspension should be mixed until all trace of blue has gone and the suspension is colorless. A homogenous colorless suspension indicates that the SDS has been effectively precipitated.

7. Centrifuge at 20,000 rpm for 30 min at 4°C. Remove supernatant containing plasmid, remove supernatant containing plasmid DNA promptly.(12000 rpm for 15 min)

Before loading the centrifuge, the sample should be mixed again. Centrifugation should be performed in non-glass tubes (e.g. polypropylene) after centrifugation, the supernatant should be clear.

8. Centrifuge the supernatant again at 20,000 rpm for 15 min at 4 °C. Remove supernatant containing plasmid DNA promptly.

9. Equilibrate QUIAGEN-tip 500 by applying 10ml of buffer QBT and allow the column to empty by gravity flow. Flow of buffer will begin automatically by reduction in surface tension due to the presence of detergent in equilibration buffer. Allow the QUIAGEN-tip to drain completely. QUIAGEN-tips can be left unattended, since the flow of buffer will stop when the meniscus reaches the upper frit in the column.

10. Apply the supernatant from step-8 to the QUIAGEN-tip and allow it to enter the resin by gravity flow.

The supernatant should be loaded onto the QUIAGEN-tip promptly. If it is left for too long and becomes turbid due to further precipitation of protein, it must be centrifuged again or filtered before loading to prevent clogging of the QUIAGEN-tip

11. Wash the QUIAGEN-tip with 2X30 ml buffer QC. Allow buffer QC to move through the QUIAGEN-tip by gravity flow. The first wash is sufficient to remove all contaminants in the majority of plasmid DNA preparations. The 2nd wash is especially necessary when large culture volumes or bacterial strains producing large amounts of carbohydrates are used.

12. Elute DNA with 15 ml buffer QF

Collect the eluate in a 50ml or 15ml tube. Use of polycarbonate centrifuge tubes is not recommended as polycarbonate is not resistant to the alcohol used in subsequent steps.

13. Precipitate DNA by adding 10.5 ml (0.7 volumes) of isopropyl alcohol (RT) to the eluted DNA. Mix and centrifuge immediately at 15 – 20,000 rpm for 30 min at 4°C. Carefully decant supernatant.

14. Wash the DNA pellet with 5 ml of room temp 70% ethanol and centrifuge at 20,000 rpm for 10min, carefully decant the supernatant without disturbing the pellets
15. Air dry the pellet for 5-10min, and redissolve the DNA in a suitable volume of buffer (e.g. TE buffer, pH 8.0 or 10mM Tris-Cl pH 8.5).
16. Check the recovery by running in 0.8 % agarose gel.

Ligation reaction calculations and protocol for CYP2C19 promoter ligation into PGL-3 Basic vector:

Always setup a control reaction (without insert) with standard to check the ligation efficacy.

Reagents	Control	Standard reaction1	STD Reaction 2
MilliQ water	16 µl	12.5µl	14µl
Insert	0	26.6ng (3µl)	2µl (20ng)
Vector	25ng (1µl)	25ng (1µl)	12.5ng (1µl)
DNA ligase	1µl	1.5µl	1µl
Buffer	2µl	2µl	2µl
Total reaction volume	20µl	20µl	20µl

(Use diluted vector so that 1 µl contains 25 ng, or 1 µl contains 12.5 ng)

Incubate at appropriate temperature (16 degrees overnight) or as per the information sheet given along with ligase.

Calculation of amount insert required for ligation:

(ng of vector x size of insert in kb/size of vector in kb) x (molar ratio of insert: vector) = ng of insert

Mass of cyp2c19 promoter required =	25 X 1714/4818) X 3:1= 26.68 ng
Vector DNA (4818 bp)	25.00ng
Insert DNA (1714)	26.68ng

Reagents/ consumables required for Cloning:

Saturated phenol, 100% ethanol, Isopropyl alcohol, 70% ethanol, Chloroform: Isoamyl alcohol or Octanol(24:1), 3M sodium acetate pH: 5.2, 100mM Calcium Chloride, Glycerol, 85mM Calcium chloride with 15% glycerol, TENS buffer, 10% SDS solution, 0.25 M EDTA solution, 0.5M EDTA, 1X TE buffer, 10X BSA, NEB buffer 2, NEB buffer 3, Alkaline phosphatase, KpnI, HindIII, Xba I, DNA ligase, Baco tryptone, Yeast extract, Sodium Chloride, Potassium chloride, Glucose, Magnesium chloride, Ampicillin Insert (purified PCR products), PGL-3 Basic vector, Primers (forward and reverse), Quiagen miniprep, maxiprep, and Gel extraction kits, DH 10 beta chemical competent cells/other competent cells, Autoclaved tips (2-20ul, 1000ul), Autoclaved culture tubes (15ml, cotton plugged), Autoclaved conical flasks (cotton plugged), Sterile 50 ml tubes for maxiprep, Pipettes, Water bath, Ice box and ICE

Microfuge tubes 1.5 ml and 2.0 ml , autoclaved, Glass beads, Inoculating loop, Thermometer, Cotton, Gauge cloth, stopwatch, Marker pens, Cello tape, parafilm.

Reagents preparation:

SOC medium:

2.0g Bacto®-tryptone + 0.5g Bacto®-yeast extract + 1ml 1M NaCl + 0.25ml 1M KCl + 1ml Mg²⁺ stock 1M MgCl₂ · 6H₂O, 1M MgSO₄ · 7H₂O filter-sterilized , 1ml of 2M glucose filter-sterilized. Bring to 100ml with distilled water.

Procedure: Add Bacto®-tryptone, Bacto®-yeast extract, NaCl and KCl to 97ml distilled water. Stir to dissolve. Autoclave and cool to room temperature. Add 2M Mg²⁺ stock and 2M glucose stock, each to a final concentration 20mM. Filter the complete medium through a 0.2µm filter unit. The pH should be 7.0

SOC medium for 1000ml:

Deionized H₂O, to 950 ml

Tryptone, 20 g + yeast extract, 5 g + NaCl, 0.5 g

Shake until the solutes have dissolved. Add 10 ml of a 250 mM solution of KCl. (This solution is made by dissolving 1.86 g of KCl in 100 ml of deionized H₂O.) Adjust the pH of the medium to 7.0 with 5 N NaOH (approx. 0.2 ml). Adjust the volume of the solution to 1 litre with deionized H₂O. Sterilize by autoclaving for 20 minutes at 15 Psi (1.05 kg/cm²) on liquid cycle. Just before use, add 5 ml of a sterile solution of 2 M MgCl₂. (This solution is made by dissolving 19 g of MgCl₂ in 90 ml of deionized H₂O. Adjust the volume of the solution to 100 ml with deionized H₂O and sterilize by autoclaving for 20 minutes at 15 psi [1.05 kg/cm²] on liquid cycle.)

Autoclave the medium. After the medium has been autoclaved, allow it to cool to 60°C or less. Add 20 ml of a sterile 1 M solution of glucose. (This solution is made by dissolving 18 g of glucose in 90 ml of deionized H₂O. After the sugar has dissolved, adjust the volume of the solution to 100 ml with deionized H₂O and sterilize by passing it through a 0.22-µm filter.)

1M Glucose solution:

18g of glucose dissolve in 90 ml of deionised water, make upto 100 ml and filter sterilize with 0.22 µ filter

Preparation of 2XYT medium:

2XYT medium = ADD

10 g of yeast extract

16 g of Bacotryptone

5 g NaCl dissolved in 200-300 ml of water distilled water.

And make up to 1 litre by distilled water and autoclave it.

TENS buffer:

10N NaOH - 1ml

20% SDS 1ml

Alkaline Lysis Solution II

0.2 N NaOH (freshly diluted from a 10 N stock)

1% (w/v) SDS

Prepare solution II

Alkaline Lysis Solution III

5 M potassium acetate, 60.0 ml

Glacial acetic acid, 11.5 ml

H₂O, 28.5 ml

The resulting solution is 3 M with respect to potassium and 5 M with respect to acetate. Store the solution at 4°C and transfer it to an ice bucket just before use.

100mM calcium chloride solution:

1.47 g of calcium chloride dehydrate dissolve in 100 ml of sterile distilled water and auto alave it before use.

85mM cacl₂ containing 15% glycerol:

Take 85 ml of 100mM calcium chloride and add 15 ml of glycerol. Or 8.5 ml + 1.5 ml of glycerol.

10% SDS: 10 g of SDS dissolve in 100 ml and aliquot and keep at 4 degrees

20% SDS: Dissolve 20 g of SDS in 100ml of water

0.25 M EDTA:

Dissolve 7.3 g of disodium edetate in 80 ml of sterile distilled water and adjust the pH to 8.0 and make upto 100ml.

Tris-Cl

Dissolve 121.1 g of Tris base in 800 ml of H₂O. Adjust the pH to the desired value by adding concentrated HCl.

pH HCl

7.4 70 ml

7.6 60 ml

8.0 42 ml

(1 M) Allow the solution to cool to room temperature before making final adjustments to the pH. Adjust the volume of the solution to 1 liter with H₂O. Dispense into aliquots and sterilize by autoclaving. If the 1 M solution has a yellow color, discard it and obtain Tris of better quality. The pH of Tris solutions is temperature-dependent and decreases approx. 0.03 pH units for each 1°C increase in temperature. For example, a 0.05 M solution has pH values of 9.5, 8.9, and 8.6 at 5°C, 25°C, and 37°C, respectively.

PBS (Phosphate-buffered Saline) :

Dissolve 8 g of NaCl, 0.2 g of KCl, 1.44 g of Na₂HPO₄, and 0.24 g of KH₂PO₄ in 800 ml of distilled H₂O. Adjust the pH to 7.4 with HCl. Add H₂O to 1 liter. Dispense the solution into aliquots and sterilize them by autoclaving for 20 minutes at 15 psi (1.05 kg/cm²) on liquid cycle or by filter sterilization.

Store the buffer at room temperature. If necessary, PBS may be supplemented with 1 mM CaCl₂ and 0.5 mM MgCl₂, but for cell culture we do not use magnesium and calcium ions.

0.5M EDTA (pH 8.0):

Add 186.1 g of disodium EDTA•2H₂O to 800 ml of H₂O. Stir vigorously on a magnetic stirrer. Adjust the pH to 8.0 with NaOH (approx. 20 g of NaOH pellets). Dispense into aliquots and sterilize by autoclaving. The disodium salt of EDTA will not go into solution until the pH of the solution is adjusted to approx. 8.0 by the addition of NaOH.

TE Buffer:

100 mM Tris-Cl (desired pH)-take 10 ml of 1M Tris cl and dilute it to 100ml

10 mM EDTA (pH 8.0) -2.92 g of EDTA. 2 H₂O dissolve in 100 ml pH8.0 with NaOH.

Store the buffer at room temperature

Protocol for transfection (using lipofectamine 2000™ reagent)

Important:

1. Use serum free medium to dilute plasmid DNA and Lipofectamine reagent
2. Do not add antibiotics to media during Transfection as this causes cell death
3. Maintain same seeding conditions between experiments
4. Check for compatibility between serum free medium and lipofectamine reagent (some of the medium may decrease Transfection efficiency)

Protocol for 24 well plates (6 well): For Hep G2 cell lines

Prepare complexes using a Plasmid DNA (ug) to Lipofactamine 2000 (ul) ratio of 1:2 to 1:3 for most cell lines.

1. One day before transfection , plate $0.5 - 2 \times 10^5$ cells in 500 ul of growth medium without antibiotics so that at the time of Transfection cells will be 90-95 % confluent.
2. For each transfection sample will be as follows:
 - A) Dilute DNA in 50 ul of serum free or reduced serum medium and mix gently.
 - B) Mix lipofectamine 2000 gently before use, then dilute the appropriate amount in 50 ul of serum free medium, and incubate at room temperature for 5 min. (**proceed to step C within 25 minutes after dilution of lipofectamine reagent**)
 - C) After the 5 minute incubation, combine the diluted DNA with diluted Lipofectamine™ 2000 (total volume = 100 µl). Mix gently and incubate for 20 minutes at room temperature (solution may appear cloudy).

Note: Complexes are stable for 6 hours at room temperature.

3. Add the 100 µl of complexes to each well containing cells and medium. Mix gently by rocking the plate back and forth.
4. Incubate cells at 37°C in a CO2 incubator for 18-48 hours prior to testing for transgene expression. Medium may be changed after 4-6 hours.
5. For stable cell lines: Passage cells at a 1:10 (or higher dilution) into fresh growth medium 24 hours after transfection. Add selective medium (if desired) the following day

FOR optimization of Transfection use Plasmid DNA: Lipofectamine ratios of 1:0.5 to 1:5.

For 6 well plates:

1. Use 2ml of medium for plating the cells
2. Use dilution medium of 2X 250 ul for diluting DNA, i.e. take 4ug of plasmid DNA in 250 ul of serum free medium, and 8-10ul of lipofectamine reagent in 250 ul of serum free medium and then add this complex to each well
3. Plasmid DNA of 4 ug and Lipofectamine reagent 10ul is required for optimal transfection.
4. Titrate the ratios of DNA: Lipofectamine reagent for optimal Transfection.
5. Cell density for 6 well plates usually $2-6 \times 10^5$ cells per well

Protocol: For 6 well plates

Day 1:

1. Plate the cells $2-6 \times 10^5$ (4×10^5) cells in each well by using 2 ml of serum free, and antibiotic free medium one day before the Transfection experiment. Take the cells from the flask where 95 % confluence is reached.
2. Keep the following things ready before starting a Transfection and luciferase assay experiment:
 - a) 96 well plate
 - b) Glass vials (ones used for hplc work) or siliconized polypropylene tubes
 - c) Micropipettes (1-2.5ul, 10-100ul, 20-200ul, and 1ml pipettes)
 - d) PBS
 - e) Serum and antibiotic free DMEM
 - f) Passive lysis buffer (diluted to 1X)
 - g) Luciferase reagent II [diluted with 10ml of luciferase reaction buffer (10ml)]
 - h) Stop & Glow reagent [diluted with stop Glow buffer (1:50)]
 - i) Plasmid DNA purified and whose concentration is known
 - j) Lipofectamine reagent
3. Keep the multiwall plates, pipettes, medium, PBS, plasmids, and reagents which are aliquoted and ice box ready for the experiment.

Important things to do before starting Transfection:

1. Check reader for correctness and working condition (multimode reader)
2. Create a plate and make sure that you create a plate such that the two simultaneously reading wells will be included and rest of the wells has to be excluded. i.e. place the samples and add reagent to the wells which undergo simultaneous reading by reader. Better to keep the duplicate samples on the same lane. i.e. same samples will be there on both sides of the plate, (i.e. 1 &7; 2&8; 3&9 4&10; 5&11; 6&12)
3. All the reagents, including the luciferase reagents, lipofectamine reagent, etc have to be brought to room temperature by keeping in water bath at room temperature.

DO NOT THAW THE REAGENTS WITH HANDS.

4. Have a note book with the pattern of the samples

DAY2: (for a 6 well plate).

1. For each transfection experiment prepare the following:

- A) Dilute plasmid DNA (4µg) in 250 µl of serum free or reduced serum medium and mix gently, this will be used for one well in a 6 well plate, if you want to use the same plasmid DNA for atleast 3 wells then dilute around 12-15µg of plasmid DNA in 750µl of serum free medium. AFTER DILUTION INCUBATE FOR 5 MINUTES AT ROOM TEMPERATURE.

- B) Mix lipofectamine 2000 gently before use, then dilute the appropriate amount i.e. 10ul (approximately 8ul) in 250 µl of serum free medium, and incubate at room temperature for 5 min. If you want for 3 wells then add 30ul to 750ul of serum free medium and use for three wells. AFTER DILUTION INCUBATE FOR 5 MINUTES AT ROOM TEMPERATURE.

(Proceed to step C within 25 minutes after dilution of lipofectamine reagent)

- C) After the 5 minute incubation, combine the diluted DNA (250ul) with diluted Lipofectamine™ 2000 (250ul) (total volume = 500 µl/well). Mix gently and incubate for 20 minutes at room temperature (solution may appear cloudy). After mixing incubate for 20 minutes at room temperature.

Note: Complexes are stable for 6 hours at room temperature.

2. Add the 500 µl of complexes (i.e.mixture of 250ul of diluted DNA, and 250ul of diluted lipofectamine reagent) to each well containing cell which were washed with PBS thoroughly to remove any traces of the earlier medium. Mix gently by rocking the plate back and forth.
3. Incubate cells at 37°C in a CO2 incubator for 18-48 hours prior to testing for transgene expression. Medium may be changed after 4-6 hours.

For co-transfection dilute the plasmid dna and control plasmid dna separately/ in the same tube and add to the lipofectamine reagent. For e.g. for one well of 6 well plate add 4ug of plasmid DNA + 4 ug of control plasmid DNA to 250 ul of medium, and mix with lipofectamine reagent which is diluted by adding 20ul of lipofectamine reagent to 250 ul of medium (10ul for each plasmid 1:2 ratio of plasmid DNA and Lipofectamine reagent).

NOTE: Do not use antibiotics, EDTA, RPMI/DMEM, dextran sulfate, chondroitin sulfate, other sulfated proteoglycans in the medium used for preparing plasmid DNA: transfection reagent complex.

Then check the transfection efficiency by reporter assays.

Luciferase reporter assay: (Shall be done after 48-72 hrs of Transfection)

Reagents preparation:

On the next day of Transfection procedure i.e. after keeping the cells for incubation (on the 2nd day of Transfection procedure) prepare the reagents required for dual luciferase assay.

Reagents/consumables:

1. Phosphate Buffer Saline
2. Passive Lysis Buffer
3. Luciferase assay reagent II
4. Stop&Glow Reagent
5. Siliconized polypropylene tube/glass vials (HPLC glass vials can be used)

Passive Lysis Buffer preparation (PLB)

Passive Lysis Buffer is supplied as 5X concentrate. So prepare sufficient quantity of buffer by adding 1 volume of Passive Lysis Buffer to 4 volumes of distilled water and mix well and store at -20 degrees.

5X concentrate also can be stored at -20 degrees.

Volume of passive lysis buffer required for each well in 6 well plates is 500ul.

PLB volume requirement per well is given below

Multiwell Plate 1X PLB

6-well culture plate 500µl

12-well culture plate 250µl

24-well culture plate 100µl

48-well culture plate 65µl

96-well culture plate 20µl

Preparation of Luciferase assay reagent II:

Prepare Luciferase Assay Reagent II (LAR II) by resuspending the lyophilized powder in 10 ml of supplied luciferase assay buffer II. Dispense this solution into 1 ml aliquots into each vial and store at -70 degrees.

1ml of LAR II will provide 10 assays

This solution is stable for one month if stored at **-20 degrees**, and stable for one year if stored at **-70 degrees**.

Preparation of Stop Glow reagent:

Prepare an adequate volume to perform the desired number of DLR Assays (100µl reagent per assay). Stop&Glo substrate is supplied at a 50X concentration. Add 1 volume of 50X stop&Glo substrate to 50 volumes of Stop&Glo Buffer in a glass or siliconized polypropylene tube.

Stop&Glo Reagent (Substrate+Buffer) is best when prepared just before use .If stored at 22⁰C for 48 hours,the reagent's activity decreased by 8%.If necessary, Stop&Glo Reagent may stored at -20⁰C for 15 days with no decrease in activity.It may be Thawed at room temperature up to 6 times with ≤15% decrease in activity

Note:- Reagents that have been prepared and stored frozen should be thawed at a room temperature water bath. Always mix the reagent prior to use because thawing generates density and composition gradients

Example 1 (10 assays)

Add 20µl of 50X Stop &Glo Substrate to 1ml of Stop & Glo Buffer contained in either a glass vial or siliconized polypropylene tube.This will prepare sufficient Stop & Glo Reagent for 10 assays

Example 2 (100 assays)

Transfer 10ml Stop & Glo Buffer in to a glass vial or siliconized polypropylene tube.Add 200µl of 50X Stop & Glo Substrate to the 10ml Stop & Glo Buffer .This will prepare sufficient Stop & Glo Reagent for 100 DLR Assays

Standard protocol

Note:- The LAR II, Stop & Glo Reagent and samples should be at ambient temperature prior to performing the Dual - Luciferase Assay. Prior to beginning this protocol, verify that LARII and Stop & Glo Reagent have been warmed to room temperature

The assays for firefly luciferase activity and *Renilla* luciferase activity are performed sequentially using one reaction tube. The following protocol is designed for use with manual luminometer fitted with one reagent injector

- 1) Predisperse 100µl of LARII into the appropriate number of laminator tubes to complete the desired number of DLR Assay
- 2) Program the luminometer to perform a 2-second premeasurement delay, followed by a 10-second measurement period for each reporter assay
- 3) Carefully transfer up to 20µl of cell lysate into the luminometer or multianalyser to be containing LARII; mix by pipetting 2 or 3 times. Do not vortex. Place the tube in luminometer and initiate reading

Note: We don't recommend vortexing the solution at step 3. Vortexing may coat the sides of the tube with a microfilm of luminescent solution, which can escape mixing with the subsequently added volume of Stop & Glo reagent. This is a particular concern if Stop & Glo Reagent is delivered into the tube by automatic injection

- 4) If the luminometer is not connected to a printer or a computer, record the firefly luciferase activity measurement
- 5) If available, use a reagent injector to dispense 100µl of Stop & Glo Reagent. If using a manual luminometer, remove the sample tube from luminometer, add 100µl of Stop & Glo Reagent and vortex briefly to mix. Replace the sample in the luminometer, and initiate the reading

Note: It is possible to prime auto-injector systems with little or no loss of DLR Assay reagents. Before priming injectors with LARII or Stop & Glo assay reagents, we recommend first purging all storage liquid (i.e.: deionised water or ethanol wash solution) from the injector system. Priming assay reagent through an empty injector system prevents dilution and contamination of the primed reagent. Thus the volume of primed reagent may be recovered and returned to the reservoir of bulk reagent

- 6) If the laminator is not connected to a printer or computer, record the *Renilla* luciferase activity measurement
- 7) Discard the reaction tube, and proceed to the next DLR assay

Important considerations for Cleaning Reagent injectors

Proper cleaning of an injector system exposed to Stop & Glo Reagent is essential if the device is to be later used to perform firefly luciferase assays by auto injecting LARII. One of the luciferase- quenching components in Stop & Glo Reagent has a moderate affinity to plastic materials. This compound exhibits a reversible association with the interior surfaces of plastic tubing and pump bodies commonly used in the constructions of auto injector systems. Injector plumping that has been properly cleaned following contact with Stop & Glo Reagent will leach trace quantities of quench reagent into solutions that are subsequently passed through the injector system. In such case, even very small quantities of

contaminating quench reagent cause significant inhibition of firefly luciferase reporter activity, especially if injectors are used for dispensing more than one type of reagent. It is recommended that a particular injector be dedicated to each of two reagents and that on completion of a run the wash protocol, below, be followed to ensure clean lines. Proper cleaning must be performed even when an injector is dedicating for dispensing a single reagent

General injector wash protocol

- 1) Purge Stop & Glo Reagent from the injector lines by repeated priming/ washing with a volume of deionized ater equivalent to 3pump void volumes
- 2) Prepare 70% ethanol as wash reagent. Prime the system with atleast 5ml of 70% ethanol to completely replace the void volume and rinse the injector plumbing. It is preferable to allow the injector to soakin this wash solution for 30 mnutes prior to rinsing with deionised water

Note: The design and materials used in the construction of injector systems vary greatly, and some pumps may require longer than a 30 minutes soak in the wash reagent to attain complete surface cleaning. Luminometers equipped with Teflon® tubing are not a concern, but other tubing such as Tygon® will require an extended soak time of 12- 16 hours (overnight) to ensure complete removal of the Stop & Glo Reagent from the injector system

- 3) Rinse with a volume of deionized water equivalent to at least 3 pump void volumes to thoroughly remove all traces of ethanol.

Wash Protocol for the Injectors in the GloMax. 20/20 Luminomete

Trace contamination of Stop & Glo® Reagent may be removed from the GloMax. 20/20 Luminometer injector system as follows:

1. Purge Stop & Glo® Reagent from the injector by performing 1 priming cycle with deionized water.
2. Perform a flush cycle with 70% ethanol, and allow tubing to soak in this wash solution for 30 minutes.
3. Perform a flush cycle with deionized water to remove all traces of ethanol.

Determination of Assay Backgrounds

The expression of a luciferase reporter is quantitated as the luminescence produced above background levels. In most cases, because the background is exceptionally low, luciferase activity is directly proportional to total luminescence. However, when measuring very small amounts of luciferase, it is to subtract the background signal from the measurement of total luminescence. The following sections describe how to determine background signals for firefly and *Renilla* luciferases, respectively.

Firefly Luciferase

With rare exceptions, all background luminescence in measurements of firefly luciferase arises from the instrumentation or the sample tubes. Background in sample tubes may result from static electricity or from phosphorescence. In particular, polystyrene tubes are capable of accumulating significant static buildup that may contribute to persistent, elevated levels of background luminescence. Handling and storage of tubes should be done carefully to minimize static buildup, and samples should be handled away from sunlight or very bright lights before making luminescence measurements.

The electronic design of a given luminometer can greatly affect its measurable level of background signal; many luminometers do not read .0. in the absence of a luminescent sample. To determine the background signal contributed by the instrument and sample tube:

1. Use Passive Lysis Buffer to prepare a lysate of nontransfected control (NTC) cells.
2. Add 100µl of LAR II to 20µl of NTC lysate.
3. Measure apparent luminescence activity.

The lysates of mammalian cells do not express endogenous luminescence activity; the low apparent luminescence in NTC lysates is the background due to the instrument and, possibly, the plate or tube holding the luciferase reaction. Beware that the relative noise in background signals is often quite high. Therefore, **5.10 readings should be performed** and the mean reading used to obtain a statistically significant value for instrument and plate or tube background. An additional source of high luminescence activity is overflow from an adjacent well when measuring luminescence in multiwell plates. This can be eliminated by using high-quality opaque plates that prevent cross-talk. Additionally, the luminometer mechanics and its ability to read luminescence emitted from individual wells should be examined before launching an experiment. Each instrument differs in its method of injection and luminescence detection, which can play a significant role in cross-talk.

Determination of Assay Backgrounds (continued) *Renilla* Luciferase

Background luminescence in the measurement of *Renilla* luciferase activity can arise from three possible sources:

1. Instrument and sample tube or plate background luminescence is similar to that noted above for firefly luciferase.
2. Autoluminescence of coelenterazine is caused by nonenzymatic oxidation of the coelenterazine in solution. Although the level of autoluminescence is dependent on solution composition, lysates prepared with PLB generally yield a low and constant luminescence level. Stop & Glo® Reagent has been developed with a proprietary formulation to further reduce autoluminescence. Between the effects of the PLB and the Stop & Glo® Reagent formulations, many luminometers are unable to measure the residual autoluminescence.
3. Residual luminescence from the firefly luciferase reaction can occur from a small amount of residual luminescence remaining from the firefly luciferase assay in the Dual-Luciferase® measurement. However, since the firefly luciferase reaction is quenched greater than 100,000-fold, this residual luminescence is only significant if the *Renilla* luciferase luminescent reaction is 1,000-fold less than the intensity of the first firefly luciferase luminescent reaction.

Culture vessel	Surf. Area per well ¹	Shared reagents		DNA transfection	
		Vol. of plating medium	Vol. of dilution medium ²	DNA	Lipofect-amine™ 2000
96-well	0.3 cm ²	100 µl	2x25 µl	0.2 µg	0.5 µl
24-well	2 cm ²	500 µl	2x50 µl	0.8 µg	2.0 µl
12-well	4 cm ²	1 ml	2x100 µl	1.6 µg	4.0 µl
6-well	10 cm ²	2 ml	2x250 µl	4.0 µg	10 µl
60-mm	20 cm ²	5 ml	2x0.5 ml	8.0 µg	20 µl
10-cm	60cm ²	15ml	2x1.5 ml	24 µg	60 µl

Gene copy number analysis for CYP2C19 by qPCR using SYBR-green

Primers for CYP2C19 (Target) (F) - 5'-GAAAAATTGAATGAAAACATCAGGATTG-3'

(R) - 5'-CGAGGGTTGTTGATGTCCATC-3'

Primers for IL2 (Reference gene) (F)-5'-TGCACATAATCTCATCTTTCTAACACTCTT-3'

(R) -5'-TTGAAAGCGCAATAGATGGACAT-3'

Stock concentration of all primers is 100 μ M

2X SYBR green mix with ROX from Abgene

1. Use disposable pipette tips containing hydrophobic filters or positive displacement pipettes to prevent cross contamination.
2. Thaw all required reagents completely and put them on ice. Mix all reagents well by inversion prior to pipetting.
3. Preparation of Primers: Dilute 1/5 of the all the stock (100 μ M) primers with water to 20 μ M
4. Preparation of range of standards:
Use 1 sample (J2) as standard: conc- 1500 ng/ μ l

Dilute the concentration to 40 ng/ μ l and do the 1/10 serial dilution to get 4, 0.4, 0.04 and 0.004 ng/ μ l

Std 1: 1500ng/ μ l; 40ng/ μ l x 50 μ l /1500ng/ μ l = 1.33 μ l of J2 + 48.67 μ l of water = 40 ng/ μ l

Std 2: 1/10 of Std 1= 4 ng/ μ l

Std 3: 1/10 of Std 2= 0.4 ng/ μ l

Std 4: 1/10 of Std 3= 0.04 ng/ μ l

Std 5: 1/10 of Std 4= 0.004 ng/ μ l

If 5 μ l of the above standards are added to 20 μ l of reaction mix, the concentration will be 200, 20, 2, 0.2, 0.02 ng/25 μ l

5. Preparation of samples:
Bring all the samples to 20 ng/ μ l; if 5 μ l is added from this will 100 ng/ μ l
6. Prepare a volume of MasterMix 10 % greater than the required number of reactions to be performed by combining the following components in 2 separate eppendorf tubes:

No. of reactions	SYBR green mix with ROX 2X (Abgene) Stock- 2 X Final- 1 X	Primer IL2 F Stock-20 µM Final- 400 nM	Primer IL2 F Stock-20 µM Final- 400 nM	Sterile water
1 rxn	12.5 µl	0.25 µl	0.25 µl	7 µl
X no. of samples + 3 extra				
No. of reactions	SYBR green mix with ROX 2X (Abgene) Stock- 2 X Final- 1 X	Primer (F) for CYP2C19 Stock-20 µM Final- 400 nM	Primer (R) for CYP2C19 Stock-20 µM Final- 400 nM	Sterile water
1 rxn	12.5 µl	0.25 µl	0.25 µl	7 µl
X no. of samples + 3 extra				

- Briefly vortex & spin the mix and distribute 20 µl to the respective wells in 96 QPCR optical plate. Load the wells from the bottom without air bubbles.
- Add 5 µl of the standards, samples to the respective wells.
- Include two NTC's (Non Template Control), add 5 µl of sterile water to it.
- Centrifuge the reaction plate gently to avoid bubbles.

Plate layout:

A1 Std1 IL2	A2 Std1 IL2	A3 Std2 IL2	A4 Std2 IL2	A5 Std3 IL2	A6 Std3 IL2	A7 Std4 IL2	A8 Std4 IL2	A9 Std5 IL2	A10 Std5 IL2	A11 S1 IL2	A12 S1 IL2
B1 S2 IL2	B2 S2 IL2	B3 S3 IL2	B4 S3 IL2	B5 S4 IL2	B6 S4 IL2	B7 S5 IL2	B8 S5 IL2	B9 NTC IL2	B10 NTC IL2	B11	B12
C1 Std1 CYP2C19	C2 Std1 CYP2C19	C3 Std2 CYP2C19	C4 Std2 CYP2C19	C5 Std3 CYP2C19	C6 Std3 CYP2C19	C7 Std4 CYP2C19	C8 Std4 CYP2C19	C9 Std5 CYP2C19	C10 Std5 CYP2C19	C11 S1 CYP2C19	C12 S1 CYP2C19
D1 S2 CYP2C19	D2 S2 CYP2C19	D3 S3 CYP2C19	D4 S3 CYP2C19	D5 S4 CYP2C19	D6 S4 CYP2C19	D7 S5 CYP2C19	D8 S5 CYP2C19	D9 NTC CYP2C19	D10 NTC CYP2C19	D11	D12

Real Time programming:

- Open a new document and select absolute quantification (but our study is relative quantification)
- Name the plate and select NEXT.
- Create new detectors for IL2 & CYP2C19 using FAM as reporter dye and no quencher dye or select from the menu if they are already created and select NEXT.
- Select the Well inspector icon and label the plate. Standards, unknown & NTC for both IL2 & CYP2C19.
- For standards label as 200 ng, 20 ng, 2 ng, 200 pg & 2000 pg and quantity as 10000, 1000, 100, 10 & 1 respectively (as this is a relative quantification, exact quantity is not needed.)
- Select the INSTRUMENT tab and change the volume to 25 µl and add Dissociation stage.

7. Programme Real-Time thermocycler using the following recommended parameters:

Enzyme activation	15 min at 95 °C	} 40 cycles
Denaturation	15 s at 95 °C	
Annealing and extension	1 min at 60 °C	

Data collection should be done at 60 °C.

8. Save as the file in SDS format.

9. Place the microtiter plate in the Real-Time thermocycler and Click START.

Report analysis:

1. Open the file, select the standard wells and check the standard curve.
2. In the Amplification Plot the difference between two standards should be 3 ct if not select the appropriate standards which are in 3 ct difference.
3. In Standard Curve atleast 3 points should be in line, the slope should be around -3.2 and the R2 should be 0.99
4. In Report column for IL2, the difference between the duplicates of the sample should be very minimum or almost equal ct (for intersamples 1 ct difference of total is accepted. E.g 22.32, 22.58, 23.29, 22.92, 23.86 but not 24.00).
5. In Report column for CYP2C19, the difference between the duplicate should be very minimum or almost equal ct (for intersamples difference will be there as they have different expression).
6. The standard deviation between the duplicates should also be minimal.
7. The NTC should be undetermined otherwise it is contaminated and the whole procedure has to be repeated again. (Primer dimer can also give some values to NTC so check the dissociation curve for extra peaks and their ct will be very high).

Data analysis using the $2^{-\Delta\Delta Ct}$ method and its validation

Determination of real-time PCR efficiencies

For the $\Delta\Delta Ct$ calculation to be valid, two important parameters must be considered beforehand. First, the efficiency of a given PCR amplification must be close to

100%, and second, the relative efficiency must be optimal, that is, the amplification efficiencies of the target and reference genes must be approximately equal. PCR efficiency for each gene was determined from the curve of serial 10-fold dilutions and the Ct value at each dilution was measured.

Real-time PCR efficiencies (E) were calculated from the given slopes, according to the equation:

$$E = 10^{(-1/\text{slope})} - 1 \times 100 \text{ where } E = 100 \text{ corresponds to } 100\% \text{ efficiency.}$$

If the absolute value of the slope was close to zero ($m < 0.1$), the efficiencies of the target and reference genes were similar, and thus the $\Delta\Delta Ct$ calculation could be applied.

After validation of the method, results for each sample were expressed in N-fold changes in unknown target gene copies, normalized to IL2 relative to the copy number of the target gene in Standards, according to the following equation:

$$\text{Gene copy number} = 2^{-(\Delta\Delta Ct \pm \text{SD})}$$

where $\Delta\Delta Ct = (Ct \text{ ref gene} - Ct, \text{ target gene})_x - (Ct \text{ ref gene} - Ct \text{ target gene})_y$

where x = calibrator and y = unknown sample.

In cases where N-fold was comprehended between the values ($0.7 < N\text{-fold} < 1.3$), it was accepted that the test sample harboured a single copy of the target gene, i.e., N-fold = 1.

Instead of interpolating unknown samples from a standard curve, it is also possible to calculate the diploid copy number solely based on the observed CT values:

$$2 * 2^{-\Delta\Delta Ct} = 2 * (1 + E)^{-\Delta Ct \text{ tar gene}} / (1 + E)^{-\Delta Ct \text{ ref gene}}$$

with

E = efficiency of the PCR reaction (set at default value 0.95),

$\Delta Ct \text{ tar gene}$ = difference in threshold cycle value between test sample and calibrator sample for the gene under investigation (test gene) and

$\Delta Ct \text{ ref gene}$ = difference in threshold cycle value between test sample and calibrator sample for reference gene.

Protocol for electrophoretic mobility shift assays (CYP2C19 promoter region)

Chemicals, Reagents, Kits and Instruments:

1. HepG2 cell lines (p50-55)
2. DMEM medium (Invitrogen)
3. PBS (Ion free)
4. Gel shift assay system (Chemiluminescent Nucleic acid detection system from Thermo scientific)
 - a) Stabilized streptavidin-Horseradish Peroxidase Conjugate
 - b) Chemiluminiscent substrate (with Luminol / Enhancer solution and stable peroxide solution)
 - c) Blocking buffer
 - d) 4X wash buffer
 - e) Substrate equilibration buffer
5. Biodyne B Nylon membrane
6. Plastic forceps
7. Plastic weigh boats or plates
8. CCD imaging facility or X –ray film or
9. LightShift EMSA Optimization and Control Kit (Thermo scientific)

With the following components:

10X Binding Buffer, 1mL

Biotin-EBNA Control DNA, 50µL

Unlabeled EBNA DNA, 50µL

EBNA Extract, 125µL

Poly (dI•dC), 125µL

50% Glycerol, 500µL

1% NP-40, 500µL

1 M KCl, 1mL

100 mM MgCl₂, 500µL

200 mM EDTA pH 8.0, 500µL

5X Loading Buffer, 1mL

10. Biotin labelled and unlabelled double stranded oligos of transcription factor binding sites: (For preparation of double stranded oligos please refer to Annealing protocol of oligos)
11. Polyacrylamide (8%- 12%)
12. TBS buffer
13. Buffer A (hypotonic buffer)
14. Buffer C (low salt/nuclei resuspension buffer)
15. Dialysis Buffer

16. Vertical gel electrophoresis unit
17. Western blot apparatus
18. Centrifuge (cooling)
19. Unit with CCD camera or dark room with X-ray
20. Micro centrifuge tubes and vials (0.5, 1.5, 2.0ml)
21. Ice bucket
22. Ice
23. Parafilm

The EMSA will be performed in the following three steps

1. Preparation of Nuclear extracts
2. Setting up of Binding reactions of double stranded oligos and nuclear extracts
3. Detection of DNA-protein interaction by Chemiluminescent method

1. Preparation of nuclear extracts:

Note: All procedures must be quick and buffers shall be made freshly. All procedures shall be performed in ice for preventing proteolysis. Keep all the Buffers and other reagents in Ice.

- a) Grow the HepG2 cells in DMEM culture medium (Invitrogen) to confluence.
- b) At 70-80% confluence harvest the cells in ice cold phosphate buffer saline (use 4-10 flasks for preparation)
- c) Scrap the cells using **5 ml** of PBS for large flask and transfer to a **50/15 ml** tube
- d) Centrifuge at **2000rcf** for 10 min at 4⁰C
- e) Resuspend the pellet in at least 5X volume of Buffer A (for one large flask cell mass may be 50-100ul; hence add 0.5 ml of **Buffer A**. **(If the cell volume is around 250-500ul then add 2.5 ml of Buffer A)**)
- f) Keep in Ice for **10 min** , make sure that the cells are re-suspended well for lysis (as this buffer is hypotonic it causes the cells to swell and lyse the cells)
- g) Centrifuge the tubes again at **2000rpm** for **10min** at 4⁰C
- h) Re-suspend in 2X volume of Buffer A (approx 1 ml)
- i) Transfer the cell suspension to a small homogenizer and apply 10-15 strokes to lyse the cells keeping the nuclei intact (Alternatively take the cell suspension into a syringe washes with Buffer A and in one stroke pass the cells through the needle of guage no. 23 into a tube, repeat it 3-5 times for effective cell lysis)
- j) Transfer the contents to a microfuge tube and centrifuge the lysed cells at 12000rpm(16000rcf) for 5 min at 4⁰C
- k) Discard the supernatant, pellet contains the nuclei
- l) To the pellet add 2X volume of **Buffer B (nuclear extraction buffer with high salt content allow the Transcription Factors to be extracted; if pellet is 100ul add 200ul of Buffer B)**

- m) Keep the tubes in rotor Or shaker in a cold room for 30 min (note: if the mixture is viscous it indicates the presence of genomic DNA as the nuclei were lysed at this stage)
- n) Centrifuge the contents at 12000 rpm (16000 rcf) for 15 min at 4⁰C
- o) Collect the supernatant which is NUCLER EXTRCAT and aliquot into different tubes of 25 ul each and store at -80⁰C.

Note: Do not freeze thaw the nucler extract multiple times once you store take it only when you are going to set up the binding reactions

- p) Measure the protein content by Bradford method using bovine serum albumin as standard.

Annealing protocol for oligonucleotides:

Note: Always use similar concentration and similar volumes of oligonucleotides for annealing. We can anneal either by heat block or by thermal cycler or by water bath

Annealing buffer

10 mM Tris

1mM EDTA

50mM NaCl (pH7.8 or 7.5-8.0)

Alternatively you may use 100 mM sodium phosphate, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA (pH= 7.5) as Annealing buffer. Alternately use NEB 2 buffer.

1. Re suspend the oigonucleotides in at the same molar concentration in **annealing buffer**.
(Keep volume of buffer for each oligo below 500 ul)
2. Mix equal volumes of each oligo in equimolar concentrations in a 1. 5ml microfuge tube

Annealing by Heat Block:

- a) Keep the tube in standard heat block at 90-95⁰C for 3 -5 min
- b) Gradually reduce the temperature to room temperature. i.e keep the tubes on work bench at room temperature of 25 ⁰C. The time for cooling takes around 40-60 min (Slow cooling)
- c) Then keep the tube in ice and then store at 4⁰C (double stranded oligos can be stored at 4 degrees for months, whereas single stranded oligos have to be stored at -20 ⁰C).

Annealing by Water bath:

1. Heat 500 ml of water in a beaker on a hotplate
2. Incubate the oligos for 5 min in boiling water
3. Take out the oligos mixture and keep in room temperature to cool and then store at 4⁰C

2. Setting up of Binding reaction for nuclear extracts and double stranded oligos:

Always use three reactions for checking the test system and control system. One reaction contains only the labelled double stranded oligos without protein extracts or nuclear extracts, second reaction contains the labelled oligos and nuclear extract, and the third one containing labelled oligos, unlabeled oligos and nuclear extract.

In the second reaction we will be sure that there is binding (comparing the band position to that of first reaction without nuclear extract, in the third reaction we can find out the specific binding wherein in the

presence of unlabeled oligos labeled oligos may not bind indicating the specific binding.) In addition to this super shift assay reactions can be performed with specific antibodies in the reaction mixture.

Table 1: Setting up of test reactions (Always add labelled oligos at the end)

Components	Final amount	Test Reactions			
		1(No nuclear extract)	2(with nuclear extract)	3(with labelled and unlabelled oligos)	4(with specific antibodies)
MilliQ water	---	14 ul	8 ul	6 ul	10 ul
10X binding buffer	1X	2 ul	2 ul	2 ul	2 ul
1 ug/ul of poly (dI,dC) or salmon sperm DNA	50 ng/ul	1 ul	1 ul	1 ul	1 ul
Optional: 50% glycerol	2.5%	1 ul	1 ul	1 ul	1 ul
Optional: 1% NP-40	0.05%	---	---	---	---
Optional: 100mM MgCl ₂	5mM	---	---	---	---
Optional: 1M KCl	---	---	---	---	--
Optional: 200mM EDTA	---	---	---	---	---
Unlabelled Oligos (use 1 pmol annealed)	4 pmol	---	---	4 ul	---
Nuclear extract	4 -5 ug (measured by Bradford assay)	---	4 ul	4 ul	4 ul
Labelled Oligos (Use 20 fmol annealed biotin labelled ones)	20 fmol	2 ul	2 ul	2 ul	2 ul
Total Volume	--	20 ul	20 ul	20 ul	20 ul

Optional ingredients: These reagents have to be added only when the standard protocol is not efficient. These reagents have to be added according to the final concentrations mentioned into the reaction mixture.

Reaction 1: Includes only the location of the band of oligos alone (labelled) without the nuclear extracts.

Reaction 2: Reaction with nuclear extracts and labelled oligos gives the interaction and shifting of the band of oligos bound to protein in the nuclear extract.

Reaction 3: Reaction reveals the specificity of the protein bound to oligos where in the presence of excess of unlabelled oligos (4 pmol) the binding of the band. This reaction demonstrates that the signal shift observed in the reaction 2 can be made similar to that of reaction 1 after addition of excess of unlabelled oligos.

Reaction 4: This reaction demonstrates even more specificity, where an antibody specific to the protein will be used to identify that particular protein involved in the binding to oligos during Gel Shift. It is called super shift assay.

Table 2: Settings up of control reactions (Always check it first then proceed to test system)

components	Final amount	Control Reactions		
		1 (Nonuclear extract)	2(with nuclear extract)	3 (with labelled and unlabelled oligos)
MilliQ water	----	13 µl	12 µl	8 µl
10X binding buffer	1X	2 µl	2 µl	2 µl
1 ug/ul of poly (dI.dC) or salmon sperm DNA	50ng/ul	1 µl	1 µl	1 µl
50% glycerol	2.5%	1 µl	1 µl	1 µl
1% NP-40	0.05%	1 µl	1 µl	1 µl
100mM MgCl ₂	5mM	---	---	-----
EBNA extract	1 unit	----	1 µl	1 µl
Unlabelled DNA	4 pmol	----	----	4 µl (from the 1 pmol oligos annealed)
Labelled (Biotin) DNA	20 fmol	2 µl (from 20 fmol oligos annealed)	2 µl	2 µl
Total volume		20 µl	20 ul	20 ul

3. Detection of DNA-Protein interaction by Chemiluminescent method:

- a) PAGE
- b) Transferring of DNA-protein complex to the membrane
- c) Detection using chemiluminescence assay

Detailed Procedure for EMSA:**Step 1: Plan Binding Reactions****A• Setting up of control reactions with EBNA system**

Include a complete set of three reactions each time an EMSA is performed. These reactions and expected results for the Control Epstein-Barr Nuclear Antigen (EBNA) System. The Control EBNA System results reported in Table 2 were generated using binding reactions prepared according to Table 2.

Each 20 µl binding reaction contains 20 fmol of Biotin-EBNA Control DNA. Reactions were electrophoresed, transferred and detected according to the steps in Sections B-G of this protocol. If the kit is being used for the first time, perform the Control EBNA System reactions to verify that the kit components and overall procedure are working properly.

B• Planning and optimizing the Test System

As with the Control EBNA System, a complete set of three reactions should be performed with the Test System. Use Table 1 as a guide for planning the Test System binding reactions. If specific binding conditions are not already known, use only minimal reaction components; e.g., 10X binding buffer and Poly (dI•dC), together with the biotin-labelled target DNA, protein extract and unlabeled DNA of the Test System.

Nuclear protein extracts prepared using NE-PER® Nuclear and Cytoplasmic Extraction Reagents (see Related Pierce Products) are an excellent source of target protein. Use 2-3 µl of NE-PER® Nuclear Extract per 20 µl binding reaction. If a greater volume of NE-PER® Extract is required, remove excess salts in the extract by dialyzing into a buffer containing 200 mM salt (use a Slide-A-Lyzer® MINI Dialysis Unit; see Related Pierce Products) before use in the LightShift® EMSA Kit.

Optimization of the Test System can be achieved by adding other components supplied in the kit such as KCl, glycerol, MgCl₂ and detergent and determining their effects on the shift. Bovine serum albumin and basic peptides have also been shown to enhance some DNA-protein interactions. Too much glycerol in the binding reactions may cause vertical streaks along the edges of the lanes.

Poly (dI•dC), which is included in the kit, is the nonspecific competitor DNA of choice for most systems. However if the Test System target DNA sequence is GC-rich, try Poly (dA•dT), sonicated calf thymus, salmon sperm or *Escherichia coli* DNA.

The order of addition of the nuclear extract and biotin-labeled target DNA may affect the specificity of the DNA-protein complexes. Always add the binding reaction components in the order listed in Table 3. To overcome strong nonspecific interactions, a short pre-incubation may be required before adding the biotin-labeled target DNA.

Step 2. Prepare and Pre-Run Gel:

1. Prepare a native polyacrylamide gel in 0.5X TBE or use a pre-cast DNA retardation gel. The appropriate Polyacrylamide percent depends on the size of the target DNA and the binding protein. Most systems use a 4 -6% polyacrylamide gel in 0.5X TBE (use pre chilled buffer and run the gel at low temperatures).
2. Fill an electrophoresis unit with 0.5X TBE to just above the bottom of the wells. (This reduces heat generated during electrophoresis.) Flush wells and pre-electrophorese the gel for 30-60 minutes. Apply 100 V for an 8 x 8 x 0.1 cm gel.
3. Proceed to Step 3 while gel is pre-electrophoresing.

Step 3. Prepare and Perform Binding Reactions:

Note: Include controls in the assay to ensure the system is working properly by setting up control reactions.

1. Thaw all binding reaction components, EBNA Control System components and Test System samples, and place them on ice. Avoid excessive warming of DNA probes. Do not thaw the EBNA Extract until immediately before use.
2. Prepare complete sets of 20 µl binding reactions for the Control EBNA System and/or the Test System according to Procedure Step 1.
3. Incubate binding reactions at room temperature for 20 minutes.
4. Add 5 µl of 5X Loading Buffer to each 20 µl binding reaction, pipetting up and down several times to mix. Do not vortex or mix vigorously.

Step 4. Electrophorese Binding Reactions:

1. Switch off current to the electrophoresis gel.

2. Flush the wells and then load 20 μ l of each sample onto the polyacrylamide gel.
3. Switch on current (set to 100 V for 8 x 8 x 0.1 cm gel) and electrophorese samples until the bromophenol blue dye has migrated approximately 2/3 to 3/4 down the length of the gel. The free biotin-EBNA Control DNA duplex migrates just behind the bromophenol blue in a 6% polyacrylamide gel.

Step 5. Electrophoretic Transfer of Binding Reactions to Nylon Membrane:

1. Soak nylon membrane in 0.5X TBE for at least 10 minutes.
2. Sandwich the gel and nylon membrane in a clean electrophoretic transfer unit according the manufacturer's instructions.

Use 0.5X TBE cooled to \sim 10°C with a circulating waterbath. Use very clean forceps and powder-free gloves, and handle the membrane only at the corners.

Note: Use clean transfer sponges. Avoid using sponges that have been used in Western blots.

3. Transfer at 380 mA (\sim 100V) for 30 minutes. Typical transfer times are 30-60 minutes at 380 mA using a standard tank transfer apparatus for mini gels (8 x 8 x 0.1 cm).
4. When the transfer is complete, place the membrane with the bromophenol blue side up on a dry paper towel. (There should be no dye remaining in the gel.) Allow buffer on the membrane surface to absorb into the membrane. This will only take a minute. Do not let the membrane dry. Immediately proceed to Step 6.

Step 6. Cross-link Transferred DNA to Membrane:

Three options are available for cross-linking:

- Option 1: Cross-link at 120 mJ/cm² using a commercial UV-light cross-linker instrument equipped with 254 nm bulbs (45-60 second exposure using the auto cross-link function).
- Option 2: Cross-link at a distance of approximately 0.5 cm from the membrane for 5-10 minutes with a hand-held UVlamp equipped with 254 nm bulbs.
- Option 3: Cross-link for 10-15 minutes with the membrane face down on a transilluminator equipped with 312 nm bulbs.

After the membrane is cross-linked, proceed directly to step 7. Alternatively, the membrane may be stored dry at room temperature for several days. Do not allow the membrane to get wet again until ready to proceed with step 7.

Step 7. Detect Biotin-labeled DNA by Chemiluminescence:

The recommended volumes are for an 8 x 10 cm membrane. If larger gels are used, adjust volumes in step 7 accordingly. Perform all blocking and detection incubations in clean trays or in plastic weigh boats on an orbital shaker.

1. Gently warm the Blocking Buffer and the 4X Wash Buffer to 37-50°C in a water bath until all particulate is dissolved. These buffers may be used between room temperature and 50°C as long as all particulate remains in solution. The Substrate Equilibration Buffer may be used between 4°C and room temperature.

2. To block the membrane add 20 ml of Blocking Buffer and incubate for 15 minutes with gentle shaking.
3. Prepare conjugate/blocking buffer solution by adding 66.7 μ l Stabilized Streptavidin-Horseradish Peroxidase Conjugate to 20 ml Blocking Buffer (1:300 dilution).

Note: This conjugate/blocking buffer solution has been optimized for the Nucleic Acid Detection Module and should not be modified.

4. Decant blocking buffer from the membrane and replace it with the conjugate/blocking solution. Incubate membrane in the conjugate/blocking buffer solution for 15 minutes with gentle shaking.
5. Prepare 1X wash solution by adding 40 ml of 4X Wash Buffer to 120 ml ultrapure water.
6. Transfer membrane to a new container and rinse it briefly with 20 ml of 1X wash solution.
7. Wash membrane four times for 5 minutes each in 20 ml of 1X wash solution with gentle shaking.
8. Transfer membrane to a new container and add 30 ml of Substrate Equilibration Buffer. Incubate membrane for 5 minutes with gentle shaking.
9. Prepare Substrate Working Solution by adding 6 ml Luminol/Enhancer Solution to 6 ml Stable Peroxide Solution.

Note: Exposure to the sun or any other intense light can harm the Working Solution. For best results keep the Working Solution in an amber bottle and avoid prolonged exposure to any intense light. Short-term exposure to typical laboratory lighting will not harm the Working Solution.

10. Remove membrane from the Substrate Equilibration Buffer, carefully blotting an edge of the membrane on a paper towel to remove excess buffer. Place membrane in a clean container or onto a clean sheet of plastic wrap placed on a flat surface.
11. Pour the Substrate Working Solution onto the membrane so that it completely covers the surface. Alternatively, the membrane may be placed DNA side down onto a puddle of the Working Solution. Incubate membrane in the substrate solution for 5 minutes without shaking.
12. Remove membrane from the Working Solution and blot an edge of the membrane on a paper towel for 2-5 seconds to remove excess buffer. Do not allow the membrane to become dry.
13. Wrap the moist membrane in plastic wrap, avoiding bubbles and wrinkles.
14. Expose membrane to an appropriately equipped CCD camera, or place the membrane in a film cassette and expose to X-ray film for 2-5 minutes. Develop the film according to manufacturer's instructions. Exposure time may be adjusted to obtain the desired signal.

Preparation of reagents:

Buffer A: Total volume for 5 ml of reagent

10mM HEPES:	100 μ l of HEPES pH7.9 (take from stock of 0.5 M)
1.5 mM MgCl ₂ :	7.5 μ l of MgCl ₂ (1 M stock)
10 mM KCl:	16.5 μ l of KCl (3 M stock)
1 mM DTT:	5 μ l of DTT (1 M Stock)

To this add 500 μ l of protease inhibitor and 4.35 ml of MilliQ H₂O to make upto 5 ml.

Note: Protease inhibitor can be prepared from complete, Mini, EDTA free tablets from ROCHE and by dissolving in One tablet of this kit in 700 ul of milliQ water and take 500 ul from that and use.

Buffer B: Total volume for 1 ml

20 mM HEPES: 40 ul of HEPES, pH 7.9, (0.5 M stock)

1.5 mM MgCl₂: 1.5 ul of MgCl₂ (1 M stock)

0.5 M NaCl: 100 ul of NaCl (5 M stock)

25% Glycerol: 300 ul of glycerol (80% stock)

1 mM DTT: 1 ul of DTT (1 M Stock)

To this add 200 ul of protease inhibitor and add 356.5 ul of milliQ water to make upto 1 ml.

Table 1: Haplotype structures and frequencies of *CYP2C19* 5' flanking region variations

Haplotype	Location of SNPs from the translational start site (ATG)																Frequency in the South Indians (n=58)
	636	681	-1558	-1498	-1442	-1418	-1289	-1051	-1041	-934	-889	-833	-828	-806	-779	-98	
1	G	G	T	T	T	C	T	T	G	del	T	del	T	C	A	T	36.56
2	G	A	T	T	T	C	T	T	G	del	T	del	T	C	A	C	10.62
3	G	A	T	T	T	C	T	T	G	del	T	del	T	C	A	T	4.32
4	G	G	T	G	T	C	T	T	G	del	T	del	T	C	A	T	3.99
5	G	A	T	G	T	C	T	T	G	del	T	del	T	C	A	T	3.94
6	G	G	T	T	T	C	T	T	G	del	G	del	T	C	A	T	3.64
7	G	A	T	T	C	C	T	T	G	del	T	del	T	C	A	T	2.60
8	G	G	T	T	C	C	T	T	G	del	T	del	T	C	A	T	1.95
9	G	G	T	G	T	C	T	T	G	del	T	del	T	C	C	T	1.95
10	G	A	T	T	T	C	T	T	G	del	T	del	T	C	C	C	1.91
11	G	A	T	G	T	C	T	T	G	del	T	del	T	C	A	C	1.66
12	G	G	T	T	C	C	T	T	G	del	G	del	T	C	A	T	1.52
13	G	G	T	T	T	C	T	T	G	del	T	del	T	C	A	C	1.36
14	G	G	T	G	C	C	T	T	G	del	T	del	T	C	C	T	0.90
15	G	A	T	T	T	C	T	T	G	del	T	T	T	C	A	T	0.90
16	A	A	T	G	T	C	T	T	G	del	T	del	T	C	A	T	0.89
17	A	G	T	T	C	C	T	T	G	del	G	del	T	C	A	C	0.86
18	G	A	G	G	T	C	T	T	G	del	T	T	T	C	A	C	0.86
19	G	A	G	G	T	T	T	T	G	del	G	del	T	C	C	T	0.86
20	G	A	T	T	C	C	G	T	G	del	T	del	T	C	C	T	0.86
21	G	A	T	T	T	C	T	T	G	del	G	T	A	C	C	C	0.86

Continued ...

Table 1: Haplotype structures and frequencies of *CYP2C19* 5' flanking region variations

Haplotype	Location of SNPs from the translational start site (ATG)																Frequency in the South Indians (n=58)
	636	681	-1558	-1498	-1442	-1418	-1289	-1051	-1041	-934	-889	-833	-828	-806	-779	-98	
22	G	G	T	G	T	C	G	T	G	del	G	del	T	C	A	T	0.86
23	G	G	T	G	T	C	T	T	G	del	T	T	T	C	A	C	0.86
24	G	G	T	G	T	C	T	T	G	del	T	T	T	T	A	C	0.86
25	G	G	T	G	T	C	T	T	G	del	T	T	T	T	C	T	0.86
26	G	G	T	G	T	C	T	T	G	del	T	del	T	T	C	T	0.86
27	G	G	T	T	T	C	G	C	G	del	T	del	T	C	C	C	0.82
28	G	G	T	T	T	C	G	T	G	del	T	del	T	C	A	C	0.86
29	G	G	T	T	T	T	T	C	G	del	T	del	T	C	C	C	0.86
30	G	G	T	T	C	C	T	T	G	T	T	del	T	C	A	C	0.86
31	G	G	T	T	T	C	T	T	G	T	G	del	T	C	C	C	0.86
32	G	A	T	G	T	C	T	T	G	T	T	del	T	C	C	T	0.86
33	G	A	T	G	T	C	T	T	G	del	T	T	A	C	C	C	0.86
34	G	A	T	T	T	C	T	T	G	del	T	T	A	C	A	T	0.86
35	G	A	G	G	T	C	T	T	G	T	G	T	T	C	A	T	0.86
36	G	A	T	T	T	C	T	T	G	del	T	T	T	C	C	C	0.84
37	G	A	T	G	C	C	T	T	G	del	T	T	T	C	C	T	0.83
38	A	A	T	G	T	C	T	T	G	del	T	del	T	C	A	C	0.82
39	G	A	T	G	C	C	T	T	G	del	T	del	T	C	A	C	0.74
40	G	G	T	T	T	C	T	T	G	del	T	del	T	C	C	C	0.68
41	G	A	T	G	C	C	T	T	G	del	T	del	T	C	C	T	0.61
42	G	A	T	T	C	C	T	T	G	del	T	del	T	C	A	C	0.30
43	G	G	G	G	T	C	T	T	G	T	G	T	T	C	A	T	0.001

Key

- 3 Backbone sugar and base number
- P Phosphate group
- * Residue/water on plot more than once
- Hydrogen bond to DNA
- ⋯ Nonbonded contact to DNA (< 3.35Å)
- 88 O Water molecule and number

ATF-2 and TBS complex (-806 C)

Key

- 3 Backbone sugar and base number
- P Phosphate group
- * Residue/water on plot more than once
- Hydrogen bond to DNA
- ⋯ Nonbonded contact to DNA (< 3.35Å)
- 88 O Water molecule and number

ATF-2 and TBS complex (-806 C)

Key

- 3 Backbone sugar and base number
- P Phosphate group
- * Residue/water on plot more than once
- Hydrogen bond to DNA
- ⋯ Nonbonded contact to DNA (< 3.35Å)
- 88 O Water molecule and number

ATF-2 and TBS complex (-806 T)

Key

- 3 Backbone sugar and base number
- P Phosphate group
- * Residue/water on plot more than once
- Hydrogen bond to DNA
- ⋯ Nonbonded contact to DNA (< 3.35Å)
- 88 O Water molecule and number

ATF-2 and TBS complex (-806 T)

Key

- 3 Backbone sugar and base-number
- P Phosphate group
- * Residue/water on plot more than once
- Hydrogen bond to DNA
- - - Nonbonded contact to DNA (< 3.35Å)
- 88 O Water molecule and number

CDP and TBS complex (-98 T)

Key

- 3 Backbone sugar and base-number
- P Phosphate group
- * Residue/water on plot more than once
- Hydrogen bond to DNA
- - - Nonbonded contact to DNA (< 3.35Å)
- 88 O Water molecule and number

CDP and TBS complex (-98 T)

Key

- 3 Backbone sugar and base-number
- P Phosphate group
- * Residue/water on plot more than once
- Hydrogen bond to DNA
- - - Nonbonded contact to DNA (< 3.35Å)
- 88 O Water molecule and number

CDP and TBS complex (-98 C)

Key

- 3 Backbone sugar and base-number
- P Phosphate group
- * Residue/water on plot more than once
- Hydrogen bond to DNA
- - - Nonbonded contact to DNA (< 3.35Å)
- 88 O Water molecule and number

CDP and TBS complex (-98 C)

C/EBPB and TBS complex (-1442 T)

C/EBPB and TBS complex (-1442 C)

GRE and TBS complex (-828 T)

GRE and TBS complex (-828 T)

GRE and TBS complex (-828 A)

GRE and TBS complex (-828 A)

— *Annexure*

CONSENT FORM - Part I: Information for the participant of the study

- Name of the study** : Characterization of the 5'-regulatory region of *CYP2C19* in the South Indian Population
- Institute** : Jawaharlal Institute of Postgraduate Medical Education and Research
- Student** : U.S. Chakradhara Rao
- Guide** : Dr. D.G. Shewade, Professor, Department of Pharmacology, JIPMER-605006

Introduction: We would like you to take part in a study being conducted by us at JIPMER. Before you decide whether or not to participate, we would like to call your attention to three matters. First, your participation is entirely voluntary, your own personal choice. Second, if at any time you want to withdraw from the study you can do so. Your withdrawal would in no way result in JIPMER withholding goodwill or normal medical care. Finally, we would like to point out that, although we expect the study to produce knowledge that might generally benefit others, this would not bring any direct benefit for you. Below is a brief description of the background, purpose, design and expected outcome of the study. Before you decide to participate, please feel free to ask any questions.

Background Information: When a drug is given to a group of individuals, not all of them respond similarly to the drug. The drug may be inactive in some persons, but may cause toxicity in others. Genes play an important role in the way drugs are metabolized.

It is known that certain important enzymes such as CYP2C19, which eliminate these drugs, possess genetic mutations that lead to decreased metabolism in carriers of these mutations. A previous study in our laboratory showed that a relatively high percentage of South Indians exhibit this genetic mutation. The decreased metabolism may lead to drug toxicity in these individuals.

Purpose: To study the regulatory region of this gene in South Indians. This would be the first study to find out the mutations that are present in this region of the *CYP2C19* gene.

Method: You should not take any medication, including over-the counter drugs and alcohol for at least 3 days before and on day of blood sample collection. After an overnight fast, you have to take 200 mg of proguanil orally. You should not take food for at least two hours after the drug intake. Four hours after ingestion of the drug 5 ml of venous blood will be collected from you by venepuncture. The blood will be used to estimate the levels of proguanil and cycloguanil (metabolite of proguanil) and to extract DNA from leukocytes. The *CYP2C19* gene will be studied by amplifying and sequencing DNA.

Risks, Inconvenience and discomforts: Proguanil is a safe drug used for the prophylaxis of malaria. With the given doses side effects like nausea, vomiting, headache, and bowel upset are very rare. Collection of blood may cause you minimal pain

Expected Outcome: The results of this study will help to find out the role of the regulatory region in influencing *CYP2C19* mutations. A look at your genetic profile will help your physician select the right drug at the right dose for the disease needing therapy with drugs metabolized by CYP2C19 with minimum risk of therapeutic failure or side-effects.

Signature of the Investigator

CONSENT FORM – Part II: Declaration by the Participant of the Study

The details of the study have been provided to me in writing and the details have been fully explained to me. I am aware that the results of the study may not be directly beneficial to me but will help in the advancement of medical sciences. I fully consent to participate in the study titled “Characterization of the 5’-regulatory region of CYP2C19 in the South Indian Population” and donate 5 ml of blood. I also consent for genetic analysis of my DNA for the CYP2C19 gene relating to drug metabolism and also for analysis of any other genes which will be relevant to this study.

Signature & Date

Name:

Code number:

Address:

witness:

VOLUNTEER DETAILS:

“Characterization of the 5’-regulatory region of *CYP2C19* in the South Indian Population”

Code Number:

Date:

Name:

Address:

State:

Age:

Sex:

Height:

Weight:

Religion:

Sub division:

Alcohol: Yes/No (Duration:; Quantity:.....)

Smoking: Yes/No (Duration:; Quantity:.....)

Food: Vegetarian/ Non-vegetarian/ Both

Drug history:

Drug Allergy:

History of chronic illness:

General Physical Examination:

BP:

Temperature:

Pulse:

History of adverse reaction to any drug:

(For office use only)

Code No.:

Name:

Date of sample collection:

Genetic status:

ஒப்புதல் படிவம்

பகுதி - 1

ஆராய்ச்சியில் பங்கு பெறுவோர்க்கான தகவல்கள்

- ஆராய்ச்சி தலைப்பு : “தென்னிந்திய மக்கள்தொகையின் CYP2C19 மரபணுக்களின் ஒழுங்குமுறை சீர்ப்படுத்தும் பகுதியின் தனித்தன்மை பற்றிய ஆய்வு”.
- ஆராய்ச்சி கூடம் : ஜிப்மர்
- ஆராய்ச்சி தலைவர் : டாக்டர். டி. கோ. சிவலே ,
பேராசிரியர்,
மருந்தியல்துறை,
ஜிப்மர், புதுச்சேரி – 605 006.

முன்னுரை:

தாங்கள் இந்த ஆராய்ச்சியில் பங்கு பெற காட்டும் ஆர்வத்திற்கு நன்றி தெரிவித்து தங்களை அன்புடன் அழைக்கிறோம். இந்த ஆராய்ச்சியில் பங்கு பெறுவதற்கு முன் இதன் நோக்கத்தை தாங்கள் தெரிந்து கொள்வது முக்கியம். ஆராய்ச்சியைப் பற்றிய முழு தகவல்களையும் இந்த படிவம் தங்களுக்கு அளிக்கும். இப்படிவம் இந்த ஆராய்ச்சியை பற்றிய தன்மை, நோக்கம், நன்மைகள், ஏற்படக்கூடிய சுகமின்மைகள் மற்றும் தற்காப்பு நடவடிக்கைகள் ஆகியவை பற்றி விளக்கம் அளிக்கிறது. இந்த படிவத்தை படித்து இதன் சாரத்தை புரிந்து கொள்வது தங்களுக்கு முக்கியமானதாகும். இந்த படிவத்தில் மருத்துவ விஞ்ஞான துறை சார்ந்த பதங்கள் உள்ளதால், சந்தேகம் இருப்பின் இதனைப் பற்றி மேலும் தெரிந்துகொள்ள இந்த ஆராய்ச்சியாளரையோ, அல்லது கீழே கொடுக்கப்பட்ட நபர்களையோ, தாங்கள் ஒப்புதல் அளிக்கும்முன் அணுகி தெரிந்து கொள்ளலாம்.

ஆய்வின் நோக்கம்:

தென்னிந்திய மக்கள்தொகையின் CYP2C19 நொதியின் ஒழுங்குமுறை சீர்ப்படுத்தும் பகுதியின் தனித்தன்மை பற்றிய ஆய்வு. இதை பற்றிய ஆய்வுகள் நம்முடைய சமூகத்தில் அதிகம் இல்லை. CYP2C19 மரபணுக்களின் முறைமாற்றத்தைப் பற்றி கண்டறிவது இதுவே முதன்முறையாகும். இந்த CYP2C19 மரபணுக்களின் முறைமாற்றத்தைப் பற்றி கண்டறிவதே, இந்த

ஆய்வின் நோக்கமாகும். ஒரு சிலருக்கு மருந்து வேலை செய்யலாம், சிலருக்கு பக்கவிளைவுகள் ஏற்படலாம்

ஆய்வின் செயல்முறை:

நீங்கள் மருத்துவரின் ஆலோசனை இல்லாமல் மாத்திரைகளையும் மதுவும் மூன்று நாட்களுக்கு முன்பிலிருந்தே எடுக்கக்கூடாது. ஆய்வின் முன்தின இரவில் எந்த உணவும் உட்கொள்ளக்கூடாது, புரோகுவனில் 200மில்லி கிராம் எடுத்துக் கொள்ள வேண்டும். அதன்பிறகு இரண்டு மணி நேரம் எந்த உணவும் எடுத்துக்கொள்ளக்கூடாது. நான்கு மணி நேரம் சென்றபின்பு 5 மில்லி இரத்தம் எடுக்கப்படும். பிறகு புரோகுவனில் மற்றும் சைக்லோகுவனிலின் இரத்த அளவு அறியப்படும். பின்பு மரபணுவின் முறைமாற்றம் பற்றிய ஆய்வும் மேற்கொள்ளப்படும்.

ஆய்வில் பங்குபெறுவதனால், பங்குகொள்பவருக்கு ஏற்படும் பயன்கள்/நன்மைகள்:

ஆய்வின் முடிவில், CYP2C19 மரபணுக்களின் ஒழுங்குமுறை சீர்ப்படுத்தும் பகுதியின் தனித்தன்மை பற்றி அறியலாம். அதனால் தங்களுடைய மருத்துவரிடம், தங்களுக்கு அளிக்கப்படும் மருத்துவசிகிச்சையின் மாற்றம் பற்றி பரிந்துரைக்கப்படும். அதுமட்டுமின்றி, இந்த ஆய்வு முடிவுகள் மற்றவர்களுக்கும் பயன்படும் வகையில் சில அறிவியல் பதிவேடுகளிலும் வெளியிடப்படும். ஆகவே இந்த ஆய்வில் பங்கு கொள்வதன் மூலம் மருத்துவதுறையின் வளர்ச்சிக்கு நீங்கள் உதவி புரியலாம்.

ஆய்வில் எதிர்பாராத விதமாக ஏற்படும் பாதிப்புகள்:

இரத்தம் எடுக்கும் இடங்களில் சிறிதளவு வலி ஏற்படலாம். சில நபர்களுக்கு புரோகுவனில் மருந்தினால் சில பக்க விளைவுகள் (மயக்கம், வாந்தி, தலைவலி, வயிற்று உபாதைகள்) ஏற்பட அரிய வாய்ப்புகள் உள்ளன. ஏதேனும் பக்க விளைவுகள் நேர்ந்தால், அவற்றிற்கு ஜிப்மர் மருத்துவமனையின் சிகிச்சை கோட்பாடுகளின்படி மருத்துவம் செய்யப்படும்.

ஆய்வில் பங்கேற்கும் நபருடைய ஆய்வு முடிவுகளின் பாதுகாப்புப்பற்றிய விவரங்கள்:

தங்களுடைய ஆய்வு முடிவுகள் பற்றிய கோப்புகள், எந்த நிலையிலும் தங்களுடைய அனுமதியின்றி வெளியிடப்படாது, இரகசியமாகப் பாதுகாக்கப்படும்.

ஆய்வில் தங்களின் பங்கேற்பு மற்றும் விலகல் பற்றிய விவரங்கள்:

இந்த ஆய்வில் நீங்கள் பங்குக்கொள்வது யாராலும் கட்டாயமாக்கப்படாது. நீங்கள் எப்பொழுது வேண்டுமானாலும் ஆராய்ச்சியிலிருந்து விலகிக்கொள்ளலாம்.

இந்த ஆய்வில் தாங்கள் பங்குக்கொள்வதற்கு முன்னால் தங்களுக்கு ஏற்படும் சந்தேகங்களை, எந்தவித தயக்கமுமின்றி கேட்டுக்கொள்ளலாம்.

எதிர்கால ஆய்வுகளில் தங்களுடைய பங்கேற்பு:

தேவைப்பட்டால் தங்களின் மரபணுக்களை வேறு மரபணுக்களின் முறைமாற்ற சோதனைக்காகவும் பிற்காலத்தில் உபயோகப்படுத்திக்கொள்வோம்.

இந்த ஆய்வில் தங்களுக்கு ஏற்படும் சந்தேகங்களை பற்றி அறிந்துக்கொள்ள அனுக வேண்டிய முகவரி பின்வருமாறு:

ஆராய்ச்சி தலைவர் : டாக்டர். டி. கோ. சிவடே ,
பேராசிரியர்,
மருந்தியல்துறை,
ஜிப்மர், புதுச்சேரி – 605 006.

ஒப்புதல் படிவம்-2

பங்கு பெறுவோரின் ஒப்புதல் படிவம்

பங்கேற்போரின் பெயர் :

விலாசம் :

அலைப்பேசி :

ஆராய்ச்சியின் தலைப்பு :

“தென்னிந்திய மக்கள்தொகையின் CYP2C19 மரபணுக்களின் ஒழுங்குமுறை சீர்ப்படுத்தும் பகுதியின் தனித்தன்மை பற்றிய ஆய்வு”

இந்த ஆய்வு பற்றிய முழு விபரங்களும் எழுத்து மற்றும் எனக்கு தெரிந்த மொழியில் விளக்கப்பட்டுள்ளது. மேற்கண்டவைகளை நான் புரிந்துகொண்டபின் இதன் சம்பந்தமாக வினாக்களை எழுப்ப சந்தர்ப்பம் அளிக்கப்பட்டது. இதில் பங்கு பெறுவது தன்னார்வத்தினால் மட்டுமே என்றும் எந்த நேரத்திலும் இதிலிருந்து காரணம் கூறாமல் விலகிக்கொள்ளலாம் என்று புரிந்துகொண்டேன். இந்த ஆய்வின் முடிவுகளை விஞ்ஞானப்பூர்வ தேவைகளுக்குப் பயன்படுத்திக்கொள்ள சம்மதிக்கிறேன். ஒப்புதல் படிவம் 2ல் முதலாவதை “பங்குபெறுவோர்க்கான தகவல்” என்ற தலைப்பில் பெற்றுக்கொண்டேன். இதில் பங்கு பெறவும், 5மி.லி. இரத்தம் கொடுக்கவும் என் முழு சம்மதத்தைத் தெரிவிக்கிறேன். மேலும் இவ்வாய்வுக்கு தேவைபடி, பிற மரபணுக்களைப் பற்றி ஆராயவும் சம்மதம் தெரிவிக்கிறேன்.

பங்குபெறுவோரின் கையொப்பம் :

தேதி :

சாட்சியாளர் கையொப்பம் :

தேதி :

List of research publications and presentations

- i) **Satyanarayana CR**, Devendran A, Jayaraman M, Jayakanthan M, Mathur PP, Gopal SD, Rajagopal K, and Chandrasekaran A. Influence of the genetic polymorphisms in the 5' flanking and exonic regions of CYP2C19 on proguanil oxidation. *Drug Metab. Pharmacokinet.* 2009; 24:537-548.
- ii) **Satyanarayana CR**, Devendran A, Sundaram R, Gopal SD, Rajagopal K, Chandrasekaran A. Genetic variations and haplotypes of the 5' regulatory region of CYP2C19 in South Indian population. *Drug Metab Pharmacokinet.* 2009; 24:185-93.
- iii) **Chakradhara Rao US**, Satyamoorthy K, Shewade DG, Krishnamoorthy R, and Adithan C. Characterization of polymorphisms in the promoter of the human CYP2C19 gene (*Manuscript Accepted for publication in Molecular Biology Reports*).
- iv) Anichavezhi D*, Chakradhara Rao US*, Shewade DG, Krishnamoorthy R, Adithan C. Distribution of CYP2C19*17 allele and genotypes in an Indian population (*Manuscript submitted in Journal of Clinical Pharmacy and Therapeutics*). * Both authors contributed equally.

Sequence/SNP data submission to public database

- v) CYP2C19 5' flanking regions (contig) from the South Indian populations were submitted to NCBI. The sequences (n=58) were published and available in public domain. (Accession IDs: EU369428 to EU 369485).
- vi) Novel polymorphisms and other variations of promoter region were submitted to dbSNP database (NCBI ss#158145850 to ss# 158145863). The information on these SNPs is available in the public domain of dbSNP database.

Publications in Conference proceedings

- vii) Anichavezhi D, **Chakradhara Rao U S**, Rajan S, Shewade DG, Krishnamoorthy R, Adithan C. Distribution of CYP2C19 ultrarapid drug metabolizer gene variant (CYP2C19*17) in an Indian population. *Indian Journal of Pharmacology.* 2009;41: (Supplement 1): S102

Presented at international conference on Integrative & Personalized Medicine and 42nd Annual Conference of Indian Pharmacological Society - 2009, Swabhumi, Kolkata).
- viii) **Chakradhara Rao US**, Shewade DG, Adithan C. proguanil metabolic ratio and CYP2C19 genotype in South Indian population. *Indian Journal of Pharmacology* 2008; 40 (Supplement 2): S79.

Presented at International Conference on Translational Pharmacology & 41st annual conference of Indian Pharmacological Society (IPS) held at AIIMS, New Delhi from 18th – 20th December 2008. (*Won the Prize for ‘Best Poster’*).

- ix) **Chakradhara Rao US**, Anichavezhi D, Rajan S, Shewade DG, Krishnamoorthy R, Adithan C. ‘ Genetic variations and haplotypes of 5’ regulatory region of CYP2C19 in South Indians’ *Genomic Med* 2008;2:349.

Presented at Human Genome Meeting (HGM)-2008 organized by Human Genome Organization (HUGO) held from 27th September 2008 to 30th September 2008 at Hyderabad. (*Received the travel grant*)

Conference / Workshop presentations

- x) Shewade DG, **Chakradhara Rao US**, Anichavezhi D, Satyamoorthy K, Krishnamoorthy R, Adithan C. Genetic variations in the 5’ flanking region of CYP2C19 gene and their functional importance as explored in South Indian population, presented during Indo-French workshop on Pharmacogenomics held from 30th November to 2nd December 2009 at JIPMER, Pondicherry.
- xi) **Chakradhara Rao US**, Anichavezhi D, Rajan S, Shewade DG, Krishnamoorthy R, Adithan C. Genetic variations of CYP2C19 5’ flanking region in South Indian population, presented at Annual conference of Southern Regional Pharmacological Society-2008 held from 11th July 2008 to 13th July 2008 in Department of Pharmacology, JIPMER, Pondicherry.
- xii) Anichavezhi D, **Chakradhara Rao US**, Rajan S, Shewade DG, Krishnamoorthy R, Adithan C. Genetic Inter-ethnic distribution of variations of 5’ regulatory region of CYP2C19 gene, presented at ‘Annual conference of Southern Regional Pharmacological Society-2008’ held from 11th July 2008 to 13th July 2008 in Department of Pharmacology, JIPMER, Pondicherry (*won the best poster prize*).

Other publications from similar work but not related to thesis

- xiii) Arunkumar AS, **Chakradhara Rao US**, Ramu P, Umamaheswaran G, Keshavan R, Shewade DG, Balachandar J, Adithan C. Haplotype structures of common variants of CYP2C8, CYP2C9 and ADRB1 genes in a south Indian population. (*Manuscript submitted*)

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2. Satyanarayana CR, Devendran A, Sundaram R, Gopal SD, Rajagopal K, Chandrasekaran A. Genetic variations and haplotypes of the 5' regulatory region of CYP2C19 in South Indian population. Drug Metab Pharmacokinet. 2009; 24:185-93

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